

Proceedings
of the
**Twelfth International Conference on Environmental Management,
Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2025)
and SECOTOX Conference**

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- Division of Hydraulics and Environmental Engineering,
School of Civil Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Society of Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety (SECOTOX)

In collaboration with:

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- Department of Civil Engineering, University of Thessaly, Greece
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Editors' Preface

The 12th International Conference on Environmental Management, Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE) covers the latest issues in environmental science, engineering and management and it is taking place together with the special conference of the International Society of Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety (SECOTOX), providing a special forum to ecotoxicology.

The 12th CEMEPE Conference deals with environmental engineering and management, incorporating subject areas related to planning and economics, aiming at creating a potential for osmosis between environmentalists and other scientists such as economists, engineers, planners, policy makers etc. The conference is designed to encourage the exchange of ideas and knowledge between diverse groups of the scientific community concerned by current issues in environmental science, engineering, management, planning and economics. The 1st, 3rd and 10th CEMEPE conferences were successfully completed in the picturesque Skiathos island in June 2007, 2011 and 2023 respectively; the 2nd, 4th, 5th, 7th and 9th were held in the famous island of Mykonos in 2009, 2013, 2015, 2019 and 2022, the 6th and 8th took place in the city of Thessaloniki in June 2017 and in July 2021 respectively and the 11th was held in Lefkada island in June 2024. The current 12th CEMEPE takes place in Mykonos island, Greece. A total of 115 manuscripts are included in the conference proceedings. Participants from more than 20 countries contributed their work to the conference. A book of proceedings including all the participations was edited and published as e-proceedings in a CD-ROM complete with ISBN number. Participations have been classified in the following topics:

- Advances in Water and Wastewater Treatment (10)
- Ecotoxicology and environmental toxicology (19)
- Pollution monitoring and remediation (10)
- Energy and Environment (9)
- Environmental impact assessment and risk analysis (18)
- Industrial Symbiosis and Sustainable Production (17)
- Global climate change (9)
- ARSINOE Project Special Session (4)
- NexusNet COST Action Special Session (7)
- Advances in Environmental Sciences (5)
- Environmental Education (7)

The editors would like to thank and acknowledge the aid of the following:

- The SECOTOX Society for being eager to organize a joint event with CEMEPE;
- The participating authors for their scientific contribution;
- The reviewers of the participating submissions for their invaluable help;
- The sponsors of the 12th CEMEPE Conference for their financial support, which has enabled keeping the fees at a reasonable cost;
- All participants for their involvement in the exchange of knowledge, know-how and ideas, which is the essence of this conference;
- Grafima Publications for their collaboration as well as for their contribution to the editing of both the book of abstracts and the e-proceedings.

Athanassios Kungolos
Chrysi Laspidou
Konstantinos Aravossis
Paraschos Melidis
Georgios Kyzas
Antigoni Zafirakou
Christina Emmanouil
Vicky Manakou

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**Twelfth International Conference on Environmental Management,
Engineering, Planning and Economics (CEMEPE 2025)
and SECOTOX Conference**

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Organized by:

- Division of Hydraulics and Environmental Engineering, School of Civil Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
- Society of Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety (SECOTOX)

In collaboration with:

- Sector of Industrial Management and Operations Research, School of Mechanical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Greece
- Department of Civil Engineering, University of Thessaly, Greece
- Department of Environmental Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece
 - Department of Chemistry, Democritus University of Thrace, Greece

Under the aegis of:

School of Civil Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

May 25-29, 2025 • Mykonos island, Greece

18:30-19:30 Registration (Imperial Mykonian Resort)

19:30-21:00 CEMEPE/SECOTOX Conference opening session
Chairs: **A. Kungolos, G. Kyzas, K. Aravossis, C. Laspidou**

Opening remarks by officials

Invited lectures

**From waste to worth: unlocking biowaste potential
for zero waste and carbon neutrality**

Professor M. Loizidou

**Transforming and integrating sewage sludge with biochar
for enhanced soil applications**

Professor P. Oleszczuk

M. Raczkiwicz, A. Rombel, A. Siatecka, A. Bogusz, M. Stefaniuk, P. Oleszczuk

**Role of Regulation in Advancing Solid Waste Management:
A Literature Review**

Professor K. Aravossis

K. Aravossis, K. Yenouzi, K. Mouka

21:00 Welcoming reception at Imperial Mykonian Resort

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Monday, May 26, 2025 | Day 2

ROOM A	
Advances in Water and Wastewater Treatment <i>Chairs: P. Ziegler, G. Kyzas</i>	
09:00-09:15	Static multi-commodity network flow model for closed-loop water-supply chains management. <i>D.-P. Gerakinis</i>
09:15-09:30	Cold atmospheric plasma for effective degradation of PFAS in water: Comparative reactor study and optimization. <i>K. Papalexopoulou, M.H. Belay, F. Dondero, C.A. Aggelopoulos</i>
09:30-09:45	Phytoremediation of heavy metal-contaminated waters and disposal of the bioaccumulated metals. <i>P. Ziegler</i>
09:45-10:00	Plasma-activated zinc foil as a synergistic immobilized catalyst with plasma bubbles for antibiotic degradation in water. <i>D. Tsokanas, S. Meropoulis, C.A. Aggelopoulos</i>
10:00-10:15	Explosive contaminants in soil and groundwater: A comprehensive review of remediation strategies. <i>C. Mystrioti, N. Papassiopi, A. Xenidis</i>
10:15-10:30	Improving water management on smallholder farms in Limpopo Province, South Africa. <i>J. Lindblom, F. M. Murungweni, C. Hagberg, R. Coetzee, G. du Preez</i>
10:30-10:45	Cold plasma for activation and regeneration of adsorbents used for perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) removal from water. <i>S. Giannoulia, C.A. Aggelopoulos</i>
10:45-11:00	Artificial intelligence in water management: a case study on ChatGPT's role in water network clustering <i>L. Palma, E. Creaco, M. Iervolino, D. Marocco, G. F. Santonastaso, A. Di Nardo</i>
11:00-11:15	Hexavalent chromium removal from water and wastewater by adsorption onto modified activated carbons derived from olive stones. <i>A. K. Tolkou, K. N. Maroulas, I. Moschou, G. Z. Kyzas</i>
11:15-11:30	Beneficial aspects of in-situ non-metal-doped carbocatalysts for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern from wastewater. <i>S. Panić, N. Vasiljević, M. Petronijević, I. Antić, J. Živančev, N. Đurišić-Mladenović</i>
11:30-12:00 COFFEE BREAK	
ROOM A	
Industrial Symbiosis and Sustainable Production I <i>Chairs: P. Papadaki, F. Rögener</i>	
12:00-12:15	Assessment of bagasse and vinasse management for the advancement of circular economy in Campos dos Goytacases' sugar energetic industry. <i>F. Rögener, F. Cancino Schweikart, S. Schlüter</i>

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Monday, May 26, 2025 | Day 2

12:15-12:30	Improving sustainable production in construction: Field studies in current issues and end-user needs in IT Document Management. G. E. Giannadakis, P. Arsenos, M. Chalikias, P. Kalantonis
12:30-12:45	Valorization of lignite fly ash and waste glass into novel nickel-reinforced ceramic composites, under the circularity concept. E. Markopoulos, X. Spiliotis, A. Kyrgiazoglou, A. Stimoniaris, K. Tsanaktsidis, V. Karayannis
12:45-13:00	3D printing and topology optimization: assessing key sustainability aspects. A. Chortis, A. Iliadi-Manou, K. Katakalos, K. Tsikaloudaki
13:00-13:15	Study of the removal of the herbicide metribuzin from aqueous solutions by using organic hydrogels. P. Souliou, A. Sklavounou, H. Grilla, A.A. Ioannidi, H. Kalorizou, M. Papadaki, V. Bekiari
13:15-13:30	Application of nano-magnetite-chitosan adsorbent for removal of emerging contaminants in different environmental media S. Šemčuk, D. Montvydienė, K. Jokšas, G. Lujanienė, V. Pakštas, A. Selskis, K. Mažeika, M. Talaikis, N. Kazlauskienė, R. Butrimienė, Ž. Jurgelėnė
13:30-13:45	Enhancing awareness and engagement of students and young researchers on New Genomic Techniques to increase the food system sustainability. E. Sturchio, P. Boccia, M. Zanellato
13:45-14:00	Pro-environmental behavior under risk and ambiguity: evidence from a lab experiment. R. Caferra, A. Morone, P. Morone
14:00-14:15	Optimizing Safety Stock Levels for Aircraft Spare Parts under Uncertainty and Circular Economy Principles K. Kontodimou, K. Kepatsoglou
14:15-14:30	Optional poster presentations

14:30-16:00

LUNCH BREAK

ROOM A	
	Ecotoxicology and Environmental Toxicology <i>Chairs: K. Costil, L. Manusadžianas</i>
16:00-16:15	Comparative evaluation of extraction methods on the bioactive compounds and antimicrobial properties of <i>Cercis siliquastrum</i>. G. Serifi, M. Dormousoglou, A.A. Ioannidi, E. Giannakopoulos, S. Santzouk, H. Kalorizou, G. Salachas, V. Bekiari, M. Papadaki
16:15-16:30	Assessment of the geochemical availability and ecological risk of trace metals in marine sediments of the Tremiti Islands. M. Fattobene, R. E. Russo, M. Berrettoni, M.D. Galindo-Riaño
VIRTUAL ROOM B	
	Industrial Symbiosis and Sustainable Production II <i>Chairs: I. Giannakis, S.H.S. Osama</i>
16:00-16:15	Manufacturing and theoretical processes of BIT: fabrication devices processes. S.H.S. Osama
16:15-16:30	An improved support vector regression model for the prediction of WEEE in Turkey. T. Ozcan, O. Yucel, A. K. Konyalioğlu

ROOM A		VIRTUAL ROOM B	
16:30-16:45	<p>Effects of 21-day exposure to copper and high temperatures on the survival, behaviour and physiology of female shrimp, <i>Palaemon serratus</i>. K. Costil, C. Guegan, R. Coulaud, C. Caplat, A. Serpentinini</p>	<p>Environmental Impact Assessment and Risk Analysis I <i>Chairs: F. Gagné, A. K. Konyalioğlu</i></p>	<p>Revisiting wastewater forecasting in Istanbul: An optimised grey Bernoulli modelling approach. A. K. Konyalioğlu, T. Apaydin, T. Ozcan</p>
16:45-17:00	<p>An integrated approach to investigate the potential effects of environmental and occupational exposure to microplastics. S. Mauro, P. Boccia, Zanellato, E. Sturchio</p>		<p>Plastic contamination and water quality assessment of urban wastewaters. F. Gagné, S.A. Smyth, C. André</p>
17:00-17:15	<p>Ecological impacts of military activities and climate change on Ukraine's aquatic ecosystems. N. Matvienko, D. Montvydienė, O. Lyanzberch</p>		<p>PM10 concentration distribution in surface layer of the atmosphere of Kutaisi city, Georgia - during calm weather. A. Surmava, N. Gigauri, L. Intskirveli, G. Dumbadze</p>
17:15-17:30	<p>Ecotoxicity of hybrid alkali cements on the marine ecosystem by aquatic toxicity bioassays: Bioluminescence and sea urchin embryogenesis. V. Muñoz-Ruiz, J. Santos, E. Cifrián, A. Rodríguez-Romero, A. Fernandez-Jimenez, A. Palomo, A. Andrés</p>		
17:30-17:45	<p>Bioassays as a tool to evaluate the efficiency of diesel-contaminated soil remediation. J. Žaltauskaitė, A. Dikšaitytė, G. Sujetovienė, D. Gimžauskaitė, M. Aikas, R. Uscila, J. Eimontas</p>		<p>Abandoned in the sea: fishing related debris in the seabed of Northern and Central Aegean. N. Kamidis, D. Karampetsis, S. Triantafyllidis, M. Koutrakis</p>

ROOM A	
Environmental Impact Assessment and Risk Analysis II	
<i>Chairs: N. Mihalopoulos, E. Sturchio</i>	
09:00-09:15	RNA sequencing technology as a new approach to investigate microplastics emerging issue. <i>M. Zanellato, F. Santini, P. Boccia, E. Sturchio</i>
09:15-09:30	Evolution of the Italian Environmental Information Systems: synergies between data sharing systems and research. A case study within the EU Water4All Partnership. <i>V. Laterza, A. Lotti, L. Perin, M.C. Sole</i>
09:30-09:45	Analysing citizens' perceptions and behavioural responses to transport-related air pollution through a mixed-methods survey approach <i>A. Balatsoukas, I. Tyligada, G. Tseva, G. Chatzinaikos, A. Zachariadou, G. Adamos, C. Laspidou</i>
09:45-10:00	Real-Time Source Apportionment Using the ACSM-Xact-Aethalometer (AXA) System and SoFi RT Software. <i>M. Manousakas, O. Zografou, F. Canonaco, E. Diapouli, S. Papagiannis, M. Gini, V. Vassilatou, A. Tobler, S. Vratolis, K. Daelenbach, J. Slowik, A. Prevot, K. Eleftheriadis</i>
10:00-10:15	Analysis of solid wastes in Pieria's ports: The impact of tourism and fishing <i>M. Amanatidou, S. Galinou-Mitsoudi, C. A. Papadimitriou</i>
10:15-10:30	Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from stickney WRP in Chicago. <i>M. Amouamouha</i>
10:30-10:45	Dynamic surface leaching and release controlling mechanisms of blast furnace slag binders <i>I. Salas, E. Cifrián, V. Muñoz-Ruiz, A. Fernandez-Jimenez, O. Maltseva, A. Palomo, A. Andrés</i>
10:45-11:00	Application of GIS technology as a base of AI tools for remediation of brownfield sites containing NORM residues <i>I. Prlić, Ž. Veinović, L. Pavelić, D. Perković</i>
11:00-11:15	Green innovation and environmental performance: the role of economic interactions and technological contaminations across industries. <i>F. Zilia, I. De Noni, L. Orsi, S. Stranieri</i>
11:15-11:30	Assessment of water quality in Muratlı Dam Lake based on selected physicochemical parameters <i>K. Özseker, A. Şahin, Ö. H. Durrani, Ş. Atasaral, K. Seyhan</i>
11:30-11:45	Mobility of elements from tailings produced of low-grade, vanadium-bearing titanomagnetite ores <i>K. Komnitsas, D. Vathi</i>

11:45-12:15

COFFEE BREAK and POSTER PRESENTATIONS

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Tuesday, May 27, 2025 | Day 3

ROOM A	
	Plenary Talk <i>Chairs: A. Alexopoulos, F. Öztürk</i>
12:15-12:30	Environmental impact of climatic relevant particulate species emitted by shipping in the Eastern Mediterranean. <i>N. Mihalopoulos, V. Assimakopoulos, K.-M. Fameli, E. Fragkou, S. Genitsaris, A. Gogou, M. Moustaka-Gouni, G. Grivas, I. Hatzianestis, I. Kapsomenakis, V. Kolovoyiannis, A. Kotrikla, E. Krasakopoulou, N. Liora, A.A. Mazioti, L. Ntziachristos, C. Parinos, A. Poupkou, A. Progiou, E. Skylaki, S. Solomos, M. Tsagkaraki, G. Tsegas, E. Tragou, V. Zervakis</i>
	Global Climate Change <i>Chairs: A. Muhammetoglu, J. Žaltauskaitė</i>
12:30-12:45	Climate change impact on road networks: Investigation of slopes erosion due to insufficient hydraulics. <i>E.Tagkas, F.Kehagia</i>
12:45-13:00	Regional benchmarks for water footprint of crops. <i>S. Symeonidou, D. Vagiona, C. Laspidou, D. F.Lekkas</i>
13:00-13:15	Improving efficiency & reliability in urban water distribution systems for combating climate change. <i>A. Muhammetoglu, T. Akdeniz, P. Orhan, O. Sütçü, E. Akdemir, E. Kildiran, C. Oğuz, M. Sapiano, H. Muhammetoglu</i>
13:15-13:30	Greenhouse application of boron carbon oxynitride (BCNO) nanocomposite material as novel luminescent solar concentrator. Effects on growth and organoleptic quality of lettuce and basil plants. <i>S.A. Barla, V. Giannakopoulos, E. Pitsika, E. Stathatos, G. Lykokanellos, C. Stefanou, A. Alexopoulos, G. Salachas</i>
13:30-13:45	Technical assessment of a hybrid renewable energy system for meeting water and electricity demand on the island of Mykonos. <i>I. Platanitis, A.-F. Papatheanasiou, E. Baltas</i>
13:45-14:00	Desalination technology-is the answer to water scarcity on the Greek Islands? <i>E.Tzen</i>
14:00-14:15	Carbon pools and CO₂ equivalents in oak forest ecosystems. <i>K. Radoglou, S. Zacharoudi, G. Spyroglou, M. Fotelli, E. Milios, K. Kitikidou</i>
14:15-14:30	Optional poster presentations
14:30-16:00	LUNCH BREAK

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Tuesday, May 27, 2025 | Day 3

ROOM A	
ARSINOE Project Special Session	
<i>Chairs: G. Adamos, D. Likar</i>	
16:00-16:15	Integrated cross - sectoral adaptiveness to water scarcity induced by climate changes and economy growth. <i>D. Likar, Z. Ilijovski, I. Nikoloski, A. Bozinov</i>
16:15-16:30	Enhancing sustainability in transboundary regions: stakeholder engagement for climate resilience in Ohrid and Prespa Lakes under the H2020 ARSINOE Project. <i>S. Kasovska Georgieva, D. Likar, S. Trajkovska, O. Roussos, T. Grigoriadou, N. Lalaj, I. La Jeunesse</i>
16:30-16:45	Maximizing the legacy of the ARSINOE Project: innovation, policy, and sustainability. <i>L. Pourcher, N. Olivier</i>
16:45-17:00	Supportive tools for increasing urban resilience against heatwaves. <i>D. Kofinas, G. Adamos, K. Ziliaskopoulos, G. Papangelis, E. Athanasopoulou, N. Votsi, S. Papageorgiou, C. Crilly, G. Lewis, S. Mimis, N. Mustafee, A. Chen, L. Vamvakieridou, C. Laspidou</i>
ROOM A	
NEXUSNET COST Action Special Session	
<i>Chairs: D. Kofinas, A. Spyropoulou</i>	
17:00-17:15	Decoupling Nexus interlinkages: strategies for urban resilience <i>D. Kofinas, C. M. Kazezyilmaz-Alhan, G. Adamos, S. Caucci, T. Radjenovic, D. Đorđević, T. Dasic, C. Calheiros, N. Nikolova, D. Vasovic, D. Likar, M. Lazreg, E. Hewelke, J. Guzman, M. Nones, S. Milliken, M. Rajic, A. Spyropoulou, M. Akin, K. Koca, M. Sertić Perić, K. I. Demirezen, G. A. Chatzistefanou, M. Falda, H.-Y. Liu, C. F. M. Rivera, A. Balatsoukas, M. Suskevics, J. Domínguez-Soberanes, B. Taiwo, V. Vasilíć, R. Pineda-Martos, I. Zekker, S. Munaretto, F. Brouwer, C. Laspidou</i>
17:15-17:30	Investigating flood-driven Nexus interlinkages: insights into strengthening urban resilience in changing climate conditions. <i>T. Radenović, G. Adamos, S. Caucci, D. Kofinas, C. M. Kazezyilmaz-Alhan, D. Đorđević, T. Dašić, N. Nikolova, D. Vasović</i>
17:30-17:45	WEFE Nexus interlinkages in the context of wildfire-induced extreme events: evidence from Mediterranean case studies. <i>A. Spyropoulou, J. Guzman, S. Caucci, M. Nones, L. Giammateo, S. Milliken, M. Rajić, D. Kofinas, C. Laspidou</i>
17:45-18:00	Unpacking the role of participatory approaches as catalysts for co-design in climate adaptation. Lessons from multiple case studies. <i>A. Spyropoulou A., C. Laspidou</i>
18:00-18:15	Groundwater numerical modelling in semiarid regions as a tool to support sustainability with a Water-Food-Energy Nexus focus: a case study. <i>C. F. M. Rivera</i>
18:15-18:30	Urban and peri-urban agriculture and WEFE Nexus approach for biodiversity conservation and sustainable urban futures. <i>M. Falda, S. Caucci, D. Karthe, J. Guzman</i>
18:30-18:45	Exploring the development of a disaster risk management methodology to enhance urban and peri-urban resilience. <i>A. Balatsoukas, G. Adamos</i>

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Wednesday, May 28, 2025 | Day 4

Optional field trip

BANQUET

21:00

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CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Thursday, May 29, 2025 | Day 5

ROOM A	
Advances in Environmental Sciences <i>Chairs: A. Donati, K. Radoglou</i>	
09:00- 09:15	Integrating archaeology and physical chemistry for a new approach to archaeological surveys. <i>V. Volpi, L. Dallai, A. Bardi, C. Rossi, A. Donati</i>
09:15- 09:30	The application of Material Flow Analysis as an Approach towards the Estimation of Materials Circularity in WEEE Management. <i>K. Poullos, G. Perkoulidis, D. Voulkogou</i>
Environmental Education <i>Chairs: S. Stylianidis, P. Morone</i>	
09:30-09:45	Impact of virtual reality application and digital transformation on water education. <i>M. Ćirić, A. Đorđević, M. Gocić and V. Milošević</i>
09:45-10:00	Urban vineyards as a nexus: harnessing citizen science for environmental sustainability, community engagement, and science-society integration. <i>A. Bakousi, E. Karachaliou, I. Tavantzis, Z. E. Tsifodimou, C. Emmanouil, M. Partalidou, E. Stylianidis</i>
10:00-10:15	UN Sustainable Development Goals - A challenge for industrial and social development with a sustainable future. The case for development through the creation of a corresponding culture, starting from Preschool Education - How are the foundations laid in preschool? <i>V. Tryfona, C. Panagopoulou, E. Panagopoulou, N. Charalampidis, A. Kungolos</i>
Energy and Environment <i>Chairs: J. Lindblom, A. Grigoriadis</i>	
10:15-10:30	Increasing the water production of solar stills through forced convection and external condensation. <i>J. Lindblom, J. Ekstedt</i>
10:30-10:45	Low-grade waste heat applied to farmland in Northern Sweden for increased food productivity. <i>M. Södergren, J. Lindblom</i>
10:45-11:00	Load-dependent shipping emission factors considering alternative fuels, biofuels and emission control technologies. <i>A. Grigoriadis, T. Chountalas, E. Fragkou, D. Chountalas, L. Ntziachristos</i>
11:00-11:15	Institutional allocation of regulatory powers in the field of energy waste and water. A comparative perspective. <i>A. Gourzi, G. Loizos</i>
11:15- 11:30	Possible enhanced levels of natural radioactivity originating from NORM while performing the construction works at the site of new coal storage dome of the Thermal Power Plant. <i>Prlić, Ž. Veinović, L. Pavelić</i>

A01	Valorization of brewery spent grain through chitin extraction from black soldier fly larvae. J. J. R. Luna, V. C. Rabell, C. Gutiérrez Antonio, S. Bedia, E. Ieronymaki, E. Giannakopoulos, V. Bekiari, P. Souliou, M. Papadaki	A11	<i>Mytilopsis leucophaea</i> (Conrad, 1831) as a sentinel species to monitor the environmental state in brackish waters: a case study in four populations in Normandy (France). A. Serpentine, A. Levallois, G. Conseil, J. Muller, E. Chapuis, C. Roger, C. Caplat, K. Costil
A02	Unveiling the bio-control potential of <i>Myrtus communis</i> L. extracts against phytopathogenic bacteria. A. Kapsimalis, M. Dormousoglou, K. Droukas, E. Giannakopoulos, M. Papadaki	A12	Toxicity of commercial sunscreens on <i>Artemia franciscana</i>: rethinking eco-friendly claims. V. Aranda-Quirós, M. Úbeda-Manzanaro and A. Rodríguez-Romero
A03	Understanding household waste source separation: an integrative review of Theory of Planned Behaviour and key extensions. S.-E. Chachami-Chalioti, C. Emmanouil, A. Kungolos	A13	Acute toxicity in war-affected waters: evaluating risk to aquatic crustaceans. B. Gyltė, D. Montvydienė, Ž. Jurgelėnė, N. Matviienko, S. Skrotzkyi
A04	Public perception and environmental significance of non-chemical fertilizers. A. Bakousi, I. Skalidi, A. Skondras, C. Emmanouil, E. Stylianidis	A14	Impact of rare earth metal-based nanoparticles on <i>Daphnia magna</i>: the correlation between nanotoxicity and physico-chemical properties. R. Butrimienė, D. Montvydienė, N. Kazlauskienė, Ž. Jurgelėnė
A05	The NEO-CYCLE approach to circularity: upcycling NdFeB permanent magnets from waste of electrical and electronic equipment. R. Dagliūtė, J. Žaltauskaitė, G. Sujetovienė	A15	Assessing the impact of water from war-affected areas of Ukraine on test-organisms. D. Montvydienė, J. Karosienė, R. Butrimienė, N. Kazlauskienė, N. Matviienko, S. Skrotzkyi, Ž. Jurgelėnė
A06	Physicochemical characterization and ecotoxicological assessment of municipal biosolids for sustainable agricultural use I. Giannakis, C. Emmanouil, E.E. Golia, S.G. Papadimou, D. Alexiou, A. Kungolos	A16	Effects of upconverting nanoparticles on photosynthetic pigments and oxidative stress of the green alga <i>Desmodesmus communis</i>. Ž. Jurgelėnė, D. Montvydienė, J. Karosienė, E. Ežerskytė, T. Mustafa, R. Butrimienė, V. Klimkevičius
A07	Twinning green-editing vibes for food-The CREDIT Vibes project. D. Papadopoulou, M. Giortsou, C. Kopra, A. G. Kuhar, A. Žibrat Gašparič, K. Petrović	A17	The impact of modified biochars on the adsorption of anions from water. Ling-Syuan Tzeng, Chih Ming Tsai, Hsin-Liang Huang
A08	“RiViVe” - Education perspectives for rethinking biodiversity in a transdisciplinary and collaborative way. A. L’Astorina, A. De Lazzari, A. Pugnetti, D. Fontaneto, G. Matteucci, N. Vuolo, N. Margnelli, A. Caretto, R. Spagna	A18	DMAIC-driven improvements in optical lens inspection equipment for production efficiency and sustainability. Chih-Ming Tsai, Hsin-Liang Huang, Jia-Fang Wang, Jia-Uei Chan

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Poster Presentations | Monday, May 26, 2025

A09	<p>A comparative study examining women's childbirth satisfaction in relation to hospitals' pro-environmental design.</p> <p><i>I. Gertner Moryossef</i></p>	A19	<p>Study of the potential environmental impacts of anticorrosion protections commonly used in the offshore renewable energy industry, including galvanic anodes cathodic protections (GACP) and impressed current (ICCP) - the ECOCAP project.</p> <p><i>A. Caplat, N. Zitouni, A. Serpentina, K. Costil, M. Blanc-Legendre, X. Cousin, G. Guichard, J-L. Boudenne, G. Martin, C. Leballeur, N. Michelet, V. Faure, G. Safi, M. Dussauze</i></p>
A10	<p>Advanced wastewater treatment for water recovery using reverse osmosis: hydraulic performance, effluent quality and costs.</p> <p><i>T. Zioga, A. Eftaxias, D. Marmanis, V. Diamantis</i></p>	A20	<p>Elevated temperature influence on pesticide terbuthylazine toxicity to duckweed <i>Lemna minor</i>.</p> <p><i>D. Miškelytė, J. Žaltauskaitė, L. Manusadžianas</i></p>

B01	<p>Enhancing PFAS risk characterization through a cloud-based PBK model repository. <i>P. Tsiros, V. Minadakis, P. Papakyriakopoulou, A. Arvanitidis, H. Sarimveis</i></p>	B12	<p>Spatial distributions and temporal trends (2009–2020) of pesticide mixtures in streams and rivers across Lombardy region (Italy). <i>A. Tosadori, A. Di Guardo, A. Finizio</i></p>
B02	<p>Microbiological assessment state of water reservoirs in Kyiv region that have suffered as a result of Russian aggression. <i>S. Skrotskyi, L. Khomenko, O. Vasyliuk, L. Artiukh, D. Montvydiene, N. Matviienko</i></p>	B13	<p>Performance assessment and data analysis of low-cost air quality sensors within the framework of the LIFE City TRAQ project. <i>D. Brzoja, M. Kvakić, V. Milić, V. Gugec, S. Šarčević, V. Jagić</i></p>
B03	<p>Hydrological analysis of long-term post-fire conditions in a subbasin of the Alfeios River, Greece. <i>A. Bournas, M. Moschou, E. Baltas</i></p>	B14	<p>Contaminants of emerging concern in the water of the Danube-Tisa-Danube canal, Vojvodina Province, Serbia. <i>J. Živančev, I. Antić, M. Buljovčić, D. Rakić, N. Đurišić-Mladenović</i></p>
B04	<p>The improvement of the status of hake stocks in the Mediterranean requires effective combinations of tailor-made management. <i>V. Vassilopoulou, M. M. Brodersen</i></p>	B15	<p>Fluoride removal from aqueous solutions by using hybrid super-adsorbents of chitosan/orange peels/activated carbon functionalized with MgO. <i>A. K. Tolkou, A. Posantzis, K. N. Maroulas, R. I. Kosheleva and G. Z. Kyzas</i></p>
B05	<p>Assessment of potential health risk of contaminants in soils in urban areas around the steel industrial zone of Volos (Greece). <i>G. Charvalas, A. Molla, C. Emmanouil, A. Lolas, E. Skoufogianni, A. Kyparissis, O. Christopoulou</i></p>	B16	<p>Assessment of freshwater pollution in Ukraine: impacts and prospects for ecological restoration. <i>N. Savenko, A. Kucheruk, S. Skrotskyi, N. Matviienko</i></p>
B06	<p>One health applied to zoonotic diseases. <i>P. Tomao, S. Di Renzi, P. Mellis, S. Ullah Khan, E. Sturchio, N. Vonesch</i></p>	B17	<p>Introduction of microbial concentrates as the basis of biotechnology for accelerated damage recovery due to hostilities in water bodies. <i>S. Skrotskyi, L. Khomenko, O. Vasyliuk, L. Artiukh, D. Montvydiene, N. Matviienko</i></p>
B07	<p>Achelooos River in Greece: a paradigm for local Governance to achieve Environmental Water Justice. <i>D. Koumparou, Z. Nivolianitou</i></p>	B18	<p>Behavior of antifouling paint particles in artificial seawater. <i>A. Nakamura, R. Nozaki, Y. Horie, C. Emmanouil, H. Okamura</i></p>

CONFERENCE PROGRAM

Poster Presentations | Monday, May 26, 2025

B08	Climate resilience of trees in urban areas through the science of phenology. <i>D. Papagiannopoulou, T. Tsitsoni</i>	B19	The role of fluorescence techniques in monitoring aquatic ecosystem health impacted by pollution. <i>Z. Romanowska-Duda, A. Kaźmierczak, M. Król, C. Emmanouil, A. Kungolos</i>
B09	Techno-economic assessment of MEA absorption and membrane separation technologies for carbon capture in maritime industry. <i>C. Siskos, G. Romanos, G. Charalambopoulou, T. Steriotis</i>	B20	Assessing the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect using Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Normalized Difference Built up Index (NDBI) indexes: The case study of Paphos, Cyprus <i>C. Demetriou, D. Hadjimitsis, G. Papadavid, K. Themistocleous, D. Abade</i>
B10	Development of a green hydrogen production system to cover water and electricity needs on Kythera. <i>V.-P. Sarla, K. Braimakis, S. Karellas, E. Baltas</i>	B21	Estimating Crop Water Requirements using Earth Observation for promoting low Carbon Agriculture <i>G. Papadavid, D. Hadjimitsis, G. Kountios, C. Demetriou</i>
B11	Drought impact on the nitrogen use efficiency in the swards of different botanical composition. <i>G. Šidlauskaitė, A. Dikšaitytė, J. Žaltauskaitė</i>	B22	Preliminary data on the distribution and risk assessment of bisphenol A, phthalates, and heavy metals in <i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> from Naples (Italy) coastal waters <i>L. Borriello, M. Scivicco, N. A. Cacciola, F. Esposito, S. Velotto, B. De Simone, T. Cirillo, L. Severino</i>

***Advances in Water
and Wastewater Treatment***

Hexavalent chromium removal from water and wastewater by adsorption onto modified activated carbons derived from olive stones

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Abstract

Drinking water pollution with high concentrations of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) concerns millions of people around the world, including Greece. The new European Commission directive on drinking water (DIRECTION (EU) 2020/2184), reduced the relevant acceptable limit of Cr(VI), from 50 µg/L, which is still in force, to 25 µg/L Cr(VI) from 2036 onwards, while in Greece, in inland waters, e.g. rivers and lakes, the limit is 3 µg/L (Government Gazette 1909/B/08-12-2010). Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop effective techniques that will produce water with very low concentrations of Cr(VI). In the present study, novel adsorbent materials were developed based on activated carbon derived from food waste recycling, such as olive stones (OSAC), which are appropriately modified with functional groups, such as La-O, that can successfully bind hexavalent chromium from water. Non-modified activated carbon does not efficiently adsorb Cr(VI) and should be further modified by incorporating functional groups into its structure that are effective in binding Cr(VI). Lanthanum (La) is a relatively low-cost element, used as an additive to modify the surface of adsorbents, displaying a very strong affinity for ions such as phosphate, fluoride and chromium. In this study, a new modified with La₂O₃, activated carbon derived from olive stones (abbreviated hereafter OSAC@La₂O₃) was prepared for the removal of Cr(VI). The effect of adsorbent dosage, pH value, contact time and initial Cr(VI) concentration was examined to determine the feasibility of the proposed adsorbents. According to the results obtained, it was found that at pH 3.0±0.1 by applying 0.5 g/L of OSAC@La₂O₃ in 2 mg/L of Cr(VI), total removal (99.8%) was achieved. For a better understanding and interpretation of the adsorption process, kinetic and isothermal models were applied, as well as thermodynamic analysis. In addition, the structure and morphology of the resulting adsorbents were studied in detail by applying BET, XRD, FTIR and SEM techniques, which confirmed the existence of lanthanum in the structure of unmodified OSAC.

Keywords: hexavalent chromium, activated carbon, olive stones, lanthanum

Fate of Explosive Contaminants in Soil and Groundwater: A Comprehensive Review of Remediation Strategies

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Abstract

The contamination of soil and groundwater by explosive compounds, such as TNT and RDX, poses significant environmental and public health risks. This study provides a comprehensive review of the fate of these contaminants and the various remediation strategies employed to mitigate their impact. This study covers physical, chemical, and biological approaches, highlighting their effectiveness, challenges, and applicability. Physical methods, including excavation and disposal, are effective but often limited by high costs and logistical challenges. Chemical methods, such as oxidation and reduction, transform explosives into less toxic byproducts but require careful management to prevent secondary pollution. Biological remediation, utilizing plants and microorganisms, emerges as a cost-effective and sustainable alternative, though it faces challenges related to the persistence of explosive compounds and potential groundwater leaching. It should be noted that polluted areas need site-specific strategies that consider contaminant type, concentration, soil properties, and regulatory requirements. Integrated and sustainable remediation approaches are advocated, with a focus on pilot-scale applications to evaluate the practical effectiveness of various methods. This review concludes by assessing the advantages and disadvantages of different remediation techniques, providing insights into their duration, effectiveness, and cost.

Keywords: *soil contamination, explosives, TNT, RDX, soil remediation, groundwater remediation, environmental sustainability.*

Phytoremediation of heavy metal-contaminated waters and disposal of the bioaccumulated metals

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Abstract

Municipal, agricultural and industrial wastewaters and natural waters can contain numerous contaminants including nutrients, organic xenobiotics and metals. Metals, especially heavy metals (HMs) that originate from the exploitation of fossil fuels, metal smelting, the use of chemical fertilizers and sewage discharge are particular threats to organisms and aquatic ecosystems. They are non-biodegradable, persist in aquatic ecosystems and bioaccumulate in the food chain. Traditionally used physical and chemical technologies for remediation of HMs in contaminated sites are effective, but require complex procedures, are expensive and have relatively narrow application ranges. Bioremediation for HM removal from contaminated waters is more flexible, cost-effective, and free from side effects of secondary pollution. Several hydrophytes including water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*), watermilfoil (*Myriophyllum verticillatum*) and water lettuce (*Pistia stratiotes*), remove HMs from contaminated water and accumulate them in their tissues, but have relatively low removal efficiencies and high phytoremediation costs due to limited growth and HM enrichment capacity. Species of the Lemnaceae, or duckweeds, such as *Spirodela polyrhiza*, *Wolffia globosa* and several members of the genus *Lemna* are ideal for aquatic HM phytoremediation: they grow very rapidly, tolerate relatively high HM concentrations and take up HM at high removal efficiencies with high bioconcentration factors. They are also easy to cultivate, harvest and process.

Any aquatic plants used for the phytoremediation of HM-containing waters on a large scale produce large amounts of HM-rich biomass, the safe disposal of which has always been a challenge. Traditional means of disposing of unwanted biomass such as combustion, landfill, field-spreading as fertilizer and composting can all easily lead to reintroduction of HMs into the environment. The exploitation of HM-contaminated biomass by conversion to biogas, biofuels and organic chemicals leaves behind HM-containing residues. HMs have been traditionally reclaimed from contaminated biomass by environmentally non-friendly chemical means. However, a modern approach to making productive use of HM-contaminated biomass is the conversion of the biomass and its HM contents into value-added products for various HM-supported applications. The HMs can be immobilized on carbon derived from the biomass itself to form biochar as a metal-loading material that can serve further HM remediation in the forms of soil additives and absorbents. HM-containing biomass can also be processed into catalysts to facilitate many types of chemical reactions, capacitors for electrochemical purposes and antibacterial materials. The preparation and use of these derivatives of HM-containing biomass can help to round out the remediation of HM-contaminated waters in the sense of a circular economy.

Keywords: wastewater remediation, heavy metals, duckweeds, contaminated biomass, functional derivatives

Plasma-activated zinc foil as a synergistic immobilized catalyst with plasma bubbles for antibiotic degradation in water

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Abstract

As water scarcity continues to intensify, the need for innovative and efficient water treatment methods has become critical. Antibiotics are among the emerging recalcitrant pollutants due to their widespread use and the associated rise of antimicrobial resistance. Cold atmospheric plasma (CAP) has emerged as a highly competitive, rapid, and cost-effective advanced oxidation process (AOP) for degrading contaminants in water. This technology relies on electrical discharges that generate reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS), energetic electrons, and ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The plasma-induced chemistry in water facilitates the rapid oxidation and mineralization of organic pollutants. The remediation efficiency, both in terms of energy consumption and degradation performance, can be further enhanced by integrating plasma technology with catalysis (plasma-catalysis). A critical aspect of plasma-catalysis is the immobilization of catalysts to enable their easy removal after plasma treatment and to prevent secondary pollution.

In this study, the synergistic effect of plasma discharges and zinc (Zn) foil was investigated for the degradation of the antibiotic sulfamethoxazole (SMX). The Zn foil was pre-activated with plasma in water, subsequently oxidized to ZnO, and then used as an immobilized catalyst. Experiments were conducted in a dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) reactor designed to produce plasma bubbles directly within the aqueous medium. The Zn foil was characterized before and after plasma treatment using photoluminescence and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The electrical and optical characteristics of the plasma were analyzed, and the main reactive species ($\cdot\text{OH}$, O_3 , H_2O_2) were quantified both in the presence and absence of the activated Zn foil (immobilized ZnO). Finally, the effect of the plasma feed gas on the degradation of SMX was explored, comparing results with and without the immobilized ZnO catalyst.

Keywords: wastewater treatment, plasma bubbles, plasma-catalysis, catalyst immobilization, catalyst activation

Acknowledgments

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Improving Water Management on Smallholder Farms in Limpopo Province, South Africa

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Abstract

Freshwater availability is a critical concern for smallholder farmers in rural South Africa, where natural rainfall is often insufficient to meet agricultural needs. This study investigates the current management and utilization of freshwater resources in the village of Vhulaudzi, Limpopo province, and explores strategies to enhance water efficiency and agricultural productivity. Site investigations revealed significant water losses due to degraded irrigation infrastructure and inefficient furrow irrigation methods. Recommendations include improving conveyance efficiency through canal lining and adopting drip irrigation to reduce water consumption and increase crop yields. The study also highlights the need for better water quality management for livestock to ensure sustainable agricultural practices. Future research will focus on the impact of regenerative farming combined with drip irrigation on soil health and water efficiency, and developing solutions for improving water security for livestock. These efforts aim to contribute to sustainable socioeconomic development in the region.

Keywords: *irrigation efficiency, livestock productivity, smallholder farms, sustainable agriculture, water resources management*

Cold Plasma for Activation and Regeneration of Adsorbents Used for Perfluorooctanoic Acid (PFOA) Removal from Water

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Abstract

The persistence of perfluorochemicals (PFCs) has raised significant global concern in recent years, with perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) being one of the most commonly encountered PFCs. PFOA pollution in aquatic environments poses a serious threat to both the environment and human health, drawing considerable attention to its remediation. This study explores the use of cold plasma to activate and regenerate adsorbents for PFOA removal from water. Three types of adsorbents were examined and compared: biomass, mineral nanoclay, and nanotubes. Among these, biomass exhibited the lowest adsorption capacity. To enhance performance, walnut shells were activated using cold plasma before being employed as adsorbents for PFOA removal. Evaluating the adsorption performance of the plasma-activated material an increase of the maximum removal efficiency of PFOA (88%) was recorded compared to the pristine walnut shells (47%).

After multiple adsorption cycles, saturated walnut shells were effectively regenerated using plasma bubbling, requiring minimal energy (33.3 Wh/g-adsorbent). Notably, the regenerated adsorbents displayed even higher adsorption capacity during subsequent cycles compared to cold plasma-activated walnut shells. This improvement is attributed to the simultaneous regeneration of existing adsorption sites and the creation of new active sites on the adsorbent surface during the regeneration process. This study presents a green, sustainable, and highly effective alternative for water remediation.

Keywords: cold plasma, PFOA, adsorption, regeneration, activation.

Acknowledgments

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H.F.R.I.
Hellenic Foundation for
Research & Innovation

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Artificial Intelligence in Water Management: A Case Study on ChatGPT's Role in Water Network Clustering

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Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) tools such as ChatGPT into water distribution networks offers significant potential to enhance network management and optimize several operations. Defining clusters within a water network is a particularly challenging task due to the complexity of network topology, multiple operational constraints, and the need for balancing hydraulic performance. Traditionally, clustering water networks requires expert knowledge and the use of computationally intensive algorithms, as it involves creating coherent partitions that respect contiguity, minimize boundary pipes, and balance parameters such as water demand, node distribution, and pipe length. This study explores the application of ChatGPT in automating the clustering phase of distribution network partitioning, focusing on its ability to assist in the design of clusters. Using the water distribution network of Parete, Italy, as a case study - characterized by 184 demand nodes and 1 reservoir - ChatGPT was tasked with partitioning the network into 4 clusters with the use of different algorithms, including k-means, spectral clustering, and hierarchical clustering. In addition to partitioning the network, ChatGPT was evaluated for its ability to process EPANET files, generate detailed reports, visualize clustering results, and provide insights on clustering performance indices. The methodology was further validated using the larger and more complex water distribution network of Giugliano in Campania, Italy, which consists of 994 demand nodes and 5 intake points. Despite the increased complexity, ChatGPT successfully implemented clustering algorithms and generated solutions. While some challenges regarding node contiguity were identified in certain approaches, adjustments and validations ensured reliable results, demonstrating the scalability and adaptability of ChatGPT in managing diverse water network scenarios. This research highlights ChatGPT's potential as a tool for democratizing access to advanced water management techniques by enabling non-experts to perform complex tasks of water distribution management, such as clustering. However, the study also underscores the importance of expert oversight to address potential errors and refine results. Moving forward, the integration of ChatGPT with specialized hydraulic software and robust validation mechanisms could significantly enhance its role in water distribution management, bridging the gap between AI-driven insights and practical implementation.

Keywords: water distribution networks, clustering, artificial intelligence, ChatGPT

Static multi-commodity network flow model for closed-loop water-supply chains management

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Abstract

This paper proposes a mathematical model for the representation of closed-loop multi-type water supply chains as static multi-commodity flow networks and formulates the planning of cost-efficient water conveyance as a minimum cost flow optimization problem. The network includes storage, consumer, and purification nodes, with the latter representing water-treatment facilities capable of replenishing the water supply. Both consumer and purification nodes may have multi-type water demands, while only one type flows out, which may differ from the incoming types. Also, the concept of "water-type compatibility" is introduced, allowing compatible types to satisfy demands for others as substitutes. Finally, the model's robustness is evaluated on synthetically generated test problems, where each optimization problem is solved independently using four open-source linear programming solvers. The obtained results confirm the model's feasibility.

Keywords: *water management, closed-loop supply chains, static multi-commodity network flow problem, constrained optimization*

Cold atmospheric plasma for effective degradation of PFAS in water: Comparative reactor study and optimization

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Abstract

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of synthetic chemicals widely used as key components in numerous commercial products. Despite their industrial importance, PFAS are classified as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) due to their low degradability in the environment and high potential for bioaccumulation. Consequently, PFAS are frequently detected in various environmental matrices, including surface water, drinking water, and groundwater. Efforts to remove PFAS from water have involved various chemical, physical, and biological methods, but these approaches often face significant limitations, such as incomplete degradation, secondary pollution, and high energy consumption. Recently, cold atmospheric plasma (CAP) has emerged as a promising water remediation technology, offering a rapid, cost-effective, and environmentally friendly method for the destruction of emerging pollutants in water. CAP generates a wide range of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS), UV radiation, and high-energy electrons, which have been shown to effectively cleave the strong C-F bonds characteristic of PFAS.

This study aimed to evaluate the degradation of two types of PFAS in water - potassium heptadecafluorooctanesulfonate (PFOSK/C8) and perfluoropentanoic acid (PFPeA/C5) - using cold plasma. The influence of reactor configuration was investigated by comparing the performance of two plasma reactors: a gas-liquid dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) plasma reactor and an underwater plasma bubble reactor. Key parameters, including treatment time, plasma gas, water matrix, initial PFAS concentration, and the composition of plasma-treated water, were systematically explored. Additionally, the system's overall effectiveness was assessed through defluorination experiments. The findings of this study provide valuable insights for optimizing PFAS-contaminated water treatment using cold plasma technology.

Keywords: water treatment, Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), dielectric barrier discharge (DBD), plasma bubbles, defluorination

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Advanced wastewater treatment for water recovery using reverse osmosis: hydraulic performance, effluent quality and costs

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Abstract

The growing demand for clean water has intensified the need for innovative wastewater treatment technologies, particularly for water recovery and reuse. Reverse osmosis (RO) has emerged as a key technology for advanced treatment, offering high contaminant removal. This study evaluates the hydraulic performance and effluent quality of RO membranes operated under different pressures using wastewater from a coastal city in northern Greece. Experiments were conducted using a bench-scale RO system (ultra-low pressure element, surface area 0.46 m²), varying operating pressures from 3 to 5 bar to assess their impact on hydraulic performance, salt rejection and effluent quality. The secondary effluent used in the study had the following characteristics: pH = 7.5, COD 56 mg/L, BOD = 11 mg/L, TSS = 18 mg/L, TN = 8.1 mg/L and TP = 3.8 mg/L. Heavy metal concentrations were generally low, with values of Cr = 0.4 µg/L, Mn = 34 µg/L, Co = 0.5 µg/L, Zn = 80 µg/L, As = 7 µg/L, Mo = 3 µg/L, Cd < 0.1 µg/L, Hg = 0.2 µg/L and Pb = 0.2 µg/L. The secondary effluent exhibited electrical conductivity between 1700 and 2500 µS/cm, primarily due to seawater intrusion into the city's sewer network. The permeate contained negligible concentrations of COD, ammonia nitrogen, phosphorus, and heavy metals, with an electrical conductivity of 80-120 µS/cm, corresponding to salt rejection rate of 95%. However, nitrate nitrogen was not fully removed, with concentrations of 1 mg/L in the permeate. The permeate flux increased linearly from 20 to 35 L / m² h as the operating pressure increased from 3 to 5 bar, while the recovery factor rose exponentially from 12% to 35%. Notably, permeate quality remained unaffected by pressure variations. A preliminary techno-economic analysis for an RO facility treating 2000 m³/d of secondary effluent estimated a total treatment cost of 0.5-0.7 €/m³. The findings demonstrate that higher operating pressures enhance water recovery rates but also lead to increase energy consumption. This research contributed to the advancement of circular water management practices, promoting sustainable solutions for addressing global water scarcity.

Keywords: *water reuse, wastewater treatment, membrane filtration, water quality.*

***Ecotoxicology
and Environmental Toxicology***

Comparative Evaluation of Extraction Methods on the Bioactive Compounds and Antimicrobial Properties of *Cercis siliquastrum*

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Abstract:

This study aimed to investigate the influence of different extraction methods on the bioactive compounds and antimicrobial properties of *Cercis siliquastrum*. *Cercis siliquastrum*, commonly known as the Judas tree, is a deciduous tree native to southern Europe and western Asia. This plant has been traditionally used in folk medicine for its various therapeutic properties. Three extraction techniques were employed: Soxhlet, ultrasound, and percolation, using an 80:20 ethanol/water solvent. The extraction yield, total phenolic content (TPC), antioxidant activity (DPPH), and antimicrobial activity against *Escherichia coli* were evaluated. Results demonstrated that ultrasound extraction yielded the highest extraction efficiency (31.4 wt%), followed by percolation and Soxhlet. TPC analysis revealed a significant difference among the extracts, with ultrasound extracts exhibiting the highest TPC (6002.6 mg GAE/100g dry extract). Similarly, the antioxidant activity, measured by DPPH, was highest in Soxhlet extracts (5543.9 mg Trolox/1g dry extract). Antimicrobial testing against *E. coli* revealed that ultrasound extracts exhibited the most potent inhibitory activity, with a zone of inhibition of 23.66 mm at a concentration of 66.4 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Soxhlet and percolation extracts displayed moderate antimicrobial activity. In conclusion, this study highlights the impact of extraction methods on the bioactive compounds and antimicrobial properties of *Cercis siliquastrum*. Ultrasound extraction proved to be the most efficient method for recovering bioactive compounds, while Soxhlet extraction yielded extracts with superior antioxidant activity. The findings suggest the potential of *C. siliquastrum* as a natural source of bioactive compounds with antimicrobial properties

Keywords: antioxidant activity, antibacterial activity, ultrasound extraction, percolation, Soxhlet

Assessment of the Geochemical Availability and Ecological Risk of Trace Metals in Marine Sediments of the Tremiti Islands

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Abstract

This study aims to further characterize the environmental status of the Tremiti Islands Marine Protected Area (MPA) through an integrative assessment of sediment contamination. Building upon previous research, this study incorporates new sediment sampling campaigns conducted in 2023. The research focuses on grain size distribution analysis using sieving techniques and the determination of pseudo-metal concentrations and the evaluation of metal available fraction using BCR extraction method. This approach enables the evaluation of trace metal geochemical partitioning and potential effect over the environment and the biota. Additionally, pollution and ecological risk indices, including, Contamination indices (C_f , C_d and mCa), Enrichment factor (EF), Geoaccumulation Index (I_{geo}), Potential Ecological Risk Index ($PERI$) and Availability Index (AI) are applied to assess contamination levels and their potential environmental impact using Sediment Quality Guidelines (SEQs). These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of trace metal mobility, temporal variation and ecological risk in Mediterranean marine sediments.

Keywords: *ecological risk assessment, BCR, environmental monitoring, marine sediments, geochemical availability*

1. INTRODUCTION

Marine sediments function both as sinks and potential secondary sources of trace metals, depending on their physicochemical characteristics, which influence metal mobility and availability. Among these characteristics, grain size distribution plays a key role, as finer particles like silts and clays offer larger surface areas and higher cation exchange capacities, enhancing the adsorption of metals and organic contaminants [1]. Finer sediments are generally associated with higher contamination levels due to their capacity to retain metals, particularly in bioavailable and moderately available phases [2].

In the Mediterranean Sea, weak sea currents and shallow depths limit pollutant dispersion, favoring metal accumulation. The Tremiti Islands Marine Protected Area (MPA), located in the Adriatic Sea, represent a vulnerable zone subject to natural and anthropogenic pressures. To assess metal availability, both pseudo-total metal concentrations and the BCR (Community Bureau of Reference, European Commission) extraction method can be employed. This protocol allows to differentiate the available fraction (bioavailable and moderately available)

from the the residual phase, offering insight into mobility and potential geochemical and biological availability. The study integrates granulometric analysis, pseudo-total and fractionated metal assessment, and multivariate statistical tools such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Pearson correlations to explore relationships between metals and sediment texture. Additionally, contamination indices like the Igeo, PERI and SEQs are applied to quantify the severity and ecological implications of trace metal contamination [3] and the effect on biota.

This integrated analytical approach enables a comprehensive evaluation of metal distribution, sources, and associated environmental risks in the sediments of the Tremiti Islands.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Tremiti Islands constitute a small archipelago located in the Adriatic Sea. A targeted sampling campaign was conducted along the coastal marine environment of San Domino Island. The sites were selected following the detection of heavy metal accumulation in samples collected in July and September 2023 [4], as well as significant annual changes in the density and health of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows [5]. The designated sites - Cala Pagliai (P), Cala Matano (CM), Cala Spido (CS), and Grotta del Sale (GS) (Table 1) - are all located within the southern side of the island and are relatively close to one another (300-600 m) (Figure 1). The area features shallow sandy bottoms that support the growth and stability of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, and is geologically composed of layered carbonate rocks shaped by strong karstic, marine, and gravitational forces. On San Domino, karst landforms such as circular depressions and sinkholes are prominently developed, frequently incised into calccrete surfaces and infilled with wind-blown sands [6], [7]. The region is subject to elevated levels of marine traffic, primarily due to transportation routes and intense seasonal tourism. Sediment samples were obtained near the *P. Oceanica* bundles by scuba divers using 1000 mL PTFE bottles at the designated points. After collection, the bottles were sealed and stored at 4°C to maintain sample integrity and sieved with a 2 mm sieve. X-Ray diffraction in the sample (< 2 mm) treated with agate mortar was performed to detect the most abundant mineralogical fractions for each sampling site.

Figure 1: San Domino Island view with sampling sites

Table 1: Localization of each site and sampling conditions for 4th sampling (January 2025). This order is based on the previous metal assessment [4] where the two sediment samplings were referred to as the 2nd and 3rd (July and September 2023).

	<i>Site</i>	<i>Long °E</i> (<i>gg pp ss.dd</i>)	<i>Lat °N</i> (<i>gg pp ss.dd</i>)	<i>Depth</i> (<i>m</i>)	<i>Temperature</i> (<i>°C</i>)
1.	Pagliai (P)	15° 29' 46.65" E	42° 06' 43.13" N	10.3	16.7
2.	Cala Spido (CS)	15° 29' 45.89" E	42° 06' 59.65" N	10.0	16.9
3.	Cala Matano (CM)	15° 29' 38.90" E	42° 06' 50.24" N	15.0	16.5
4.	Grotta del sale (GS)	15° 29' 29.11" E	42° 06' 31.94" N	19.0	16.7

2.1 Granulometric analysis

Grain size analysis was performed by sieving the sediment through a series of stacked sieves, progressively separating the sample into smaller size fractions by using a vibrating sieve shaker [8]. The material collected was dried at 40°C and weighed to determine its proportion relative to the entire sample [9]. Between 200 and 300 g of sediment were weighed and then sieved with 3 sieves used to categorize sediments into coarse (>0.250 mm), medium (0.250-0.063 mm), and fine fractions (<0.063 mm). The sieving process was carried out with a FTS-0200 model IRIS electromagnetic sieve shaker from Filtra Vibration S.L. (Barcelona, Spain), for 4 h, at power 6 and cycle 3. At the end, each fraction of sample was weighed, packed in polyethylene (LDPE) bottles and stored at room temperature until analysis.

2.2 Metal analysis

Pseudo-total fraction metals were analyzed by weighing approximately 0.5 g of sediment into PTFE microwave digestion vessel through 3 mL of HCl 36% w/w from Supelco and 9 mL of HNO₃ 65% w/w from Panreac. The digestion were accomplished using a Milestone Ethos One High Performance Microwave Digestion System, at 230°C increasing 8°C/min for 35 minutes, following EPA Method 3051A[10]. The solutions were filtered through a 0.45 µm regenerate cellulose membrane filter brought to a total volume of 25 mL and analyzed by ICP-OES. Extraction of the available fraction was performed using the BCR protocol [11]. The quantitative determination of pseudo-total metals and metals in BCR-residue, was performed using Spectrogreen ICP-OES from SpectroAmetek (Karnataka, India). The quantification was carried out using external standards calibration curve of the MultiElement Standards (Carlo Erba 504311, Germany) and individual standards for Al (Sigma Aldrich 61935), Fe (Merck, 119761) and Sn (Merck 43922907).

2.3 Exploratory analysis of chemical/metals compositional data

To explore data patterns and assess the expected variations in chemical composition among samples collected in different seasons, sites and their relationships with sediment characteristics, both Pearson correlation analysis and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were applied. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated using MATLAB R2024b[12] to assess the linear relationships between metal concentrations, grain size fractions and mineralogical components. PCA was conducted using the PLS_Toolbox 9.5 (2024)[13]. The analysis was performed with data from 2023 [4] and 2025, following logarithmic

transformation and autoscaling. The aim was to explore data patterns and assess the expected variations in chemical composition among samples collected in different seasons and sites.

2.4 Pollution and Risk Assessment Indices

Several indices were obtained to evaluate the quality of the sediment and to assess the degree of contamination by comparing with background levels of metal, following the methodologies outlined by [14] and [15].

Contamination factor (Cf) is an index used to evaluate the contamination of a specific substance in a basin.

$$Cf = \frac{Cs}{Cb} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

where C_s is the concentration of the substance in sediment, and C_b is the background values for the same element. The *Contamination degree (Cd)* is the sum of all Cf for various heavy metals and the *Modified Contamination degree (mCd)* is an overall average value for a range of pollutants (the number of heavy metals considered (n)) (eq.2). The *Enrichment factor (EF)* evaluate the metal contamination and enrichment degree and it normalizes the trace element content with respect to a sample reference metal, such as Al (eq.3)

$$mC_d = \frac{C_d}{n} = \frac{\sum_1^n Cf}{n} \quad (\text{Eq.2})$$

$$EF = \frac{\left(\frac{M}{Al}\right)_{\text{sediment}}}{\left(\frac{M}{Al}\right)_{\text{background}}} \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

The *Geoaccumulation index (Igeo)* gives an assessment of heavy metals contamination of sediments with respect to the background natural levels (eq.4). The *Pollution Load Index (PLI)* evaluate the contamination status of sediments to heavy metals (eq.5).

$$I_{geo} = \log_2 \frac{Cs}{1,5 \times Cb} \quad (\text{Eq.4})$$

$$PLI = \sqrt[n]{Cf1 \times Cf2 \times \dots \times Cfn} \quad (\text{Eq.5})$$

The Potential Ecological Risk Index (PERI) is the sum of Potential Ecological Risk factor, which can be calculate using the toxicity response index of elements proposed by [3] for selected elements Cu, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb and Zn. The formula for the calculation of the potential ecological risk factor (E_f^i) of single metal pollution is:

$$PERI = \sum E_f^i = \sum C_f^i \times T_f^i \quad (\text{Eq.6})$$

Where T_f^i is toxic response factor for a given element ($Cd = 30$, $Cr = 2$, $Cu = 5$, $Ni = 5$, $Pb = 5$, $Zn = 1$) and C_f^i is the contamination factor for each metal. The Availability Index AI_{tot} is calculated based on the difference between the metal content in the residual fraction ($C_{residue}$) obtained through the BCR extraction and the pseudo-total metal content (C_{tot}) (Eq. 7):

$$AI_{tot} = \sqrt[n]{AI_{m1} \times AI_{m2} \times \dots \times AI_{mn}} = \sqrt[n]{\left(\frac{C_{tot} - C_{residue}}{C_{residue}}\right)_{m1} \times \left(\frac{C_{tot} - C_{residue}}{C_{residue}}\right)_{m2} \times \dots \times \left(\frac{C_{tot} - C_{residue}}{C_{residue}}\right)_{mn}} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Granulometric composition, spatial-bathymetric trends and XRD analysis

Figure 2 shows that along the San Domino coast, there is a variation in sediment texture and mineral content. At P (10.3 m), sediments are dominated by coarse sand and dolomite, characteristic of a high-energy environment. Moving to CS (10.0 m), fine sand increases and the mineral composition becomes change with the appearance of quartz, calcite, and Fe-bearing dolomite.

Figure 2: Percentage of grain size and mineralogical composition of sediments. (Aluminosilicates included: Albite (Ca-bearing) and Albite (Na-bearing); Carbonates included: Aragonite (CaCO₃), Calcite (CaCO₃), Calcite (Mg-bearing), Dolomite (CaMg(CO₃)₂), Dolomite (Ca(Mg,Fe)(CO₃))).

This suggests a shift toward a moderately lower-energy environment with more varied sediment sources. At CM (15.0 m), the mineral assemblage includes aragonitic calcite, aragonite, and Fe-bearing dolomite, indicating a combination of biogenic and terrigenous inputs. Aragonite, less stable than calcite, can arise from marine organisms such as corals and shell-producing fauna. Its presence, along with aragonitic calcite, points to active biogenic contributions, while its eventual transformation into calcite reflects ongoing diagenetic processes. Finally, GS (19.0 m) contains the finest sediments and the most varied mineralogy, including quartz, calcite, and dolomite. Calcite, formed via biochemical processes in sedimentary environments and the most abundant mineral in the dataset, is consistently associated with finer grain sizes across the sites, supporting the observed trend of increased mineralogical complexity and carbonate accumulation in lower-energy zones.

3.2 Metal content and contamination assessment

The results (Table 2) show a wide variation in average metal concentrations between sites. For instance, Al ranges from 457.69 ppm at P to over 5210 ppm at GS, suggesting different environmental conditions or contamination sources. High levels of Al and Fe may reflect local geology or anthropogenic influences. By merging this data with the 2023 dataset, it is possible to observe the patterns previously highlighted by the PCA. The score plot (Figure 3) shows the distribution of the samples along the first two principal components, PC1 (48.88%) and PC2 (20.15%), which together explain approximately 69% of the total variance. The samples from P are clearly separated along PC1, indicating a distinct metal composition compared to the other locations. In contrast, samples from CM, CS, and GS show partial overlap but still exhibit separation, especially along PC2, suggesting site-specific differences as well as seasonal variation in metal content. The corresponding loading plot (Figure 4) provides insight into which elements contribute most to the observed separation. The differentiation between sites along PC1 appears to be driven by increasing concentrations of nearly all metals. Overall, the PCA highlights clear compositional differences between sampling sites, with P samples that are consistently positioned on the negative side of PC1, possibly linked to localized environmental or geological factors.

The percentage of metals in the residual fraction of the BCR extraction represents the fraction not potentially available. Metals such as Al, Fe, Cr, and Ni show high inert fraction, suggesting a strong lithogenic origin and low environmental mobility. Conversely, Cu and Zn display much lower percentages in this fraction (often <50%), implying a higher percentage from available metal and thus greater potential ecological risk. Pb and Cr exhibit intermediate behavior, with notable portions in both available and residual forms, especially in Cala Matano and Grotta del Sale, pointing to mixed natural and anthropogenic sources. To further explore the temporal variability of metal concentrations of samples from July 2023 (SCS-2,SGS-2,P-2,CM-2), September 2023 (SCS-3,SGS-3,P-3,CM-3) and January 2025 (SCS,SGS,P,CM -4) and their associations with sediment characteristics, PCA-score plot and correlation analysis were applied.

The PCA score plot (Figure 5) reveals a clear temporal separation of the samples collected in 2023 and 2025, particularly along PC2 (20.15%). Samples from 2025 (red) are distinctly shifted from those collected in July and September 2023 (green and blue), indicating significant changes in elemental composition over time. The loading plot (Figure 3) shows that this temporal differentiation is primarily driven by increased levels of metals with positive loadings on PC2.

The Pearson correlation matrix (Figure 6) provides valuable insights into the relationships among metal concentrations, mineralogical composition (quartz, dolomite, calcite), and grain size fractions (coarse sand, fine sand, and silt). These correlations allow for a better understanding of the mechanisms influencing metal distribution and potential sources, whether lithogenic or anthropogenic. Strong positive correlations were observed between quartz and several trace metals, including Cu, Zn, and Pb, suggesting that finer quartz-rich fractions may play a role in adsorbing or retaining these elements. This is further supported by the strong association of silt with many metals, indicating that fine-grained particles are likely important carriers of metal contaminants due to their higher surface area and adsorption capacity.

Table 2: Mean values of metal concentration (mg/l), standard deviations and percentage of residual fraction (F4) after the BCR extraction respect to the pseudo-total metal (nd: not detected (<LOD))

Site	Value	Ag	Al	As	Ba	Be	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Mn	Mo	Ni	Pb	Sb	Se	Sn	Ti	Tl	V	Zn
P	Mean	nd	457.69	2.26	6.44	nd	0.30	0.67	4.39	1.84	486.68	63.60	nd	2.04	3.08	nd	0.92	nd	9.81	nd	4.14	9.72
	SD	-	31.38	0.29	0.42		0.01	0.07	0.23	0.82	22.49	9.16		0.19	0.09	-	0.08	-	0.15		0.04	2.60
	%F4	nd	8.55	nd	6.59	nd	nd	nd	12.37	nd	9.53	0.84	nd	3.40	24.41	nd	-0.98	nd	33.13	nd	4.98	45.05
CM	Mean	nd	2132.93	2.90	28.10	0.13	nd	1.54	8.73	6.09	1755.28	95.81	0.14	5.22	11.51	nd	1.35	nd	47.52	nd	8.54	23.28
	SD	-	110.61	0.16	6.93	0.02	-	0.34	0.50	4.96	62.20	9.21	0.01	0.02	2.09	-	0.16	-	5.30		0.04	10.39
	%F4	nd	61.48	44.64	30.87	55.37	nd	35.03	49.43	8.80	96.14	13.24	51.43	47.20	20.01	nd	8.17	4037.9	78.31	nd	44.83	41.62
CS	Mean	nd	2514.89	4.62	24.65	0.15	nd	1.68	10.06	2.73	2112.42	108.53	0.16	6.64	6.15	nd	1.15	0.28	57.69	nd	8.89	29.69
	SD	-	29.45	0.03	8.82	0.01	-	0.08	0.18	0.35	66.38	2.16	0.01	0.45	0.06	-	0.12	0.08	2.10		0.06	8.02
	%F4	nd	46.77	32.15	26.98	43.43	nd	42.29	48.48	16.76	62.78	5.40	56.83	49.13	28.42	nd	8.45	-	47.61	nd	40.35	50.14
GS	Mean	nd	5210.13	3.34	31.40	0.24	0.19	1.72	11.86	3.92	3045.11	110.51	0.42	6.31	6.80	0.77	1.30	0.40	81.76	nd	12.87	24.38
	SD	-	201.72	0.08	0.37	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.39	0.12	241.84	8.10	0.04	0.28	0.23	0.04	0.01	0.08	0.84	-	0.76	11.10
	%F4	nd	72.93	36.03	44.56	65.04	nd	58.87	74.13	26.47	88.26	14.44	11.56	72.11	63.66	101.64	28.60	-	73.71	nd	59.92	91.32

Figure 3: Loading plot of the first two principal components (PC1 and PC2)

Figure 4: Score plot showing the distribution based on the sampling sites

Figure 5: Score plot show the distribution of sampling sites in different time, where the number -2, -3 and -4 indicates the sampling time July 2023, September 2023 and January 2025 respectively.

Conversely, calcite and dolomite showed predominantly negative or weak correlations with trace metals, suggesting a more limited role in metal binding. Their association with coarser grain sizes, particularly coarse sand, supports the idea that carbonate-rich and coarser fractions are less involved in the retention or accumulation of metals. Moreover, metals such as Fe and Al exhibited strong mutual correlation ($r \approx 0.96$), which aligns with their common lithogenic origin. These correlations allow for a better understanding of the mechanisms influencing metal distribution and potential sources, whether lithogenic or anthropogenic. Strong positive correlations were observed between quartz and several trace metals, including Cu, Zn, and Pb, suggesting that finer quartz-rich fractions may play a role in adsorbing or retaining these elements. This is further supported by the strong association of silt with many metals, indicating that fine-grained particles are likely important carriers of metal contaminants due to their higher surface area and adsorption capacity. Conversely, calcite and dolomite showed predominantly negative or weak correlations with trace metals, suggesting a more limited role in metal binding. Their association with coarser grain sizes, particularly coarse sand, supports the idea that carbonate-rich and coarser fractions are less involved in the retention or accumulation of metals. Moreover, metals such as Fe and Al exhibited strong mutual correlation ($r \approx 0.96$), which aligns with their common lithogenic origin. The high correlations between fine sand/silt and several metals (e.g., Cu, Zn, Pb) emphasize the importance of grain size in controlling metal distribution. This finding is consistent with the PCA results, where sites enriched in fine sediments and quartz also displayed higher metal loads.

All the metals concentration was compared with the most empirical SQGs (Threshold-Effects Level (TEL)/Possible-Effects Level and Effects Range Low (ERL)/Effects Range Median (ERM)[16], [17]) and none of the values exceeded the limits. The other calculated indexes are reported in table 3.

The values of background levels reported by [15] and [18] were used because of the proximity of sampling sites. Be, Mo, Sb, Se, Sn, Tl were not considered because of the absence of reference values for the background level. Fe and Al were not considered because of also natural high content.

Figure 6: Pearson correlation matrix among metal concentrations, most abundant mineralogical fractions (quartz, dolomite, calcite), and granulometric components (coarse sand, fine sand, silt).

Table 3: Pollution and Risk Assessment Indices (C_d , mC_d , PLI, PERI and AI_{tot} are calculated on all the metals analyzed).

Label	1. P				2. CM				3. CS				4. GS			
	Cf	Igeo	EF	Ei	Cf	Igeo	EF	Ei	Cf	Igeo	EF	Ei	Cf	Igeo	EF	Ei
As	0.2	-2.7	34		0.3	-2.4	43.8		0.5	-1.7	69.6		0.3	-2.2	50.3	
Cd	0.7	-1	110.9	22.1	0.6	-1.4	86.1	17.1	0.7	-1.2	101.3	20.2	0.5	-1.7	70.7	14.1
Cr	0	-5.5	5.2	0.2	0.1	-4.5	10.3	0.3	0.1	-4.3	11.8	0.4	0.1	-4	14	0.5
Cu	0	-5	6.9	0.2	0.2	-3.3	23	0.8	0.1	-4.5	10.3	0.3	0.1	-3.9	14.8	0.5
Mn	0.1	-4.2	12.4		0.1	-3.6	18.6		0.1	-3.4	21.1		0.1	-3.4	21.5	
Pb	0.2	-3.1	25.8	0.9	0.6	-1.2	96.3	3.2	0.3	-2.1	51.5	1.7	0.4	-2	56.9	1.9
Ti	32.7	4.4	4927.1		158.4	6.7	23880		192.3	7	28986.6		272.5	7.5	41084.3	
Zn	0.2	-2.9	30.5	0.2	0.5	-1.6	73.1	0.5	0.6	-1.3	93.2	0.6	0.5	-1.6	76.6	0.5
C_d	34.3	PERI	23.5		C_d	161.1	PERI	21.9	C_d	195	PERI	23.2	C_d	274.8	PERI	17.4
mC_d	2.6	AI_{tot}	9.3		mC_d	12.4	AI_{tot}	1.38	mC_d	15	AI_{tot}	1.86	mC_d	22.9	AI_{tot}	0.78
PLI	0.1				PLI	0.3			PLI	0.3			PLI	0.4		

The analysis of heavy metals reveals moderate and localized contamination, with notable spatial differences. Among the elements studied, Cd stands out due to its elevated concentrations and enrichment indicators, particularly in CS and GS, suggesting a clear anthropogenic influence. Pb, Zn and Ti also show significant accumulation, with Ti reaching exceptionally high levels in GS. In contrast, most other metals, such as Co, Ni, V, and Ba, show values consistent with natural background levels, indicating a predominantly lithogenic origin. Global indices like mC_d and PLI support the overall assessment of low contamination ($PLI < 1$), although a gradual increase is observed from north to south. The PERI index remains low at all sites and AI_{tot} shows a decreasing trend in the order: $P > CM > CS > GS$.

The temporal trends across sites reveal differing contamination patterns as shown in Figure 6. P shows a peak in C_d and mC_d levels in September 2023, followed by a decline by January 2025, alongside a steady decrease in the PERI. At CM, the data show more fluctuation, with a decrease followed by a rise in January 2025, possibly indicating contamination inputs. CS exhibits stable C_d and mC_d values during the first two samplings and reductions in PLI and PERI. GS reports the highest overall contamination levels in the first two periods but also shows improvement by January 2025. Among all sites, GS and CS emerge as the most impacted from an ecotoxicological perspective.

Figure 7: Temporal variation of pollution indexes (C_d , mC_d , PLI, and PERI) across four sampling sites over three sampling times (July 23, September 23 and January 25).

The Figure 7 shows the correlation matrices of trace metal concentrations (from 2023) for two ecological factors (from 2023): the PERI index and the DMSP/DMSO ratio in leaves of *P.Oceanica*, providing insight into the behavior and potential impact of metals in *Posidonia Oceanica* meadows, which are regressing. The correlation matrix a shows a positive correlation between metal in sediment and PERI, which is logical since the higher the metal concentration, the higher the PERI index; e.g. Cd, Cu, Mo, Pb, Sn and Tl show a medium-trong positive correlation. The matrix b shows a general negative correlation between metal content and DMSP/DMSO ratio in every types of *P.Oceanica* leaf, which is correct since a low ratio indicates a high oxidative stress of the plant except for Cd, Mo, Se and Sn which show a positive but not significant correlation since the DMSP/DMSO ratio may depend on different environmental factors. This pattern suggests that, even in the absence of updated biotic data, metals may be related to the health status of the plant.

Figure 8: Correlation matrices for: a) the PERI index; b) DMSP/DMSO ratio in leaves of *P.Oceanica*

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of trace metal contamination and ecological risk in marine sediments of the Tremiti Islands. The results reveal spatial variability of metal concentrations, with Cala Spido and Grotta del Sale showing the highest levels of contamination indices, particularly for As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Mn, Pb, Ti. Pollution indices (mCd and PLI) generally indicate low to moderate contamination. While other metals appear to be mainly of lithogenic origin and bound to residual fractions, a notable portion of potentially available metals was detected, especially in fine-grained, quartz-rich sediments.

Importantly, a temporal decrease in Cd concentrations and associated risk indicators (mCd and PERI) were observed in the most recent sampling (January 2025) at several sites, suggesting a potential reduction in contaminant inputs due to the winter season or natural attenuation processes.

Multivariate analysis confirmed the influence of both natural and anthropogenic sources, as well as the key role of sediment texture in metal distribution. Overall, the integration of geochemical, granulometric, and statistical data supports a nuanced understanding of metal behavior in coastal marine environments and highlights the importance of long-term monitoring to capture both spatial patterns and temporal dynamics in protected areas.

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Preliminary Data on the Distribution and Risk Assessment of Bisphenol A, Phthalates, and Heavy Metals in *Mytilus galloprovincialis* from Naples (Italy) Coastal Waters

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Abstract

Environmental pollution significantly impacts marine ecosystems, threatening biodiversity and human health. Contaminants of Emerging Concern such as heavy metals, bisphenol A, and phthalates are particularly crucial due to their persistence, bioaccumulation potential, and toxic effects. Marine organisms like *Mytilus galloprovincialis* are effective bioindicators as they filter large volumes of water, concentrating pollutants in their tissues. Their wide distribution and ability to bioaccumulate pollutants make them ideal for assessing pollution levels and potential risks to human consumers. This study aimed to quantify six phthalates (DEHP, DMP, DEP, DBP, DnOP, BBP), bisphenol A, and twelve heavy metals (Hg, Pb, Cd, As, Ni, Cr, Cu, Mn, Ba, Sb, V, Fe) in *M. galloprovincialis* from the Bay of Naples (Southern Italy). Additionally, it assessed the toxicological risks related to their consumption, providing useful insights into environmental and human health implications. Samples were collected in July 2023 from three sites at two depths per location. Advanced analytical methods were employed: phthalates and bisphenol A were measured using HPLC-FLD and GC-MS, while heavy metals were analyzed with ICP-MS. Exposure risks were evaluated using the Target Hazard Quotient (THQ) and Incremental Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR). Results revealed significant spatial variations in contamination. Arsenic posed a non-carcinogenic risk across all demographic groups, while nickel and arsenic presented carcinogenic risks in specific locations. Phthalates, including DEHP and DEP, were detected below regulatory limits, suggesting localized rather than widespread contamination. These findings highlight the importance of continuous surveillance of marine ecosystems and seafood products to ensure public health and environmental sustainability, also providing valuable insights for policymakers and contributing to the understanding of marine contamination and its broader social impacts.

Keywords: *marine pollution, risk assessment, food safety, bioaccumulation, mussels*

Effects of 21-day exposure to copper and high temperatures on the survival, behaviour and physiology of female shrimp, *Palaemon serratus*

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Abstract

Palaemon serratus belongs to the Palaemonidae family, and it is quite a large shrimp (up to 11 cm in length). Its geographical distribution includes the Eastern Atlantic, from Denmark to Mauritania, the English Channel, the North Sea, the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea. This species lives on the rocky coasts, up to 20-40 m deep, in shady areas and among the algae. In France, *Palaemon serratus* is fished by both recreational and professional fishermen; compared to other species, the shrimp landings are limited but *P. serratus* is the most expensive seafood. Quite surprisingly, the biology and ecology of the French and European populations remain poorly understood, and this is the reason why the European Project Gedubouq was launched in 2020. In the frame of both the climate change and the contamination of the coasts by various pollutants including trace metals, it has been chosen to experimentally study the effects of copper (Cu) and elevated temperatures on the behaviour and physiology of *P. serratus*. For this first study, 8 female individuals were individually exposed to 3 Cu concentrations (10, 100, 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, plus control) and 3 temperatures: 15°C (control), 22°C and 24°C. The exposure lasted 21 days and was performed twice, in spring and autumn 2022. Every day, the mortality, the moult presence and the shrimps' behaviour were visually checked. In addition, the shrimps' reaction to a stimulus was tested every other day whereas the reaction to food (commercial pellets) was studied every day but only the last week of exposure. Finally, at the beginning of the study (T0) and after 21 days of exposure, some endpoints were studied to assess the physiological status of the shrimps: the phagocytic activity of the hemocytes, the content in glycogen in the muscle, the content of both proteins and malondialdehyde (proxy of oxidative stress) in the digestive gland. The concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ revealed lethal for *P. serratus* and mortality was often preceded by a moult. Sublethal effects were observed for the concentrations of 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ with, for example, shrimps more active and a stimulation of the phagocytic activity. However, these effects were modulated by temperature which interacted with Cu concentration. The most pronounced effects were observed for temperature and shrimp behaviour, whatever the behavioural parameter considered. Indeed, the high temperatures induced an increase in shrimps' activity, and it would be interesting to assess the consequences on the natural populations and thus the exploited stocks in further studies.

Keywords: *Palaemon serratus*, ecotoxicology, copper, elevated temperatures, behaviour, phagocytic activity

An integrated approaches to investigate the potential effects of environmental and occupational exposure to microplastics.

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Abstract

Microplastics (MP) are recently defined as plastic particles with a range between 1 µm and 1 mm, that accumulate in the environment due to their slow degradation. Given the scarcity of scientific data relating to human health effects and the lack of standardized methods for the collection, identification, and quantification of microplastics in a complex mixture, the development of new protocols is of great importance for the analysis and characterization of commonly used microplastics (textiles, cosmetics).

MP effects on human health are still being evaluated as the toxicity studies still limited and largely influenced by the level of exposure, the properties of the particles, the adsorbed contaminants, the tissues involved and the individual susceptibility.

In this scientific research project, particular attention was paid to the living and working environments given the high exposure of workers to dust, vapors and dangerous gases. The categories of workers most exposed are those involved in the waste management and recycling industries, in the production and processing of plastic and in the textile industry. Commercial and certified standard at different size were analyzed by FTIR and µ-FTIR spectroscopy. Then, considering the most significant results obtained in this first phase, toxicity tests were conducted using different end point of exposure on *Caenorhabditis elegans*, to evaluate any potential toxicity effects *in vivo* induced by MP exposure. *C. elegans* is considered an excellent model system to examine the impact of microplastics on reproductive behaviour, on the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and to investigate the molecular pathways that mediate reproductive toxicity induced by microplastics.

We suppose that the development of an integrated approach, based on complementary techniques, will lead to understand deeply the molecular mechanism underlying toxicity effects and to the drafting of new operational protocols to minimize the risk of MP exposure.

Keywords: *microplastics, FTIR, µ-FTIR spectroscopy, C. elegans model system*

Ecological impacts of military activities and climate change on Ukraine's aquatic ecosystems

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Abstract

In Ukraine, the combination of military activities and global climate change acting jointly poses a significant threat to aquatic ecosystems and fish health. Military operations, such as the destruction of infrastructure and industrial facilities, result in severe water pollution. During armed conflicts, toxic chemicals, including heavy metals, petroleum products, and other hazardous substances, are released into rivers, lakes, and groundwater, contaminating ecosystems and degrading water quality.

Climate change is already profoundly impacting Ukraine's aquaculture industry, particularly on the health of fish reared in artificial reservoirs. The twin impacts of global climate change and military activity significantly impact Ukraine's aquaculture, increasing the risk of fish diseases and degrading water resources. This highlights the urgent need for adaptation strategies to increase the resilience of fish farms and preserve biodiversity.

The RestoAqua project (No. G6085) focuses on the assessment and restoration of war-damaged aquatic ecosystems in Ukraine. The project aims to develop rapid ecosystem assessment methods and restore bioresources and clean water bodies using biodestructor-based technologies. It will also develop damage assessment algorithms and recommendations for reducing harmful compounds in water. This initiative is expected to contribute to the restoration of aquatic ecosystems and aquaculture while mitigating the environmental and social consequences of the war.

Keywords: *water resource degradation, aquaculture, ecosystem restoration*

Ecotoxicity of hybrid alkali cements on the marine ecosystem by aquatic toxicity bioassays: Bioluminescence and sea urchin embryogenesis

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Abstract

The shift toward sustainable materials in the construction industry has positioned alkali cements as pivotal alternatives to conventional Portland cement, with their lower carbon footprint and the valorisation of industrial by-products. However, the ecological implications of these materials particularly their long-term interactions with marine ecosystems remain inadequately characterized. Ecotoxicity testing has emerged as a critical tool for assessing the risks posed by diverse materials, including novel construction composites. Among the most widely applied assays, the *Vibrio fischeri* bioluminescence inhibition test and the sea urchin embryogenesis assay have become cornerstones for rapid screening and detailed teratogenic evaluations, respectively. Two different binders, Portland cement (CEM-I) as reference and Hybrid Alkaline Cement (HAC) as alternative cement has been analysed from an ecotoxicological point of view. While in the reduction of the bioluminescence results there are no significant differences between the two products, the mobility of some trace elements is slightly higher in HAC samples compared to CEM-I samples. This could show a certain influence on embryogenesis results. At low concentrations, HAC affects less than CEM-I, while at high concentrations, the behaviour is the opposite, with a significant difference between both.

Keywords: *hybrid cement, marine ecotoxicity, bacteria luminescence, sea urchin embryogenesis*

1. INTRODUCTION

The construction sector faces mounting pressure to adopt sustainable materials that mitigate environmental impacts while maintaining structural performance. Conventional Portland cement (CEM-I), responsible for ~8% of global CO₂ emissions, has stimulated intensive research into alternative binders such as hybrid alkaline cements (HACs). These systems, combining Portland cement (15–30%), industrial by-products (e.g., fly ash, slag), and alkaline activators, reduce clinker content by up to 70% while achieving comparable mechanical properties. However, their ecological safety, particularly in marine environments, remains underexplored compared to traditional assessments of compressive strength or carbon footprint.

Alkaline cementitious systems, introduce high-pH leachates into marine environments, raising concerns about their ecotoxicological impacts. Recent studies have documented the dual role of these materials: while they immobilize certain heavy metals through geopolymerization, their alkaline matrices can mobilize trace elements like arsenic and antimony, depending on the raw material composition and activation conditions [1]. The ecological consequences of these contaminants range from acute toxicity to chronic disruptions in marine food webs, necessitating robust methodologies to evaluate their environmental impacts.

Ecotoxicity testing has emerged as a critical tool for assessing the risks posed by diverse materials, including these novel construction composites and usually employ tiered bioassays to address environmental behaviour [2]. The Microtox® assay (*Vibrio fischeri* bioluminescence inhibition) provides rapid screening for acute toxicity, detecting disruptions to bacterial metabolism from soluble ions and trace metals [3]. Complementarily, the *Paracentrotus lividus* embryogenesis test evaluates chronic effects on complex multicellular systems, where developmental abnormalities signal sublethal toxicity from contaminants [4].

In this work, a comparative analysis of the ecotoxicity results of two different binders, Portland cement (CEM-I) as reference and HAC as alternative, containing mainly CEM-I, coal fly ash, and an activator, on the marine ecosystem has been accomplished. For this purpose, the UNE-EN 12457-4 leaching test as well as two different toxicity tests, the bioluminescence test with the marine bacterium *Vibrio fischeri* UNE-EN 11348-3 and the embryo-larval development test with sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The binders used in this study were a commercial Portland cement (CEM-I) type CEM I 52,5R and a hybrid alkaline cement (HAC) containing 27.5% CEM I 52,5 R + 67.5% Coal Fly Ash + 2.5% gypsum +2.5% Sodium sulphate, developed by the authors. The coal fly ash (FA) was provided by Endesa. The chemical composition determined by XRF (Bruker S8 TIGER) are shown in Table 1. The HAC had a lower CaO and a higher SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ content than the PC.

Table 1. Chemical composition (expressed as oxides in wt %) of Materials

	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	Other	^a LoI
CEM I	62.94	19.29	5.28	2.62	0.85	3.58	0.10	0.67	0.24	1.55	2.88
FA	4.32	40.48	22.08	8.36	1.65	3.29	1.06	3.56	1.03	2.37	11.80
HAC	22.72	32.10	15.94	6.22	1.33	6.01	1.81	2.51	0.74	2.01	8.53

Mortar samples were prepared with a sand/cement ratio of 3/1 according to the EN 196-1 standard and were hydrated with deionized water with water/cement ratio of 0.5.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Equilibrium/Compliance leaching test EN 12457-4

The compliance leaching test EN 12457-2:2003 was used to determine the release of metals from the cement mortars under equilibrium conditions. Samples were milled to obtain a material with a grain size of at least 95% less than 10 mm, promoting contact between phases and maximum mobility of trace elements. In 1 L polyethylene bottles, 90 ± 5 g of each sample (dry mass) was weighed and mixed with the correspondent leaching agent, deionized water (DW) or seawater (SW), at a liquid to solid ratio of 10 l/kg. The bottles were placed in rotating equipment at 10 rpm for 24 h. The solid was separated by filtration through a 0.45 μm cellulose nitrate membrane filter using a vacuum filtration device.

The pH and conductivity values of the leachates were measured, and the critical elements included in Decision 2003/33/EC (As, Ba, Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Mo, Ni, Pb, Sb, Se, and Zn) were analysed using Inductive Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES) at the Central Analysis Service of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) according to ISO quality standards. The concentration of trace elements was determined in the leachates (in triplicate) and averages were calculated.

2.2.2. Luminescence inhibition bioassay

The bioluminescence test was conducted according to ISO 11348-3:2007[5] using the MICROTOX LX bioluminescence toxicity analyser from Modern Water. This sensitive photometer measures light emission by microorganisms automatically under controlled conditions using Microtox LX software. *Vibrio fischeri* bacteria (NRRL B-11177 strain) were supplied by Aqua Science, lyophilized, and stored in 1 ml vials at -18°C to -20°C . The bacteria were reconstituted with a commercial solution (sodium chloride, magnesium chloride hexahydrate, and potassium chloride) to emit the required light.

Four sample dilutions of each DW leachate and a blank were used: 45%, 22.5%, 11.25%, 5.6%, and 0%. The pH values were adjusted to 6.5–7.5 using NaOH or HCl (0.1 N), and the osmotic adjustment (20 g/L of NaCl) was added. Luminescence was measured before and 15 minutes after the bacteria contacted the leachate dilutions. The ecotoxicity parameter obtained was the reduction in luminosity between both measurements.

2.2.3. Sea Urchin embryo-larval assay

First, the pH values of the leachates were adjusted, in this case to suitable seawater pH (7–8.5). Five dilutions of each SW leachate were used: control (clean filtered seawater), 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%.

Sea urchins (*Paracentrotus lividus*) were collected by hand at low tide from a clean coastal area near Santander (NW Spain) and transported to the laboratory. Gametes were obtained from mature organisms (three males and three females) and their maturity was checked with a microscope. The fertilization procedure began by transferring eggs to a 100 mL cylinder with clean filtered seawater, and 10 μL of sperm were added. The mixture was gently shaken to facilitate fertilization. Aliquots of 20 μL were taken, and the total number of eggs and fertilized eggs were counted under a microscope. Fertilization success was approximately 95% [6].

Then, vials (20 mL) were filled with different dilutions (5 replicates per dilution) of each leachate, and approximately 500 fertilized eggs were placed in each vial. The eggs were

incubated for 48 hours at 20°C in the dark. After incubation, larvae were fixed with 1 mL of 40% formalin and observed under a microscope. The number of pluteus larvae that reach each level of development per 100 organisms (Figure 1) was recorded. The control treatment ensured test acceptability (> 90% normal larval development) [7].

Figure 1. Levels of development of the pluteus larvae and endpoints considered [6].

2.2.4. Statistical analysis

Data from ecotoxicological tests and trace elements analysis in leachates were expressed as means ± standard deviations. Data from the Microtox® bioassay were obtained directly from the equipment program and represented using the light variation parameter (Γ).

Embryogenesis bioassay data were tested for normality and homogeneity using the Shapiro–Wilk and Levene Tests. One-way ANOVA with Tukey’s HSD Post Hoc Test determined significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) in larvae development between different leachates and the control (clean filtered seawater). If normality and homogeneity assumptions were not met, data were logarithm-transformed ($\ln + 1$). Dose-response curves for the embryogenesis bioassay were adjusted using non-linear regression analysis via the MOSAIC web-interface, based on the R package [8].

The EC_x value, representing the concentration of leachate causing 20% and 50% inhibition of luminescence in bacteria or negative effects on sea urchin larvae development, was used to express bioassay results. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS 21.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Environmental behaviour based on leaching tests: Compliance leaching test (UNE-EN 12457-4)

Table 2 shows the chemical analysis, pH and conductivity results obtained from both products eluates after the application of two different extract leachate agents.

Table 2. Leaching concentration values (mg/kg) of Portland (CEM-I) and Hybrid Alkaline Cement (HAC) according to Compliance leaching test EN 12457-2.

	Deionised water			Sea water		Control**
	CEM-I	HAC	Inert Limits *	CEM-I	HAC	
As	0.002	0.042	0.50	0.013	0.058	0.021
Ba	13.718	0.246	20.00	7.056	3.300	0.064
Cd	0.000	0.001	0.04	0.000	0.001	0.003
Cr	0.046	0.096	0.50	1.212	0.163	0.005
Cu	0.009	0.003	2.00	0.007	0.001	0.004
Mo	0.033	1.569	0.50	0.126	2.609	0.123
Ni	0.007	0.000	0.40	0.010	0.010	0.008
Pb	0.005	0.000	0.50	0.003	0.003	0.007
Sb	0.000	0.029	0.06	0.028	0.241	0.013
Se	0.014	0.016	0.10	0.010	0.039	0.004
V	0.042	8.230	1.50***	0.037	7.599	0.019
Zn	0.079	0.000	4.00	0.015	0.003	0.041
Cl ⁻	6.465	7.855	800	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
F ⁻	1.105	1.535	10	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
SO ₄ ²⁻	25.845	1110.9	1000	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
pH	12.38	11.71	-	9.27	9.38	7.98
Conductivity (mS/cm)	7.54	1.80	-	51.10	50.30	49.90

* Limit values for leachates according to EU Landfill Waste Acceptance Criteria 2003/33/EC [9].

** Control: clean seawater used as reference leachate.

*** Limit value for V in leachate according to the Regional Decree 64/2019 of the Basque Country for slag valorisation

The pH values demonstrate the high alkalinity of both products in deionized water, which decrease in clean filtered sea water, as it is expected due to a higher presence of diluted ions. The concentration values obtained from chemical analysis shows that Mo and V trace elements, and SO_4^{2-} anion concentrations are above inert limits for HAC sample, demonstrating a higher release behaviour, respect to CEM I. The alkaline activation of HAC during its configuration could be a determining factor in this behaviour, since these trace elements are classified as oxyanions, due to their ability to change speciation and be released more easily in alkaline media. For this reason, the characteristics of HAC are like those reported in previous studies for alkali activated cements [4].

On the other hand, the chemical analysis of the Control based on the clean filtered sea water that has been used as extract leachate agent, allow to validate the assay as there is no cross contamination. In general, when using clean filtered seawater as extract leachate agent,

all previous highlighted elements release more concentration from each sample, in comparison with their behaviour in contact with deionized water. Only Cr is released in higher amount from CEM I than from HAC, while metals such as Mo, Sb, Se and specially V release significantly more concentration from HAC.

3.2. Luminescence reduction of bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* test (ISO 11348-3:2007)

Figure 2 shows the luminescence reduction from bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*, in function of the contact with different leachate concentrations, after 30 minutes of contact with each eluate of the products.

Figure 2. Bioluminescence test results expressed as percentage of luminescence emission reduction of bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* after 30 min exposure as a function of leachate concentration: a) Basic Test, with standard error bars and; b) Retested as Higher leachate concentrations.

The analysed samples in both test modalities do not present toxicity for luminescent bacteria according to German legislative framework for the construction sector [2], while does not reach the 20% of luminescence reduction for the analysed leachate concentrations. Authors have reported in previous studies that luminescent bacteria test does not present toxic effects from the contact with similar activated materials [4].

3.3. Sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* embryogenesis test.

Diagram bars in Figure 3, and dose-response curves in Figure 4, share information about the levels of development, and the endpoints that integrate these levels, that have been reached by the embryos during the contact with the different leachate concentrations.

The results validate the assay due to the Control reach the 90% of completed larvae development, which demonstrates that reproduction period of sea urchins, and the quality of fertilization process, are optimal to develop the test.

The results based on larval development during contact with CEM I sample, show that each leachate concentration allow the beginning of all larvae to develop from fertilized egg, while the contact with high leachate concentrations of HAC demonstrates a low percentage of embryos that cannot start their development. Otherwise, during the contact with high leachate's concentrations of HAC (75%), the larvae development starts for approximately the 45% of embryos, which does not occur during the contact with CEM I.

Figure 3. Sea urchin embryogenesis test results: Percentage of Normal development of *Paracentrotus lividus* embryos according to the endpoints classification on the different leachates for CEM-I (a) and HAC (b). The numbers 5, 3, 1 above bars refers to significant differences in toxicity level respect to the control ($p < 0.05^*$) for the toxicity level represented.

Dose-response curves defined in Figure 4 share information about the percentage of embryos that reach the transition between levels, depending on the leachate concentration percentage with which they are in contact during the assay. The sample HAC has registered a larger percentage of larvae that have passed to higher stages of development from the initial stage, even after contact with high leachate concentrations, compared to CEM I.

The evolution of dose-response curves is similar for both samples in each Endpoint: The complete development of larvae (Endpoint 1) is reached in a high percentage of larvae in contact with HAC, until 15% of leachate concentration, while the contact with CEM I leachates produces a higher complete development inhibition. The beginning of development of four legs (Endpoint 2) is common until the contact with 50% of leachate concentration, a point of inflexion from where the curve starts to decrease in both cases. Finally, when considering Endpoint 3, the response obtained from HAC is slightly worse than CEM I, due to under high leachate concentration, there are some embryos that do not start their development.

These results highlight significant differences between products. When considering those embryos that reach high levels of development, HAC demonstrates better response during contact than CEM I. On the other hand, when considering initial stages of development, the response obtained from those embryos in contact with CEM I is better, due to all of them start their development after fecundation, than HAC.

Figure 4. Early development dose-response curves exposed to the leachates of CEM-I and HAC for different toxicity endpoints. The area between the discontinuous lines represents the model 95% credible band.

These results are aligned with the differences observed from the chemical analysis in clean filtered sea water, where there are some metals that release bigger concentrations for the first sample, and there are others for the second sample. Previous authors have reported the effect of specific trace elements, such as V [10], during embryogenesis test, a phenomenon that could be considered from the higher release capacity of these species from HAC, in comparison with CEM I, and its inhibition effects over larvae development.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From a chemical perspective, the alkaline formulation of HAC supposes higher release of some elements known as oxyanions (Mo and V), in comparison with CEM I, from the leachates based on deionized water and clean filtered sea water.

The luminescent reduction of bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* has demonstrated that both products do not present toxicity for this test. The embryogenesis test results demonstrated more significant differences between products, which could reflect the observed trace elements mobilization from equilibrium leaching test, sharing more precise information to differentiate the effects between samples.

For initial stages of larvae development, the response is better during contact with CEM I, which allows all embryos to start their development. Nevertheless, when considering high

levels of larvae development, the response obtained is better during contact with HAC, since a greater number of embryos manage to begin their development.

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Bioassays as a tool to evaluate the efficiency of diesel-contaminated soil remediation

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Abstract

In the EU more than 2.8 million potential contaminated sites have been identified, of which around 342 thousand were contaminated and required remediation. Petroleum products are the main pollutants contributing jointly approximately 45% to soil contamination. Finding optimal environmentally friendly remediation technique which ensures effective petroleum products removal from the soil and soil quality restoration is of high interest. Thermal desorption is recognized as a fast and highly effective in removing organic chemicals, however it may adversely affect soil functions. Understanding the effects of thermal desorption on soil ecological properties is vital to successful soil remediation and soil health restoration. In this study the impact of thermal desorption (250 and 300 °C) on the ecological properties of soils were investigated. Diesel contaminated (25 and 50 g kg⁻¹) and thermally treated soils toxicity was assessed by the means of bioassays with *Daphnia magna* and *Lemna minor*. Diesel-contaminated soil had acute lethal toxicity to *D. magna* and thermal remediation of diesel-contaminated soil significantly reduced acute soil toxicity to *D. magna*. However, chronic toxicity assessment with *D. magna* has shown low mortality and the rate of mortality was temperature and diesel concentration dependent. In addition, the time to the first breeding was somewhat delayed leading to lower reproduction in thermally treated soil leachates. The assessment with *L. minor* revealed that thermal soil treatment significantly reduced soil toxicity although inhibitory effect on *L. minor* frond production and fresh weight remained.

Keywords: diesel, *D. magna*, *L. minor*, thermal desorption, remediation

Abandoned in the sea: fishing related debris in the seabed of Northern and Central Aegean Sea

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Abstract

In recent decades, the amount of marine debris, particularly plastics, has reached alarming levels, with their disposal showing an increasing trend over time. Debris that accumulates on the seafloor originates from various sources (terrestrial and/or marine) and results from a wide range of human activities, including urban centers, industries, maritime trade, tourism, and fishing. In this study the findings of the seabed litter monitoring effort in the Northern and Central Aegean Sea, conducted during the MEDITS Survey (International Bottom Trawl Survey in the Mediterranean) for the years 2018–2023, under the Greek Data Collection Framework (GDCF), are presented. Particular emphasis was given on litter originating from fishing activities (nets, pots, long lines, hooks), as they pose significant threat to the marine ecosystem. The results showed that the maximum litter weight density reached up to 4,912 kg/km², while the fishing related debris (FRD) accounts for 25.8% of the total litter on average, exceeding 90% in some cases. Based on the FRD densities, two major fishing grounds were detected, the first in North Evoikos Gulf and the second in Thracian Sea, from Thassos Island to Strymonikos Gulf. The application of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) demonstrated the hotspots of specific fishing gears operation, such as traps and purse seine nets in North Evoikos and east of Thassos, and long lines together with purse seine nets West of Thassos and in Strymonikos Gulf.

Keywords: *seabed litter, pollution, fishing related debris, Aegean Sea*

1. INTRODUCTION

Marine litter is increasing worldwide [1] and is considered a significant problem that threatens marine biodiversity. The Mediterranean Sea is considered an important hotspot for biodiversity, an alarmingly polluted area, and one of the most affected by marine debris region worldwide [2,3]. Plastics make up three-quarters of marine litter, as these are widely used and incredibly persistent in the marine environment [4]. Among litter, abandoned, lost, or discarded FRD constitutes one of the primary sources of marine benthic habitat degradation [5,6].

The Mediterranean Sea is particularly vulnerable to litter accumulation due to its isolated basin and its important coastal economy, which is supported by maritime transport, high fishing activity, tourism and oil/gas extraction infrastructure. According to [7], fishing, tourism and maritime traffic are important and endless sources of marine debris. Plastic items are the most dominant litter found on the seabed of the Mediterranean basin and represent

82% of all human-generated floating debris [8]. Additionally, FRD may account for up to 98% of the total recorded litter in the Mediterranean, in areas where fishing activity constitutes the most significant economic sector [9,10]. The main problem caused by marine litter are related to their accumulation in marine habitats and the interaction with marine organisms (entanglement, ingestion) [11]. Concerning the seabed, litter alters the surrounding habitat, disrupting life and providing a hard substrate that previously was absent [12].

The aim of this study is to highlight the issue of seafloor debris, to examine its spatial distribution, and to identify accumulation hotspots in the Northern and Central Aegean Sea. Another objective is to assess the contribution of the fishing sector to the litter accumulation problem in the marine environment. Additionally, an effort was made to identify key areas where specific fishing gear is used, based on the fishing-related debris (FRD) recovered from the seafloor.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study site

According to the General Fisheries Council of Mediterranean (GFCM) classification the study area falls within the Geographical Sub-Area (GSA) 22 and covers the marine region of Northern (NAS) and Central Aegean Sea (CAS). The area is considered a complex system since it includes a rambling coastline, several gulfs (Thermaikos, Strymonikos, and Kavala), and a number of islands as well as deep basins (Athos, Limnos and Sporades Basins). The area and especially Thermaikos Gulf and Thracian Sea, is characterized as the most productive fishing grounds, compared to other Greek marine regions (South Aegean, Ionian Sea and Crete) and significant fishing effort as well as increased daily catches take place, especially by purse seiners [13], but also trawlers and small-scale coastal fishing vessels. According to [14], Thermaikos Gulf and the Thracian Sea together account for 46.7% of the total Greek fish catches during 2022, while Central and Eastern Aegean Sea presented lower percentage (19.5%).

2.2 Data collection and analysis

For the data collection, six samplings were conducted in the NAS and CAS during the period 2018-2023 in 65 stations, under the Greek Data Collection Framework and within the MEDITS Survey. The stations are distributed across the coastal (10-50 m) and deep waters (up to 650 m; Figure 1) and all surveys were conducted during the summer months (June–August), as directed by the project strategy [15]. The fishing gear used to collect the seabed litter was the GOC 73 IFREMER otter trawl, a standard gear used by all Mediterranean member states. The average trawling speed was constant for all stations (3 knots) and the vessel's direction and speed were continuously recorded. The retrieved litter from all stations/hauls were weighted and sorted according to its material in nine main categories (L1: plastic, L2: rubber, L3: metal, L4: glass/ceramic/concrete, L5: clothes/textil/natural fibres, L6: processed wood, L7: paper/cardboard, L8: other debris and L9: unspecified material), according [15]. These main litter categories were further divided to 25 specific sub-categories and from these sub-categories the FRD were counted and weighted individually. The sub-categories that includes FRD are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Fishing related debris classification to sub-categories and material, according to the MEDITS Protocol [15].

Major Category	Sub-category
L1: Plastic	Fishing nets
L1: Plastic	Fishing lines
L1: Plastic	Other FRD (usually containers/traps)
L1: Plastic	Fishing ropes/strapping bands
L3: Metals	Metallic FRD
L4: Glass/ceramic/concrete	Concrete objects

Figure 1. Location of sampling stations (trawling hauls) used for the litter collection in the period 2018-2023.

The transformation of the debris’ measured weight (kg) into weight density (D_w ; kg/km²) was accomplished by calculating the swept area, which is derived from the trawling distance and the net’s horizontal opening measurements. The horizontal opening of the trawl-net in each station/haul was measured using the Simrad TV80 sensor system, a Doppler based instrument that is installed on the trawl-net and records the trawl net geometry (horizontal and vertical net’s openings) and the depth in real time.

The visualization of all spatial distributions (D_w , FRD) were carried out with the QGIS software. Any statistical difference of the mean weight density as well as the individual FRD densities between the examined years were examined with the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the Dunn's pairwise test. Additionally, to investigate the relationships and the variance between the selected FRD sub-categories and to examine which FRD prevails in each station, the principal component analysis (PCA) was performed. PCA is capable to reduce the dimensionality of the data while retaining as much variability as possible. The analysis was performed using the `prcomp()` function in R-4.4.1. The data were scaled using the z-standardization method to ensure that all variables contributed equally to the analysis without any single variable dominating due to its scaling.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Total litter on the seabed

The mean weight density of total seafloor litter for all measurements ($N=382$) was found to 63.02 kg/km² (stdev: 300.8 kg/km²), with values ranging from 0 kg/km² to 4,912.3 kg/km² (station 37; year 2023). Only two stations were found to be litter free accounting for 0.5% of the total sample, while five stations recorded weight densities exceeding 1,000 kg/km² (1.3%). The distribution of mean D_w across all stations is presented in Figure 2. The highest mean D_w were measured in Trikeri Passage (station 37: 909.5 kg/km²), followed by Northern Evoikos Gulf (station 39: 445.6 kg/km²), the Central Aegean (station 19: 418.6 kg/km²), and the area around Thassos Island (stations 1-2 and 63: 226.9–303.5 kg/km²). In contrast, lower mean D_w were measured in areas such as Thermaikos Gulf (D_w : 1.6–12.3 kg/km²), Sporades (D_w : 5.4–11.8 kg/km²), and Skyros (D_w : 1.9–28.8 kg/km²). The year with the highest mean D_w was 2023 (136.3 kg/km²), while the lowest was recorded in 2021 (26.8 kg/km²). For the rest of the examined years, the mean density ranged between 49.3 and 61.3 kg/km². The Kruskal-Wallis analysis showed no statistical differences between the examined years.

3.2 Fishing related debris on the seabed

Regarding fishing-related debris (FRD), the mean D_w was measured at 23.9 kg/km², ranging from 0 kg/km² (multiple stations) to 1,150 kg/km² (station 39; year 2019). The stations with the highest mean FRD weight densities are presented in Table 2. Most of these stations exhibited high FRD proportions relative to the total litter weight density, reaching up to 97.7%. Data analysis indicates that FRD contributed an average of 25.8% to the total seafloor debris and only 59 hauls out of 380 (15.4%) were found to be free of FRD. Plastic materials dominated the composition of FRD (Figure 3), with the highest proportion belonging to plastic ropes/strapping bands (44.7%), followed by plastic fishing nets (26.8%) and plastic fishing lines (13.2%).

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of the mean weight density (kg/km^2) of seabed litter for the period 2018-2023.

Table 2. Stations with the highest fishing related debris mean weight density and FRD percentage of total litter.

Stations	Mean weight density of FRD (kg/km^2)			FRD percentage (%)
39	429.40			96.37
2	296.45			97.67
63	219.01			80.82
1	158.07			69.66
23	99.63			49.15
26	76.81			38.30
62	65.88			94.91
58	50.35			96.32

The highest annual mean FRD was measured for the year 2019 ($43.2 \text{ kg}/\text{km}^2$), while the lowest in 2021 ($9.9 \text{ kg}/\text{km}^2$). This reduction may be attributed to the decrease in the fishing effort during the COVID lockdown period, since the consumer preference shifted toward long-life food products. Similar to the total litter, the total FRD did not show any statistical difference between the examined years according to Kruskal-Wallis (Kw: 0.79, $p= 0.44$).

However, the annual distribution of two individual sub-categories of FRD presented significant disparities throughout examined period. Namely, the “Other-FRD” sub-category (pots, traps) was found most abundant in 2019 and differentiated from 2021 (Kw: 26.8, $p < 0.01$) and 2022 (Kw: 23.5, $p < 0.05$), while for “fishing ropes/strapping band” sub-category the year 2021 was found to be statistically higher compared to 2018 (Kw: 86.1, $p < 0.001$), 2019 (Kw: 60.8, $p < 0.05$) and 2023 (Kw: 65.9, $p < 0.01$).

Figure 3. Contribution of each fishing related debris sub-category to the total FRD weight density (%) for the period 2018-2023.

The spatial distribution of the FRD percentage, as part of the total seabed litter is presented in Figure 4. This figure reveals the major fishing grounds which are characterized by FRD contribution above 40%: the first fishing ground is located in the Thracian Sea to the north, and covers the area between Thassos Island and Strymonikos Gulf, and the second is located in North Evoikos Gulf, at the southern part of the examined area. Individual stations with FRD percentage above 40% were also detected at Sporades, Lesvos Strait and Chalkidiki Peninsula.

The outcomes of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) are presented in Tables 3 and 4. According to the results, four components have been selected, explaining 92.9% of the variance (Table 3). The variables’ scores in the chosen principal components (PC) are presented in Table 4. Usually, two variables contribute the most to each PC, for example fishing lines and ropes/strapping bands in PC1.

Principal component analysis (PCA) revealed the potential prevalence of specific fishing gear types in the examined stations or areas (Figure 5). Notably, stations 1 and 2 (east of Thassos Island) and station 39 (N. Evoikos Gulf) appear to be dominated by "other plastic FRD" and "ropes and strapping bands," suggesting the presence of small fishing boats utilizing traps, as well as purse seiners, given that ropes are commonly associated with both fishing methods. Furthermore, station 63 is characterized by the presence of coastal fishing boats employing long lines, alongside purse seiners, as indicated by the presence of small to medium-sized concrete fragments attached to nets, likely used as additional weight. Similarly, stations 58 and 62 in the same area appear to be influenced by purse seiner activity. As illustrated in Figure 5, net fishing is prominent at hauls 19 (Central Aegean), 37 (Trikeri Passage), and 23 (Lesvos Strait). However, safe conclusions cannot be drawn for the remaining stations due to insufficient evidence. Nevertheless, certain hauls are distinguished by the presence of metallic FRD, primarily hooks (hauls 36, 53), which are indicative of long-line fishing activity.

Figure 4. Heat map of fishing related debris percentage as part of the total seabed litter in the examined area for the period 2018-2023.

Table 3. Results of the Principal Component Analysis including eigenvalues, the variance explained (%) in each component and the cumulative variance (%).

Components	Eigenvalue	Variance explained	Cumulative
1	2.44	40.65	40.65
2	1.14	18.98	59.63
3	1.02	17.06	76.69
4	0.97	16.20	92.89
5	0.28	4.66	97.55
6	0.15	2.44	100.00

Table 4. Variable scores obtained for each component.

Sub-categories	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
Fishing nets	0.024	0.141	0.692	-0.707
Fishing lines	-0.520	-0.428	0.037	-0.094
Other FRD	-0.489	0.530	-0.042	0.066
Fishing ropes/strapping bands	-0.520	0.445	-0.029	0.028
Metallic FRD	0.029	0.043	-0.719	-0.693
Concrete objects	-0.468	-0.563	0.027	-0.075

Figure 5. Ordination produced by the PCA analysis, based on the used FRD sub-categories.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The accumulation of litter in the marine environment is a significant problem that humanity will need to address, as the impact on marine ecosystems is devastating. The study of seafloor debris in the Northern and Central Aegean revealed very high localized weight densities, while the contribution of the fishing sector in the primary fishing grounds reaches up to 97.7%.

The type of fishing gear used by fishers can be verified by analyzing the composition of the seafloor debris. The issue of marine litter requires vigilance and continuous monitoring, which will lead to more reliable conclusions and support the development of future solutions.

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Unveiling the Bio-Control Potential of *Myrtus communis* L. Extracts Against Phytopathogenic Bacteria

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Abstract

The excessive use of synthetic pesticides in agriculture has a negative impact on the environment and human health. Furthermore, their continuous use has led to the emergence of pesticide-resistant phytopathogenic bacteria. This research focuses on the potential of *Myrtus communis* L. as a source of bioactive compounds with antimicrobial activity against key phytopathogenic bacteria. *Myrtus communis* L., is an evergreen bush native to southern Europe and western Asia. This plant has been traditionally used in folk medicine for various diseases. In the present work, extracts from different parts of the plant (seeds and leaves) were formed by means of ultrasound-assisted extraction (HAE), using different solvents (ethanol, methanol and n-hexane). The solvents were evaporated and the extracts were collected in a dry form. The solids formed were dissolved in suitable solvent which did not have any antimicrobial activity and the antimicrobial activity of the solution was studied on three phytopathogenic bacteria namely *Clavibacter michiganensis*, *Pseudomonas syringae* and *Xanthomonas campestris*, using the disk diffusion method (DDM). Different extracts displayed varying degrees of inhibition against the tested phytopathogenic bacteria. All leaf extracts demonstrated notable activity against *C. michiganensis*, with the methanol leaf extract (ML1) showing the largest inhibition zone (21 mm), followed by the hexane (18 mm) and ethanol (17 mm) leaf extracts. The hexane seed extract (MS3) also exhibited moderate activity (10 mm) against *C. michiganensis*, while the ethanol seed extract (MS2) showed a smaller inhibition zone (8 mm), and the methanol seed extract (MS1) showed no inhibition. For *P. syringae*, the hexane leaf extract (ML3) presented the highest antibacterial activity (11 mm), followed by the methanol leaf extract (ML1) (9 mm). Against *X. campestris*, the leaf extracts again demonstrated the most potent antibacterial effects, with the methanol leaf extract (ML1) and hexane leaf extract (ML3) exhibiting the largest inhibition zones (21 mm and 19 mm, respectively), followed by the ethanol leaf extract (ML2) (17 mm). Overall, the methanol and hexane extracts from *Myrtus communis* L. leaves consistently demonstrated the most promising antibacterial activity across the tested phytopathogenic bacteria, suggesting their potential as a source of bio-pesticides.

Keywords: *extraction, biopesticides, antimicrobial activity, myrtle*

***Mytilopsis leucophaeata* (Conrad, 1831) as a sentinel species to monitor the environmental state in brackish waters: a case study in four populations in Normandy (France)**

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Abstract

Mytilopsis leucophaeata (Conrad, 1831), commonly known as the false brown mussel, is a bivalve species within the Dreissenidae family, originally native to the Atlantic coastline, extending from the Gulf of Mexico to the Hudson River estuary. Its presence in Europe was first documented in 1835 in the port of Antwerp (Belgium), and since then, its range has expanded considerably, now encompassing regions from southern Europe to Scandinavia. This species exhibits remarkable ecological adaptability, being both euryhaline, tolerating salinities between 0 and 22 PSU, and eurythermal, thriving within a temperature range of 5 to 30°C. Such resilience enables it to colonize a wide variety of habitats, making it a potentially valuable candidate for environmental monitoring in transitional aquatic zones, such as estuaries and ports. Despite these attributes, *M. leucophaeata* remains significantly understudied compared to *Dreissena polymorpha*, a well-established model organism in freshwater ecotoxicology.

In this context, the present study aimed to evaluate the bioindicator value of *Mytilopsis leucophaeta* to assess the quality of transitional water masses. To this goal, we performed a passive biomonitoring by using 4 populations located at 4 different sites along the coasts of the French part of the English Channel. We measured a battery of biomarkers relative to important physiological functions, i.e. reproduction, energetic reserves and immune system of this bivalve in order to compare the physiological status of the 4 populations at each sampling dates (March and May) during the three years of the study (2020, 2021 and 2022).

The results revealed that the localisation of the population have an effect on the physiological status of the individuals. Considering all the results, the most variable biomarker was the weight of individuals, and the most stable biomarker was the phagocytic activity. Finally, the year during which the studies were carried out could be an important source of variability. This work has enabled us to acquire data on its immune and reproductive characteristics of *Mytilopsis leucophaeata*. This species is interesting in a biomonitoring context especially because its presence in a wide range of salinities and its easy maintenance in the laboratory. However, this work is not yet sufficient to qualify *M. leucophaeata* as a bioindicator species, and further studies are required.

Keywords: brown mussel, biondicators, estuary, biomarkers

Toxicity of Commercial Sunscreens on *Artemia franciscana*: Rethinking Eco-Friendly Claims

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Abstract

In the last decade, the widespread use of sunscreens has raised growing concerns about their environmental impact, particularly on marine ecosystems. In response to this concern, many cosmetic companies have launched product lines labeled as "eco-friendly" or "ocean-friendly," supposedly designed to reduce their environmental footprint. However, due to the lack of environmental regulations governing the formulation of these products, the criteria for labeling a sunscreen as "eco-friendly" rely solely on each company's internal standards, creating uncertainty about their actual environmental risk. This work evaluated the toxicity of six commercial sunscreens on three life stages of *Artemia franciscana*: cyst, nauplius, and adult. Seven different concentrations, ranging from 0 to 500 mg/L, were tested for each sunscreen over 48 hours at 25°C. The assessed endpoints were hatching inhibition (cysts) and mortality (nauplii and adults). The selected sunscreens included different application formats and ingredient formulations: C1, C2, and C3 (without eco-friendly labeling), EC1 (labeled as eco-friendly), and EC2 and EC3 (labeled as ocean-friendly). The results indicated that nauplii were the most sensitive life stage to sunscreen exposure, showing a higher mortality rate compared to adults and a higher hatching inhibition rate than cysts. The highest nauplii mortality was recorded after exposure to sunscreen EC1 ($LC_{50} = 3.09$ mg/L), which was significantly higher than that observed with the non-eco-labeled sunscreens (sunscreen C1 $LC_{50} = 9.52$ mg/L, sunscreen C2 $LC_{50} = 116.71$ mg/L, sunscreen C3 $LC_{50} = 378.93$ mg/L). These findings highlight the urgent need to develop a standardized ecotoxicological testing battery to determine whether a sunscreen can be considered eco-friendly.

Keywords: *sunscreens, Ultraviolet filters, marine ecosystem, eco-labeling, toxicity test*

Acute Toxicity in War-Affected Waters: Evaluating Risk to Aquatic Crustaceans

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Abstract

The intense hostilities in Ukraine have led to significant ecological changes, with lasting impacts on aquatic ecosystems. Explosions, the destruction of industrial infrastructure and the spilling of pollutants into rivers, lakes and groundwater have disrupted hydrological processes, posing serious threats to biodiversity and water quality. Twelve water samples and seven sediment samples were collected in five regions of Ukraine - Kyiv, Kharkiv, Chernigov, Mykolaiv and Odessa - from water bodies that have been affected in one way or another by the war. Hydrochemical analysis of the collected samples was carried out and the concentrations of heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in these samples were evaluated. The concentrations of heavy metals and PAHs in the analysed water samples were relatively low or below the detection limits. Mercury concentrations above the good environmental status limits were detected in several sediment samples. The aim of this study was to assess the acute ecotoxicological effects of aquatic and benthic sediments exposed to warfare on three different crustacean species: *Heterocypris incongruens* (*Ostracoda*), a benthic bivalve of fresh and brackish waters, a detritophagous bivalve that feeds on organic matter and algae; *Daphnia magna* (*Branchiopoda, Cladocera*); planktonic crustacean of freshwater, filter-feeder, feeding on phytoplankton, bacteria and detritus; *Thamnocephalus platyurus* (*Branchiopoda, Anostraca*); a crustacean living in temporary freshwater pools, feeding on organic particles and plankton. Toxicity to the crustacean *Heterocypris incongruens* was assessed by analysing growth inhibition and mortality; immobilisation response, heart rate changes and swimming behaviour of *Daphnia magna*; and mortality of the shrimp *Thamnocephalus platyurus*. The toxicity values obtained were converted into toxicity units. It was found that the water from the water bodies studied was mostly free of acute toxicity, but that there were also mildly to moderately toxic samples with TU > 1. These findings indicate that some water bodies in war-affected areas pose a risk of acute toxicity to aquatic organisms. This work was funded by the NATO Science for Peace and Security Programme project "Development of a strategy for assessment and restoration of war-affected aquatic ecosystems" (Project No. G6085) and by the Research Council of Lithuania under the Lithuania-Ukraine Bilateral Cooperation in Science and Technology Programme "Assessment of the risk to aquatic biota from the release of rare earth elements through the use of modern technologies (including military)" (Project No. S-LU-24-13).

Keywords: warfare impacts, water bodies, pollution, crustacean bioassays, acute toxicity, toxicity assessment

Impact of rare earth metal-based nanoparticles on *Daphnia magna*: the correlation between nanotoxicity and physico-chemical properties

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Abstract

Rare earth metals (REMs) comprise a group of 17 chemical elements, including lanthanides, scandium, and yttrium. REMs-based nanoparticles (NPs) have gained significant attention due to their unique magnetic, optical and catalytic properties, making them highly valuable in various fields such as electronics, energy, medicine, biotechnology [1]. Among them, gadolinium (Gd)-based NPs are particularly promising for biomedical imaging. Our preliminary results have shown that Gd-based NPs, which exploit the paramagnetic nature of the trivalent Gd ion, are particularly effective for MRI applications due to their ability to shorten the T1 relaxation time of tissues (Morkvėnas et al., 2024). However, despite their biomedical potential, concern about the ecotoxicological effects of REMs-based NPs are growing. Currently, the available data on the effects of REMs-based NPs on the aquatic environment [3] and human health are limited, particularly regarding the relationship between their physicochemical properties and toxicity to the organism. Thus, this study aimed to investigate the toxicological effects of GdPO₄:Eu³⁺ NPs on *Daphnia magna* after 48 hour exposure to different morphologies (rod, prism and sphere) and concentrations (0, 3.124, 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100 µg/mL). The results demonstrated that *D. magna* heart rate and behavioral parameters (total moved distance and velocity) were predominantly influenced by higher NPs concentrations. These findings are critical for developing standardized toxicity assessment protocols, informing NPs regulations, and evaluating the safety of emerging nanotechnological tools for medical diagnostics and therapy. Given the anticipated increase in nanomaterial applications in biomedicine, further research is essential to ensure their safe and sustainable use.

Keywords: rare earth metals nanoparticles, nanotoxicity, physico-chemical properties, aquatic organisms, biological parameters

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the Research Council of Lithuania, agreement No [S-MIP-24-92] “Effects of rare earth metals-based nanoparticles on aquatic organism: correlation between nanotoxicity and physico-chemical properties”.

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Assessing the impact of water from war-affected areas of Ukraine on test-organisms

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Abstract

The ongoing armed conflict in Ukraine has triggered an environmental crisis, with military activities having both direct and indirect impacts on aquatic ecosystems. It is therefore necessary to develop a strategy for the restoration of natural ecosystems in Ukraine, including rapid assessment of the ecological status of degraded ecosystems using cost-effective methods, identification of risks and restoration of bioresources. The first step for achieving these goals was to create the cost-effective complex of test-organisms from autotrophs to consumers for examining the damaged ecosystems. Six water samples were collected from water bodies in four regions (Kyiv, Chernihiv, Kharkiv and Odessa) of Ukraine, and it was found that all the water bodies studied were affected to some extent by military operations. The aim of the present study was to evaluate the effects of these waters on germination, root growth, pigments, malondialdehyde (MDA) and hydrogen peroxide content in garden cress (*Lepidium sativum* L.). In addition, a hydro-chemical analysis was carried out and the concentrations of heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in these waters were assessed. The concentrations of heavy metals and PAHs in the water samples tested were relatively low or below the detection limit. No significant changes in seed germination and biomass of roots and above-ground parts as well as root growth of *L. sativum* were observed in most of the tested water samples compared to the control ($p > 0.05$). The study also showed that the tested water samples did not affect chlorophyll *a* and *b* level or carotenoid synthesis in *L. sativum* seedlings. No significant changes were observed in the amount of MDA in the above-ground parts and roots of *L. sativum* in response to the tested water samples ($p > 0.05$). However, the level of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) in the above-ground parts of *L. sativum* was statistically higher ($p = 0.002$) in one water sample compared to the control, suggesting a potential oxidative stress response, while no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed for these parameters in the root tissue between the test samples and the control. These acute toxicity test results suggest that the water bodies in the study area may be resilient to the effects of military activities. However, long-term toxicity studies, using test organisms from different trophic levels, are required to fully evaluate potential ecological risks.

Keywords: military activities, water bodies, pollution, *Lepidium sativum*, biological parameters

Acknowledgement

This work was funded by NATO Science for Peace and Security Programme “Creating a Strategy for Assessing and Restoring War-affected Aquatic Ecosystem” (project No G6085).

Effects of upconverting nanoparticles on photosynthetic pigments and oxidative stress of the green alga *Desmodesmus communis*

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Abstract

The increasing use of upconverting nanoparticles (UCNPs), which are composed of rare metals, has raised concerns about their potential impact on aquatic ecosystems. These nanoparticles exhibit unique optical properties, making them valuable for biomedical imaging, sensing and environmental monitoring. However, the understanding of their interactions with aquatic organisms remains limited. This study investigates the effects of NaYF₄:Yb³⁺,Er³⁺ UCNPs at different concentrations (0, 2.5, 5, 10, 25, 50, and 100 mg/L) on the levels of chlorophyll *a* (Chl *a*), carotenoid (Car), and malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of oxidative stress, in the freshwater microalgae *Desmodesmus communis* (Chlorophyta). The green algae isolates were cultured in two media: in an artificial algae growth medium (MWC) and in the water of the river Neris. The results indicate that the UCNP exposure did not significantly affect the Chl *a* and Car levels in both media ($p > 0.05$). However, total Chl *a* and Car concentrations were significantly higher in the MWC medium than in the river Neris water ($p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that although the UCNPs had no direct effect on photosynthetic pigments or oxidative stress markers (MDA), the differences in pigment content and oxidative stress response between the two media may be due to differences in overall water chemistry, including buffering capacity.

Keywords: nanoparticles, *Desmodesmus communis*, chlorophyll, carotenoids, malondialdehyde

Acknowledgment

This work was supported by the Research Council of Lithuania, agreement No [S-MIP-24-92] “Effects of rare earth metals-based nanoparticles on aquatic organism: correlation between nanotoxicity and physico-chemical properties”.

Study of the potential environmental impacts of anticorrosion protections commonly used in the offshore renewable energy industry, including galvanic anodes cathodic protections (GACP) and impressed current (ICCP) - the ECOCAP project

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Abstract

ECOCAP (ECOtoxicology analysis of CATHodic Protections) is an R&D program «Environmental integration of Renewable Marine Energy (RME)» carried out by France Energies Marines (FEM, <https://www.france-energies-marines.org>). It aims to assess the chemical risk of elements released by cathodic protection systems using galvanic anodes (GACP) or impressed current (ICCP) on the marine environment. These protections are used across all industrial sectors in the marine environment, including port areas, transport vessels and offshore oil or gas extraction platforms. With the growth of the offshore wind market in France, the question of the potential impact of cathodic protection on the environment is emerging and is being put forward by the French public authorities, as well as by civil society. This concern translates into a strong expectation by public authorities, offshore wind farm developers and civil society to obtain scientifically verified evidence of a limited impact of these anti-corrosion protections on the marine environment.

For the first time, a wide range of experimental toxicity tests was carried out in the laboratory on different marine species covering different trophic levels in order to evaluate the potential synergistic or antagonistic impacts of elements released from GACP and ICCP on marine organisms. At the same time, a hydrodynamic model applied to different cases of offshore wind farms studies allowed to simulate the dispersion of the elements diffused in the marine environment. The data collected informed a chemical risk assessment carried out according to the REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals) technical guide described by ECHA (European Chemicals Agency, 2016). All the results were then used to support a holistic approach to assess the impact of contaminants on

marine food webs. For this, a trophic model was adapted to study the trophic transfer of contaminants, with a first application focusing on aluminium from GACP.

The project conducted to publish a report of recommendations that will be available for the MRE sector on best practices for the corrosion protection of MRE offshore infrastructures. The ECOCAP project also contributed to the development of new standardized protocols for environmental impact assessments that will provide the MRE sector with additional tools for water quality assessment.

Keywords: *water contamination, cathodic protection, toxicity, marine environment*

Elevated temperature influence on pesticide terbuthylazine toxicity to duckweed *Lemna minor*

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Abstract

Anthropogenic chemical pollution has the potential to pose one of the largest environmental threats to humanity, but global understanding of the issue remains fragmented. Inland waters and freshwater biodiversity constitute a valuable natural resource, in economic, cultural, aesthetic, scientific and educational terms. Anthropogenic activity results in the contamination of water bodies with various chemicals, which in turn reduces ecosystem functioning. Pesticides stand out for their widespread occurrence and highly diverse biological effects. They enter adjacent water bodies through different ways and their residues may be overtaken by non-target organisms, leading to chronic lethal and sublethal effects. In the European Union, herbicide terbuthylazine (TBA), a member of the chloro-s-triazine group, has emerged as one of the most frequently detected herbicides in water bodies. However, TBA toxicity to aquatic plants is poorly documented. In addition to the direct stress caused by chemical contamination, there are certain environmental stressors (such as temperature) that might cause additional stress; thus, it is important to understand the effects of changing environmental factors on pollutants' ecotoxicity to aquatic organisms. To address this knowledge gap, we aimed to test the influence of elevated temperature on ecotoxicological effects of pesticide terbuthylazine (TBA) to the duckweed *Lemna minor* growth, metabolites and antioxidative stress levels. *L. minor* grew in at 5 different TBA concentrations under different temperature regimes (23°C and 27°C). *L. minor* morphological indicators (fresh weight, frond area), biochemical indicators (enzyme activity and metabolites) as well as oxidative stress damage (lipid peroxidation) were measured.

Keywords: climate change, terbuthylazine, *Lemna minor*, oxidative stress.

**Spatial distributions and temporal trends (2009–2020)
of pesticide mixtures in streams and rivers
across Lombardy region (Italy)**

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Abstract

Mixtures of chemicals in the environment are of growing concern in the scientific community. In this study, a large monitoring dataset relating to the presence of plant protection products in surface water bodies of the Lombardy Region was analyzed. A methodology was implemented allowing the georeferencing and calculation of the toxicity of all the mixtures present in each sampling and monitoring station in the period considered (2009-2020). The toxicity of the mixtures was evaluated for the three representative aquatic organisms (algae, daphnia, fish) of the trophic chains of aquatic ecosystems. The analysis of the data has highlighted that the southern part of the Lombardy Region is most at risk (provinces of Mantua, Lodi, Cremona, and Pavia), as the widespread presence of corn and rice leads to greater contamination of water bodies by herbicides (e.g. terbuthylazine and metolachlor) and insecticides (mainly organophosphorus). Finally, it has been highlighted that, generally, only one or two components are responsible for almost all of the toxicity of the mixture. This aspect is very relevant for risk management purposes, as by reducing the presence of these components the total toxicity of the mixture is reduced.

Keywords: *mixture toxicity, aquatic ecosystems; measured environmental concentrations; Lombardy region, concentration addition*

Pollution Monitoring and Remediation

Fluoride removal from aqueous solutions by using hybrid super-adsorbents of chitosan/ orange peels/activated carbon functionalized with MgO

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Abstract

Exposure to excessive concentrations of fluoride in potable water is harmful to human health; therefore, its limitation is deemed necessary. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the allowable limit is 1.5 mg/L, but the recommended range is between 0.5 and 1 mg/L. Among the commonly applied technologies, adsorption is selected, as it gathers the most advantages, compared to other techniques, as it is a highly effective, simple, and economically efficient treatment. In the present study, several combinations of chitosan (CS), orange peels (OP), activated carbon (AC), and MgO were synthesized and examined as adsorbents in order to find the most effective derivative for fluoride ions (F⁻) removal. The impact of the adsorbent dosage, pH level, contact time, and initial concentration was investigated. According to the results, the modification of chitosan with AC, OP, and MgO in a unique adsorbent (CS/OP/AC@MgO), especially in acidic conditions (pH 3.0 ± 0.1) by using 1.0 g/L of the adsorbent, demonstrated the highest efficiency, up to 97%. The pseudo-second (PSO) order model and Langmuir isotherm model fitted better to the experimental results, especially for CS/OP/AC@MgO, providing a $Q_m=26.92$ mg/g. Thermodynamic analysis confirmed the spontaneous nature of the adsorption process. The structure and morphology of the modified OP/CS@AC-Mg were extensively characterized using BET, XRD, FTIR, and SEM techniques. Overall, this research demonstrated that chitosan composites modified with environmentally friendly materials can effectively remove F⁻ from water, presenting new opportunities for enhancing water quality and protection of public health.

Keywords: *fluoride, adsorption, chitosan, activated carbon, peels*

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The Role of Fluorescence Techniques in Monitoring Aquatic Ecosystem Health Impacted by Pollution

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Abstract

Many toxic chemicals, including pesticides, heavy metals, plastics, pharmaceuticals and disinfectant, pose significant threats to air, soil, and water quality. Water pollution is particularly concerning, as substances such as for example bisoprolol and ketoprofen—widely used in medical treatments—adversely affect the growth and metabolism of microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Desmodesmus armatus*. These impacts underscore the urgent need for regular monitoring of chemical concentrations to safeguard ecosystems and human health.

This study explores the toxic effects of AKWATON 10, a widely used disinfectant, on *Lemna minor* L., utilizing two innovative and repeatable fluorescence techniques. The first technique measures photosynthetic efficiency by analyzing chlorophyll fluorescence, providing insights into the plant's stress response. The second technique evaluates cell viability through fluorescence microscopy, employing ethidium bromide and acridine orange to differentiate between live, dying, and dead cells. Furthermore, the study examines how AKWATON 10 impacts the overall growth dynamics of *Lemna minor* L., including changes in frond number and surface area. Physiological responses, such as alterations in pigment composition and photosynthetic efficiency, are analyzed to assess the broader implications for plant metabolism. By integrating these parameters, the research provides a comprehensive view of how AKWATON 10 disrupts aquatic plant physiology.

Keywords: Lemnaceae, toxicity, chlorophyll fluorescence, fluorescence microscopy

PM10 concentration distribution in surface layer of the atmosphere of Kutaisi city, Georgia - during calm weather

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Abstract

Spatial distribution and time change of PM10 concentration in the atmosphere of Kutaisi city in Georgia has been modeled. The 3D regional model of atmospheric process evolution, admixture transfer-diffusion equation and terrain-tracking coordinate system have been used. A situation of surface calm during background wind of all four directions has been considered. Patterns of time change and spatial distribution of PM10 concentration in case of western, eastern, southern and western winds in surface layer of the atmosphere have been analyzed. It has been established that the terrain of the city and surrounding territories provides formation of anticyclonic vortex in surface layer of the atmosphere. Vortex centers are located at the different territories of the city during different background winds and there is a difference between spatial distribution and time change of concentration fields. In all four cases, a time change of aerosol concentration runs in four stages and depends on the intensity of motor-vehicle traffic, highway location and city terrain. The areas of relatively high pollution have been determined. It has been shown that a time change of atmosphere thermal stability in surface layer of the atmosphere plays important role in time change of microaerosol concentrations and in high-concentration establishment process.

Keywords: *atmosphere, PM10 pollution, numerical modeling, surface calm.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The PM2.5 and PM10 are among the main ingredients polluting the atmospheric air. Due to small sizes, they freely penetrate human organism, cause many diseases and frequently even death [1-5]. The influence, caused by presence of PM particles in the atmospheric air, and which has an effect on human health and living conditions is thoroughly analyzed in [6]. The level of atmospheric air pollution with PM2.5 and PM10 particles is quite high in the industrial centers of Asia and Africa, in megalopolis and some small cities, where their air content frequently exceeds several times the maximum permissible concentrations [5-7]. High pollution is registered in some European cities, as well [8]. Atmospheric emissions of polluting ingredients, including PM2.5 and PM10 has been reduced and the atmospheric air purity quality has been improved as a result of air-protection measures taken in the EU countries and the United Kingdom over the last quarter of the century. However, in a whole range of the cities, the air pollution level still exceeds the EU standards [9, 10].

PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ monitoring in Georgia has started since 2018 [6]. As of today, we have studied the distribution of PM particles and urban air quality in the atmosphere of Rustavi, Zestaponi and Tbilisi cities. These cities are not among the heavily polluted cities worldwide, but it is not so uncommon that microparticle concentrations in the atmosphere of these cities exceed the respective maximum permissible concentration values [11-15]. In this article, for the first time we present the results of study of PM particle distribution in the atmosphere of Kutaisi city. Kutaisi city is an important medical-recreational, touristic and administrative center of Georgia. That is why evaluation of city air purity, operational and diagnostic forecasting of pollution level are of particular importance. For this purpose, pollution of Kutaisi atmospheric air with PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, other ingredients and in general an air purity quality were studied using operational and experimental measurements [16]. Big role in this problem research is assigned to computer modeling, as well [17,18]. Using mathematical and numerical models, the modeling describes the impact of urban, ecological and meteorological processes on spatial distribution and time change of air polluting microparticles in the city and surrounding territories. The present article firstly studies impact of background wind direction impact in the atmosphere on PM₁₀ propagation as well as the time change processes in the atmosphere of Kutaisi and adjacent territories using numerical modeling.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Atmospheric air mathematical monitoring method is used for study of PM₁₀ pollution of Kutaisi air. This method, through combined integration of the system of 3D nonlinear non-steady equations of hydrothermodynamics of β -mesoscale atmospheric processes and equation of admixture transfer-diffusion [18-20], implements the modeling of microaerosol admixtures' propagation in the city and its surrounding territories. Numerical modeling is performed for atmosphere at the territory of Kutaisi and its surroundings having a complex terrain with 13.4 km x13.4 km in area (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Terrain, administrative units (AU) and infrastructure of Kutaisi city (Google map)

The terrain-tracking coordinate system ($t, x, y, \zeta = (z - d)/h$) is used for mathematically correct description of dynamic fields of atmosphere and meteorological parameters. Here t is a time, x and y are coordinates directed along the parallel and meridian, ζ is a dimensionless vertical coordinate, $\delta(x, y)$ is a terrain height above sea level, $h = H - \delta$ troposphere thickness, $H(t, x, y)$ – tropopause height. An equation of passive ingredients transfer-diffusion in the atmosphere can be written in the selected coordinate system as follows:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} + (\tilde{w} - \frac{w_0}{h}) \frac{\partial C}{\partial \zeta} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mu \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mu \frac{\partial C}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{h^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \zeta} \nu \frac{\partial C}{\partial \zeta} + F \quad (1)$$

where, C is an ingredient concentration; u, v, w and \tilde{w} wind velocity components along the x, y, z and ζ axes; w_0 – ingredient deposition rate, $F(t, x, y, \zeta)$ - the rate of ingredients' discharge in the atmosphere by a source; μ and ν – coefficients of horizontal and vertical turbulency. Wind velocity components and turbulence coefficients in the free atmosphere and boundary and surface layers of the atmosphere are calculated according to formula given in [18-20].

PM aerosols propagation modeling is made by means of numerical integration of the equation (1) using respective initial and boundary conditions. Splitting method according to processes and coordinates and Crank-Nicolson scheme [20] are used for integration. Numerical grid steps along the x and y axes are equal to 200 m. Vertical dimensionless step in the free atmosphere equals to 1/31, which approximately corresponds to 300 m. In the 100-m thick surface layer of the atmosphere a vertical step varies from 0.5 to 15 m. Time step is 1 sec. Calculations are made for a 3-day period in June. Parameters and initial conditions included in the model are selected in such a way that a calm situation – wind velocity 0 m/sec takes place at 100 m height of the surface layer. Above the surface layer a wind velocity linearly increases and reaches 20 m/sec at 9 km height. There are considered four cases – stationary cases of eastern, western, southern and northern background winds. Relative atmospheric humidity is 50%.

It is assumed that the atmosphere is polluted with PM10 particles due to motor-transport vehicle at 0.5 m height from the earth ground in the city and its adjacent territories in 5-type areas: territories of highways, central city streets, residential, industrial zones and unsettled areas of surrounding villages. Discharge rate is different depending on areas, is periodic with 24-hour interval and is proportional to motor-transport traffic intensity. It is minimal within 0-4 h time interval, linearly increases from 4 h to 10 h and constant from 10 h to 18 h. Within an interval from 18 h to 24 h the discharge rate linearly decreases and becomes equal to the value registered at 0 h. Maximum emission rate along the highways is 11.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{sec}$. The figures were performed in the software “visual fortran”.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 2 wind velocity and PM10 concentration are shown, at 2 m height from the earth ground. These results are formed under influence of background meteorological processes and terrain during Western Background Wind (WBW), Eastern Background Wind (EBW), Northern Background Wind (NBW), Southern Background Wind (SBW) at the territory of Kutaisi and its surroundings, under calm conditions in surface layer of the atmosphere and

during formation of high concentrations – at 7 AM. It is seen from Figure 2 that as a result of terrain and background flows interaction in modeling domain, a local-scale surface vortex is formed in surface layer of the atmosphere (2m). Surface wind velocity in the modeling domain varies within limits of 0-3 m/sec. Wind velocity is minimal in the vortex center and increases in a direction away from center to periphery.

Anticyclone vortex center during WBW is located in the southern-eastern part of the modeling domain, in Kolkheti lowland, at the territory of Mukhrani AU (administrative unit); during EBW a vortex center is located to the north of modeling domain center at the densely populated historic area of the city – hilly territories of Ukimerioni and City Museum AUs. During NBW and SBW, anticyclone vortex centers are located at the territories of City Museum, Dzelkviani and Kakhianouri AUs. Pattern of a formed local vortex circulation and terrain thermodynamics determine spatial distribution and time change of concentrations. During WBW, high concentration (30-50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) is obtained in the northern part of anticyclone in the surroundings of Nikea, A. Tsereteli and I. Chavchavadze streets. These streets bypass anticyclone center from the east, west and north sides.

Qualitatively similar patterns of concentration distribution are obtained during NBW and SBW (Figure 2. NBW and SBW). Higher concentrations up to 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ are obtained on 3 sections of international highway located in the southern part of territory. As for concentration distribution on other central city streets, they are analogous with each other and their values are within limits of 20-30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Especially high concentrations ($>70 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) are registered in the surroundings of eastern part of the city – in the neighbor of main trunk lines passing the territories of City-Museum and Dzelkviani AUs. High concentrations are also obtained on Javakhishvili street, D. Aghmashenebeli Avenue, some other central streets and at the separate sections of by-pass road, which pass the Ukimerioni, D. Aghmashenebeli, Dzelkviani AUs.

Emitted aerosol due to convection and turbulent diffusion processes extend in both vertical and horizontal directions over surface layer of the atmosphere (Figure 3). At this time pollution thermals are formed, which expand in width, height and occupy wide areas (Figure 4). In Figure 4 there is shown PM10 concentration during DBW, EBW, NBW and SBW at the upper limit of surface layer of the atmosphere in the moment close to achievement of maximum value (9 AM). It is seen from Figure 4 that the wind velocity field formed at 100 m height has a clearly defined anticyclone pattern. Spatial distribution of concentration is qualitatively the same, and values are changed within limits of 1-30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Atmosphere pollution level is relatively lower during WBW and higher – during EBW. As for cases of NBW and SBW, concentration fields are roughly the same. In both cases, high concentration values are obtained in the vicinity of vortex circulation center.

In Figure 5 there is shown a time change of microparticle concentrations in case of WBW, obtained via calculations in 5-types of urban points. It is seen from the figure that a time change of concentration in a main discharge area is characterized with 2 maximums – one of them is at 7 AM and second one – around 9 PM, and with 2 minimums – within intervals of 0-4 AM and 1-3 PM. The mentioned pattern of time change of concentration in residential zones is weakly expressed. As for unsettled territories of neighbor villages, the concentration here is small ($< 1 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and virtually unchanged in time.

Figure 2. Wind velocity and PM10 concentration at 2 m height from the earth surface, in Kutaisi and surrounding territories during WBW, EBW, NBW, SBW at 6 AM

Figure 3. PM10 concentration during WBW, EBW, NBW and SBW at 6 AM in the vertical section along a parallel in surface layer of the atmosphere, when a meridian step number of numerical grid equals to 40

Figure 4. Wind velocity and PM10 concentration during WBW, EBW, NBW and SBW at 9 AM on the border of surface layer of the atmosphere

Figure 5. Time change of PM10 concentration during WBW at 2 m height from earth surface in the points located on highways (1), central city streets (2), industrial (3) residential zones (4) and unsettled points of adjacent villages (5)

First concentration minimum is caused by minimum emission rate, on one hand and by weak turbulence stipulated by stable thermal stratification of surface atmospheric air. Within time interval from 4 AM to 7 AM, earth surface temperature decreases, respectively, stratification stability increases and turbulization reduces. The mentioned thermodynamic effect, along with intensive growth of emission rate causes accumulation of polluting ingredients and, respectively, rapid growth of concentration. After 7 AM takes place an increase of earth surface temperature, related reduction of thermal stability, growth of vertical

turbulization and export of ingredients from the emission zone. At that, concentration dropout caused by dynamic effects exceeds an increase stipulated by motor-vehicle traffic growth and pollution zone reduction takes place as a result. From 10 AM to 6 PM aerosol discharge rate becomes constant, and only thermal stability is changed. Until 1 PM occurs concentration reduction caused by stability reduction and increase of vertical turbulence. After 1 PM the process is reversed. Approximately until 9 PM takes place a concentration growth caused by thermodynamic process. After 9 PM the process runs in reverse direction. Quantity of ingredients emitted by motor vehicles is reduced and takes place a concentration growth caused by stratification stability increase. At that, a growth rate is less than a reduction rate that ultimately causes concentration decrease down to value existing at midnight (0 h). In the ensuing time periods, the process continues on a quasi-periodical basis.

Figure 6. Time change of PM10 concentration at 2 m height from earth ground in case of WBW (1), EBW (2), SBW (3) and NBW (4) in the highway point with grid coordinates (43,45,3).

In Figure 6 a time change of concentration values for all four directions in the point of extremely high emission with grid coordinates (43, 45, 3) is shown. It is seen from Figure 6 that during EBW and NBW, as well as SBW, extremely high ($140 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and high ($90 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) concentrations are obtained in this point at 7 AM, and respectively, maximum concentration values are obtained in the evening at different moments from 9 PM to 11 PM.

The carried-out studies showed that dissipation of PM particles in atmosphere of Kutaisi city as well as other cities of Georgia is mainly caused by motor transport and operating industrial enterprises.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Using a numerical modeling, a surface local wind velocity field in the surroundings of Kutaisi city has been obtained. It has been shown that a terrain effect on background flow of four main types present in the atmospheric boundary layer and in the free atmosphere forms the local anticyclone vortices. Location of anticyclone centers depends on background wind direction. A formed wind velocity field determines spatial distribution of microaerosols and

pollution levels. Maximum pollution at 2 m height from the earth surface, according to both concentration value and polluted area, is obtained during EBW, while minimum – during WBW. In case of SBW and NBW, a spatial distribution of concentration is virtually the same. Maximum pollution domains are determined. During EBW, surface air of the central parts of the city – the territories of Ukimerioni, Gamarjveba, City-Museum, Dzelkviani and Kakhianouri, Sulkhan-Saba AUs is heavily contaminated (> 1.5 MPC). During SBW and NBW, high pollution level is obtained in the vicinity of City-Museum, Dzelkviani and Kakhianouri, Sulkhan-Saba and Nikea AUs. As for the case of DBW, a concentration within 1 MPC is obtained in the vicinity of crossroads of highways at the territory of the city and its surroundings. Time change of concentration is characterized by a presence of two maximums and two minimums. Maximal concentrations are obtained at 6-7 h and 18-21 h, while minimum concentrations are within intervals of 0-4 h and 14-16 h. The mentioned effect substantially depends on a time change of thermal stability of surface layer of the atmosphere. Vertical transfer of PM10 discharged to surface layer of the atmosphere occurs in the form of “thermal”-like clouds. Maximum concentrations 25-30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at 100 m height from the earth ground are obtained with 3-hour delay.

Results of carried-out studies enable us to formulate recommendations for local government units and for incorporation in environmental policy. In particular, it is recommended:

- to establish the recreation zones in the central parts of heavily polluted cities;
- to tighten supervision over vehicle emissions;
- to restrict the private car traffic in the central city districts during rush hours;
- to clean city streets using wet scavenging.

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Beneficial aspects of *in-situ* non-metal-doped carbocatalysts for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern from wastewater

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Abstract

In recent decades, as an adverse effect of global population growth, contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) are continuously released into the environment, resulting in a huge threat to human health and aquatic ecosystems. Traditional methods for wastewater treatment are not adequate enough to tackle the growing complexity of these contaminants found in wastewater today. As environmental standards become more stringent, the need for innovative, efficient treatment solutions has never been greater. Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), especially sulfate radical-based AOPs, represent a cutting-edge solution designed to avoid secondary contamination by oxidizing CECs to biodegradable or harmless substances, carbon-dioxide and water. The addition of a heterogeneous catalyst into the system enables the high efficiency and easy operation of the process, as well as low energy consumption. In relation to this, the design of appropriate catalysts for AOPs still remains an important challenge since their synthesis has to follow the principles of green chemistry implying the replacement of conventional metal-based catalysts with the metal-free ones. Biomass waste reutilization, as highly desired in the environmental engineering, can be used for the production of carbon material – biochar (pyrochar and hydrochar), serving as a green catalyst for persulfate-mediated oxidation of CECs. In this study, one series of non-metal-doped pyrochar-based catalysts was prepared using a facile one-pot green strategy with urea and boric acid mixed with pinewood sawdust. The obtained single- and double-doped (N, (B)-) samples of pyrochar were used to activate peroxydisulfate (PDS) for the removal of 25 CECs from the water solution model mixture (30 µg/l concentration of each compound) – 15 pesticides and 10 pharmaceutically active compounds (PhACs). Compared with the pristine pyrochar, the catalytic activity of all doped samples was significantly higher, resulted from the enhanced adsorption capacity for all tested CECs. The obtained B-doped catalyst exhibited excellent capability to boost PDS activation for almost 100% removal of 12 pesticides and 9 PhACs within 15 min. The introduced boron species, acting as Lewis acid sites, enhanced the surface affinity towards PDS and modulated the electronic structure of carbon matrix resulting in an increased electron transfer rate. More importantly, the high stability of boron sites enabled a superior recyclability of this catalyst for up to four cycles making it a promising candidate for practical applications in the CECs removal from wastewater.

Keywords: persulfate-based oxidation, pyrochar, non-metal-doped carbocatalysts, CECs

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Microbiological assessment of water reservoirs in Kyiv Region that have suffered as a result of Russian aggression

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Abstract

Russia's continuous military aggression against Ukraine has been going on for over ten years. The military actions have a crushing effect, because of exposure to toxic compounds of organic origin, which leads not only to a change in the natural state of water bodies, but also to a negative impact on aquaculture. Chemicals derived from old and new ammunition that are known to negatively impact the health of various species of fish, reptiles, birds, and mammals. Therefore, the topic of this research was to assess the state of water bodies affected by military aggression based on the microbiological indicators. So, to solve this problem, the quantitative levels of the most important ecological and trophic groups of microorganisms are determined as potential signal factors in determining the pollution of water bodies by toxic substances and the sanitary and bacteriological state of water bodies and to investigate the ability of microorganisms to destroy nitroaromatic substances that are part of explosives on the territory of Ukraine. Sanitary and microbiological pollution is extremely dangerous not only for aquatic organisms, but also for humans, therefore, standardized methods of counting microorganisms by the bacteriological method (according to ISO 8199) were used to assess the infectious safety of water.

We conducted a microbiological study of the water and bottom sediments of Lake Chorne, v. Petrushky (50.41293, 30.15799), which was damaged by artillery shells and cruise missiles, and Lake, v. Kalynivka (50.2396, 30.23202), which was contaminated with oil products because of a cruise missile explosion at an oil depot in the Kyiv region. The data obtained during the study indicate that only water samples from the lake in the Kalynivka region are contaminated with oil and oil products, and we isolated many hydrocarbon-oxidizing microorganisms (3.99 ± 0.05 CFU/g, lg). On the other hand we did not detect these microorganisms in other samples studied. Effect of toxic explosives of benzene nature on the viability of the studied groups of microorganisms was not detected. It was established that no microorganisms that absorb 2-dinitrotoluene were detected in water samples from the Kalyniv district, and in water samples from Lake Chorne their number was 1.6 ± 0.01 CFU/g, lg. In samples of bottom sediments of Lake Chorne, an increased number of staphylococci (3.63 ± 0.06 CFU/g, lg), coliform bacteria (3.87 ± 0.04 CFU/g, lg) and micromycetes (2.02 ± 0.02 CFU/g, lg) was detected, compared to samples of bottom sediments of the Kalynivka region. Determining the trophic index, it was found that the samples from Chorne Lake was the most polluted with organic matter.

It can be concluded that the data obtained during the study of Lake Chornoe on the sanitary indicator groups of microorganisms indicate intensive processes of pollution by 2-nitrotoluene, domestic wastewater and decay components. Microbiological monitoring of water samples from the lake in the Kalynivka region indicates its contamination by oil and oil products.

Keywords: *ammunition chemicals, water bodies, lake microorganisms, sediment, 2-nitrotoluene*

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Assessment of Freshwater Pollution in Ukraine: Impacts and Prospects for Ecological Restoration

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Abstract

The study of damaged aquatic ecosystems is of critical importance, given the fundamental role of water in sustaining life. One of the most pressing environmental challenges remains the pollution of water resources caused by anthropogenic impacts and military activities. The ecological and sanitary classification of water bodies revealed a range of water quality from "clean" (moderately clean) to "polluted" (conditionally polluted), corresponding to the β -oligosaprobic to λ -mesosaprobic zones. Water was classified as "conditionally polluted" during the summer months, characterised by elevated temperatures and visible algal blooms. The most polluted water bodies were identified in the Kherson and Kyiv regions compared to Zaporizhzhia, Odesa, Mykolaiv, and Chernihiv regions. The results indicate a significant increase in pollution levels, with heterotroph counts exceeding 16,000 thousand CFU/mL, compared to previous levels of 4–10 thousand CFU/mL. A comprehensive approach is urgently required to address the challenges facing Ukrainian water bodies. This should include cessation of military activities, water body remediation, habitat restoration, introduction of key species, and reinforcement of environmental legislation. This research was conducted under the project "Creating a Strategy for Assessing and Restoring War-affected Aquatic Ecosystems" (RestoAqua, No. G6085) with support from the NATO "Science for Peace and Security" program. The project was coordinated by the Nature Research Centre (Lithuania) in partnership with the D.K. Zabolotny Institute of Microbiology and Virology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine and the Institute of Fisheries of the National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine.

Keywords: aquatic ecosystems, ecological state, water quality, pollution

Introduction of microbial concentrates as the basis of biotechnology for accelerated damage recovery due to hostilities in water bodies

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Abstract

The full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation into Ukraine has caused an unprecedented impact on the environment. The war brought in water types and concentrations of pollutants that had not been detected before. Accordingly, the level of their negative impact on water bodies, has increased and expanded and it requires immediate in-depth study to develop effective measures to eliminate it.

The main sources of pollution of water bodies during hostilities are the direct ingress of explosives and rocket fuel into water bodies. This leads to long-term contamination with several toxic substances, including explosive residues (TNT, hexogen, etc.) and their metabolites, as well as with petroleum products, which together cause long-term pollution, often very toxic and not subject to natural biodestruction.

Therefore, **the topic of** this study was the creation of effective microbiological concentrates of biodestructors of various xenobiotics for their introduction into water bodies damaged by military aggression, to further develop effective biotechnologies for their accelerated recovery.

From the zones contaminated with xenobiotics, we isolated, identified and selected the most effective strains of microorganisms - destroyers of petroleum products, organochlorine compounds and explosives DNT (dinitrotoluene), RDX (hexogen). These microorganisms were deposited in the State Depository of Industrial Microorganisms of Ukraine under the following names: *Dietzia maris* IMB B-7350, *Bacillus subtilis* IMB B-7349, *Rhodococcus erythropolis* IMB B-7351, *Pseudomonas aureofaciens* IMB B-7558.

We conducted model studies using concentrates of various compositions of these strains by introducing it into water contaminated with explosives DNT (dinitrotoluene), RDX (hexogen). The studies were carried out in laboratory conditions with the maintenance of optimal temperature for the development of microorganisms and additional aeration. It was found that the degree of DNT destruction after 20 days was 78-81%, and after 45 days it reached 93%. At the same time, RDX was less susceptible to destruction; its indicators of degradation reached 25% after 20 days and 42% after 45 days. In the control group (without introduced bacterial concentrates), destruction by native microflora was 4% for DNT on day 20 and 6% for 45 days, while RDX destruction was absent.

Therefore, it was established that it was expedient to introduce the studied microbial composition to significantly accelerate the processes of cleaning water bodies contaminated with explosives, and to develop effective remediation biotechnologies on their basis.

Keywords: microbial biotechnology, water bodies recovery, a hostilities

Financing

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Behavior of antifouling paint particles in artificial seawater

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Abstract

Micro/nanoplastics have become global environmental pollution issues due to possible ingestion by marine organisms. We have reported that antifouling paint particles (APP) float on the seawater surface of Osaka Bay. APP contain high concentration of biocides such as copper and organic compounds to damage aquatic species. In this study, we aimed to clarify the behavior of APP generated from commercially available ship antifouling paints into artificial seawater (ASW) through laboratory experiments.

Two self-polishing paints (hydrolysis type and hydration type) containing copper were used. An acrylic plate with painted surface (2 × 2 cm) was immersed in ASW stirred and the ASW was changed every day until less APP produced. The paint surface after drying was physically damaged by UV irradiation, sanding, and beating. The treated paint plates were immersed in stirring ASW for 3 days, and the copper-containing APP (>100 μm) produced in ASW was counted using micro-Xray Fluorescence. APP was produced from all painted plates, and the number of APP produced was significantly higher in the sanding and beating treatments. Next, a thin paint sheet made by applying the commercial paint on a cooking sheet was cut, frozen, and crushed to make APP with two particle size (>500 and 125-500 μm). The APP after soaking in water was administered at the water surface or from the 10 cm above the water surface of ASW (0.4 L, water column height 20 cm) in a graduated cylinder, and the behavior of the APP was recorded with a video camera. All the APP (>125 μm) sank, and no APP was observed floating in the water. The settling velocity of hydration APP was low regardless of particle size and administration method. On the other hand, the one of hydrolysis APP with larger size was 5 to 6 times higher than that of smaller APP regardless of administration method.

The laboratory experiments suggest that APP could be produced in seawater when the paint surface is physically damaged by anchor chains, etc. It was also shown that APP with larger particle size (>125 μm) produced in seawater would sink. It is needed to develop methodology to clarify the behavior of smaller APP (<125 μm) in seawater.

Keywords: APP, copper, hydration, hydrolysis, self-polishing

Assessing the Role of Regulation in Advancing Solid Waste Management: A Literature Review

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Abstract

Solid Waste Management (SWM) is a critical component of sustainable development, with direct impacts in environmental quality and resource economy. In the past few decades regulation has emerged as an essential element in advancing SWM practices, transforming systems from linear production models towards circular ones. This literature review evaluates the role of regulatory frameworks in SWM, with special emphasis not only on their success but also on their constraints. The study investigates the development of regulatory instruments involving Market-based incentives and Command – Control schemes. Case studies from EU and non-EU countries -presented in this paper- demonstrate how high circularity rates and waste prevention can be accomplished through well-designed frameworks. The study concludes by specifying policy gaps and suggestions for a robust regulatory scheme in support of a circular and sustainable future.

Keywords: *solid waste management, regulation, circular economy.*

Performance assessment and data analysis of low-cost air quality sensors within the framework of the LIFE City TRAQ project

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Abstract

Air quality is among the most significant environmental factors, contributing to an estimated 7 million premature deaths annually, as reported by the World Health Organization (WHO). Monitoring and improving air quality is essential to mitigate the effects of air pollution, which can lead to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, environmental degradation, and climate change.

The LIFE CityTRAQ project is implemented on behalf of the European Commission under the LIFE program, led by VMM (Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij) – Flanders Environment Agency. The CityTRAQ project addresses air quality challenges in Flanders by integrating all relevant information through implementing new measurements and air quality modeling tools. The tools developed within the project enable policymakers to identify air quality hotspots, assess the impact of specific measures, and support the adoption of optimized local air quality plans. City partners explore these features through case studies involving traffic flow and emissions measures, ultimately developing generic approaches for use by other EU cities. Suggested methodologies are being tested and replicated in Croatia, specifically in the City of Zagreb.

As part of this project, the Croatian Meteorological and Hydrological Service (DHMZ) procured eight sensor boxes to assess their performance and potential for supplementing existing air quality monitoring networks. Sensor boxes are all equipped with particulate matter, nitrogen oxides, and ozone sensors. To evaluate the reliability of these sensors, they were co-located at the Zagreb-1 air quality urban traffic monitoring station in Zagreb. This setup allowed parallel measurements using both the sensor boxes and the automatic reference-grade analyzers at the station. The data collected over a one-month monitoring period were analyzed in the context of varying meteorological conditions, including temperature and humidity fluctuations. The performance of the sensors was evaluated both in comparison to each other and against the reference instruments.

The findings provided a comprehensive evaluation of the accuracy and reliability of the sensors, highlighting their performance strengths and limitations under diverse real-world conditions. This study highlights the potential for integrating sensor-based monitoring into broader air quality networks while addressing the challenges of ensuring data quality and comparability with established methods. The results contribute to the overall objective of improving urban air quality management through innovative technological solutions.

Keywords: LIFE City TRAQ, low-cost sensors, air quality, Zagreb, DHMZ

Energy and Environment

Increasing the Water Production of Solar Stills through Forced Convection and External Condensation

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Abstract

A laboratory study was conducted where a solar still was modified to provide an external airflow entering from one side of the still just above the saline water surface, thereby increasing the evaporation and heat transfer rate inside the still through forced convection. The evaporated vapour was picked up by the airstream and the heated and humidified air was led out of the still on the opposite side to the entrance. The water production in the original (passive) and modified (active) still was measured at different water temperatures, salinity, and duration. With a constant water temperature of 60°C, the passive still managed to produce about 0.2 kg/m²,h of freshwater during the first hour. The production thereafter declined to about 0.1 kg/m²,h due to the gradual heating of the top cover. Under the same circumstances, the active solar still was instead able to continuously produce 5.2 kg/m²,h during all hours of the experiment. The productivity were most significantly influenced by the water temperature: by lowering the water temperature to 40°C, the passive solar still produced <0.06 kg/ m²,h of freshwater and the active still maintained a production of 1.7 kg/h,m².

Keywords: *solar desalination, accessible freshwater, water management, rural development*

1. INTRODUCTION

Freshwater scarcity is a growing concern in warm and arid parts of the world, especially in coastal regions. The United Nations predict that half of the global population will live in water scarce regions within the coming year. The usual method to alleviate the lack of water is seawater desalination, which is an energy intensive process, often powered by fossil fuel. The traditional solar powered stills are known for being low-tech and low-cost desalination solutions, with free solar thermal energy as fuel source. However, they are also known for their low productivity, approximately 3 kg/m² per day, which makes them unsuitable for any large-scale water production.

Agriculture consumes roughly 70% of the world's available freshwater for crop irrigation. This vast amount of irrigation water is distributed on less than 20% of the cultivated fields and is responsible for producing 40% of the world's food supply [1]. In general, irrigation can increase crop yield on a field by up to three times, especially in semiarid and arid regions that are prone to draughts. This is why irrigation must be further expanded to support food production in arid and semi-arid regions, such as sub-Saharan Africa, where about 24% of the population lives with severe hunger and undernourishment

[3]. In the same region less than 5% of the cultivated fields are irrigated [2]. By expanding the irrigation to 10% of the fields, the food production could sustain the whole population. The main issue then becomes how to allocate freshwater resources to irrigation in an already water stressed land.

The Condensation Irrigation (CI) technology combines solar distillation and subsurface irrigation, to convert saline or mildly polluted water into safe irrigation water in regions experiencing periodical water shortages. There have been several studies performed on CI in the recent decades that show that CI has the capacity to provide a low-tech and cost-effective alternative for small-scale, water-efficient irrigation [4-13]

In the CI system, solar thermal energy is used to evaporate saline or otherwise polluted water in basins or canals covered with a transparent cover. The rising vapour heats and humidifies the ambient air flowing above the water surface, and the resulting warm, humid air is pumped into an underground pipe system where the airflow cools and the vapour precipitates as freshwater.

When drainage pipes are used in the pipe system, condensed water and some humid air leave the pipes through the perforations and thereby irrigate and aerate the surrounding soil. By using non-perforated pipes, the condensed water from the pipes can be collected at the pipe endings and used for drinking or other purposes. The principle of the CI system is shown in Figure 1. As shown there, saline or non-potable water is heated inside solar stills or covered irrigation canals. The produced vapour heats and humidifies an airflow above the water surface, and the warm, humid air is then pumped into buried drainage pipes, where the air cools and vapour precipitates as fresh irrigation or drinking water.

Figure 1. Outline of a Condensation Irrigation (CI) system using *Inkscape 1.3*.

The irrigation yield in a CI system has previously been tested in both laboratory and fields tests at Luleå University of Technology (LTU), Sweden, and Chamran University (SCU), Iran, and the results were presented at the CEMEPE conference 2023 [13]. In both tests, the warm, humid airflow was supplied using electrical heaters with thermostats, to provide stable and predictable airflow properties into the pipe. This paper presents results from a laboratory study where a conventional passive still was modified with an external airflow, such as in the CI system, and the resulting evaporation rates were observed and compared for the passive, and active still for varying temperatures, salinities, and velocities [14]. The results serve as a foundation for understanding how to construct and dimension CI systems in the field.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental Setup

The experimental still was constructed using a plastic box with internal dimensions of 36 x 55.5 cm, and XPS boards were used for insulation (Figure 2). An acrylic sheet cover served as the condensation surface, and a spiral duct was used for the inlet air. The duct was 2 meters long with a diameter of 10 cm. An axial fan with a maximum airflow rate of 187 m³/h was used to create the airflow in the active still. Transitions between the duct, fan, and box were made using a 3D printer, and plugs to seal the inlet and outlet air holes were also 3D printed from TPU. These plugs allowed the model to function as both an passive and active distiller (Figure 3).

Two heating elements were used as the heat source and connected in series for a total power of 1000 W. These heating elements were clamped between two 3 mm thick aluminum plates to create a heating plate. The heating elements were controlled by a thermostat that read the actual water temperature in the distiller and regulated it according to the setpoint. A protection circuit was also connected to monitor the temperature of the heating plate, ensuring that the surrounding materials did not overheat and melt.

An Intab PC-Logger 31000-BT was used to collect data for the water temperature, air temperature inside the distiller, air temperature outside the distiller, wet and dry air temperature at the inlet and outlet of the distiller (for determination of absolute moisture content of the airflow), and the temperature of the heating plate. A humidity meter was also placed inside the distiller during all the experiments. The experimental model was also placed on a scale to measure the amount of water leaving the distiller.

Figure 2. Distiller box with measurements used in the experiments.
The distiller is adapted for a water depth of 6 cm [14].

Figure 3. Laboratory setup for the still. The external pipes are only used when an external airflow is applied above the water surface in the still [14].

2.2 Experiment execution

The experiments were conducted in three separate trials, consisting of different sets of experiments (Table 1). During the first trial, the temperature dependence of the water production was measured in the active and passive still setup, at constant water temperatures. In the second trial, the water production decline over time was investigated in the passive and active stills. Lastly, the influence on salinity was investigated in the active solar still in a third trial.

Table 1. Experiment plan with the parameters listed for each trial

Trial	Active/Passive	Water temperature (°C)	Water level (cm)	Airflow velocity (m/s)	Salinity (%)	Run time (h)
1	Passive	40, 50, 60	6	-	<0.5	3
	Active	40, 50, 60	6	1.26	<0.5	3
2	Passive	60	6	-	<0.5	5
	Active	60	6	1.26	<0.5	4
3	Active	50	6	1.26	0.5, 1.5, 2.5, 3.5	3

During tests with the passive still, the water production rate was measured as the amount of distilled water collected via the collector trough into the outside beaker (Figure 3). In the active still, there was no condensation facility attached to the still, so the evaporation rate was monitored instead, and the added vapour to the airstream was assumed to be completely condensed in an external condenser, such as underground pipes. In the Condensation

Irrigation system, the airflow is able to cool to nearly ambient temperature inside the buried drainage pipes [8], which means that most of the evaporated water from the active still will be condensed as freshwater, but not all. The results of evaporation rates must therefore be seen as the upper limit to the water production rate in the active still.

In the experiments with the active still the airflow was created from the ambient air in the laboratory. On average, the room was at 20°C with a relative humidity of about 50%. The airflow velocity before the diffusor in the inlet pipe was held at 1.26 m/s. All experiments in trials one and three were continued for three hours. The hourly water production rate was then taken as the average over the three hours.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The influence of temperature on the water production rates

In the first trial, the water production rate was measured as a function of water temperature in both the active and passive still variations. Each experiment was carried out for constant water temperatures of 40, 50 and 60°C, for passive and active stills, respectively.

When comparing the results in Figure 4, it is clear that the water production rate is highly temperature- dependent for both passive and active distillation. The difference in water production capacity between the two setups is noteworthy, as the water production rate in the active still is about 28 times that of the passive still. The data in Figure 4 implies that the constructed passive solar still would produce about 1.7 kg/m² of water over a ten-hour day, while the active still could produce as much as 52.4 kg of freshwater per evaporator surface area on the same day.

Figure 4. Water production as a function of constant water temperature for passive and active stills.

For a field equipped with a Condensation Irrigation system, this implies that 1 m² of evaporator surface area is able to supply a 20 m² field with 2.62 mm of daily irrigation, which on average is sufficient for most crops.

3.2 Evaporation decline over time in the passive and active still settings

In a conventional solar still, the efficiency of the water production drops during the day due to the heating of the transparent cover. To investigate how the evaporation rate changes over time in the laboratory still, the evaporation rate was measured in the active and passive settings over four and five hours respectively, at a constant temperature of 60°C (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Variation in water production rate over time at constant water temperature of 60 °C in a passive (left) and active still (right).

The results clearly show that the water production rate in the passive setting still indeed slowed down over time and seemed to reach a steady water production rate of approximately 0.1 kg/m² per hour. In the active still, however, the evaporation rate to the airstream was maintained at around 5.2 kg/m²,h over the experiment duration. The steady evaporation rate in the active still is to be expected, as the water and ambient air temperatures were constant over time, as well as the airflow speed. In an outdoor setting, the solar radiation and ambient air temperature will vary over the day, and the water productivity of the active still will hence also vary accordingly.

3.3 Influence of Water Salinity on Evaporation Rate in the Active Still

To see how the salinity affects the evaporation rate in an active still, salt was increasingly added to the water, and the evaporation rate was measured during three hours at a constant water temperature of 50°C (Figure 6). It is clearly noted that the evaporation rate decreases as a result of increased salinity.

Figure 6. The effect of water salinity on evaporation rate inside an active solar still with a constant water temperature of 50 °C

This is in agreement with other literature, where the water production rate has been shown to decrease with salinity [15-16].

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the main findings from an experimental comparative study on the water production rate of a conventional passive solar still and an active solar still, where ambient air is blown across the saline water surface and carries the evaporated vapour to an external condenser. The results have shown that the forced convection combined with the externally located condenser in the active still increases the water production by 28 times, from 0.17 kg/m²,h in the passive, to 5.24 kg/m²,h in the active still. In a Condensation Irrigation system, the surface area ratio of the still to the subsurface irrigated field is about 1:20, which makes the CI system a possible low-tech and low-cost solution to achieve irrigation on smallholder farms using water from non-potable water sources on the farm.

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Low-grade Waste Heat applied to Farmland in Northern Sweden for Increased Food Productivity

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Abstract

A farm produces large volumes of waste heat in the form of ventilated warm air from barns, stables, greenhouses, and other constructions. In this project, we investigate if it is possible to utilize this heat by directing the exhaust warm air into an underground heating system buried below a crop field in the North of Sweden. The field is thawed by the subsurface heating during the spring, which means that cultivation can be advanced. This has a potential to provide vegetable farmers in Northern Sweden with higher crop yields and also to potentially introduce new crops such as artichokes, asparagus, or grapevines for white wine production, which under normal circumstances have too long growing season to be cultivated in the North.

A field test plant of the heating system was constructed during 2024 at Öjebyn AgroPark, Sweden, where strawberry plants are heated by a warm airflow in underground drainage pipes placed about one pipe diameter below the soil surface. The maturation speed, quantity, and quality of the strawberries in the heated field will be compared to an identical field with no heating during 2025. The heat source is simulated using electrical heaters to be able to control the inlet temperature and heat flux, and the temperature development in the soil along the pipes are monitored continuously. This paper describes the early findings from the field tests and theoretical studies.

Keywords: *low-grade waste heat, farming in cold climate, sustainable food production, natural resources management, circularity in agriculture*

Load-dependent shipping emission factors considering alternative fuels, biofuels and emission control technologies

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Abstract

Shipping is a high-energy-consuming sector and a significant source of climate-related and harmful pollutant emissions. In response to growing environmental concerns, the maritime sector has been subject to stringent regulations aimed at reducing emissions, achieved through the adoption of alternative fuels and emission control technologies. Accurate and diverse emission factors (EFs) are critical for quantifying shipping's contribution to current emission inventories and projecting future trends under various policy scenarios. This study presents advancements in the development of emission factors for ships, incorporating alternative fuels, biofuels and emission control technologies. The methodology integrates statistical analysis of emission data from an extensive literature review with newly acquired on-board emission measurements. To ensure high resolution and applicability across diverse operational conditions, the emission factors are formulated as functions of engine load and categorized by engine type and fuel used. The results provide insights into the emission performance of ships and intend to support the development of robust, up-to-date emission models and inventories, contributing to the broader goal of sustainable maritime transport. This work was conducted in the framework of NAVGREEN project.

Keywords: emission inventories, emission models, alternative fuels, biofuels, emission control technologies

Institutional allocation of regulatory powers in the field of energy waste and water. A comparative perspective

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Abstract

Greece's regulatory landscape in the fields of energy, water, and waste has undergone significant transformations, particularly over the last two decades (in energy) and in the last two years (in waste and water). These reforms have been driven by both internal imperatives—such as improving service delivery, sustainability, economic efficiency—and external pressures, most notably compliance with European Union directives and post-crisis structural adjustment requirements. This paper examines the regulatory architecture in each sector, focusing on institutional powers, legal developments, and implementation challenges. Additionally, it highlights the similarities and differences of the institutional frameworks between sectors to enhance understanding and demonstrate the value of the regulatory architecture to the various stakeholders.

More specifically, the primary regulatory body for the energy sector is the Regulatory Authority for Waste, Energy, and Water (RAAEY), formerly known as the Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE), established under Law 2773/1999. RAE was originally tasked with liberalizing the Greek energy market in compliance with the EU's internal energy market directives.

Recent legal updates, especially Law 5037/2023, redefined RAE's scope, renaming it RAAEY and extending its competencies to include water and waste. In the energy sector, RAAEY retains full regulatory oversight:

- Licensing or Certification for production, transmission, and supply
- Tariff approval and network access rules
- Market surveillance and dispute resolution
- Integration of renewable energy sources (RES) and compliance with the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP)

With the expansion of RAAEY's Mandate in 2023, water regulation was formally assigned to RAAEY. This followed rulings by the Council of State affirming the need for strong public oversight while respecting constitutional protections on access to essential services.

RAAEY's water-related powers include:

- Approval of tariff structures and cost-recovery methodologies
- Supervision of water quality and infrastructure investments
- Monitoring of compliance with EU directives (notably the Water Framework Directive 2000/60/EC).

Also, after 2023, the regulation of waste management is shared between RAAEY, the Hellenic Recycling Agency (EOAN), and municipal authorities. RAAEY is primarily responsible for infrastructure and investment planning, the certification and the operational

adequacy of the municipal solid waste operators and the minimum level of quality of services they offer, while EOAN oversees Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes.

The National Waste Management Plan (2020–2030) sets ambitious targets for waste reduction, recycling, and landfill diversion, in line with EU directives (e.g., Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC).

In conclusion, Greece's regulatory powers in energy, water, and waste are now centralized under RAAEY, reflecting a modern governance model aligned with European norms. While legal frameworks are robust and largely compliant with EU directives, implementation remains uneven. Key challenges include ensuring regulatory independence, addressing public resistance, and accelerating the green transition.

Future reforms should focus on capacity building, digital transformation of services, and participatory governance to enhance trust and performance in these critical sectors.

Keywords: regulation, regulatory framework, energy, water, waste

Possible enhanced levels of natural radioactivity originating from NORM at the construction works at the site of new coal storage dome of a Thermal Power Plant

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Abstract

This paper deals with the technological need to gather all possible data (small meta-analysis) of the performed monitoring of a Thermal Power Plant (TPP) site in Croatia and its wastes, underground waters and biota regarding NORM residuals. The possible occupational impact to workers performing construction of a new coal Storage Dome in the TPP is also assessed.

All other environmental not radioactive stressors present at the new construction site and originating from regular TPP operation (including regulated wastes) were noticed, sampled and measured but are NOT in the scope of the dosimetric measurements or/and laboratory gamma spectrometric analysis of collected soil and water samples across the site. This was the basis for the present field work. Ambient equivalent dose rate trace measurements at 1 m height from the ground (originating from NORM) were performed. Isodose plane was calculated so that local background radiation of the whole site (LBG) was established. Samples for laboratory gamma spectrometric analysis were sampled at the site according to the sampling protocol given by IMROH. Additionally, a magnetometer contour map (matrix of magnetic field values (nT/m) across the future coal storage dome construction site was created and radar depth of soil measurements were performed to support the statements that no production wastes were incorporated in the soil.

Keywords: *brownfield, NORM residues, remediation, GIS, magnetometer contour*

Manufacturing and Theoretical Processes of BIT: Fabrication Devices Processes

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Abstract

This paper presents in detail the processes used to fabricate the emitter, base, and collector to achieve the desired results. It shows how the bipolar transistors were fabricated step-by-step as presented in Figure (1). The device' fabrication runs were completed and tested. After that, the study was demonstrated the fabrication process. As summary, an Agilent HP4155C Semiconductor parameter analyzer and IV characterization system (Optronics Lab OL 770-LED) were used to test most of the device characteristics. As the testing results from each fabrication run were examined, changes in the process were made to improve the results.

Keywords: *fabrication, process, manufacturing, BJT, devices*

Contaminants of emerging concern in the water of the Danube-Tisa-Danube canal, Vojvodina Province, Serbia

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Abstract

The Danube-Tisa-Danube (DTD) canal, in Vojvodina Province, Serbia, is a complex and vulnerable water body where human activities and natural dynamics have always been interconnected. Pollutants including contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) that can reach the canal directly from households, agricultural discharges, and various industrial sectors, pose one of the major threats to this hydro system. Accordingly, one part of this Hydro system (the Great Bačka Canal) is marked as a European environmental hotspot. Given that water from the DTD Hydro system is used for irrigation of agricultural soil in the Vojvodina Province, which is a region of intensive agro-food production in Serbia, revealing the chemical status of the canal is very important. Thus, this work aspires to showcase how the presence of CECs in Hydro-system DTD could be investigated, with the aim of the creation of the CECs list that can serve as a “watch” list for future surveillance of these contaminants in this water body. In this context, water samples were collected from 40 sampling points in three seasons, to investigate the occurrence and distribution of CECs present in the DTD canal. To ensure multicomponent extraction of CECs present in surface water samples, the sample prep protocol is based on solid phase extraction using “in-house” prepared multilayer columns. Liquid chromatography with high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) was used for sample extract analysis. Data obtained using the suspect screening approach was processed by Compound Discoverer software to identify the most frequently occurring CECs in the analyzed water samples. Based on the frequency of occurrence of the identified compounds and the best matching scores from software-linked database, 25 compounds (8 pesticides, 1 industrial chemical, 2 sweetener, and 14 pharmaceuticals) were selected for quantification using reference standards. Although this is a specific case study, the obtained results will be compared with those available in the literature and could have widespread implications at the global level, providing useful data to better address existing gaps in knowledge about the occurrence, sources, distribution, and fate of CEC in water bodies.

Keywords: *surface water, CECs, DTD canal, screening and target analysis*

Acknowledgement

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Techno-economic assessment of MEA absorption and membrane separation technologies for carbon capture in maritime industry

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Abstract

Due to the increase in global trade and the demand for maritime carriage goods, the sector's carbon footprint, primarily because of CO₂, is poised to potentially surge by 50% to 250% by the year 2050 if proactive measures are not taken. Within the framework of the research project for a sustainable maritime industry "NAVGREEN", two carbon capture units are designed in Aspen Plus V14 software: the first utilizes MEA absorption to capture 1 t CO₂/h, while the second uses membranes (previously created in Aspen Custom Modeler software) of varying technologies for a capture rate of 1.07 t CO₂/h. Furthermore, the operational expenditure (OPEX) of each unit is calculated and compared: for the MEA absorption unit, OPEX equals 1.56 M€/y, with solvent make-up and steam cost being the main cost factors (73 % and 13.5 % respectively). OPEX of the membrane unit is equal to 1.26 M€/y and its main cost factors are equipment maintenance (59.5 %) and electricity demand (34 %).

Keywords: carbon capture, maritime industry, techno-economic analysis, membranes, chemical absorption

1. INTRODUCTION

Global trade is expanding with rigorous rates and its dependency on the maritime sector leads to increased greenhouse gas emissions, intensifying the phenomenon of climate change [1]: in 2018, the emissions equaled approximately 3% of the total anthropogenic emissions in the globe [2,3]. Due to this rising concern, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) has set goals in mitigating the industry's carbon footprint by 20% at 2030 and 70% at minimum, while simultaneously aspiring to accomplish net-zero emissions by 2050 [4].

There are several strategies available for reducing the carbon intensity of the shipping industry, such as utilizing alternative fuels (LNG, methanol, hydrogen, ammonia etc), using power and propulsions systems that rely solely on electricity, capturing the emitted greenhouse houses (with emphasis placed on CO₂ capture) improving the sustainability of ports in regards to energy and environmental performance ("green port framework") and improving the ship energy efficiency. CO₂ capture specifically is already being utilized in many land industries (such as cement, steel and power plants) and is actualized through 3 main frameworks: capturing CO₂ from flue gases after combustion has taken place (post-combustion), processing the fuel before combustion and capturing the relevant emissions (pre-combustion) and using an enriched oxygen instead of air in the fuel combustion, which enhances future separation of CO₂ from oxygen (oxy-fuel combustion) [5]. From all the available post-combustion Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies, chemical absorption through specific amine solutions e.g. monoethanolamine (MEA) is characterized

by the most technological maturity in land applications, while membrane separation technology still requires more studies before its implementation [4].

There have been numerous studies that assess the feasibility of a CCS system aboard a seafaring vessel, however, to our knowledge, comparative data regarding the financial profile between CCS units on ships that utilize chemical absorption and membrane separation is lacking. Consequently, the purpose of this study is the design and subsequent techno-economic comparison of an MEA CCS and a membrane separation CCS unit for possible use in the maritime industry.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology of this study entails the unit design of two carbon capture (CC) processes: one which chemically captures CO₂ from ship flue gases with an aqueous monoethanolamine (MEA) solution and one which separates carbon dioxide from the remaining gases with membranes. Both processes are designed and have their heating, cooling heating and electricity needs derived through Aspen Plus V14 software. Subsequently, mechanical equipment is sized with Aspen Plus V14 and cost-estimated by empirical equations from available literature [6]. The occurring units are then compared financially by calculating their respective operational expenditure (OPEX). The flue gases enter the capture units at 28 °C and 1.07 bar and their composition is presented in Table 1 [7]. It is assumed that they are the result of a ship engine that runs on Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) and have been pre-treated to subtract the quantities of trace chemical compounds.

Table 1. Composition of the ship flue gases

Chemical Compound	Molar fraction
CO ₂	0.04
N ₂	0.7304
H ₂ O	0.1295
O ₂	0.0911
Ar	0.0086
SO ₂	0.0005

2.1 MEA Solution CC Unit

The process flowchart of the MEA CC unit is shown in Figure 1. Thermodynamic properties are derived from the Electrolyte Non-Two Random Liquid- Redlich Kwong equation of state [8,9]. Chemical reactions are based on an existing paradigm of AspenTech [9].

Figure 1. Flowchart of CO₂ capture process with MEA solution in Aspen Plus V14.

The MEA solution, which is in 40 °C temperature and pressure of 1 bar (LEANIN stream), along with the engine flue gases (FLUEGAS stream) enter the absorption column (ABSORBER block), where 77% of the available CO₂ is captured. The remaining flue gases (GASOUT stream) are released to the atmosphere, while the rich amine stream which contains the captured CO₂ (RICHIN stream) is pumped (PUMP block) from the bottom of the absorption and heated at 95 °C in the process heat exchanger (HX block), before inserting into the stripping column (STRIPPER block). Its top stream (H₂O-CO₂ stream) contains nearly pure gaseous CO₂, while the lean amine solution that exits the column from the bottom (LEANOUT stream) is cooled at 40 °C in 2 stages: at the process heat exchanger and then at the process cooler (COOLER block), is replenished in MEA (MEAMU stream) and water (WATERMU stream) (this is achieved through the nominal MU block). Finally, a small percentage of the resulting lean amine stream is purged (PURGE stream), while the remaining solution is recycled back into the absorber column (the DUMMIX block is nominal and utilized to equate the simulation NLEANIN and LEANIN streams).

2.2 Membrane Separation CC Unit

The process flowchart of the complete membrane CC unit is based on the proposition of Alshehri et al. [10] and presented in Figure 2. Due to the absence of a membrane sub-unit in Aspen Plus V14, an existing membrane model in Aspen Custom Modeler software is carefully altered and exported to Aspen Plus simulation environment. Assuming ideal conditions, the necessary thermodynamic properties are derived through IDEAL equation of state.

Figure 2. Flowchart of CO₂ capture process with membranes in Aspen Plus V14.

The entering gases in this unit are similar to those of the MEA process, except that they contain only CO₂ and N₂. After their entrance, the flue gases (FLUEGAS stream) are compressed to 9.5 bar (COMP1 block), mixed with the retentate from the second membrane (RET2 stream), cooled to 28 °C through a cooler (HX1 block) and inserted into the first membrane module (MEMB 1 block), which is assumed to simulate a hollow fiber membrane, with 8600 m² area, 15 μm fiber thickness and permeability of 7500 and 222 barrer for CO₂ and N₂ respectively. The retentate stream of the first membrane is released to the atmosphere (WASTEGAS stream), while its permeate stream (PERM1 stream), where 90% of the entering CO₂ is captured, exits at 1 bar pressure and follows similar iterative steps like the flue gases stream: is compressed at 9.5 bar (COMP2 block), mixed with the retentate stream of the third membrane (RET3 stream) and the occurring mixture is cooled to 28 °C (HX2 block), before entering the second membrane (MEMB2 block), which is a hollow fiber membrane as well, with 4800 m² area and permeabilities of 3000 and 30 barrer for CO₂ and N₂ respectively. The permeate stream of the second membrane (PERM2 stream) similarly compressed to 9.5 bar (COMP3 block), cooled to 28 °C (HX3 block) and inserted into the third membrane module (MEMB3 block), which is identical to the second membrane, except for its total area (300 m²). The occurring permeate (PERM3 stream) contains approximately pure gaseous CO₂.

2.3 Techno-economic assessment and comparison

In order to assess and compare the financial feasibility of the above units, for each one, the necessary mechanical equipment is sized (through Aspen Plus V14), priced (based on empirical equations from literature) and then operational expenditure (OPEX) is calculated. The necessary components of the OPEX in each unit are calculated based on the cost factors presented in Table 2.

Table 2. OPEX cost factors

Cost factor	Cost	Reference
MEA solution	1450 €/t	11
Natural gas (steam)	0.0085 €/MJ _{LHV}	12
Wastewater treatment	0.038 €/m ³	6
Electricity	51.1 €/MWh	13
Chilled water	0.18 €/m ³	6
Membrane surface	37 €/m ²	14

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Unit Capture Rate

Through the utilization of amine chemical absorption technology, 1 t CO₂/h is captured, at 99% wt purity, while in the membrane separation unit captured CO₂ equals to 1.07 t CO₂/h, 99% wt pure. Compared to the proposed MEA unit, the membrane unit is characterized by a higher % capture rate (90% vs 77%) and slightly higher CO₂ quantity at identical purity (1.07 t/h vs 1 t/h).

3.2 Operational Expenditure Evaluation and Comparison

The OPEX of each unit, along with the contribution of each cost factor, is shown in Figure 3. The operational expenditure of the MEA unit amounts to 1.56 M€/y, with significant contribution from the MEA solution make-up (73%), the required steam (14.5%) and equipment maintenance (12.5%), while the membrane unit is characterized by an OPEX of 1.26 M€/y, with the main cost contributors being equipment maintenance (59.5%) and electricity (34%).

Figure 3. Contribution of cost factors and total operational expenditure of each CC unit.

Consequently, it can be ascertained that the membrane separation unit is more cost-efficient in comparison to the MEA unit. Despite the technological immaturity compared to MEA CC and while it is necessary for more variables and parameters to be included (e.g. flue gases with water, oxygen and trace chemicals, possible non-ideal phenomena that occur in membranes such as plasticization etc.) for more complete simulations and future field implementation, this cost efficiency highlights the prospect for more detailed research on membrane separation technology for use in the maritime sector.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Due to the increase of trade in the modern world, the carbon intensity of the maritime sector is expected to increase in the following. Measures to mitigate its greenhouse gas emissions are necessary and with CO₂ being a chemical compound that greatly impacts climate change, efforts to capture and store it are needed. With this goal in mind, two carbon capture units, one which utilizes chemical absorption technology with an aqueous MEA solution and one which uses membrane separation, are simulated and financially evaluated through calculation of individual operational expenditure (OPEX). The MEA unit captures 1 t CO₂/h at 99% wt purity, with OPEX reaching 1.56 M€/y, while the membrane unit 1.07 t

CO₂/h at 99% wt purity, with OPEX reaching 1.26 M€/y. Thus, it can be concluded that while there are certain improvements that need to take place in order to be implemented on ships, membrane separation technology is a promising prospect for carbon capture in the shipping industry.

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Development of a green hydrogen production system to cover water and electricity needs on Kythera

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Abstract

This research analyzes the exploration of green hydrogen production systems to cover water and electricity demands on Kythera, which is interconnected with the mainland Greece. The water supply of Kythera is provided through available water springs and boreholes through an old distribution network. Green hydrogen production is achieved through proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyte. Two scenarios of green hydrogen production are being evaluated. The 1st scenario examines the installation of 5 wind turbines (11.5 MW) and 1 PEM fuel cell (66.5% for electricity demand covered by wind turbines, 33.5% for electricity demand covered by PEM fuel cell, 84.98% coverage of water supply). The 2nd scenario studies the combination of 4 wind turbines and 1 photovoltaic (PV) park (11.5 MW in total) and 1 PEM fuel cell (72.0% for electricity demand covered by wind turbines & PV park, 28% for electricity demand covered by PEM fuel cell, 85.67% coverage of water supply). This study highlights the potential of green hydrogen as a means of storing water and electricity, sustainably meeting both the water and electricity demand of the island.

Keywords: green hydrogen production, electrolysis, PEM fuel cell, wind turbines, Photovoltaic Park, water demand, electricity demand

Environmental Impact Assessment and Risk Analysis

Plastic contamination and water quality assessment of urban wastewaters

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Abstract

The peroxidase toxicity assay (Perotox) represents a quick and inexpensive methodology to screen for the water quality of municipal wastewaters. This assay was initially proposed as an alternative to fish toxicity test and was revisited for municipal wastewaters. The purpose of this study was to assess wastewaters from 7 cities using the following 5 treatment processes: aerated lagoons, secondary aerated sludge, biofiltration, trickling filter and primary treatment. In parallel, the presence of plastic nanoparticles and plastic materials in the organic matrix were determined. The untreated (influent) and treated effluents were fractionated on C18 solid phase cartridges and eluted in ethanol (50 X concentration) before testing with the Peroxtox assay. A DNA protection index was also derived from the recovery of peroxidase (Per) activity in the presence of DNA as an indication of genotoxicity. The data revealed that the wastewaters contained organic matter at the mg/L range, polyaromatic hydrocarbons (Pahs), humic and fluvic acids (HA/FA), polystyrene nanoplastics (PsNPs) and plastic-related materials. Inhibition of the peroxidase reaction was observed in most wastewaters (90%) leading to reduced elimination of toxic reactive species. The addition of DNA during the Per reaction and the effluents prevented inhibitions in nearly 60 % of the effluents suggesting the potential of genotoxic compounds in these effluents. The study also revealed that effluents using biofiltration and aeration processes were generally less harmful towards the Perotox and DNA protection assays. The Perotox assay represents a cost-effective alternative for the rapid and cheap screening for municipal wastewaters quality.

Keywords: *peroxidase, wastewaters, DNA protection, plastics, alternative methods*

Mobility of elements from tailings produced of low-grade, vanadium-bearing titano-magnetite ores

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Abstract

The European Commission (EC) Critical Raw Materials (CRM) Act sets multiple benchmarks for reducing Europe's dependency on several strategic/CRMs mined in third countries. Through the domestic extraction of two CRMs – “vanadium” (V) and “titanium metal” (Ti metal) the first target of the Act (> 10% domestic extraction, for V & Ti) addresses the first target of the Act (> 10% domestic extraction, for V & Ti) is met. On the other hand, mining, processing and metallurgical operations result in the generation of large volumes of wastes, of different types, characteristics and risk, which if improperly managed may cause impacts to environmental receptors and mainly to soil, surface- and ground water.

The present geochemical study investigates the mobilization of potentially harmful elements (PHEs) present in tailings obtained from the treatment of low-grade, V-bearing titano-magnetite ores from the Otanmäki mine, in Finland.

First, chemical and mineralogical analyses of the ores and the tailings are presented and discussed. Then the mobility of PHEs is investigated through a series of standard leaching, involving the EN 12457-2 and the Toxicity Characteristics Leaching Procedure (TCLP) tests as well as pH-dependence tests.

The mobility of Cr, Ni, Zn, Ti and V was assessed. Based on these results and the thresholds set the reliability of each test to determine the potential risk of the tailings is discussed. Finally, potential valorization options for the management of the tailings, by following the principles of circular economy, and the elimination of environmental risk in disposal sites is discussed.

The mine waste under study raises the environmental mobility of some constituents and also gives the chance for the valorization of the waste.

Keywords: *mine tailings, leaching tests, EN 12457-2, pH-dependent tests*

RNA sequencing technology as a new approach to investigate microplastics emerging issue

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Abstract

Next Generation Techniques (NGS) have led to a revolution in the way of doing research, from a hypothesis-based approach to a data-driven approach, allowing new ways to respond more quickly to biological questions that arise still open. Their application to the study of alterations in gene expression represent an extraordinary tool for speeding up the identification of pathological alterations at the molecular level, even before the phenotypic signs appear, and an enhancer the possibility of identifying new potential biomarkers. Environmental and occupational exposures to potentially harmful agents can influence the individual's epigenome. Transcriptome studies combined with data mining techniques, can provide valuable information into molecular events that occur following different exposure conditions. RNA-sequencing technology is a useful tool to identify differentially expressed genes or transcripts associated with a cellular state or to identify genes with similar expression patterns. In recent years, a significant amount of transcriptomic data has been generated and deposited in open-source databases. Public gene expression data are commonly repurposed to address new biological questions by reanalyzing primary data, reducing the costs of experiments, and gaining further insights, given their richness of information on molecular events.

Microplastics are ubiquitous environmental contaminants and their potential health risks have been concerning. Although numerous articles investigating their health effects have been published in recent months, these studies have produced inconclusive results due to the lack of comparability between them and the complex nature of the toxicity data. The present work proposes the use of RNA-sequencing techniques to understand the molecular mechanisms underlying the exposure of microplastics and their combination with organic pollutants in different organisms. The ambitious objective is to create an open-source portal, which displays processed and freely usable transcriptomic data, to facilitate the understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying exposure to microplastics and make them accessible to the scientific community.

Keywords: *transcriptome, RNA-sequencing, differentially expressed genes, microplastics, open-source portal*

Evolution of the Italian Environmental Information Systems: synergies between data sharing systems and research. A case study within the EU Water4All Partnership

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Abstract

Environmental Information Systems (EIS) are essential for global sustainability, leveraging data to monitor environmental changes, assessing risks, and supporting evidence-based policies. Following the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), data sharing enhances decision-making and stakeholder engagement. Research, innovation, and emerging IT approaches drive EIS evolution, promoting API-based systems and improved interoperability. In this context, the Italian EIS, aligned with the European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET) and supported by the EEA, is strengthening data sharing in the water sector to enhance resource management.

Starting from a case study of a platform prototype based on the FROST Server, an implementation of the OGC SensorThings API (STA) data sharing standard, extended with the Water Quality IE data model, this paper explores the impact of the research carried on within the European Partnership Water4All (Water Security for the planet) on the Italian National Environmental Information System, analyzing the role of this international partnership and network as driver for evolution of EIS. In particular, the work focused on integrating ISPRA data into the platform, demonstrating how this solution enhances interoperability across environmental information systems.

Keywords: *water management, API, Shared Environment Information Systems (SEIS), interoperability and data sharing, data driven decision*

1. INTRODUCTION

The accessibility of data and information, in line with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) is essential for building robust, interoperable Environmental Information Systems (EIS). Ensuring such accessibility enables governments, researchers, and organizations to monitor environmental changes, assess risks, and implement evidence-based policies effectively [1].

The Shared Environmental Information System (SEIS) [2] is based on key principles that emphasize:

1. Managing data as close as possible to its source.
2. Collecting data once and sharing it for multiple purposes.
3. Ensuring data is readily available to meet reporting obligations efficiently.

4. Accessible to enable comparisons at the appropriate geographical scale and participation of citizens.
5. Providing full public access to information at national and local levels in relevant languages.
6. Supporting open, standardized, and freely accessible software solutions.

As such, Shared Environmental Information Systems play a crucial role in expanding the knowledge base by integrating diverse information from multiple sources.

However, despite the EU's strategic commitment to promoting knowledge and data sharing [3,4] in the environmental sector, challenges persist due to data fragmentation and the limited availability of relevant information for territorial management and research.

To address these challenges, stakeholders must work towards improving data availability and usability, particularly for high-value environmental data, whose reuse offers significant benefits for society, the environment, and the economy.

Research and innovation, combined with emerging data and IT approaches, can drive the evolution of Environmental Information Systems, fostering the development of next-generation systems based on APIs (Application Programming Interface) and enhanced interoperability [2].

This paper explores the contributions of the Water4All partnership—a Research & Innovation action funded under the Horizon Europe programme—toward advancing this vision. Specifically, it examines the development of a prototype platform for sharing an initial set of water-related datasets [5]. The analysis focuses on the improvements made to the Italian Environmental Information System, facilitated by this initiative. Before delving into the technical details of the prototype, the paper outlines the structure of the Italian system and its connection with the European Environment Agency (EEA), which plays a key role in shaping the European data-sharing framework.

2. ITALIAN ENVIRONMENTAL INFORMATION SYSTEM AND EIONET NETWORK

Since 1988, Italy has operated the National Environmental Information System (SINA) within the Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA). SINA plays a strategic role in the collection, processing, and dissemination of territorial and environmental information. Data is gathered by ISPRA and the National Environmental Protection System (SNPA), leveraging Regional Environmental Information Systems (SIRA), which serve as regional focal points (RFPs) and are managed by the Regional and Provincial Environmental Protection Agencies (ARPA/APPAs) (Figure.1).

The SNPA ensures a minimum and uniform level of environmental protection by promoting consistency in operational practices across its network, providing maps, data, and indicators, and ensuring comprehensive and widespread environmental monitoring. Through this national environmental information network—SINA-SIRA/RFPs, collectively known as SINANET—environmental data and information are collected, processed, and made accessible to support national environmental policies. The data and information provided by ISPRA and SNPA serve as an official reference for environmental management and policy-making in Italy.

The SINA framework follows the MDIAR (Monitoring, Data, Information, Analysis, Reporting) model (Figure 1), which defines the flow of data from national monitoring efforts to European-level reporting. This process is structured as a pyramidal system, where raw monitoring data form the base, while processed reporting and statistical indicators, submitted at the EU level, are at the top.

The complexity of the Italian environmental monitoring network, structured as a federated system (SNPA) in which local authorities (ARPA/APPA) play a pivotal role in data collection and monitoring, necessitates strong national-level coordination by ISPRA and SINA. This coordination is reinforced through the development and implementation of interoperable and shared information systems, in accordance with EU Directives on data sharing [4] and SEIS.

Figure. 1 SINANET model links with EEA-EIONET

ISPRA and SINA, as key actors of environmental data management, are strengthening their network and systems through the National Environmental Information System. Innovative IT technologies and approaches, such as APIs and cloud solutions are implemented, aiming at reaching full interoperability and shared information systems, as well as more flexible and dynamic systems. Under the coordination of AGID (Agenzia Italiana per il Digitale), which is responsible at national level for coordinating and supporting the digitalisation of public administration and the development of SEIS, standards and best practices have been defined to prevent fragmentation.

The SEIS's vision was outlined by the European Commission in 2005 to enhance the sharing and accessibility of environmental information, improve monitoring systems, and modernize and streamline environmental reporting. The European Environment Agency (EEA) is the body responsible for implementing SEIS, with the support of the European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET), which serves as a key component of its strategy.

Aligned with the EEA-EIONET Strategy 2021–2030 [6], addressing climate and environmental challenges requires trusted and actionable knowledge to support informed decision-making, setting priorities, and identifying solutions in line with Europe's policy objectives.

Through Strategic Objective SO3 (*Building Stronger Networks and Partnerships*) and Strategic Objective SO4 (*Maximizing the Potential of Data, Technology, and Digitalization*), the EEA aims to strengthen the network, facilitate knowledge-sharing, and integrate digital innovations. This includes the use of emerging technologies such as Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Earth observation.

A robust knowledge base, built on the latest scientific findings and quality-assured data, is essential for generating evidence-based insights that support policy implementation. This can be achieved by developing stronger and interoperable EIS in accordance with FAIR principles, ensuring that environmental data is effectively shared and utilized across different sectors and governance levels. To date, EEA-EIONET connects circa 400 national institutions from 38 member and cooperating countries and ISPRA, through SINA, is the National Focal Point (NFP) for Italy, responsible for coordinating national reference networks for environmental information. Therefore, by considering inputs by national and European stakeholders, SINA contributes to the development of a cohesive and comprehensive environmental information system, enabling Italy to actively participate in Europe-wide efforts to enhance data sharing, policy implementation, and environmental sustainability. Furthermore, participation in Research and Innovation initiatives represents an added value in pursuing this crucial goal.

3. THE WATER4ALL PLATFORM PROTOTYPE

Through the activities of SINA, ISPRA is a partner in the EU Partnership Water4All – Water Security for the Planet, which ambitious aim is to reshape the future of research and innovation in the water sector. The initiative adopts a holistic approach, covering the entire water resource management chain. Among its diverse activities, the program also seeks to promote Open Science and Open Data, emphasizing systematic and unrestricted access to scientific data and processing tools.

To this purpose, it fosters the widespread sharing of best practices in open science, enhancing the impact of research outcomes in the water sector and maximizing their value for real-world applications and water management. Furthermore, Water4All strives to facilitate collaboration, enhance the replicability and scalability of successful water management initiatives, and encourage stakeholder engagement and accountability. Ultimately, the program serves as a powerful instrument for informing policymakers, raising public awareness, and influencing policies and regulations on water management.

Recognizing the importance of data accessibility, the Water4All Partnership has adopted a digitalized, Open Data-driven approach for the European water sector. As part of a broader European effort, it has compiled experiences on Data Management and Data Sharing to foster a wider European Dialogue [7].

Water4All aims to elevate water-related knowledge to the EU level. Traditionally, individual countries have relied on local observations and measurements, often conducted at the municipal or regional level and stored in proprietary formats. Water4All seeks to leverage these fragmented datasets, integrating them into a cohesive framework that operates at national and supranational levels.

To achieve this, it is crucial to adopt a holistic perspective, ensuring that all local measurements are collected and interpreted in a standardized manner. To this end, a dedicated task has been established to enhance water-related data sharing through the development of interoperable interfaces for data discovery and access. The platform prototype developed within this framework represents a significant technical innovation, marking a key step toward a more integrated and accessible European water data ecosystem.

The platform is based on the FROST Server [8], an open-source implementation of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) SensorThings API (STA) [9], for managing water related data. The SensorThings API is an Open Geospatial Consortium standard for managing and exchanging Internet of Things (IoT) data. It provides a consistent, RESTful interface to describe, query, and update information about sensors, the data they measure, and the phenomena they observe. By conforming to this open standard, the FROST Server ensures consistent data modeling, storage, and access across diverse platforms and applications, thereby simplifying integration and promoting a shared understanding of sensor data. These characteristics make it well-suited for environmental monitoring systems.

The STA data model defines a set of entities (*Things*, *Locations*, *Historical Locations*, *Sensors*, *Observed Properties*, *Datastreams*, *Observations* and *Features of Interest*) with well-defined relationships with each other. The *Thing* is a general concept describing an object (physical or virtual) that has sensing capabilities. The *Location* provides information about the geographical position (coordinates) of a *Thing*. *Things* can move in different *Locations*, so the *Historical Location* provides a record associating a *Thing* with a *Location* at a given time. The *Observed Property* specifies the phenomenon being observed or measured, and it provides semantic clarity to the data by referencing standardized vocabularies. The *Sensor* specifies the device or instrument making the observation, which is described by properties such as the type of sensor, manufacturer details, or measurement technique, and contains any relevant metadata about how measurements are made, whether that's a physical sensor or a measurement procedure. The *Datastream* represents a flow of *Observations* for a specific *Observed Property*, *Sensor* and *Thing* combination. The *Observation* contains the actual recorded measurement or result obtained from a *Sensor*, and includes the value of the measurement, the time, and the *Feature of Interest*, i.e. the specific real-world feature to which the observation is related. A schematic representation of the SensorThings API data model is reported in Figure 2. The FROST Server has well-defined endpoints that expose these entities, all accessible via HTTP with standard methods (GET, POST, PATCH, DELETE). Data is exchanged in JSON format. The SensorThings data model can be extended with the OGC Water Quality Interoperability Experiment (WaterQualityIE) [10] data model, enabling a more sophisticated handling of water-quality observations and parameters than the base SensorThings specification allows. While the core SensorThings API data model relies

on the eight entity types (*Things, Locations, HistoricalLocations, Sensors, Observed Properties, Datastreams, Observations, Features Of Interest*), the Water Quality IE plugin provides additional structures to the core set of entities of the SensorThings API to represent sampling protocols, measurement procedures, etc. that are essential for transparent and repeatable water-quality monitoring so that water-quality observations can be represented in a clearer, more domain-specific manner [11]. The SensorThings API promotes interoperability by providing a single, open standard for describing and sharing sensor data. Because the data is delivered through RESTful endpoints in JSON, various clients and applications can easily access and integrate it without needing custom protocols. This streamlined framework makes it simpler for organizations to exchange sensor data and use it across different platforms and tools.

The pilot platform developed within the Water4All Partnership is designed to aggregate and integrate data from multiple FROST Servers, each hosted by different institutions, by utilizing the standardization provided by the OGC SensorThings API. Each FROST Server implements the SensorThings API, which exposes sensor data (e.g., *Things, Sensors, Observations*, etc.) through well-defined, RESTful endpoints using standard HTTP methods (GET, POST, PATCH, DELETE) and JSON data formatting. This common interface ensures that the platform can uniformly request and receive data, regardless of the source institution, and thanks to the uniform data model of SensorThings API, the platform can integrate data from different servers. Overall, by using standardized API requests and a unified data model, the pilot platform efficiently collects, integrates, and serves sensor data from diverse FROST Servers, thereby enhancing interoperability and simplifying data management across different institutions, promoting an environment where the exchange and sharing of information occurs in a simple and coherent way.

As part of activities, ISPRA has contributed to the pilot platform by integrating water quality data, specifically focusing on pesticide concentrations measurements in both surface and groundwater [13]. The data are exposed through the ISPRA FROST Server at the endpoint: <https://w4all.isprambiente.it/FROST-Server/v1.1>

This type of data is also available as OGC Web Map Services (WMS)/ Web Feature Service (WFS) services and CSV/SHP file for download through the National Environmental Information System. Furthermore, the portal provides statistics and reports as well as access to GeoPortal and tools for browsing data. Both services provide access to environmental data, but they have different structures and capabilities. API Frost Server provides access to data in standard JSON and XML format, allowing easier integration with modern web applications and data systems. On the other hand, WMS and WFS are primarily standards for maps and images. Additionally, API Frost Server is optimized for real-time and dynamic data, enabling integration with real-time applications like dashboards, alerts and data analytics tools.

Implementation of API Frost Server represents an added value, offering better interoperability, more efficient data usage and direct access to raw data.

The data loading process involved structuring water quality measurements according to the SensorThings API data model, ensuring compliance with the OGC standards. Each pesticide concentration measurement was represented as an *Observation* within a dedicated *Datastream*, linked to the corresponding *Sensor, Observed Property* (chemical substance concentration), and *Thing* (the station hosting the sensor). The *Feature of Interest* referenced the specific water body where the measurement was made, or the sample was collected.

Figure 2. The SensorThings API data model. Figure from [12].

We started with raw data stored in CSV format. The CSV files contained multiple columns representing parameters such as station ID, region, municipality, locality, coordinates, body of water, water basin, chemical substance, year, concentration value, with each row corresponding to an observation. A Python script was developed to parse the CSV file and construct JSON payloads for each STA entity, mapping the relevant columns to the entity fields. Before creating a new entity (e.g., *Thing*, *Location*, *HistoricalLocation*, *Sensor*, *ObservedProperty*, *Datastream*, *FeatureOfInterest*), the script checks if it already existed in the database to avoid duplication. If the entity doesn't already exist, it is created with a POST request to the FROST Server endpoint. The creation must follow the order: *Thing* first, then *Location*, *HistoricalLocation*, *Sensor*, *ObservedProperty*, and *Datastream*. Once all the other entities are in place, the *Observation* for that row can be created, linking it to the correct *Datastream*. In this way ISPRA systematically integrated the pesticide concentration data into the FROST Server to which the pilot platform connects.

The pilot platform integrates data from various FROST servers, including the ISPRA FROST Server, to provide a comprehensive visualization of environmental monitoring stations and their associated datastreams. As shown in Figure 3, the platform allows users to explore the monitoring stations on a map and analyze temporal trends of the selected parameters.

Figure 3. The pilot platform displays data from the ISPRA FROST Server. The map shows the monitoring stations, while the graph presents sample datastreams for Glyphosate and Metolachlor concentrations over time for a selected station.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The integration of ISPRA’s pesticide concentration data into the Water4All FROST-based pilot platform illustrates how standardized APIs and data models foster interoperability, scalability, and data management efficiency. By adopting the OGC SensorThings API and extending it with the WaterQualityIE plugin, multiple institutions can seamlessly share, compare, and analyze water-quality observations. This approach strengthens the national environmental information system by ensuring consistent, transparent, and easily accessible datasets, ultimately supporting more informed decision-making and advancing environmental protection goals. Moreover, the implementation of the API FROST Server adds significant value by facilitating better integration, optimizing data utilization, and providing direct access to raw data. Furthermore, this prototype serves as a best-practice example, showcasing the impact of research conducted within the European Water4All Partnership (Water Security for the Planet) on the Italian National Environmental Information System.

The availability of environmental data through shared information systems (SEIS) is crucial for fostering the continuous development and enhancement of information systems, enabling the exploration of new opportunities and innovative solutions. Data accessibility and interoperability are fundamental to more efficient decision-making processes and cross-sector collaboration. They also provide the base for advancements such as Artificial Intelligence, which can enhance data analysis capabilities, enable predictive modelling, and create new pathways for addressing complex challenges in environmental monitoring and sustainable development.

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Analysing citizens' perceptions and behavioural responses to transport-related air pollution through a mixed-methods survey approach

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Abstract

Urban air pollution represents a pressing environmental and public health issue that mitigation actions require robust policy interventions informed by the public's awareness of the issue, its perceptions and behavioral underpinnings. Advancements in air quality monitoring technologies have introduced more sophisticated measurement instruments enabling the collection of detailed data, however research on the impacts of transport-related air pollution on public perception and behavioral responses remains limited. Therefore, public engagement is critical in addressing these challenges, as it facilitates the generation of new knowledge and actionable solutions. This study investigates citizens' perceptions of transport-related air pollution, their awareness of its health impacts, and the behavioral adaptations they adopt in response to perceived exposure. Special emphasis is placed on assessing citizens' perceptions of the effects on their cognitive and mental health, which serve as a key parameter for advancing understanding in this domain. The study employs a survey-based methodology incorporating Ecological Momentary Assessment for momentary perceptions tracking and Protection Motivation Theory to analyze protective behaviors adopted by individuals. Findings from this research aim to contribute to the development of more effective strategies for addressing transport-related air pollution through informed public engagement and behavioral interventions.

Keywords: *transport-related air pollution, citizen perceptions, behavioural responses, mixed-methods approach*

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Real-Time Source Apportionment Using the ACSM-Xact-Aethalometer (AXA) System and SoFi RT Software

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Abstract

Particulate matter (PM) pollution is a major concern for public health and environmental quality, especially in urban areas. Effective air quality management requires a thorough understanding of PM sources through accurate source apportionment (SA). Traditional SA methods, which rely on offline data collection, often delay responses to pollution events. Recent advancements in monitoring technologies have enabled real-time source apportionment (RT-SA), offering continuous, high-resolution insights into pollution sources.

This study marks the first deployment of the ACSM-Xact-Aethalometer (AXA) system in combination with SoFi RT software for real-time PM source apportionment in Athens, Greece. The AXA system combines chemical, elemental, and black carbon data, providing a comprehensive view of PM sources in an urban environment. Results indicate that traffic emissions were the dominant source of PM, while secondary components—such as organic aerosols, sulfate, nitrate, and ammonium—comprised over 50% of the total PM mass. Primary emissions from biomass burning and cooking contributed approximately 10% each, with natural sources like sea salt and dust accounting for the remainder. The integration of organic, elemental, and black carbon fractions further enriched the characterization of PM composition.

The SoFi RT software enabled continuous and near-instantaneous SA with automated data processing, significantly improving the identification of pollution sources in real time. These findings highlight the system’s ability to accurately detect key PM contributors and underscore its potential to transform urban air quality monitoring. This approach paves the way for timely, targeted interventions aimed at reducing PM pollution in cities.

Keywords: particulate matter, source apportionment, air pollution, ACSM-Xact-Aethalometer

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Qualitative and Quantitative Analysis of Solid Wastes in Pieria's Ports: The Impact of Tourism and Fishing

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Abstract

This research assesses solid waste pollution loads in Pieria's (Greece) coastal areas due to professional fishing and mussel farming and touristic visitors. Solid waste at 3 fishing ports was categorized and quantified via line transects during October. Waste was recorded outside designated bins, revealing no correlation between bin availability and litter levels. Wind analysis showed minimal impact on waste dispersal, highlighting anthropogenic activity as the main factor. Seasonal traffic at port entrances and parking areas significantly influenced waste distribution. Effective coastal management and waste control in fishing and touristic ports are essential for mitigating human impact at local, national, and international levels.

Keywords: litter, fishing ports, management status.

1. INTRODUCTION

The management of solid waste in fishing and mooring ports is a complex issue, with gaps in law and implementation identified worldwide [1]. Bycatch discards, processing wastes, plastic wastes, and bilges are the main sources of waste in fishing operations, as well as from touristic and guest activities [2]. Fishing ports, which are modestly sized harbors, are established in regions with prevalent fishery and aquaculture professions to provide the necessary support for these industries. These ports are able to support leisure activities, accommodating yachts and boats used for recreational fishing as well as organized commercial fisheries and aquaculture [3]. As a result, these ports become places where people work and visit. The Pieria Prefecture, a part of Central Macedonia, presents an extensive coastline along the western Thermaikos Gulf. It is a hub for tourism, with numerous lodging facilities offering around 20,000 beds, and it attracts more than 400,000 visitors

Figure 4. The main ports of Pieria Prefecture (Central Macedonia, Greece).

annually, predominantly in the summer season, as reported by INCETE (2022) [4]._The region also thrives in small-scale fisheries and, since 1990, in mussel farming—a sector that presents annual yielding over 10,000 tons [5]. Fishermen and mussel farmers utilize these fishing ports for their vessels, and transfer their mussel harvests, with three main ports facilitating these activities from north to south: Kitros, Katerini Paralia and Platamonas, as depicted in Figure 1. The solid waste generated by passengers, visitors, and port users is noteworthy. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to quantify and qualify the solid waste pollution at Pieria’s fishing ports.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

During October 2023 solid wastes were identified and enumerated, in three fishing ports of Pieria coast (Western Thermaikos Gulf) in transect zones of 1 m step. The solid wastes were categorized in 13 types of solid wastes according to the material type as presented in Table 1. Following the characterization and classification the solid wastes found were quantified in each category and the results were assessed by one way ANOVA_(p=0.05) with Tukey pairwise comparisons.

Table 2. The 13 solid wastes types of the study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In all ports cigarette butts presents the highest percentage of solid wastes, with Katerini Paralia to present the highest one with 83.5%, as illustrated in Figure 2B, due to the increased touristic and recreational activities that take place and is situated close to the prefecture capital named Katerini city. The two other ports are used mainly for fishing and aquaculture activities. Kitros, in particular, plays a significant role in mussel farming, which is reflected in

the waste composition, whereas Platamonas is more oriented towards fishing, leading to a greater presence of fishing nets in the area compared to Kitros. As the port with the highest mean total solids, it could be inferred Kitros and lowest at Platamonas as depicted in Figure 2D. Each port exhibits a unique combination of activities, characterized by varying degrees of operational intensity, the performance of waste management frameworks, and the impact of environmental elements specific to each location. As of now, only a select group of 3 Greek ports, which represent a mere 5.4% of the total port count, are involved in systematic surveillance of environmental quality measures [6].

Figure 2. Percentage distribution of solid wastes in ports A) Kitros, B) Katerini Paralia, C) Platamonas and (D) Interval Plot (95% CI) of ports total solid wastes.

There is a pressing need for a holistic approach to monitoring solid waste practices, with a particular focus on zones that serve dual purposes, catering to both tourism and leisure activities as well as fishing and aquaculture operations. This expanded monitoring is vital for ensuring sustainable port operations and minimizing their ecological footprint [7].

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the composition and quantity of solid waste across the studied ports reflect the distinct activities and environmental pressures present at each location. Ports with a strong

touristic character tend to generate more consumer-related waste, while those focused on fishing and aquaculture show different waste profiles, often linked to their specific operations. These findings highlight the importance of tailored waste management strategies that consider local activities and environmental conditions. Expanding systematic monitoring efforts is essential to support sustainable practices and reduce the environmental impact of port operations.

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Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions from Stickney WRP in Chicago

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Abstract

As concerns about climate change and air pollution grow more, it is vital to focus on the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of major contributors. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) have been identified as significant sources of certain GHGs, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O), and methane (CH₄). While these gases naturally occur in the atmosphere, their concentrations have dramatically increased due to human activities. The Stickney Water Reclamation Plant (WRP) is one of seven wastewater treatment facilities owned and operated by the Metropolitan Water Reclamation District of Greater Chicago (MWRD) with the average treatment volume of 1,200 million gallons/day. This study investigates the key contributors to GHG emissions within Stickney WRP processes, analyzes how these processes contribute to energy consumption and GHG emissions, and proposes solutions to reduce their environmental impact based on the EPA LCA report.

Keywords: greenhouse gases, wastewater treatment, energy consumption, environmental impacts.

Dynamic surface leaching and release controlling mechanisms of Blast Furnace Slag Binders

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Abstract

Blast-Furnace Slag (BFS) can produce excellent binders through alkaline activation, being more eco-friendly than Portland cement in terms of GHG emissions. This study evaluates the environmental impact of Portland cement (CEM-I) and alkali-activated BFS (AAS) based on leaching criteria according to the European Construction Products Framework. Mortar samples were prepared and tested for leaching. Both binders meet EU inert landfill limits, but the release of trace elements differs significantly in dynamic leaching tests (DSLIT). These observed differences underline the critical importance of conducting exhaustive leaching studies. Long-term release predictions and the identification of trace element release mechanisms at the surface, in accordance with the CEN/TS 16637-2 standard, will enable an environmental assessment over the entire life cycle of the alkalinity-activated slag (AAS).

Keywords: cement, alkali activated slag, leaching test, DSLIT

1. INTRODUCTION

Cement is a widely used commodity, second only to water. Demand is expected to double by 2060 due to infrastructure expansion in developing countries [1]. However, current practices of production are environmentally unsustainable. Alternatives to traditional cement that are equal or superior in performance, more environmentally friendly and cost competitive need to be developed and applied. It is crucial to reduce long-term environmental impacts and ensure sustainable development in the construction sector. Alkali-activated materials (AAM), also known as geopolymers, are a studied alternative to OPC hydration reactions and synergistic hydraulic-pozzolanic reactions in OPC. AAM involves the chemical reaction of an aluminosilicate source with an alkaline activator solution, forming an aluminosilicate gel [2].

Although alternatives to cement claim to be ‘sustainable’ or ‘environmentally friendly’ by integrating secondary resources, sustainability encompasses a broader scope. Total greenhouse gas emissions, land use, degradation, ecotoxicity and the release of hazardous substances are critical to long-term sustainability. In particular, various reactions and combinations of materials can alter the solubility of elements, affecting the mobility or retention of trace elements. Therefore, to address environmental compatibility, leaching criteria should be characterise and evaluate the release of hazardous substances. Furthermore, in a context of material circularity, assessing leaching

throughout the lifecycle is crucial when cementitious materials contain secondary raw materials. A combination of leaching tests resembling each lifecycle stage is needed for basic characterisation. Few examples address leaching of cements, hybrid cements, and alkali-activated materials with various leaching tests [3].

Blast furnace slag (BFS), a by-product generated in a blast furnace in a molten state, can produce excellent binders through alkaline activation due to its high glass phase content and more environmentally friendly than Portland cement in terms of greenhouse gas emissions.

This study aims to conduct an environmental evaluation based on leaching criteria for the two binders mentioned: Portland cement (CEM-I) and alkali-activated blast furnace slag (AAS), in accordance with the European Framework for Construction Products. To achieve this, the Compliance Leaching Test (EN 12457-4), and the Dynamic Surface Leaching Test (DSLTL, CEN/TS 16637-2) will be performed on granular samples and monolithic samples, respectively. The novelty of this research lies in the determination of the release mechanisms, which are crucial for estimating the long-term leaching behaviour of these materials throughout their life cycle.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The binders used in this study were: a commercial Portland cement (CEM-I) type CEM I 52,5R and an Alkali activated slag (AAS) based on ground granulated blast furnace slag (BFS). The chemical composition determined by XRF (Bruker S8 TIGER) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical composition (expressed as oxides in wt %) of Materials

	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	SO ₃	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	TiO ₂	Other	LoI
CEM I	62.94	19.29	5.28	2.62	0.85	3.58	0.10	0.67	0.24	1.55	2.88
BFS	45.18	33.17	10.50	1.49	3.75	1.68	0.33	0.77	2.29	0.73	0.11

Mortar samples were prepared in accordance with EN 196-1. Commercial Portland cement was hydrated with deionized water (water/cement ratio of 0.5). However, ground granulated blast furnace slag (BFS from Turkey) (AAS) was hydrated with 4M NaOH solution/ 0.55 BFS ratio. In all cases, the sand/binder ratio was 3/1. After 28 days of curing in a climatic chamber, the compression strength (MPa) was for CEM-I 58.3 ± 2.3 and, AAS, 52.8 ± 1.1 .

Figure 1. Outline of the procedure for the DSLT setup and preparation of eluates for analysis

Two different leaching tests were conducted: Compliance Leaching Test (EN 12457-4), to obtain the equilibrium concentration of pollutants from granular samples (< 10 mm), and Dynamic Surface Leaching Test (DSLST, CEN/TS 16637-2), to obtain the release of pollutants per unit of surface area as a function of time from monolithic samples (4 x 4 x 16 cm³). The methodology of this leaching test is illustrated in Figure 1.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Compliance leaching assessment

The results of the compliance leaching test (EN 12457-4) are presented in Table 2. The pH and conductivity values of the leachates are shown along with the concentrations of trace elements and anions. The obtained values are compared with the European Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) limits for deposition in inert landfills.

Table 2. pH values, conductivity and elements concentration in leachates of CEM-I and AAS binders from compliance leaching test (EN 12457-4)

Substances (mg kg ⁻¹)	CEM-I	AAS	WAC* Inert limits
As	0.002±0.002	0.028±0.003	0.5
Ba	13.72±1.126	0.278±0.027	20
Cd	0.0004	0.0003	0.04
Cr	0.046±0.002	0.015±0.002	0.5
Cu	0.009±0.009	0.003±0.002	2
Hg	<DL	0.0006±0.0002	0.01
Mo	0.033±0.007	0.011±0.006	0.5
Ni	0.007±0.002	0.015±0.020	0.4
Pb	0.005±0.002	0.001	0.5
Sb	0.0004±0.0001	0.0006±0.0001	0.06
Se	0.014±0.0005	0.020±0.005	0.1
V	0.042±0.045	0.910±0.062	1.8**
Zn	0.079±0.100	0.026	4
Cl ⁻	6.47±0.346	31.58±5.614	800
F ⁻	1.11±0.346	9.04±1.103	10
SO ₄ ²⁻	25.85±0.375	41.04±2.807	1000
pH	12.38±0.014	12.10±0.035	-
Conductivity (µS cm ⁻¹)	7540±28.29	4545±346.48	-

* WAC European landfill Waste Acceptance Criteria

** Adopted from the SQD limit values for unmoulded building materials (Soil quality Decree, 2007)

The CEM-I and AAS samples exhibit similar pH values, approximately 12. However, the conductivity of the leachate from the CEM-I samples is nearly double that of the AAS samples, which can be attributed to the solubility of calcium oxides and other soluble substances, such as sulphates. Conversely, the release of trace elements in both the CEM-I and AAS samples is well below the limit values proposed by the European framework for the disposal of waste in inert landfills, with the exception of Ba in the CEM-I samples and a value very close to the limit for F⁻ in the AAS samples.

The oxyanionic elements, As, Cr, Mo, Sb, Se and V were identified as critical elements, as they are the most problematic in terms of their retention in BFS-based cementitious systems, and this can be seen in the chemical equilibrium mobility obtained in this section. For this reason, and also as observed in the literature [4-7], the subsequent leaching characterisations will focus on these trace elements.

3.2. Monolithic samples leaching assessment

The service life leaching assessment of the monolithic samples is conducted using the DSLT (CEN/TS 16637-2) to determine the long-term release of substances. Initially, pH and conductivity as a function of time are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Evolution of pH and conductivity over time of CEM-I and AAS samples in DSLT

The evolution of pH values over time is quite similar in the CEM-I and AAS samples. During the initial time stages (0.25, 1, 2.25, and 4 days), there is minimal variation, and the pH values remain constant. However, in the extended time stages (9, 16, 36, and 64 days), the pH values progressively increase. Conversely, conductivity does not exhibit similar patterns between the samples. In the early stages, the conductivity of the AAS samples is higher than that of the CEM-I samples, likely due to the progressive dissolution of calcium or magnesium oxides (i.e., they are progressively washed out). In the long-term stages, however, the CEM-I samples show higher conductivity values.

The cumulative release of trace elements over time from the monolithic samples is shown in Figure 3 for the elements that usually form oxyanions, As, Cr, Mo, Sb, Se and V. It can be observed that, with the exception of the cumulative release of Cr and Sb, the release of the other elements is significantly higher in the AAS (note the logarithmic scale). Specifically, for As, the CEM-I leachates were below the detection limit of the equipment. Mo and Se exhibit similar behaviour in both samples; in the initial stages, the concentrations in CEM-I are much lower, but at 64 days, they tend to equalise. In the case of V, both samples show the same trends over time, although the concentrations released are significantly different.

Figure 3. Cumulative release (mg.m⁻²) of trace elements in DSLT (CEN/TS 16637-2) of monolithic samples

3.3 Release modelling to predict long-term life

The release mechanisms are then determined based on the procedure in Annex B of the CEN/TS 16637-2 standard. All possible mechanisms are presented in Table 3 for the CEM-I,

Table 3. Release mechanisms identified in the monolithic form of CEM-I and AAS samples according to CEN/TS 16637-2 Annex B procedure

Release Mechanisms	CEM-I						AAS					
	As	Cr	Mo	Sb	Se	V	As	Cr	Mo	Sb	Se	V
M1 - Overall low concentrations	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M1.1 – Surface wash-off following M1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M2 – Diffusion	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M2.1 – Surface wash-off preceding M2	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-
M2.2 – M2 with depletion	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-
M2.3 – M2.1 and M2.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M3 – Dissolution	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M4 – Unidentified mechanism	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
M4.1 – Surface wash-off preceding M4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-
M4.2 – Depletion following M4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-
M4.3 – M4.1 and M4.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	✓	-	-	-	✓	✓

The predominant mechanism in the CEM-I control sample is diffusion. Depending on the element, surface leaching (Sb, V) and depletion (Cr) are determined, while Mo remains unidentified. The primary AAS mechanism could not be identified with the empirically available data, with the exception of Cr (diffusion). However, most of the elements showed initial surface leaching, depletion or a combination of both, which is consistent with the release pattern of the accumulated concentrations.

In the specific case of chromium (Cr), the release curves were similar, despite the significant difference in the nature of the matrices due to the chemical reactions that take place, cement hydration and alkaline activation, which correspond to samples CEM-I and AAS, respectively. This similarity is reflected in the determination of the predominant mechanisms, which are the same for both samples, diffusion followed by Cr depletion. In summary, the two construction materials exhibited different release mechanisms, which may even vary depending on the element. Therefore, it is crucial to emphasise the importance of determining release mechanisms to estimate the long-term leaching behaviour of alternative construction materials to those based on ordinary Portland cement (OPC).

Finally, the cumulative concentrations at 64 days are compared to the limit values of the Soil Quality Decree (SQD) for the unrestricted use of monolithic construction materials in the Netherlands (Table 4). SQD values are selected due to the absence of harmonised limit values in the evaluation of leaching of monolithic samples in the EU, and are used in other studies on construction materials [4]. Although, with the exception of chromium (Cr) and antimony (Sb), the leaching of SAA is much greater than that of the CEM-I samples in the DSLT leachates, it can be observed here that all the elements have concentrations well below the permitted SQD limits.

Table 4. Cumulative release values at 64 days of CEM-I and AAS samples and SQD limit values for unrestricted use of monolithic construction materials.

Elements (mg m ⁻²)	CEM-I	AAS	SQD limit
As	n.d.	0.210	260
Cr	0.050	0.097	120
Mo	0.010	0.045	144
Sb	0.017	0.009	8.7
Se	0.057	0.163	4.8
V	0.868	5.85	320

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, BFS binders were evaluated as an alternative to traditional Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) through a leaching test framework, examining the release of substances in both monolithic and granular forms. The results indicate that the concentrations of As, Cr, Mo, Sb, Se, and V, as well as anions in the leachate from the compliance test, show that both binders in granular form meet the EU inert landfill limits. However, the cumulative release of As, Mo, Se, and V over 64 days from the monolithic form, according to DSLT, varies significantly. Consequently, the release mechanisms of these trace elements differ. These findings underline the necessity of conducting comprehensive leaching studies. Predictions of long-term release and identification of release mechanisms from the surface of the metallic(loid)s, in accordance with the CEN/TS 16637-2 standard, will facilitate environmental assessment throughout the life cycle of the slag-based binder, alkali-activated BFS.

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Application of GIS technology as a base of AI tools for remediation of brownfield sites containing NORM residues

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Abstract

Brownfield sites are abandoned, neglected, unused or contaminated/polluted terrains, abandoned, neglected or unused industrial and commercial facilities or infrastructure, or land, facilities, infrastructure that require some kind of intervention in order to be put back into use. Brownfield sites represent a spatial and development resource but require remediation that most often includes decontamination or soil cleaning, cleaning or demolition of constructions/buildings and similar interventions. GIS technology enables proper records to be kept of all such sites within the country, but also facilitates the management of individual sites, since all data on sites, including radiological and total volume data, can be quantitatively and qualitatively displayed using GIS technology, thus facilitating their management. The GIS Map of a site can be incorporated into a AI tool for a future environmental and possible health risk based decision management procedures including regulatory requirements. A specific problem is represented by sites where NORM residues are found, since in addition to natural radionuclides, other contaminants such as chemically active substances, heavy metals, etc. can be expected in materials on this type of brownfield sites. ²²⁶Ra originating from NORM residues is of a high interest for final risk assessment because of its high radiotoxicity in any of mixture forms. Location of the former plastics and chemical products factory, “Jugovinil”, City of Kaštela, Croatia, is one such site, since naturally radioactive materials, heavy metals and other pollutants originating from activities on site were found on the location. Part of the pollution is a consequence of the disposal of ash and slag created by burning coal in the thermal power plant of the former factory, and the rest is related to industrial activities carried out after the demolition of the factory (small shipyards). GIS technology enables the display of both surface and distribution of pollutants by depth, the relationship of the location with other topographical features, as well as geological, hydrogeological and other characteristics of the area. The data can be used as a teaching deep learning machine tool or further development of decision making AI tools to be used for description of similar sites globally. This makes it easier to assess the situation at the location, plan and carry out remediation.

Keywords: *brownfield, NORM residues, remediation, GIS, AI tools*

Green innovation and environmental performance: the role of economic interactions and technological contaminations across industries

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Abstract

Exploring the economic interactions as well as the technological contaminations across industries, this paper investigates the extent to which being economically and technologically interlinked can drive the capacity of an industry within a specific country to foster green innovation and in turn, enhance its environmental performance.

The theoretical framework of this study integrates the concepts of core supply-chain industries and general-purpose industries to better understand the industrial drivers influencing greater green innovation capacity. From this perspective, a core supply-chain industry functions as a crucial node within the global economic network, facilitating the flow of goods, materials, and services across sectors through input-output linkages. Conversely, a general-purpose industry serves as a catalyst for innovation, driving progress across multiple sectors by developing technologies with broad and versatile applications.

The central premise is that a core supply-chain industry leverages its deep integration within supply chains to foster strategic inter-industry partnerships and access a more diverse knowledge base. Simultaneously, a general-purpose industry capitalizes on its ability to create technologies that serve as platforms or frameworks for other industries to build upon.

Given the inherently complex and collaborative nature of green technologies, we hypothesize that industries capable of aligning their roles as both economic and technological hubs—within global supply chains and innovation networks, respectively—are better positioned to access diverse knowledge pools and develop the recombination capabilities necessary to drive green technological progress and higher environmental performance.

To address this research issue, we used data from two primary sources. First, we use the Global Resource Input Output Assessment (GLORIA) database, a multi-region input-output dataset which illustrates how the output of one industry (goods or services) serves as an input for another, providing a comprehensive view of the interdependencies across industries within an economy and among different countries. From this database, we reconstructed input-output data for 31 European countries, plus US, China and the Rest of the World, disaggregated into 39 agri-food industries for the period 1990–2020. Finally, we compute network indexes as proxy to capture the position and influence of country-industries within global production networks. Second, we leverage the OECD RegPat database to obtain green patent data by country and sector from 1990 to 2020. This allows us to compute, on the one hand, the technological contamination across industry as a measure based on co-occurrence analysis and cosine similarity. On the other hand, it is also used to assess the extent to which an industry contributes to foster the green transition by measuring the number of applied green patents at industry-country level.

Finally, environmental performance is measured using GLORIA satellite accounts and computed as the ratio between CO₂ emissions and country value-added, or advancements in biodiversity preservation and sustainable resource use.

By combining these dimensions, we aim to demonstrate that economic interaction and technological contaminations better support industries to develop green innovations and to achieve environmental performance. Specifically, we expect to find evidence of higher green patent production, significant reductions in CO₂ emissions, increased value-added, and enhanced biodiversity preservation in country-industries that are more economically and technologically interlinked within their production and innovation networks.

To conclude, this research provides novel insights into the intersection of GVC integration, technological innovation, and environmental sustainability, contributing to the understanding of sustainable industrial transformation.

Keywords: *global value chains, agri-food system, centrality, relatedness, green innovation*

Enhancing PFAS Risk Characterisation Through a Cloud-based PBK Model Repository

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Abstract

Physiologically based kinetic (PBK) models are essential human and environmental risk assessment tools. When applied, in a forward dosimetry approach, these models translate external exposures into internal organ burdens. Conversely, reverse dosimetry estimates external exposures based on measured tissue concentrations. PBK models for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are invaluable for understanding the persistence, potential impacts, and safety concerns associated with these chemicals in humans and ecosystems. Given the widespread use and environmental persistence of PFAS, comprehending their behaviour and associated risks is crucial to safeguarding public health and ecosystems.

In this work, we introduce a framework developed in R that enables PBK models to be published as fully documented, ready-to-use web services on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org>), which is also accessible via the SCENARIOS cloud platform. This framework facilitates the publication of various PFAS-related PBK models from the literature and novel models developed within the SCENARIOS project, making them accessible to non-technical users. Furthermore, we demonstrate how clients across diverse programming environments enable remote access and seamless integration into computational workflows. Our goal is to continually expand the collection of PFAS-related PBK models on Jaqpot by incorporating new and existing models, thereby broadening their applicability and contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of PFAS risks.

Keywords: PBK models, PFAS, risk assessment, exposure modelling, environmental risk, biokinetics

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Assessment of potential health risk of contaminants in soils in urban areas around the steel industrial zone of Volos (Greece)

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Abstract

This study aims to assess the potential health risk of contaminants in soils of 10 Potentially Toxic Elements (PTEs) in three urban areas situated near the industrial zone of Volos. The concentrations of chromium (Cr), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), cobalt (Co), and zinc (Zn) of 30 soil samples from parks, playgrounds, and roadsides in Agios Georgios, Velestino, and Rizomilos (Magnesia, central Greece) were analyzed. Moreover, the human health hazards associated with ingestion, dermal contact, and inhalation of the studied potential toxic elements were determined. The highest average concentrations of chromium (Cr), manganese (Mn), iron (Fe), cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), copper (Cu), arsenic (As), and lead (Pb) were recorded in the urban area of Agios Georgios, while zinc (Zn) and cadmium (Cd) showed the highest levels in Velestino area. Furthermore, the findings showed that the HI values for Co, Cd and As measured for children poses an increased risk of toxicological effects due to exposure to harmful substances through multiple routes.

Keywords: *contamination, PTEs, urban areas, hazard quotient, hazard index, Volos*

One health applied to zoonotic diseases

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Abstract

Globally, about 1400 infectious diseases known to affect humans, 60% of them are of animal origin. The spread of zoonotic diseases is associated with environmental factors, climate change, animal health as well as the influence exerted by human activities including globalization, urbanization and travel. The adverse health effects of these factors have been relatively ignored by policy makers until recently, but now this is beginning to change since diseases at the human-animal-environmental interface (e.g., zoonotic diseases, vector-borne diseases, food/water borne diseases) continue to pose a risk to animals and humans with a significant mortality and morbidity, and to the environment. The one health concept plays an important role in the control and prevention of zoonoses by integrating animal, human, and environmental health through the collaboration and communication among different professionals. The currently study aims to identify what factors should be considered to perform an assessment of the zoonotic risk according to the one-health approach. Our results could be relevant to give a contribution to the management of the biological risk in occupational settings

Keywords: one health, infectious disease, zoonoses, vector-borne diseases, food/water borne diseases

Hydrological Analysis of Long-Term Post-Fire Conditions in a Subbasin of the Alfeios River, Greece

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Abstract

This study investigates the hydrological response of a sub-basin within the Alfeios River Basin in Peloponnesus, Greece, to the effects of wildfires over an extended time. Wildfires alter land cover, significantly impacting the hydrological response by reducing evapotranspiration and infiltration capacities. While these effects are immediate, flora regrowth over time contributes to faster hydrological recovery. To that end, the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT), operating within a Geographic Information System (GIS) framework, was employed to analyze these dynamics. The model integrates geomorphological characteristics such as elevation, land use, soil type, and slope and produces runoff based on meteorological data on a daily time step. The SWAT model was calibrated with observed data, and three wildfire scenarios, each exhibiting different affected areas, were simulated using synthetic 50-year time series. Finally, various flora recovery periods were modeled to reflect the impact of the natural regrowth over time of the dominant flora within the 50-year simulation period. The results revealed substantial hydrological changes in the years immediately following wildfires, which decreased over time. Comparative analysis of scenarios provided insights into the basin's hydrological resilience, recovery trends, and water potential in fire-affected regions.

Keywords: hydrological analysis, SWAT, wildfire, land use change, Alfeios

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is essential for life conservation. While water resources are renewable, the increasing need for water can overcome the renewable rate, leading to water deficiency that impacts environmental and economic growth. A basin's hydrological response depends on many attributes, such as the basin area and characteristics, the soil properties, and the amount of precipitation received. Therefore, significant land use changes within a basin can significantly alter the hydrological response, leading to water scarcity. Wildfires are among the most current and impactful disturbances in the hydrological response. Although wildfires are usually examined as a separate natural disaster, post-fire effects are reported to increase the risk of flash floods and debris flows, as well as changes to water availability [1]. Wildfires lead to deforestation of the basin, a natural way of storing water within the basin, and change the infiltration capabilities through generated debris. In recent years, excessive dry periods have led to increased wildfire risk. Areas with dry climates, like the Mediterranean, have

suffered from excessive wildfires. Only in Greece, from 2017 to 2023, 4335 km², equalling 3% of the country, were affected by forest fires, based on data acquired by the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS).

Post-fire hydrological analysis is important for proper water management, as it identifies any water deficiencies and provides the most suitable actions to mitigate land degradation and rehabilitation [2]. Most of the analyses use hydrological modeling to assess the hydrological response of a fire-affected basin. However, most of these analyses focus on applying a hydrological model and comparing post- and pre-fire results, thus not developing models for post-fire analysis [3] and, most notably, on analyzing the hydrological response in the long term. Such an analysis should include the natural rate of regrowth of forests. It is well known that the ecosystem after such disasters tends to be reinstated to its original state after a significant period.

To that end, this research focuses on investigating these dynamics, i.e., the natural flora regrowth over time and assessing the hydrological response of the basin up to 50 years after a wildfire event occurs. The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) model is used to simulate the hydrological response of the Karitaina basin, a subbasin of the Alfeios River in Greece. The model was applied and calibrated with observed data using the ArcSWAT 2012 add-on within the ESRI ArcGIS 10.8 version, where all the maps of this research were created. Following this, three wildfire scenarios, each exhibiting different sizes and Eplace-affected areas, were simulated using synthetic time series. This analysis sheds light on the long-term assessment of the hydrological response, while the comparative analysis of scenarios provided insights into the basin's hydrological resilience, recovery trends, and water potential in fire-affected regions.

2 STUDY AREA AND DATA USED

The study area is the Karitaina basin, a sub-basin of the river Afleios, located in Peloponnese, Greece, illustrated in Figure 1. The basin's total area is 892 km², with a mean elevation of 750 m and a maximum of 1854 m at the Mount Mainalo peak in the northeast. The basin is the upper part of the Alfeios River basin, the largest basin in Peloponnese, which flows through Ilia prefecture, a significant area of agriculture production in Greece, before flowing out to the Ionian Sea. The basin is considered mountainous due to its high mean elevation and can be divided into four sections. The first three are the mountainous areas, located on the northeast, east, and South areas of the basin, while the fourth is the lower elevation plane, featuring the Megalopolis mining site, covering 2.4% of the total basin, one of the first energy production mining sites in Greece. Concerning land use, forest and semi-natural areas cover 64% of the basin, while 32% is covered by agricultural activity [4].

The data used for this analysis are divided into geomorphological and hydrometeorological datasets. The first data used to establish the SWAT model are a) a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) featuring a 25m x 25m grid size, b) the 2018 Corine Land Cover (CLC) dataset, both were acquired from the Copernicus repository and c) the soil type data, obtained from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations which features information on the soil and subsoil on a global scale.

Figure 5. The Alfeios River basin with the Karitaina subbasin

Concerning the hydrometeorological datasets, historical datasets were used to calibrate the model, obtained from the Worldwide Weather Service (W3S) [5] available from the official website of the ArcSWAT model. The platform provides meteorological data (precipitation, maximum and minimum temperature) in a predefined format, compatible with the SWAT model, for any catchment throughout the year, in a daily step. As shown in Figure 1, 5 stations were identified and used near the basin. The flow datasets were calculated based on measured daily stages at the Karitaina basin and transformed to flow using the stage-flow equation extracted by Bournas and Baltas [4]. The data span used for the calibration process covered the period between 2001 and 2014 to match the period of the available flow datasets.

3. METHODS

The main methodological framework followed in this research is shown in Figure 2. Specifically, the SWAT model was first established based on the acquired datasets. The ArcSWAT 2012 addon was used in conjunction with the ArcGIS 10.8 version, while the calibration process was performed with the SWAT-CUP module. The application steps of the model are shown in Figure 2. It includes three main steps.

The first step concerns the setup of the model. The first involves the creation of the Hydrological Response Units (HRU), where rainfall-runoff calculations are performed. The HRU are created by first delineating the study area into subbasins and then establishing the classification parameters, i.e., the land use, soil type, and slope, the number of is defined. The combination of the parameters, each created as a raster image, defines the total number of the HRU and the size, location, shape, and rainfall-runoff parameters used in the model. Then, using historical data, the SWAT-CUP program is used to calibrate the remaining SWAT parameters that the HRU creation process cannot define.

Figure 6. Methodological Framework

Following the model's setup, step two concerns the generation of the synthetic time series used to assess the effect of land use changes over a long period. The stochastic autocorrelation model AR (2) was used to generate 50 synthetic time series on a daily scale of 50 years for precipitation and temperature datasets labeled from 2020 to 2070 to visualize the results better. It is important to stress that synthetic time series are not to be assumed as future predictions since they rely on statistical information from past datasets. The AR (2) model was established in two timescales, the first being a monthly time step, in which the synthetic timeseries were constructed, and the second being the daily step, in which the average percentage of rainfall of each day of a particular month is used to downgrade from monthly values to a daily step. This analysis was performed because the SWAT model operates strictly with a daily step. Nevertheless, the results were aggregated into the monthly step since it matches the timestep required for assessing and analyzing the effects.

Finally, step three concerns the three land use change scenarios, all based on the assumption that wildfires occur in selected areas. Specifically, scenarios were selected based on land use and the characteristics that favor the spread of forest fires. The areas selected were mostly covered with coniferous trees, which are remarkably flammable, while another characteristic used was the steepness of the areas, which made it easier for fire to spread. In Figure 3, the identified sites are shown. Scenario one involves the burn of 185 km² in the northern region, at Mount Mainalon, accounting for 22.41 % of the basin's total area, while the second scenario involves the burn of 60.8 km² at the southern part, accounting for 7.35%

of the basin area. Finally, scenario three includes both areas affected by wildfires, accounting for 29.75% of the basin.

Figure 3. Wildfire Scenario Implementation Areas

To better simulate the impact of wildfires on the hydrological response over time, a temporal classification is made based on the forest regeneration periods, illustrated in Figure 4. The first 5 years simulate the status quo, used also as the model warmup period. After the wildfire occurs, the next 10 years, i.e., from the fire onwards, the areas affected are transformed into barren areas, i.e., land use is changed to the (BARR) designation, thus simulating the burned area. Due to the presence of spruce in the area, for the next 30 years or so, the area is in a transitional stage, designating the coniferous forests and the remaining forests with the grassland. Therefore, land use has been changed from BARR to sparse vegetation, i.e., the (RNGE) designation. Finally, for the final years and until the end of the simulation, the vegetation is assumed to have reverted to its original stage. These stages are illustrated in Figure 4, with 2025 being the date of the wildfire event, 2035 being the date where the burnt area (BARR) transitions into sparse vegetation (RNGE), while the year 2065 the restoration of the forest occurs, returning their original land cover state.

Figure 4. Temporal simulation of vegetation changes after a fire scenario

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first step involves setting up the SWAT model. To that end, the classification parameters are first calculated and presented in Figure 5. Based on the basin's size, stream network, and geomorphological characteristics, 13 subbasins were constructed, as shown in Figure 5a. Following this, the land use classification dataset was performed by correlating the classes used in the Corine Land Cover with the land use classification used in the SWAT model. In Figure 5b, the SWAT land cover classification is used, where AGRL, AGRN, AGRO, and AGRR refer to cropland types, BARR to bare soil, FRSD, FRSE, FRST to forest types, IRRL to permanently irrigated lands, PAST to pasture, RNGB to range shrublands, i.e., sparse vegetation/degraded land, UIDU and URML to industrial/developed areas and WATR to rivers and water bodies.

Figure 5. Study Area, SWAT delineation classification; a) subbasins delineation, b) land use, c) slope, and d) soil type

The most dominant land uses are RNGB, 47.85%, AGRN, agroforestry to 18.1%, and Forests (FRSD, FRSE, FRST), 17.5% and approximately 10% for aggregation. In Figure 5c, the slope classification used is shown, while in Figure 5d, the soil types based on the FAO soil table are shown, with Lithosols being the dominant type, which features low water permeability, i.e., high runoff potential. Finally, utilizing the above data, 330 HRUs were created using thresholds of acceptable land use percentages, soil type, and slope classes for

each HRU, set as 0.5%, 5%, and 3%, respectively. Finally, the calibration of the model was performed using the historical data mentioned in section 2. The calibration was merely successful since a Nash-Sutcliffe coefficient index of 0.5 was calculated, but a better model is applied than using the default values. It is important to stress that this analysis is not dependent on the calibration quality since a comparison of different land uses is only made, thus, a comparison between calibrated and uncalibrated models would result in equal difference percentages.

Following this, the simulation using the synthetic timeseries is performed. In Figure 6, the mean hydrological response of all simulations is shown for the baseline scenario, with gray, and the three wildfire scenarios. The average annual volume is estimated at 333.6 hm³, translating to an average 10.57 m³/s daily flow. The highest average annual volume occurs in 2035, reaching 351 hm³, while the lowest is calculated at 319 hm³, one year after the wildfire event. Concerning the fire scenarios, it is visible that after the fire event, two scenarios, scenarios one and three, exhibit higher runoff volumes, whereas scenario 2 features slightly change to the baseline scenario. In scenario two, the average annual runoff volume compared to the baseline scenario increased by only 0.62%, i.e., only 2 hm³, as illustrated in Figure 7. This effect is attributed to scenario two only affecting the southern part of the basin, which features a significantly less area affected than the other two scenarios, i.e., one-third of the other scenarios. In these cases, the average annual volume difference to the baseline scenario is increased by 1.7% and 1.8% for scenarios one and three, respectively, translating to approximately 9 hm³ annual increase. Similar differences are found in the upper and lower 95% confidential intervals.

Figure 7. Comparison of annual runoff volumes

Figure 8. Percentage change in annual volume of all scenarios compared to the baseline scenario

Although differences in the annual volume between the baseline and the wildfire scenarios are not that distinct, more information can be extracted monthly. As seen in Figure 8, the higher absolute changes are identified in the rain period, i.e., October and November, although significant differences are also identified in August. When assessing the percentage change of the average monthly runoff, the summer months exhibit up to 60% change, which is logically explained by the fact that these months feature little precipitation and, thus, the runoff, and therefore any slight change in runoff leads to high percentage changes. Overall, it is shown that the distribution of monthly runoff change is not uniform, and several months feature a decrease in runoff, namely from January to July. This period, especially the beginning of Spring, matches the irrigation period, where water demand is high, and therefore, these results stress the importance of proper water management after the events of wildfires.

Figure 9. Absolute Monthly difference in monthly volume

Finally, we perform the same comparison but analyze the restoration periods separately. To that end, we investigate the results of scenario 3, the scenario with the most significant change compared to the baseline scenario, since the rest of the scenarios exhibited similar results. In Figure 9, the difference in the monthly volume per recovery stage is shown for the total year span from 2025 to 2070, whereas the red bars illustrate the changes for the transition period and the green bars for the final phase, where the forest has been reinstated.

Figure 10. The difference in monthly volume per recovery stage for scenario 3

As was expected, the first years after the fire exhibit higher changes, i.e., the monthly volume increase when comparing the entire period. This is illustrated by the high increase in the first 10 years, i.e., red bars, as shown by the changes from October to January. In 2025-2034, the monthly volume difference increases from August to January, with a maximum value in November equal to 4.61 hm³. It seems, therefore, that for the period of the fire, the month most affected is November, whereas in the years 2035-2064, the highest increase is found in October, with a value equal to 3 hm³. Moreover, a remarkable increase occurs in January only in the after-fire period, compared to the other stages. As logical yet identified in this analysis, the transition period, i.e., the green period, shows that the runoff decreases from the after-burn period and tends to reach the baseline values.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This research investigated the long-term hydrological response after wildfires using different restoration periods. The restoration periods were simulated by changing the land cover and characteristics of the basins based on the region's typical flora during the natural regrowth period. What was observed is that while there is a change in runoff after the fire, the percentage of the basin affected by fire, the overall increase is not that significant yearly, but some changes are identified monthly. Nevertheless, the examination of the different phases showed some significant results. Some main points can be summed up as follows:

- Wildfire occurrence tends to increase runoff, illustrated by comparing the average annual volume generated from the baseline scenario to the wildfire scenarios.
- The average annual volume of discharges compared to the baseline was increased by 2.31% for scenario 1, 0.62% for scenario 2, and 2.37% for scenario 3.
- While the annual runoff did not show a significant increase on an average basis, there seems to be a significant monthly variance. Specifically, rain and late summer season months exhibited an increase in runoff, whereas spring months featured a decrease in runoff.

- The increase in runoff depends not only on the area of the basin affected by wildfire but also on other characteristics such as the exact land cover change, i.e., thick forest or sparse vegetation, and, more importantly, the precipitation amount that occurs over the affected regions.
- Annual runoff, even in the scenario with the largest area, did not show a significant increase, but monthly percentage changes showed a significant increase, with months with low runoff, such as summer months, showing the highest increase.
- The months that appear to be most affected are those that receive the highest precipitation amounts, i.e., October through February.
- Examining per restoration period, the higher increase in runoff is observed in the after-burn period, with the winter months, i.e., the months after the fire, exhibiting a higher increase. In contrast, in the transition period, the increase is lowered to values like the baseline scenario

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Acheloos River in Greece: a paradigm for local Governance to achieve Environmental Water Justice

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Abstract

The Acheloos River in Greece, like many others in Europe, represents a socio-physical entity that embodies the intricate relationships between communities and nature. Indeed, rivers' fundamental importance for social and natural well-being around the world is often challenged by mega-damming, pollution, and multiple forms of domesticating that are putting riverine systems under great stress. The reversing of this situation has started across Europe, where numerous examples of dam removal—over 5,000 cases—have occurred and natural ecosystems have been restored, while local communities have been subsequently strengthened in riverine landscapes. In France and the UK, initiatives to protect wetlands and revitalize rivers, such as the Thames, have further reinforced communities' relationships with aquatic ecosystems. The concept of "riverhood" highlights the significance of rivers not only as natural resources but also as carriers of social and ecological values. In recent years, debates about the sustainability and ethics of large-scale river domestication projects have been intensified. Issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and the rights of local communities have become central to discussions about the future of river management. This has led worldwide to a large variety of new water justice movements (NWJMs); the latter are transdisciplinary, multi-actor and multi-scalar coalitions that view rivers not just as a reservoir of flowing water, but rather as a living entity in which nature and humans are ecologically and socio-economically deeply intertwined.

Previous practices used to impose top-down solutions, failing to account for the complexity of the socioecological systems and often separating social and hydrological worlds; this led to the non-inclusion of communities living near the rivers, and to the exacerbation of socio-environmental injustices. The opposition to the Acheloos River diversion is in this direction reflecting the pursuit of environmental justice and sustainable solutions through a bottom-up approach that incorporates the concept of "river solidarity; thus, the importance of participatory management and the protection of rivers as commons is highly emphasized. These initiatives promote environmental justice and empower local communities by fostering new governance models that respect and integrate a holistic relationship between communities and rivers.

Keywords: environmental justice, river commoning, NWJM, environmental heritage

The improvement of the status of hake stocks in the Mediterranean requires effective combinations of tailor-made management

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Abstract

Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*) is among the most important commercial species of demersal fisheries in the Mediterranean Sea, and is a top-predator with important effects on the structure and functioning of the food web of an ecosystem. The species' stocks, exploited by trawl fishing, as well as by longlines and nets operated using small scale fishing (SSF) vessels, are at an overexploited status; in 2022 an updated assessment for the Greek waters of the Ionian Sea (GSA 20) confirmed the overexploited status of the specific stock and suggested the reduction of fishing mortality. We argue, however, that the latter may still be inefficient, as the status of hake stocks can be also affected by its potentially low spawning biomass; indeed, the applied minimum conservation reference size (MCRS) being 20cm, which is usually implemented to protect immature fish and ensure improved spawning success, is well below the species' length-at-first maturity (L_{50}) being >30 cm. Thus, in order to shed more light on the sizes of hake catches by trawlers, which capture a large amount of smaller specimens, we used data from hauls conducted between 2018 and 2023 in the eastern Ionian Sea, as part of the EU Data Collection Framework (DCF) monitoring program of Greek fisheries. We focused on hauls whose hake catches were higher than the 30% of the overall catch, and particularly on the total length (TL) of the captured specimens, recorded by observers on board commercial trawlers. Our findings showed that in the six years of the study in the central part of the Ionian, including the Patraikos Gulf, hauls with high biomass of hakes took place in early winter, coinciding with the period following the lifting of the existing spatiotemporal closure there. Average size of hakes collected in each of those hauls ranged between 20.7 cm (± 3.9 std) and 27.3 cm (± 6.4 std) TL, while a big part of the species' catches was below the MCRS. The same was also true in hauls conducted in northeastern Ionian, where the biomass of hakes peaked (i.e. $>30\%$ of the overall catch) at the end of the winter. The average size of hakes there ranged between 25.3 cm (± 6.6 std) and 35.2 cm (± 15.5 std) TL, and once again a big part of the catch was below 20cm. The above reveal the urgent need for effective combinations of tailor-made management measures rather, than focusing mainly on options for reducing fishing pressure, as considered by Mediterranean authorities. Indeed, in order to ensure improvement of stock status of this important species, the protection of juveniles/immature specimens, as well as spawning ones, is of utmost importance; in this vein, the adoption of a higher MCRS, improved selectivity of trawl and small scale fishing activities targeting the species, and more effective spatiotemporal closures of essential fish habitats should be thoroughly investigated.

Keywords: minimum conservation reference size, length-at-first maturity, juvenile catches, Ionian Sea

Assessment of Water Quality in Muratlı Dam Lake, Turkey Based on Selected Physicochemical Parameters

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Abstract

Turkey has developed numerous hydroelectric power plants (HEPPs) on the Çoruh River, located in Northeast Turkey. It originates in Turkey and flows into the Black Sea at Batumi, Georgia, with several already operational. Many of these HEPP reservoirs are used for salmon farming, producing fish of high quality that is favoured in European and Far Eastern markets. Water quality indices are used to evaluate overall water quality by analyzing various parameters and it is considered that the conditions at Muratlı Dam are also suitable for salmon production. This study assessed therefore the current condition of Muratlı Dam Lake in spring 2024 at five different stations, utilizing physicochemical measurements such as water temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, conductivity, suspended solids, COD, BOD, nitrates, orthophosphate phosphorus, total nitrogen, and total phosphorus, in accordance with APHA standards to see if it is suitable as thought for salmon production. The average pH was determined to be 8.21 ± 0.06 , conductivity 553.58 ± 13.20 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, dissolved oxygen (DO) 8.10 ± 0.54 mg/l, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$ 0.18 ± 0.0210 mg/l, $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$ 0.13 ± 0.002 mg/l, TP 0.34 ± 0.22 mg/l, TN 11.29 ± 0.72 mg/l, chemical oxygen demand (COD) 48.99 ± 1.37 mg/l, and biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) 7.95 ± 1.11 mg/l. The water quality of Muratlı Dam Lake was classified as Class I (temperature, pH, DO, $\text{NO}_3\text{-N}$), Class II (conductivity, $\text{PO}_4\text{-P}$, TN, COD, BOD), and Class III (TP). Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed in R v4.3.2 to demonstrate the relationship between physicochemical parameters, sampling stations, and quality indices. The Water Quality Index (WQI) rated the lake as "Good," while the Pollution Index (ICO) ranged from "Excellent" to "Poor." Trophic status ranged from eutrophic to hypertrophic. Overall, the water quality varied from "Excellent" to "Poor," with trophic conditions spanning from eutrophic to hypertrophic. The findings were also evaluated concerning the potential for salmon cage farming in Muratlı Dam.

Keywords: *Muratlı Dam Lake, water quality, APHA methods, trophic chain, PCA*

***Industrial Symbiosis
and Sustainable Production***

From Waste to Worth: Unlocking Biowaste Potential for Zero Waste and Carbon Neutrality

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Abstract

Advanced biofuels are poised to play a critical role in the renewable energy transition. This presentation showcases key findings and case studies from the LIFE CIRCforBIO project—an energy-driven biorefinery initiative designed to convert municipal and industrial biowaste, as well as agricultural residues, into valuable biofuels and bioenergy, aligning with the principles of a circular bioeconomy. The project employed a structured methodology to evaluate the sustainability and feasibility of various biowaste valorisation pathways. This included feedstock availability assessments, scenario development for both single and mixed feedstocks, and a comprehensive techno-economic analysis (TEA) using a gate-to-gate approach. Capacities were defined to reflect realistic availability and logistics, while technical performance was optimized based on real data and pilot-scale trials conducted within the project framework. Economic viability was assessed through break-even point (BEP) analyses, determining the gate fee required to achieve cost neutrality for each scenario. This standardised approach enabled consistent comparison across feedstocks, while also highlighting the critical role of capacity in scaling and operational feasibility.

Among the feedstocks studied, food waste emerged as the most promising due to its high availability and conversion efficiency. Bakery waste showed the highest bioethanol yield and profitability, although its use is limited by logistical challenges. Spent coffee grounds (SCGs) proved unsustainable under ethanol production routes but showed strong potential when reconfigured to omit this step. Potato peels, while not viable on their own, are part of a broader waste stream with higher-value substrates. Mixed feedstock scenarios—combining food waste, bakery waste, and SCGs—offered scalable and robust solutions adaptable to various capacities. Less viable options such as brewer's spent grains, orange peels, and certain agricultural residues were found economically infeasible in this context. However, they retain potential when diverted to anaerobic digestion (AD) systems for biomethane production.

This study underscores the untapped potential of biowaste streams and advocates for the development of integrated, cascade valorisation schemes. Such systems provide a strategic roadmap away from fossil fuel dependency and towards a zero-waste, carbon-neutral bioeconomy. In addition, the potential for carbon dioxide capture and utilisation (CCU) within the biofuel production chain is explored, reinforcing the role of biorefineries in holistic climate mitigation strategies.

Keywords: *biowaste, biorefinery, biofuels, carbon capture, zero waste approach*

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Transforming and integrating sewage sludge with biochar for enhanced soil applications

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Abstract

The accelerated pace of industrialization and urbanization has led to an increased production of sewage sludge, or biosolids, from wastewater treatment facilities. Despite the high concentrations of phosphorus, nitrogen, and organic matter in these biosolids—making them beneficial for soil enhancement—their use in agriculture and land reclamation is hindered by contamination with toxic compounds, heavy metals, and pathogenic microorganisms. Transforming sewage sludge into biochar offers a viable strategy to mitigate its detrimental effects in agricultural applications. The conversion process significantly reduces the leaching of heavy metals, enhances soil enzymatic activities, and diminishes the bioaccumulation of heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). Biochar's high sorption capacity allows it to effectively bind and immobilize heavy metals and organic pollutants, thus reducing their long-term bioavailability and paving the way for sustainable waste management practices. An additional approach involves the integration of biochar with sewage sludge. This method not only decreases the bioavailability of PAHs and the overall toxicity of sewage sludge but also improves soil nutrient content. By incorporating a biochar-sewage sludge composite into the soil matrix, it is possible to mitigate the environmental impact of contaminants introduced by sewage sludge and considerably enhance soil health through the supplementary nutrients provided by biochar. This study investigates methodologies to harness the beneficial properties of sewage sludge while addressing its limitations, particularly concerning organic pollutants.

Keywords: *sewage sludge, biosolids, contaminants, toxicity, biochar, sustainability*

Assessment of bagasse and vinasse management for the advancement of circular economy in Campos dos Goytacazes' sugro energetic industry

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Abstract

Today, Brazil is the largest sugarcane producer in the world and the second-largest ethanol producer. The sugro energetic industry is a key driver of the country's economic growth and a component of the country's strategy to become independent of the international energy market. However, the expansion of Brazil's sugar industry has also caused significant environmental pollution. This includes contamination of soil, water, air, and a loss of biodiversity. The present research addresses the environmental challenges of the sugro energetic industry using a holistic approach that includes the implementation of sustainable agricultural practices as well as the advancement of technological innovations, and optimized product management. It is based on field studies and data analysis to assess water use efficiency and vinasse management practices of a sugar and bioethanol plant in Campos dos Goytacazes, Brazil. The results show that improvements in water management practices within ethanol production would make the agribusiness more resource-efficient and reduce its environmental impact. This includes reducing the impact caused by vinasse fertigation and decreasing the water footprint of bioethanol production from sugarcane, potentially by up to 34%. Importantly, these water efficiency gains can be achieved without increasing the company's current water withdrawal rates, demonstrating the viability of sustainable water management solutions within the existing operational framework. Using recycled water in industrial processes and transferring current water withdrawal permits from industrial to agricultural use could increase sugarcane crop yields by up to 79%.

Keywords: *circular economy, water and resource management, pollution prevention, energy market, sustainable agricultural practices*

Valorization of lignite fly ash and waste glass into novel nickel-reinforced ceramic composites, under the circularity concept

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Abstract

In the current innovative research, the synthesis process and the characteristics of ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) based on lignite fly ash, waste glass cullet, and a reinforcement phase of nickel (Ni) in particulate form, is investigated in the framework of circular economy.

For this purpose, 5cm diameter disc-shaped specimens were prepared by mixing and pressing the ingredients at 15 tonnes, followed by sintering in an oxygen free atmosphere, at a relatively low temperature (700°C), due to the incorporation of 10%wt glass cullet acting as a fluxing agent. The prepared specimens contained 0 to 30%wt nickel particles. Following the fabrication process, the specimens underwent Vickers micro-hardness tests, electrical conductivity trials with eddy currents and SEM analysis coupled with EDS to extract conclusions for their composition and microstructure.

The experimental results showed that the addition of nickel in the fly ash-based CMCs developed in this work, improve its micro-hardness while all new materials produced are electrically insulating. The findings are discussed on a strong theoretical basis. Experimental results suggest that the new material developed can be used as an improved abrasive or cutting tool or as a durable electrical insulating component among other applications. Moreover, the incorporation of secondary industrial raw materials constitutes the basis of circular economy and industrial symbiosis policies implementation.

Keywords: fly ash, waste glass, nickel particles, ceramic matrix composites, characterization, circular economy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The steady increase of waste produced in recent years creates significant environmental concerns. With the knowledge that many waste materials are harmful to the natural environment and the human body, the adoption of recycling and circular economy becomes more important by the day. The utilization of household and industrial waste can help reduce pollution while the quality of the products produced remains unchanged.

One of the many factors regarding the pollution of the environment is the continuous, widespread use of lignite combustion to produce electricity. This results in massive amounts of fly ash that is difficult to manage and thus is discarded carelessly in the environment.

Although many attempts have been made to find innovative and proper ways to reuse this waste material, little success has been found, and its use is still very limited across the globe. Worldwide, ash production account for 5-20% wt. of lignite consumption, with 75-95% being classified as fly ash, meaning that 500-600 million tons of fly ash are produced worldwide each year (Ahmaruzzaman, 2010; Yao et al., 2015). Global utilization of fly ash is around 25%, with 20% of the ash used being used for the production of concrete and building materials (Yao et al., 2015).

Another common and valuable waste material is glass. What makes it so wanted is its high content in silicon, its useful mechanical and physical properties as well as its ease to be separated (Karayannis et al., 2017; Shakhova et al., 2018). With that in mind, it is clear that glass can be reused in many ways, including manufacture of bricks and tiles, as a thermal and acoustic insulation material, for ceramic decorative products as well as for porcelains and glazes. It can also be used as a catalyst, an adsorbent, a component in resins and elastomers, an abrasive and for the production of fiberglass and glass fibers. It is also widely used as a building material for the production of cement and concrete and lastly as a binder or an aggregate (Karamberi et al., 2007; Karamberi & Moutsatsou, 2007; Karayannis et al., 2017; Silva et al., 2017). It should be noted that by using 10% recycled glass in the glass manufacturing industry, energy consumption can be reduced by up to 3% (Cetin, 2023; Silva et al., 2017). It was also found that the release of one ton of CO₂ can be avoided by recycling six tons of glass waste that ends up in landfills (Silva et al., 2017).

The objective of this research is to propose a new, innovative ceramic matrix composite material (CMC) that has a matrix derived from the above common waste material, increasing their consumption, which will be beneficial both from the environmental and economical point of view. As a reinforcing phase, nickel in particulate form has been added in various amounts to the matrix in order to study its effects on the electrical conductivity and hardness of the material.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The temperature at which the sintering of fly ash takes place can generally be said to be between 800-1200°C. This variation is due to criteria such as its composition, sintering time and additives in it (Biernacki et al., 2008; Pimraksa et al., n.d.; Sawunyama et al., 2024; Karayannis et al., 2017). Contrary, glass cullet begins to soften at around 650°C, a much lower temperature than most ceramic materials. This makes it suitable for addition to CMCs as an agent to improve heat flow between the components and matrix particles. Therefore, it is expected to improve the temperature and time of sintering, while also improving the physical and mechanical properties of the composite (Karamberi & Moutsatsou, 2007; Karayannis et al., 2017).

The addition of nickel particles to a ceramic matrix has been observed to increase electrical and thermal conductivity when nickel amounts above 20% by volume are contained in the samples (Anwar et al., 2021). As has been reported, this is due to the creation of a connected network within the matrix when such amounts are exceeded. However, the main reason for their addition is to increase the mechanical properties in fracture and bending as well as hardness (Fahrenholtz et al., 2000; Khlaisongkhram et al., 2023; Konopka et al., 2011; Sekino et al., 1997; Wang et al., n.d.).

To briefly explain the mechanism of increasing the strength of ceramic matrices by addition of metallic ductile particles, when a crack reaches a metal inclusion, the particle absorbs a significant portion of its energy as it deforms plastically, thus protecting the brittle ceramic matrix. The above mechanism depends significantly on the type, size and distribution of the metal particles as well as their bonding state with the matrix and the fabrication method of the composite (Fahrenholtz et al., 2000; Kolhe' et al., 1996; Konopka, 2015; Konopka et al., 2011). At this point it should also be mentioned that in temperature ranges of 500-1400°C metallic nickel oxidizes, although its resistance to oxidation is excellent among metals, a fact that had to be taken in consideration during the fabrication of the samples of this research (Haugsrud, n.d.; Wang et al., n.d.).

2.1 Fabrication

For the experiments, a total of four CMC specimens, named M1-4 for convenience, were prepared with different contents of Ni particles as listed in the table below in detail.

Table 1. Composition of samples by weight.

Sample Name	Fly Ash	Glass Cullet	Nickel
M1	90%	10%	0%
M2	80%	10%	10%
M3	70%	10%	20%
M4	60%	10%	30%

The raw materials used for the preparation of their matrix are similar to those reported by Karayannis et al. In summary, the fly ash came from the Megalopolis power plant and has a weight content of SiO₂ equal to 51.26% and CaO equal to 12.77%. In addition, it has a specific gravity of 2.50 g/cm³, a specific surface area of 3.87 m²/g, an average pore diameter of 165.1 (Å) and a pore volume of 0.016 cm³/g. The glass cullet came from grinding recycled glass for 10 minutes. Its composition is listed in detail in the table below.

Table 2. Chemical composition of glass cullet by weight.

Compound	Content (%)
SiO ₂	70,6
Al ₂ O ₃	1,75
K ₂ O	0,55
MgO	2,45
CaO	10,7
Na ₂ O	13,25
SO ₃	0,45
Fe ₂ O ₃	0,45

After the necessary quantities of raw materials for the preparation of each specimen were calculated and weighed, they were mixed so that they had the most uniform distribution possible. At this point, it should be mentioned that due to the high density of Ni, its

percentage by volume in each specimen is significantly lower than its percentage by weight. Firstly, for their solidification, the ingredients were pressed at 15 tons to form the green specimens which were placed in an oven with an inert atmosphere to avoid oxidizing the nickel while sintering. Then, the specimens were preheated to 550°C for 1 hour in order to burn off any amounts of residual carbon in the fly ash and glass cullet. Finally, the temperature was raised to 700°C at a moderate rate of 10°C/min due to the low thermal conductivity of fly ash to avoid significant temperature gradients between the surface and the interior that could lead to the development of stresses and endanger the integrity of the specimens. They remained at that temperature for 2 hours before being left to cool freely to ambient temperature.

The final specimens have a disc shape with a diameter of 5cm and a thickness of 8mm. These dimensions apply to both the green and final CMCs, so no significant shrinkage of their dimensions was observed during their sintering. Also, the color of the CMCs was gray to brown and as the amount of nickel increased their color became lighter and shinier. Finally, although they were hard, there were surface cracks, which indicates their brittle behavior, and they easily lost quantities of fly ash with friction.

2.2 Microstructural examination

In order to study the microstructure of the samples, a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis was employed. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was also performed to determine the composition of the material.

Figure 1. Photographs of specimens inside the chamber from the SEM camera. M1 (Top left), M2 (Top right), M3 (Bottom left), M4 (Bottom right).

Figure 2. SEM and EDS layered micrograph images of the four specimens.

2.3 Electrical conductivity assessment

The eddy current method was used to measure the electrical conductivity of the material. The purpose of the method is to compare the changes in the peaks of the resonance curves of the samples with those of the isolated coil. To achieve this, the four specimens were placed in the experiment setup of figure below. For the measurement, the Agilent 4294a Impedance Analyzer is used via LabVIEW software.

Figure 3. The eddy current experiment setup.

The coil that was used has the following specifications:

- Small diameter (d) = 1 mm
- Large diameter (D) = 3.07 mm
- Height (H) = 1 mm
- Number of turns (N) = 119
- Wire diameter = 0.08 mm

The probe positioning far away from the samples edges to avoid any influence of the edge effect. The experimental configuration is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Specimen and probe configuration.

Finally, the two diagrams that were created from the measurements can be seen below.

Figure 5. Coil resistance diagram as a function of test frequency.

Figure 6. Coil inductance diagram as a function of test frequency.

2.4 Hardness assessment

The hardness of the specimens was measured using the Vickers method during which a load equal to 9,807 N (HV1) was applied for a period of 20 sec to the surface of each specimen and the following diagram was created.

Figure 7. Diagram of hardness change as a function of the amount of Ni particles (% wt).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure of specimens

The SEM images of Figure 2 confirm that the fly ash contains quantities of calcium (Ca) greater than 20% by weight. At the same time, quantities of unburned carbon (C), sulfur (S) and metals such as iron (Fe) and aluminum (Al) are observed that can be categorized as impurities. The above metal compounds are in the form of oxides, which justifies the enormous amount of uniformly dispersed oxygen (O) in the samples. At the same time, the SEM photographs show that the microstructure of the samples is uniform for all compounds in general. The only compound that seems to create systematic aggregates is silicon (Si), which can be attributed to the presence of glass fragments.

3.2 Effects of Ni particles reinforcement on the electrical conductivity

As is evident from the diagrams of Figures 5 and 6, despite the size of the axis values, the differences of the samples compared to the pure coil are minimal to the extent that they are not significant. This indicates that with the increase in the amount of Ni particles, the electrical conductivity remains the same. This is due to the fact that, while the Ni particles are more electrically conductive compared to the matrix, they are not present in sufficient quantity to affect it. Specifically, while by weight they reach up to 30%, by volume, due to the high density of nickel, they are present in a much lower percentage, certainly below the 20% required to create a continuous phase and therefore a change in the electrical properties.

3.3 Effects of Ni particles reinforcement on the hardness

As can be understood from the diagram of Figure 7, the increase in the amount of nickel particles increases the hardness of the material. Specifically, the specimen M1 consisting only

of fly ash and cullet has a hardness equal to 40.6 HV1. With the addition of 10% by weight of nickel (M2) it increases to 56.7 HV1. The increase continues for M3 and M4 where the hardness was found to be 66.4 HV1 and 75.8 HV1 respectively. This trend confirms the operation of the crack absorption mechanism by ductile particles as described previously.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The CMC materials produced had improved properties compared to the matrix material. They have a uniform microstructure, and the addition of nickel particles had the expected reinforcing results, in addition to improving electrical conductivity, which makes it remain an insulating material. The hardness increased but overall, it remains a brittle material that needs further optimization research.

Based on the theoretical and studied characteristics of CMC, some suggestions for practical applications can be made. Initially, its improved hardness could allow it to be applied as an abrasive or cutting medium. Also, due to its general chemical, thermal and physical characteristics, it could be further examined for use in environments of high non-mechanical requirements such as in protective coatings, as a catalyst carrier or as a sensor component. At the same time, it could be integrated into electronic systems as a durable insulating material. Finally, an important feature of the CMC is its ability to be manufactured from materials that come from secondary sources, which can allow to find applications in many sectors as a substitute for non-environmentally friendly materials. Firstly, it increases the consumption of fly ash, which is its main starting material, thus reducing its harmful discharge into the environment. Also, glass cullet derived from recycled materials helps in the utilization of secondary resources which is an important part of the circular economy and the conservation of natural and energy resources. Finally, nickel particles can be obtained from industrial waste reducing the extraction of nickel.

However, there are also challenges remaining. In particular, beyond its production and optimization on an industrial scale, poor management of the individual components can be problematic for the environment if not carried out correctly. Its use as a means of managing such substances can become the subject of future research for further development and application of the material. Also, recycling after its life cycle, can be a complex issue due to the nature of the CMC.

Overall, it can be said that with proper and careful behavior, this type of material can contribute significantly to the circular economy. It is a good alternative option for the management of multiple waste whose recycling is either difficult or occurs to an insufficient extent.

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Improving sustainable production in construction: Field studies in current issues and end-user needs in IT Document Management

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Abstract

All management systems, no matter how innovative or strictly governed by formal standards, have to accommodate the needs of end-users in order to be successful and helpful. Increased demands for social benefits, sustainable methods of production in all industrial sectors and respect towards the planet's resources, have brought the need to place people and not system requirements, as the top priority for the design of information systems. In order to examine current needs and concerns of construction personnel and to verify the conclusions of previous academic research, a targeted field study was carried out with experts from multidisciplinary academic backgrounds. Current progress in the adoption of information systems and their effectiveness is examined, together with findings in user system requirements. Observations range from on-site administration at operational level, to project management teams at tactical level and to headquarters for strategic planning. According to both academic research and conducted field studies, improved project communication can lead to significant savings and competitive advantage. Although many communication problems remain unresolved, by analyzing the suggestions of executives and engineers who man such systems, a truly human-centered evolution of communication methods can be made possible.

Keywords: *sustainable production, construction project management, documents management, implementation of innovative systems, information management*

1. INTRODUCTION

No management system, even if governed by the strictest quality standards, is complete without primarily ensuring the needs of the personnel that it serves [1]. At the same time the quality and environmental balance together with the safety issues during the implementation process of modern projects, as described in *ISO 14001:2015* [2] and *ISO 9000:2015* [3] are now steadily converging with the goals established with the EU green policy [4]. All of the above, combined with the increased social demand for project implementation that protects the planet's resources, have brought the need to place people, that is, users and not the procedures, at the top of the hierarchy for the design of information systems. The so-called fifth industrial revolution is the springboard for the Construction 5.0 movement, which attempts to address the most important issues that characterize technical projects with a

holistic approach [5]. These include problems created for people inside and outside the construction industry, the negative impact on the environment and the social value of each production process, putting profits and financial indicators second in line [6].

To adopt the principles of current digital business management, also known as the fourth industrial revolution, manufacturing companies should focus on integrating new technologies to expand competitive advantage and improve environmental performance [7]. Modern construction engineering procedures are now redesigned on principles of both resource efficiency and pollution prevention. The application of modern Information Technology (IT) systems can contribute greatly in achieving this goal, as most environmental considerations can only be solved by corporate commitment to adopting operational innovations [8]. Significant savings can be reached by implementing an IT document management system to organize project information, co-ordinate communications and support supply chain and inventory management decisions [9]. The transition to such centralized IT procedures is impossible to take place without putting civil needs in the center of managerial efforts and thus investigating their demands [10].

The architecture of IT and document management systems, in general, are usually designed by mapping communication channels and standard procedures defined by regulations or quality policies. Research that focuses on the demands and views of the users is usually based on statistical analysis of questionnaires or fixed sets of questions, without much freedom of spontaneous answers. Most of the time, these studies are carried out within the operational and tactical levels of the project teams. Research inside the strategic organizational level, is not extensive when considering the field of information and documents management. Therefore, in order to examine possible unrecorded needs and concerns of the end-users and to verify the conclusions of previous academic review, a targeted field study was carried out with experienced managers of the construction industry. Experts from a multidisciplinary academic background and at top organizational levels of the project hierarchy were preferred so that in addition to many years of experience, their duties combine both technical and staff tasks [11]. Investigated sites include high-budget international projects, with multidisciplinary contributors and stakeholders from different national and cultural backgrounds. Thus, certain study findings can apply to similar projects globally and should be considered when examining project information management techniques.

2. METHODS

Conclusions drawn from previous academic review and literature are included after the main findings in the interviews, when applicable. In this way, verification and cross-referencing are sought through the field study process. In addition, possible benefits of using a system like the proposed one are explored, but also the interviewees' suggestions in the design of future document management systems. The professional experience and variety in the perspectives of the examination contributed significantly to the verification of research findings, but also to the summary of less-heard valuable opinions and useful suggestions. For a first assessment of the main interview questions, the expected length of each interview and to identify any omissions, two preliminary pilot interviews were conducted with one participant at a time. The selection of the points covered by the interview questions was made after the analysis of previous studies and the academic review [12].

2.1 Information collection methodology

Open-ended questions and personal interviews were conducted, in order to cover all issues under consideration as much as possible, but with flexibility to change wording, the order of questions and the ability to provide additional personal comments. The method of face-to-face interviews was preferred, due to the immediacy and familiarity required for the participants to cover each topic in depth and as comprehensively as possible [13].

The purpose of the field study interviews is to investigate the state of documents communication in construction, taking into account the interviewee's perspective and perceptions. The view on current progress in digital transformation, the benefits of using such systems, but also the possible barriers to their introduction offer important insights. The suggestions and ideas mentioned are a useful basis for the requirements of the stakeholders from IT project coordination and should be included in future system design principles.

For the pilot interviews, face-to-face interviews were not possible due to distance, and thus one was conducted by telephone and the other online, as the best alternative methods. Interviewees were selected based on experience and relevance of their managerial position and offered to participate after being contacted by phone. The net duration of the interviews varied between 37 and 65 minutes. The interviews took place between Thursday, May 30 and Tuesday, October 1, 2024.

2.2 Main parts of discussion

Open-ended questions were used so that respondents could answer as freely as possible [14]. For the best logical analysis of the answers and in order to serve the purposes of the research, questions asked were grouped into three thematic sections. The first section includes familiarization questions as well as questions regarding the demographic and statistical characteristics that were deemed necessary [15]. The answers allow the respondents to be categorized according to gender, work experience, educational level and current employment. To ensure data integrity, each interviewee's name and position in the employing organization is also requested. The second section includes questions that examine the current situation in the exchange of construction project documents and its implications. This section is the main part of the research process. Its purpose is to gather information on the experience of industry executives to date, regarding the performance of existing document management systems and potential weaknesses. Finally, the third section brings together the answers regarding the need for an information system and its characteristics. In this section, the questions are specialized in the proposals for the characteristics of the System, issues of the personnel who handle it, but also causes that make it difficult to adopt information systems.

In order to maximize the spontaneity of the responses and not to direct the thinking of the interviewed participants, all questions were open-ended and the interviewees were not asked to indicate the degree of agreement or disagreement, with responses on an ordered scale [16, 17]. The reason is that ordered responses can tend to subconsciously guide and in some cases force respondents to support, even slightly, one of the two options towards the extremes of the rating [18]. To inform the participants about the subject, before the field study was conducted, an introductory letter was sent to them about the purpose and privacy of the research. All findings and suggestions mentioned during the interviews, can be used as guidelines taken into account during the design stages for the architecture of new IT systems.

2.3 Brief demographic and statistical information

Participants included seventeen executives of both sexes that have answered all questions in a series of open-type interviews. In order to cover as many issues as possible, interviewees were selected according to extensive administrative, technical and legal training, with work experience that covers most of construction sectors and their support services, in complex and prominent projects. Academic backgrounds include mostly scientists such as architects, interior designers, mechanical engineers, civil engineers as well as lawyers and social science graduates. Ages ranged from thirty-six (36) to sixty-seven (67) years, on the day of the interviews and working experience ranged from thirteen to over thirty-five years in the building industry, technical companies, design offices and legal support companies for construction projects.

Projects that the interviewees have been employed on so far, were classified according to the BRE categorization [19] and include leisure projects such as hotels and casinos, industrial buildings and units, public buildings, schools and training facilities, commercial buildings such as offices and shops, as well as residential developments.

All participants gained professional experience in private sector projects and the majority in public sector projects as well. The field study participants academic background includes holders of doctoral and master's degrees, as well as university graduates with various administrative positions as displayed in Figure 1, sorted by discipline. Conclusions from the interviews, after being grouped by topic, are summarized in the following parts of the paper by area of interest. Important conclusions that are verified from both findings of the interviews and academic review, are followed by indicative sources where mentioned.

Figure 1. Field study participants' administrative duties sorted by discipline.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Current progress in the adoption of modern information systems

Currently there has been some adoption and use of systems that aggregate project information, but with fragmented or limited implementation across the sector. In major construction sites, or where companies that undertake larger and usually complex projects are involved, document management principles and standards are indeed applied. But these mainly concern *ISO* and quality standards, such as certifications from *TÜV SÜD* or management of contractual issues and legal documents.

Innovative technologies are applied in distinguished construction sites such as in the recreation of *Ellinikon*, currently the largest construction project in Europe [20]. To a large extent, however, these were introduced because there are pioneer companies from abroad and within the country that are involved, such as *Bouygues Batiment International*, the British design office *Fosters* and their joint venture with the construction company *Intrakat* [21]. In everyday life and on construction sites, there is no centralized management of documents and information. Adherence to the schedule of small and medium projects and the organization of information is based on experience and on-site planning.

Larger companies usually have an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system to support management decisions, along with an accounting or logistics software that serves finance and supply chain departments. Although these systems support a wide range of operational functions and capabilities [22], there is rarely a unified system that deals with the overall organization of information, regardless of whether it is manufacturing or administrative information.

It is also reported that even when ERP systems exist, these seem to satisfy formal obligations or specifications, such as reasons for compliance with *ISO* standards, without any substantial further exploitation of the data accumulated. Even the largest projects do not systematically use information systems for the organization of everyday life administration. The usefulness of the introduction of Building Information Management (BIM) technologies, while now realized by many companies in the sector, is carried out at a slow pace and does not solve all the problems of information transmission, but mainly design issues and associated conflicts.

In small and medium construction enterprises, information systems are often not used at all, especially at tactical and operational levels of building projects, such as subcontractors, production management departments and suppliers. It is reported that the majority considers such systems a waste of time or ignore the procedures of entering the necessary data in order to structure and operate management software.

Personnel does not have the time or resources to make the most of existing, non-interoperable systems, or even to employ to a greater extent than at present, although the means are already provided by technology. In this way, manufacturing speed is reduced, but often so is the quality of the final product, due to the deficiencies in documentation and organization of the information required for production planning [23].

Despite any initial disadvantages or disturbance brought about by the introduction of innovative technologies, current IT communication channels, even in parallel, have facilitated improvements in the organization of information. Success depends on the will or ability of each user to manage available information and incorporate new practices and technologies into the production process. The global dimensions that the supply chain has acquired, dictate

that the need for developing of practices that improve communications with partners from different countries has to be considered. Introducing a centralized project information management system is a foundation for the development of this international dimension.

3.2 The effectiveness of communicating documents with currently available means

All participants in the field study confirm that the communication of information is a complex process and often problematic. Any information required is usually not immediately available unless sought by, thus consuming administrative resources of the organization itself or the group that seeks the document containing the necessary data. In this way, however, the cost of finding information is transferred to the operational cost of the project.

Although it is verified that almost the entire documentation for each project ends up being contained in a digital file and rarely in printed form, the information contained is not disseminated in the communication ecosystem of the projects. The basic functions of managing documents and the information contained in them are impaired in terms of actual control and organization of data, as well as document planning and timely distribution, reducing the effectiveness of communications [24].

The existence of many different departments and work groups and the constant need to modify and update data are cited as causes of communication failures. Without perfect coordination and communication, the desired result is rarely achieved immediately. In addition, the focus of each team or organization exclusively on the small piece of procured work or on what project items need to be delivered immediately, results in a very specific and limited scope of information exchange, especially in larger projects.

Although today's technology provides great possibilities through available devices, applications and the internet, it does not solve communication problems completely. There are already applications available that can assist personnel from on-site management to headquarters administration and the supply chain. The average construction manager is still unfamiliar with the process of communicating information to multiple people, but also not recording it so that it is always available. Facing time pressure of everyday life, many members of the project team, both in private and public projects, lose the ability to monitor and therefore to gain thorough knowledge for expert information management.

Paperwork has not been eliminated from the construction industry, despite technological advances. It coexists and at the same time feeds the electronic bureaucracy, exacerbating the problem of isolated, parallel communication channels. In some cases, the accumulation of written forms is created purely out of habit. Printed designs are particularly reported being piled up without ever being used. The phenomenon is multiplied by the outdated sense of standard procedure that drawings, from the contractual version and on are being printed, although these already exist in electronic form with all the browsing benefits provided by digital imaging.

3.3 User requirements for effective information management

The following requirements for effective information administration emerged as suggestions from interviewed personnel and can serve as guidelines in the design of basic system architecture, when considering the introduction or customization of document management systems.

The most important features suggested are the immediate notification of changes and, at the same time, the need for updated information and documents in which it is recorded to be

as immediately and easily available as possible. An active, up-to-date database is needed, which provides in an easy way, and therefore with a simple interface, the possibility for each user to obtain the required information. A key requirement is the simultaneous notification of all interested parties at the time of each modification or posting of updated documents. The possible applicability to both private and public sector projects is an important factor to be considered.

Time saving is possible at all organizational levels by having an active database linked to a repository of all project documents, which is updated constantly. The ability to search all types of documents, especially those related to accounting, such as invoices and delivery notes, is crucial so that quantities which are to be ordered, received and stored are correctly updated. In this way, inventory management processes are simplified, waste is reduced [25] and economies of scale are achieved by the purchase of materials in bulk orders.

Even with a rudimentary ability to display available stocks in critical materials, an IT system provides solutions to permanent staff needs. By updating quantities, in combination with a correlation per invoice and budget article, useful statistics can be extracted. By combining these statistics and stored project history, a demand forecast for materials and services can be issued. This forecast can be submitted for approval to the relevant project team members or logistics executives, regarding the type of procurement to be carried out, but also as a forecast and estimate of when each task must be carried out. The rapidly evolving applications of artificial intelligence are a technology for which a centralized document management system is an ideal field of application.

The interface and organization of IT systems employed must be characterized by simplicity and ease of learning and use. For effective usage as an inventory database, as well as for document submission, data entry needs to be done promptly and in an understandable way, that is not more complex than necessary. However, younger users tend to accept the need to spend more time learning an innovative system than older personnel.

Plans and documents kept in the document repository, in addition to the ability of intervention and correction, also provide a large amount of useful data about project evolution. By adding interoperability, graphics, drawings and BIM files, document management systems can exchange information with ERP-type systems, aiding strategic and tactical business decision-making and the exploitation of corporate intelligence. In this way, a basis is built for the development and management of corporate knowledge and a historical archive of complete previous project data that can be utilized by data mining techniques. In the near future, the introduction of modern artificial intelligence applications may offer automated suggestions for better production management, implementation sequences and schedule adherence, even pre-measurements or forecasts of order placements and material quantities.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In an effort to improve project communication in the construction industry, numerous technological applications have gone through all stages of development and implementation in recent decades. The realization that optimizing information management provides a competitive advantage [26] has steadily increased the widespread use of modern technologies and available mobile devices during the implementation phase of building projects. As a

result, the development of applications for better management of project information and documents has significantly increased. These include both construction and information management systems which provide required files, such as drawings and BIM files. However, communication problems remain largely unresolved.

Table 1. Main study findings sorted by field of interest, in an alphabetical order

Field of Interest	Main Findings
Current progress in the introduction of modern information systems:	Adoption and use of systems specifically in major or distinguished construction sites, but with fragmented or limited implementation across the sector, focused on quality standards or formal regulations.
	Existing corporate systems (usually ERP) are rarely unified in a single centralized system that coordinates overall organization of information.
	In small and medium projects adherence to time schedule and information dissemination is based on personnel experience and short-term on-site planning.
	No existing centralized management of documents and information for everyday tasks in the majority of construction sites.
	Personnel does not make the most of existing systems, especially when these are non-interoperable.
	Small and medium construction enterprises lack information systems at tactical and operational levels.
Current effectiveness of communicating documents:	Although practically the entire project documentation is contained in digital files, information contained is not disseminated effectively within the communication ecosystem.
	Construction management and administrative personnel are still unfamiliar with the process of data entry and communicating documents to multiple people, reducing information availability.
	Documents containing required information are not immediately available unless sought by, consuming administrative resources.
	Paperwork has not been eliminated, coexisting and multiplying digital bureaucracy, exacerbating the problem of isolated and parallel communication channels.
	The existence of many different contributors simultaneously, in combination with the constant need to modify and update data are cited as causes of serious communication failures.
System requirements for effective information management:	Applicability to both private and public sector projects.
	Immediate notification of changes and availability of corresponding updated documents.
	Inventory and procurement management capabilities, with the provision for AI employment.
	Live, up-to-date database is required, employing a user-friendly interface characterized by ease of learning.
	Maintenance of an active searchable repository of all project documents, constantly updated.
	Simultaneous automated notification of all interested parties at the time of each modification or posting of updated documents.
	Straightforward data entry procedures that are not more complex than necessary.

To achieve a truly human-centered evolution of communication methods in construction, the reported experiences and suggestions (summarized in Table 1 above) of executives and personnel who manage the document systems must be recorded and analyzed systematically. Observations must extend from on-site administration at operational level, to project management teams at tactical level and to headquarters for strategic planning.

Rigid technocratic approaches that have been applied for the development of system architecture have been based on strictly administrative criteria and have failed in the normalization of information management. With the rising need to place people and the environment at the center of corporate development and technical innovation [27], the transition to new forms of production is possible. These revolve around respect to social impacts, personnel safety and health, while at the same time protecting natural resources and reducing pollutant emissions. Systems that lead to waste prevention and reduction are especially critical to the European Commission's Green Deal policies, making research on the field more relevant than ever.

The construction industry can be thus shielded against future legislative and technological challenges, converging with citizen demands and the expectations for modernization of its methods and people. Rapid industrial changes, the intensifying global competition and changes in production and communication methods, make the need for innovations in document management [28] one of the most influential factors on the evolution of construction management.

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3D Printing and Topology Optimization: Assessing Key Sustainability Aspects

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Abstract

The construction industry faces growing challenges in improving efficiency, reducing material waste, and minimizing environmental impact, as traditional methods often raise sustainability concerns. In response, innovative and alternative construction techniques have emerged in recent years, offering new opportunities for progress and the integration of sustainable solutions. Among these, additive manufacturing, commonly known as 3D printing, is gaining ground in this competitive sector, presenting a promising solution for achieving material efficient and sustainable design. This process is based on the sequential addition of materials to define the final geometry. 3D printing technology is revolutionizing the construction industry by offering unlimited design flexibility, improved functionality and significant reductions in material usage, costs and time. Topology optimization enables the creation of lightweight structures with optimal mechanical properties, reducing material usage while maintaining performance. With the integration of 3D printing technology in conjunction with topology optimization, it is possible to achieve up to a 60% reduction in volume. The aim of this study is to carry out a comprehensive investigation of key sustainability aspects and challenges associated with this method. The present research discusses the aforementioned aspects through a finite element analysis and a cradle-to-gate life cycle analysis of a 3D printed wall in comparison to a conventional wall. The findings provide insights into the potential for these technologies to contribute to sustainable design and highlight areas for future research and development.

Keywords: *sustainability, 3D printing, construction, FEM, LCA*

Study of the removal of the herbicide metribuzin from aqueous solutions by using organic hydrogels

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Abstract

Hydrogels are hydrophilic three-dimensional polymer networks, able to sorb water and swell, increasing several times their original volume, but they are not dissolved in water due to chemical crosslinking. Depending on the nature of the structural units, swelling of these gels can be activated by several external stimuli, such as solvent, heat, pH, electric stimuli. Therefore, these materials are attractive for several applications in a variety of fields: drug delivery, hosts of nanoparticles and semiconductors, etc. Of special interest is the application of hydrogels for water purification, since they can effectively sorb several water-soluble pollutants. In the present work UV-vis spectrophotometry and High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) are applied to investigate the sorption of the triazin herbicide metribuzin (MEB) by hydrogels based on sodium acrylate (ANa), either homopolymerized (poly(sodium acrylate), PANA) or copolymerized (P(DMAM-co-ANa)) with N,N-dimethylacrylamide (DMAM). The nonionic hydrogel of the homopolymer poly(N,N-dimethylacrylamide), PDMAM, is also used for reasons of comparison. The removal of MEB from aqueous solution by the hydrogels was studied as a function of time, initial concentration of MEB, and sorbent dosage. It is seen that the efficiency of the sorption of metribuzin decreases with the charged density of the hydrogel chains. The maximum sorption of MEB molecules occurs at initial concentration of 50 mg·L⁻¹. Langmuir sorption isotherm model fits the data well with high regression constant value whereas the maximum sorption capacity (Q_{max}) was calculated at 20 mg·g⁻¹.

Keywords: hydrogels, sorption, Metribuzin, HPLC, Langmuir isotherm

Application of nano-magnetite-chitosan adsorbent for removal of emerging contaminants in different environmental media

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Abstract

The environment, especially natural waters, is affected daily by anthropogenic pollution. Even discharges of maximum-permissible-concentration (MPC) [1] of heavy metals with wastewaters or trace amounts of radionuclides can irreversibly affect the environment integrity [2, 3]. Moreover, these contaminants can migrate and bioaccumulate within the food chains, ultimately threatening human health [4]. One of the most effective purification methods is adsorption using various sorbents, and their improvement requires thorough research. This study aims to determine the sorption parameters of synthesized nano-magnetite-chitosan (MCN), investigate its effects on aquatic organisms to assess their environmental safety and evaluate their effectiveness in various water systems for heavy metal removal. XRD, SEM, FTIR and Mössbauer methods were used for the characterization of the synthesized MCN sorbents and their changes during sorption experiments. Sorption kinetics and isothermal calculations of MCN were carried out based on laboratory sorption experiments using Cu (II), Ni (II) and Cr (III) solutions. Following the evaluation of sorbent efficiency, the effects on *Danio rerio* will be investigated. The sorption efficiency of MCN's were examined in Balsys Lake, river Neris and Baltic Sea water samples with the addition of ¹⁵²Eu (III) and ⁶⁰Co (II) radionuclides as tracers. The Gamma-spectroscopy was used for the determination of traced radionuclides concentrations and the ICP-OES for heavy metals. Obtained results suggest that MCN can be considered as an effective adsorbent for contaminant removal with the preservation of environmental integrity that is provided by magnetic separation or collection. Moreover, since MCN is a modified biodegradable polymer and its composition should not actually negatively affect the environment of use, and in cases of non-separation from it, MCN decomposes - this makes it an eco-friendly and green adsorbent.

Keywords: *magnetic chitosan, nanomagnetite, sorption efficiency, biological parameters, ecotoxicity*

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Valorization of Brewery Spent Grain through Chitin Extraction from Black Soldier Fly Larvae

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Abstract

Organic waste, such as solid kitchen residues and crop-by products, represents an opportunity for valorization through bioconversion. Insects, particularly the larvae of *Hermetia illucens* (Black Soldier Fly Larvae, BSFL), are highly efficient in converting organic matter into value-added by-products. This insect is highly adapted to organic residues and grows rapidly under optimal conditions. Thus, the by-products that can be obtained from BSFL are oil for the production of biofuels (biodiesel and green diesel), as well as protein, amino acids and chitin [1]–[4] — a biopolymer with different uses in the industrial sector. This by-product recovery encourages the principles of circular economy [5]. This work analyses the performance in the extraction of chitin. In addition, the spectrum of BSFL chitin was qualitatively analyzed.

The method for the extraction of chitin was carried following a methodology similar to the one described in [4], using the centrifugation method (1500 rpm at 15 min) for filtration after demineralization and deproteinization. In the demineralization process, 1 M HCl with a 1:10 m/v ratio was used, using 10 grams of BSFL sample with operating conditions of 100 °C with a duration of 30 min. Likewise, for the deproteinization process, 1 M NaOH was used at a temperature of 80 °C for 24 hrs. The filtration process yielded chitin with a significantly higher efficiency compared to the yield reported by [4] using prepupal stage larvae of BSFL, with a yield of 13.9 ± 0.12 % chitin. On the other hand, in the Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis was used to qualitatively analyze the chitin structure, with spectral similarity to those reported by [4], [6], [7].

These findings highlight the potential for a comprehensive use of the *Hermetia illucens* within a circular economy framework.. Likewise, areas of opportunity include quantitative analysis of the chitin to determine its purity, and a life cycle assessment to estimate potential reductions in greenhouse gas emissions from future BSFL-based biorefineries. Experimental work for the further valorisation of spent BSFL is also underway.

Keywords: *hermetia illucens*, circular economy, bioproducts.

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The NEO-CYCLE approach to circularity: upcycling NdFeB permanent magnets from waste of electrical and electronic equipment

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Abstract

Waste recycling and reuse is crucial for reducing environmental impacts and contributing to circular economy goals. Next to this, resource dependency, particularly that of critical materials, could be reduced if valuable materials and elements are upcycled. Waste of electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) is acknowledged to be one of the fastest growing waste streams and could serve as a secondary source for valuable elements. However, recycling and reuse of particular elements from WEEE is limited due to the lack of technology. The Horizon Twin transition project NEO-CYCLE (2024 – 2028) strives to fill this gap and to provide innovative technologies for sustainable upcycling neodymium–iron–boron (NdFeB) permanent magnets from hard disk drives (laptops, recorders, desktops) for high quality end products in pharmaceutical, ammonia, fertilizers and polymers industries. The project will demonstrate solid-state chlorination and electrochemical processes for separation of Nd, Fe and B as well as purification techniques. Furthermore, the upcycling of Nd, Fe, and B will lead to the validation of end products across four distinct applications. Digitalisation of processes and products for better monitoring and optimization will be employed, including digital twins and digital product passport. In addition, LCA, LCC, s-LCA, circularity, energy - efficiency and techno-economic assessments will showcase various aspects of processes and products sustainability contributing to the risk minimization, performance improvement and, finally, business model development for market uptake of project results. Such comprehensive framework will provide breakthrough solution for green and digital transition, involving relevant actors across value chain and addressing multiple sustainability challenges and EU policies.

Keywords: NdFeB magnets, upcycling, WEEE, sustainability, circularity.

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DMAIC-driven improvements in optical lens inspection equipment for production efficiency and sustainability

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Abstract

This study enhanced optical lens inspection efficiency using the DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, and Control) methodology. SIPOC (Suppliers, Inputs, Process, Outputs, and Customers) analysis was used to identify light source, inspection points, and Z-axis movement as key factors. DOE (Design of experiments) was carried out to demonstrate the optimal parameters: LED light source, 20 inspection points, and 0mm Z-axis movement. Results included a 6% reduction in inspection time, a 10.1% increase in capacity, a 92% improvement in equipment performance, and an 80% reduction in energy consumption. The study supports global sustainability goals by lowering carbon footprint and simplifying workflows, offering the actionable insights for the modern high-precision manufacturing systems.

Keywords: *optical lens, DMAIC (Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve and Control), DOE (Design of Experiment), production efficiency, sustainability*

INTRODUCTION

Optical lenses have become critical components across industries such as consumer electronics, automotive applications, and emerging virtual/augmented reality (VR/AR) technologies. Smartphones, integrating multi-lens systems, are currently the dominant market driver [1]. Concurrently, automotive safety technologies such as advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) increasingly incorporate optical lenses for functions like blind-spot detection and 360-degree monitoring [2,3]. Such a trend is also significantly shown in Figure 1. With developments in 5G communication technology, VR and AR applications have also seen significant growth, creating further demand for optical lenses [1,4]. Moreover, geopolitical situations and the COVID-19 pandemic have led to heightened lens demands in areas like aerial surveillance and medical equipment, and have also accelerated remote work and online education, significantly increasing the market for laptop cameras and conferencing equipment [1,5].

The case-study company, a prominent Taiwanese manufacturer of precision optical lenses, faced declining on-time delivery due to bottlenecks at the Modular Transfer Function (MTF) testing stage. Given that every assembled lens must undergo rigorous MTF testing before shipment, inefficiencies at this stage severely impacted overall production flow [6]. This study used the Six Sigma methodology of Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve and Control (DMAIC) approach to systematically identify, analyze, and resolve these production inefficiencies [7,8]. This study aims to optimize the operating parameters of the MTF machine, and ultimately improve the overall inspection process and production efficiency. In addition to meeting customer needs, the sustainability of production system can also be achieved.

Figure 1. Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), 2022-2027, Source: ITRI (2023)

MATERIALS

Case Study Context

This study was conducted in a high-volume optical lens manufacturing line in Taiwan. Persistent delays in shipments were traced to limited throughput at the MTF testing stage compared to the upstream assembly process [6,9].

Data Collection

Four months of detailed data were collected from assembly and MTF testing stations, including:

- Units assembled and tested per shift.
- Operational breakdowns (assembly/testing time per unit, material handling time, machine downtime).
- Specifications of inspection parameters such as Z-axis movements, number of inspection points per lens, and characteristics of the existing halogen lighting system [10,11].

METHODOLOGY: DMAIC APPROACH

Problem Definition and Measurement

The Define phase employed the 5W1H method to clearly articulate the bottleneck issue. A SIPOC analysis visualized the production flow, highlighting the critical nature of the MTF testing stage [7,8]. Pareto charts quantified the problem, revealing significant delays due to the manual grading process and inefficient machine settings, resulting in about an 8% discrepancy in output between assembly and inspection stations [7,12]. The relevant results are shown in Figures 2-4.

Figure 2. 5W1H analysis of shipment delays

Figure 3. Pareto chart of assembly machine cycle times

Figure 4. Pareto chart of MTF testing machine cycle times

Data Analysis

A cause-and-effect (fishbone) diagram shown in Figure 5 was created through cross-departmental brainstorming, categorizing potential issues into the 4M1E framework (Man, Machine, Material, Method, Environment) [7,8]. A decision matrix then prioritized these issues, highlighting machine parameters—specifically the lighting source, inspection point counts, and Z-axis movements—as the key areas for improvement [7,8,13].

Figure 5. Cause-and-effect (Fishbone) diagram of factors affecting MTF testing machine efficiency

Improvement Experiments

A structured Design of Experiments (DOE) skills was used to evaluate the effects of adjusting three critical parameters [7,8]:

- **Lighting Source:** Compared traditional halogen lamps with newer LED technology, considering lifespan, energy efficiency, and impact on quality [11,14].
- **Inspection Points:** Evaluated the effects of decreasing inspection points per lens from 30 to 20 [15].
- **Z-axis Movement:** Initially included a 6 mm scanning offset; tests assessed reducing or removing this movement entirely to save cycle time without affecting inspection accuracy [15].

A full factorial DOE involving eight experimental scenarios systematically determined the optimal parameter combination [7,8,15]. The main effects of all involved parameters are illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Main effects plot for inspection parameters

Implementation and Control

After analyzing DOE results, optimal settings—LED lighting, 20 inspection points, and no Z-axis offset—were implemented in production [7,8,15]. The impact of these changes was monitored over four months to ensure improvements were maintained [7]. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) were updated to reflect these changes, and a schedule was created to roll out LED lighting across all MTF testing equipment, ensuring sustained efficiency gains and facilitating standardization [7,8,14].

RESULTS

Optimization of Inspection Parameters

The DOE identified significant improvements with the new parameter settings. Statistical analysis (ANOVA and main effects) showed that LED lighting reduced inspection times compared to halogen lamps. Decreasing inspection points to 20 and removing unnecessary Z-axis movement also yielded measurable efficiency gains [7,8,15]. The optimal setting (LED, 20 points, 0 mm offset) also achieved the lowest average inspection time—22.56 seconds per lens, representing a substantial time reduction over the previous settings [15].

Impact on Inspection Capacity

Before implementing improvements, the average daily inspection volume was approximately 1,214 units. Post-optimization, daily inspection volume rose to about 1,336 units—an improvement of 122 units per day (10%). This translates to approximately 30,675 additional units inspected annually [7]. The results are illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Comparison of production quantities between assembly machines and optical inspection machines (Dec 2023 - Mar 2024)

Assembly vs. Inspection Output

Post-implementation monitoring indicated that the inspection output closely matched assembly output, significantly reducing previous discrepancies from approximately 8% down to within $\pm 1.5\%$. Such a result also effectively resolved the original production bottleneck [7].

Cost-Benefit Analysis of LED Implementation

- **Lifespan and Replacement Costs:** Halogen lamps required frequent replacements (50-hour lifespan), incurring annual costs around \$14,000 per machine. The LED

replacements, with lifespans of around 30,000 hours, reduced annual costs to approximately \$1,005 per machine, a 92% reduction [11,14].

- **Energy Savings:** LED lights consumed only 20W compared to 100W halogen lamps. Annual energy consumption per machine dropped from 200 kWh to 40 kWh, an 80% saving [11,14].

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Through the structured application of DMAIC and DOE methodologies, significant operational improvements were realized in optical lens inspection. Specifically, changes in lighting technology, inspection points, and Z-axis movements led to notable efficiency gains, cost savings, and production optimization [7,8,14,15]. This systematic improvement methodology not only resolved immediate production bottlenecks but also significantly aligned with environmental sustainability objectives, highlighting energy reduction and lower carbon footprints [11,13,14]. After obtaining the preliminary improvement results, a project management team was established within the company to introduce the optimized parameters into the actual manufacturing process, comprehensively improve the equipment utilization and efficiency based on the process flow shown in Figure 8.

In addition, the improvements documented in this study serve as valuable case evidence for other precision manufacturing contexts, providing a roadmap for efficiency enhancement and sustainable production practices [7,8,14]. Future research can explore the extension of similar optimization methods to other production areas or incorporate emerging automation technologies further to enhance productivity and environmental sustainability in manufacturing operations [7,13,14].

Figure 8. Process flow for comprehensive equipment improvement

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The impact of modified biochars on the adsorption of anions from water

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Abstract

In this project, waste caltrop shells were transformed into biochar material, demonstrating impressive abilities in removing harmful Cr(VI) and As(III) ions from water. To further enhance its adsorptive powers, the biochar was modified using specialized ionic liquids - compounds known for their low volatility, thermal stability, and versatility. By experimenting with both hydrophobic and hydrophilic ionic liquids, we were able to optimize the biochar's efficiency in capturing anionic contaminants. The modifications led to a remarkable 5-fold increase in adsorption capacity. Analytical techniques, such as FTIR and NMR spectroscopy, were used to unravel the intricate interactions between the ionic liquids and the biochar. This innovative approach showcases the potential of biochar-based adsorbents as a sustainable and effective solution for water purification.

Keywords: Biochar, ionic liquid, adsorption, anion pollutant.

1. INTRODUCTION

The wastewaters containing chromium, arsenic, copper, lead, cadmium, and nickel are discharged from factories during production processes. The wastewater should be treated before discharge. Generally, metals are positively charged. However, Cr(VI) and As(III) are formed of CrO_4^{2-} , HCrO_4^- , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, HAsO_4^{2-} , and AsO_2^- . Therefore, the treatment procedures are different from those for general metals. Cr and As usually coexist in mine drainage, smelting wastewater, mining wastewater, and wood preservative production wastewater [1]. Human exposure to Cr(VI) may cause symptoms such as dermatitis, skin and mucosal ulcers, nasal septum perforation, bronchial cancer, and gastroenteritis. Because of its potential to cause the above hazards to the human body, the United States Environmental Protection Agency has classified Cr(VI) as a Class A human carcinogen [2]. Arsenic forms as As(III) and As(V) in nature [3, 4], which is extremely toxic and lethal to living organisms [5]. Precipitation, reverse osmosis, ion exchange, electrocoagulation, electro dialysis, and adsorption, are usually to reduce concentrations or remove Cr and As in the wastewater. Adsorption has advantages such as low cost, high removal efficiency, and simple operation, so it is often used in the process of adsorbing pollutants. The adsorbents include activated carbon [6-8], silica gel [9, 10], absorbent resin [11] and zeolite [12].

Biochar is made from biomass in the absence of oxygen and is environmentally friendly. It can be used as an adsorbent because of its high specific surface area and functional groups. Biochar made from sugar beet tailing (SBT) can effectively adsorb Cr(VI) from a pH 2 solution. In acidic conditions, the surface of SBT biochar is positively charged, which produces electrostatic attraction with negatively charged Cr(VI) and enhances the adsorption effect. In a neutral pH solution, biochars made from dry waste leaves litter of *Tectona* and *Lagerstroemia speciosa* have high adsorption capacity for As(III), and the main mechanisms of adsorption are electrostatic attraction and complexation [13]. However, the surface of biochar made from plants is mainly negatively charged [14]. In order to enable biochar to adsorb anions in alkaline conditions, chemical modification can change the surface chemical properties of biochar and improve its adsorption capacity [15]. The advantages of ionic liquids (ILs) are low volatility, thermal stability, non-flammability, wide potential window, and wide liquid temperature range. ILs can replace traditional organic solvents and are, therefore, called green solvents. We also found that the Cr compounds are extracted from meso- and micro-pores by ILs [16, 17]. Therefore, the biochar was made from a water caltrop shell waste by pyrolysis in this study. The ILs such as 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate ([C₄mim][PF₆]) and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ([C₄mim]Cl) were used to improve the adsorption efficiency of biochar for Cr(VI) and As(III) in the solution. We also found the mechanism of the adsorption reaction of Cr(VI) and As(III) on biochar modified with ILs.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Waste from water caltrop shells was gathered from agricultural land in southern Taiwan to produce biochar. This biochar was produced through pyrolysis at temperatures between 1073-1173 K under oxygen-limited conditions for 0.5 to 1.0 hours. The biochar underwent multiple washes with water, was dried at 343 K to eliminate moisture, ground in an agate mortar, and then screened to achieve a particle size of 0.025-0.048 mm. The synthesis methods for [C₄mim][PF₆] and [C₄mim]Cl have been described previously [18, 19]. 4% [C₄mim][PF₆] and 4% [C₄mim]Cl were mixed with biochar in beakers, respectively. Then, an appropriate amount of acetone was added into beakers and stirred for three hrs. After removing the acetone, the modified biochars were ground to obtain the desired composite adsorbents which are [C₄mim][PF₆]/biochar and [C₄mim]Cl/biochar.

K₂CrO₄ (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) was used to prepare a 750 ppm Cr(VI) solution, and NaAsO₂ (99%, Aldrich) was used to prepare a 432 ppm As(III) solution. The Cr(VI)/As(III) solution contained both 750 ppm Cr(VI) and 432 ppm As(III). The individual solutions of Cr(VI) and As(III), as well as the Cr(VI)/As(III) solution were adjusted to pH 7, 8, and 9 using 1 M NaOH (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) and 1 M HNO₃ (70%, J.T Baker).

0.05 g of adsorbent was added to five mL of each solution (Cr(VI), As(III), and the Cr(VI)/As(III) solutions) and reacted for four hours. The samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for five minutes, and the supernatant was collected and filtered through a 0.22 μm pore size filter paper. The concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) in the supernatants were measured by AA (Hitachi Z-5000, Japan) and ICP-OES (Agilent 725, USA), respectively. Therefore, the adsorption concentrations of Cr and As in the adsorbents were estimated. The functional groups of the solid samples were examined using FTIR spectroscopy (Thermo Nicolet 6700,

USA) with a wavenumber of 4000-400 cm^{-1} , 32 times scanning frequency, and a 4 cm^{-1} resolution. ^1H NMR spectra of the ILs were also determined on a Bruker Avance 500 spectrometer with tetramethyl silane (TSM) as an internal standard (acquisition, time = 1.373 s, actual pulse repetition time = 2 sec, number of scans = 32 and excitation pulse-angle = 30°).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) in biochar from solutions at pH 7, 8, and 9, respectively. In Cr(VI) solution, the best adsorption concentration is 8.2 mg/g at pH 9. The adsorption concentration of As(III) in biochar is only 1.3 mg/g at pH 8 of solution. Table 2 shows that the adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI)/As(III) solution in biochars modified with 4% ILs are significantly improved. The $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]/\text{biochar}$ had the highest adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) at pH 7 and pH 9, respectively. In addition, the maximum Cr(VI) and As(III) adsorption concentration is 20.5 mg/g at pH 9 of the Cr(VI)/As(III) solution. The $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]\text{Cl}/\text{biochar}$ had the highest adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI), As(III), and Cr(VI) and As(III) at pH 7 of the solutions.

Table 1. The adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) in biochar

pH in solution	Biochar	
	Cr(VI) (mg/g)	As(III) (mg/g)
7	4.4	—
8	4.8	1.3
9	8.2	—

Table 2. The adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) in ILs/biochar

pH in solution	$[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]/\text{biochar}$		$[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]\text{Cl}/\text{biochar}$	
	Cr(VI)(mg/g)	As(III)(mg/g)	Cr(VI)(mg/g)	As(III)(mg/g)
7	9.7	8.7	11.2	7.9
8	8.2	7.9	11.0	5.7
9	8.9	11.6	8.6	1.0

In order to understand the adsorption mechanism of Cr(VI) and As(III) with ILs/biochar, the changes in functional groups of modified biochars before and after adsorption by FTIR. Figure 1(a) shows that functional groups of hydroxyl (-OH), aromatic C-H, asymmetric aliphatic C-H and symmetric aliphatic C-H, and their peaks in biochar are located at 3438.5 cm^{-1} , 3056.6 cm^{-1} , 2964.1 cm^{-1} and 2871 cm^{-1} , respectively [20-23]. After modification by $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]$, the peaks of asymmetric aliphatic C-H (2964.1 $\text{cm}^{-1} \rightarrow 2958.3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and symmetric aliphatic C-H (2871.5 $\text{cm}^{-1} \rightarrow 2856.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]/\text{biochar}$ are shifted in

Figure 1(a), which indicates that interaction of $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ and biochar is observed. Moreover, the broad peaks of -OH (3438.5 cm^{-1}) and aromatic C-H (3056.6 cm^{-1}) of $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ /biochar also occurred due to interaction between $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ and biochar.

Compared FTIR spectra of $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ /biochar prior to and after adsorbed Cr(VI)/As(III) solutions at pH 7, 8, and 9. Figure 1(b) shows that the peaks of -OH and aromatic C-H in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ /biochar are observed remarkably due to the interaction of $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ and Cr(VI) and As(III). Therefore, the forces between $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ and biochar are weak during adsorption. In addition, the shift of aromatic C-H in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ /biochar ($3056.6\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 3058.5\text{ cm}^{-1}$) after adsorption of Cr(VI) and As(III) from the solution at pH 9. Moreover, the shifts of aliphatic asymmetric C-H in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ /biochar ($2964.1\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 2966.0\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $2964.1\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 2967.9\text{ cm}^{-1}$) after adsorption of solution at pH 7 and 9 are observed. The shifts of aliphatic symmetric C-H ($2856.1\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 2871.5\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are also found at pH 7, 8, and 9 of the solutions. Therefore, the complexation or ion exchange occurs between adsorbed ions (Cr(VI) and As(III)) and $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ /biochar [24]. The more shift peaks and the largest shift are obtained after the adsorption of Cr(VI) and As(III) from the solution at pH 9. Therefore, the adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) are the highest at pH 9 of the solution.

Figure 1(a) shows that shifts of asymmetric aliphatic C-H ($2964.1\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 2954.4\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and symmetric aliphatic C-H ($2871.5\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 2854.1\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of $[C_4mim]Cl$ /biochar are occurred due to interaction of $[C_4mim]Cl$ and biochar. The broad peaks of -OH (3438.5 cm^{-1}) and aromatic C-H (3056.6 cm^{-1}) of $[C_4mim]Cl$ /biochar are also found. In Figure 1(c), the peaks of -OH and aromatic methyl groups of $[C_4mim]Cl$ /WCSB are shifted after adsorption of Cr(VI)/As(III) solutions at pH 7, 8, and 9. This is because Cr(VI) and As(III) interact with $[C_4mim]Cl$, so the weak interaction between $[C_4mim]Cl$ and biochar has occurred. The shift of -OH ($3438.5\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 3417.2\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in $[C_4mim]Cl$ /biochar after adsorption of Cr(VI) and As(III) from the solution at pH 9 is observed. After adsorption of Cr(VI) and As(III) from the solutions at pH 7, 8, and 9, aromatic C-H in $[C_4mim]Cl$ /biochar also have shifts at $3056.6\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 3054.7\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $3056.6\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 3058.5\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3056.6\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 3064.3\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. Interestingly, the peak of aromatic C-H in $[C_4mim]Cl$ /biochar has a redshift after the adsorption of Cr(VI) and As(III) from the solution at pH 7. Furthermore, the symmetric aliphatic C-H ($2854.1\text{ cm}^{-1}\rightarrow 2873.4\text{ cm}^{-1}$) also shifts at pH 7, 8, and 9 of Cr(VI)/As(III) solutions.

1H NMR spectra of $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ and $[C_4mim]Cl$ are also measured in Figure 2. In Figures 2(a) and (b), the intensity of proton (IV: $\delta\ 3.86$) in the methyl group of the imidazole ring in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ with biochar is reduced. After Cr(VI) adsorption of solutions at pH 7, 8, and 9, the protons of the methyl group of the imidazole ring in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ have downfield shifts (pH 7 IV: $\delta\ 3.58\rightarrow 3.65$, pH 8 IV: $\delta\ 3.58\rightarrow 3.60$, pH 9 IV: $\delta\ 3.58\rightarrow 3.61$) (shown in Figures 2(c)-(e)). Furthermore, a significant shift in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ occurred after adsorbing Cr(VI) from the solution at pH 7. Therefore, the proton in the methyl group of the imidazole ring in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ has a strong interaction with Cr(VI), which affects Cr(VI) adsorption efficiency. Similarly, the interaction of proton in the methyl group of the imidazole ring in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ and As(III) causes downfield shifts (pH 7 IV: $\delta\ 3.58\rightarrow 3.71$, pH 8 IV: $\delta\ 3.58\rightarrow 3.63$, pH 9 IV: $\delta\ 3.58\rightarrow 3.75$) (shown in Figures 2(f)-(h)). It can be seen that $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ has an obvious force to As(III) in a solution with a pH of 9, so it has a higher As(III) adsorbed concentration. The results of the chemical shifts in 1H NMR spectra correspond to concentrations in Table 2. Biochar modified with $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ can improve the adsorption capacities of Cr(VI) and As(III).

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of adsorbents: (a) adsorbents before adsorption, (b) $[C_4mim][PF_6]/biochar$ after adsorption of Cr(VI)/As(III) solutions, and (c) $[C_4mim]Cl/biochar$ after adsorption of Cr(VI)/As(III) solutions.

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectra of (a) $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]$ and $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]$ contain (b) biochar, (c) $\text{Cr}(\text{VI})$ from pH 7 solution, (d) $\text{Cr}(\text{VI})$ from pH 8 solution, (e) $\text{Cr}(\text{VI})$ from pH 9 solution, (f) $\text{As}(\text{III})$ from pH 7 solution, (g) $\text{As}(\text{III})$ from pH 8 solution, and (h) $\text{As}(\text{III})$ from pH 7 solution.

As shown in Figures 3(a) and (b), the density of proton (4: δ 3.86) of $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]\text{Cl}$ contains biochar is significantly reduced due to the interaction of proton in the methyl group of the imidazole ring of $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]\text{Cl}$ and biochar. The protons of $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]\text{Cl}$ have a little perturbed after $\text{Cr}(\text{VI})$ adsorption from solutions at pH 7, 8, and 9 (shown in Figures 3(c)-(e)). During adsorption of $\text{As}(\text{III})$ from solution at pH 7 and 9, the shifts of proton in the methyl group of the imidazole ring are observed (pH 7 4: δ 3.86 \rightarrow 3.90, pH 9 4: δ 3.86 \rightarrow 3.89) (shown in Figures 3(f)-(h)). The most significant shift is the adsorption of $\text{As}(\text{III})$ from solution at pH 7, that is, $\text{As}(\text{III})$ and protons in the methyl group of the imidazole ring of $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]\text{Cl}$ have a strong interaction. Modified biochar with $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}]\text{Cl}$ improved the adsorption capacity of $\text{As}(\text{III})$.

Figure 3. ¹H NMR spectra of (a) [C₄mim]Cl and [C₄mim]Cl contain (b) biochar, (c) Cr(VI) from pH 7 solution, (d) Cr(VI) from pH 8 solution, (e) Cr(VI) from pH 9 solution, (f) As(III) from pH 7 solution, (g) As(III) from pH 8 solution, and (h) As(III) from pH 7 solution.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The comprehensive results of FTIR and ¹H NMR show that the absorption efficiencies of Cr(VI) and As(III) are affected by interaction with [C₄mim][PF₆] and biochar. The highest adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) occurred at pH 7 and 9 of solutions by [C₄mim][PF₆]/biochar, respectively. The highest adsorption concentrations of Cr(VI) and As(III) from the solution at pH 7 by [C₄mim]Cl/biochar. The adsorption efficiencies of Cr(VI) and As(III) are affected by biochar and [C₄mim]Cl, respectively.

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Twinning Green-Editing Vibes for Food – The CREDIT Vibes project

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Abstract

The **CREDIT Vibes** project embodies the principles of Creativity, Research, Education, Development, Innovation, and Transformation, with a focus on the training of highly qualified researchers and non-research staff. The initiative promotes a vision of healthy food/feed, an eco-friendly environment, and sustainable living on a healthy planet. Accepted under the Horizon Europe Program's Twinning Western Balkans Call, the project is led by the Maize Research Institute Zemun Polje (MRI), Serbia's premier institution dedicated to sustainable organic agriculture through cutting-edge research and technology. The project is based on the belief that by transforming MRI's structural organization, the institute can enhance the transfer of agro-technology and knowledge, while expanding its project management capabilities. This transformation is expected to serve as a model for other entities, encouraging similar advancements.

Keywords: *structural transformation, sustainable organic agriculture, agro-technology transfer, research training, project management*

Physicochemical Characterization and Ecotoxicological Assessment of Municipal Biosolids for Sustainable Agricultural Use

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Abstract

Excess sludge generated in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) poses significant disposal challenges, as landfilling is now largely prohibited. Biosolids, derived from sludge through various treatment processes, can be utilized as fertilizers or soil amendments, depending on their quality. In alignment with circular economy principles, this study evaluates the physicochemical properties and ecotoxicological impact of biosolids from three WWTPs in Northern Greece. Metal concentrations (pseudo-total and leachate content) were analyzed, and acute toxicity was assessed using *Daphnia magna* neonates. Results indicated low metal concentrations, well below the limits set by Greek agricultural regulations. However, low but detectable toxicity to *D. magna* was observed, regardless of biosolid origin or seasonal variations. Biosolids from WWTP1, previously studied, underwent additional thermal hydrolysis treatment. While this process altered metal leaching patterns, resulting in increased Ni and Zn levels and variable Cu leaching, it did not mitigate *D. magna* toxicity. A correlation between Cr concentration in leachates and toxicity was noted but was not statistically significant. These findings highlight the need for further investigation into treatment methods that optimize biosolids safety for agricultural applications.

Keywords: biosolids, circular economy, soil amendments, metals

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Public perception and environmental significance of non-chemical fertilizers

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Abstract

Sustainable agriculture and circular economy initiatives offer viable solutions to the environmental challenges of conventional farming and waste management. The disposal of biosolids, a by-product of wastewater treatment, presents disposal challenges due to strict regulations such as the EU Landfill Directive 1999/31/EC, which restricts the disposal of biodegradable waste in landfills. A sustainable alternative is the use of biosolids as fertilisers, which enhance soil health, improve water retention, and reduce reliance on synthetic fertilisers-lowering carbon footprints and chemical runoff. By repurposing sewage sludge, biosolids not only divert waste from landfills but also minimise greenhouse gas emissions and close nutrient cycles. This approach aligns with circular economy principles, promoting sustainable waste management while addressing soil degradation. However, public acceptance remains crucial for widespread adoption. The BIOSOIL project focuses on developing and implementing soil improvement methods using biosolids from wastewater treatment plants and bioaugmentation techniques, integrated within a circular economy and citizen science framework. It assesses the feasibility and public perception of biosolids as soil amendments while leveraging urban agriculture to advance sustainability. A structured questionnaire was conducted to evaluate awareness, experience, and willingness to engage with biosolid applications, identifying knowledge gaps, barriers to adoption, and strategies to build public trust. A total of 100 respondents participated, including engineers (40%), farmers (24%), agricultural consultants (22%), and employees in technical firms (14%). Findings revealed that 32% had moderate familiarity with biosolids, with engineers demonstrating the highest expertise (62.5%). While 35% were aware of sustainable agriculture, many lacked in-depth knowledge. Additionally, 43% of professionals expressed interest in further research, and 69% sought training through online resources, conferences, and practical demonstrations.

Keywords: *sustainable agriculture, circular economy, biosolids, wastewater treatment, non-chemical fertilizers, soil improvement, urban agriculture, public perception, environmental impact*

BIOSOIL-Development and utilization of soil improvement methods using biosolids from Wastewater Treatment Plants and bio-reinforcement techniques in the context of circular economy and citizen science- Green Fund Research and Application- "Natural Environment and Novel Actions 2023"; FUNDING: GREEN FUND 200,000 euros; beneficiary: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Understanding Household Waste Source Separation: An Integrative Review of Theory of Planned Behaviour and Key Extensions

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Abstract

This paper presents an integrative review of empirical studies applying the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to household waste source separation. Drawing from a range of peer-reviewed articles published between 2013 and 2024, the review investigates both the predictive strength of TPB's core constructs (attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control) and the added value of key extensions, including moral norms, environmental concern, situational constraints, and other behavioral or contextual variables. Findings confirm the model's robustness and highlight the contribution of additional psychological and contextual variables in enhancing its predictive capacity. The review also reveals variations in the performance of specific TPB extensions across cultural and infrastructural contexts, highlighting the importance of translating behavioral insights into locally grounded policy tools that can accelerate progress toward sustainable municipal waste management and the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: *Theory of Planned Behavior, source separation, municipal solid waste, moral norms, integrative review*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), introduced by Ajzen in 1991 [1], is a widely used psychological framework for predicting and explaining human behavior, particularly in environmental contexts. According to the model, behavior is primarily predicted by behavioral intention, which is influenced by three key constructs: attitude toward the behavior (ATT), reflecting the individual's evaluation of the behavior; subjective norms (SN), referring to perceived social pressure to perform or not perform the behavior; and perceived behavioral control (PBC), denoting the perceived ease or difficulty of performing the behavior.

Figure 1. The original TPB model, adapted from [1].

In the context of municipal solid waste (MSW) management, TPB offers a strong theoretical basis for analyzing household source separation behavior. Sorting waste at the source is a critical step toward increasing material recovery and reducing landfill dependency, and several studies have employed TPB to examine the psychological mechanisms that drive such behavior. Favorable attitudes, perceived social expectations, and a strong sense of control have consistently been associated with individuals' intention to separate waste, and in some cases, with actual behavioral engagement [2–7].

Despite its explanatory strength, the TPB has also been criticized for certain limitations, especially when applied to complex environmental behaviors such as waste separation. One key concern is its difficulty in accounting for habitual or morally driven actions, as well as behaviors influenced by situational constraints. In the domain of source separation, the well-documented gap between intention and actual behavior has raised questions about the sufficiency of the original model [4].

In particular, TPB has been found to overlook important internal mechanisms that shape behavior. While ATT, SN, and PBC are central to the model, they do not always capture deeper motivational forces rooted in personal ethics. Moral Norms (MN), for instance, refers to an internalized sense of duty to act in line with one's environmental values. This sense of responsibility may operate independently of SN or external rewards, and is often a powerful predictor of pro-environmental behavior [5]. In a similar vein, environmental concern (EC), a broader affective and cognitive orientation toward environmental protection, has also been shown to influence behavioral intention.

Other constructs that have enriched TPB-based models include situational factors (SF) (e.g. time constraints, access to infrastructure), government policies and perceived policy effectiveness, incentives (both financial and non-financial), as well as environmental awareness and knowledge about recycling practices. These variables expand the scope of the original model by incorporating both psychological and contextual determinants of behavior, thereby enhancing its applicability to real-world waste management contexts [2,6].

This paper presents an integrative review of empirical studies that apply or expand the TPB in the context of household waste source separation. It focuses on identifying the most frequently used additional variables, assessing their impact across different case studies, and clarifying the conditions under which these extensions improve the model's performance. Beyond theoretical refinement, the review also provides practical insights for the development of evidence-based strategies to promote sustainable waste behavior at the local level.

2. METHODOLOGY

This paper adopts an integrative literature review approach, as outlined by Snyder (2019) [8], which is particularly suited for conceptually grounded reviews that aim to build or refine theoretical frameworks. The objective was to identify empirical studies that applied or extended the TPB in the domain of recycling and household waste source separation. The literature search targeted peer-reviewed articles published between 2010 and 2024 that examined the three core TPB variables (ATT, SN, PBC).

Particular emphasis was placed on studies incorporating additional constructs, such as MN, EC, SF, habitual behavior, and perceived policy effectiveness.

To ensure conceptual consistency with household-level waste behaviors, the review included only empirical studies investigating individual or household-level behavior. Research conducted in clearly institutional or commercial settings (e.g. hospitals, workplaces, industries) was excluded. However, studies involving university students were retained when the examined behavior referred to everyday personal choices, such as food waste management in canteens or plastic separation in dormitories.

Relevant sources were retrieved through targeted searches in major academic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct, and Google Scholar. Search terms combined keywords such as “Theory of Planned Behavior”, “waste separation”, “recycling intention”, “household behavior”, “moral norms”, “environmental concern”, “situational factors”, “habitual behavior”, and “policy effectiveness”. Additional studies were identified through backward citation tracking and expert consultation.

3. LITERATURE SYNTHESIS

The selected studies encompass a diverse range of geographical regions, populations, and methodological approaches, including structural equation modeling (SEM), regression analysis, and survey-based assessments. While many studies incorporate the original constructs of the TPB, a growing body of research proposes expanded models that incorporate psychological and external factors, such as ethical values, environmental attitudes, perceived barriers, and policy-related influences. These extensions have significantly improved the model’s capacity to explain recycling-related intentions and behaviors.

For instance, several studies report that MN can significantly enhance the predictive strength of the TPB, often surpassing traditional attitudinal measures in explaining recycling intentions. Similarly, perceived convenience, awareness of environmental consequences, and trust in waste collection systems have emerged as key determinants of source separation behavior. Such findings suggest that both psychological and contextual factors must be considered to fully capture the complexity of household recycling decisions.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The TPB has proven to be a valuable framework for understanding and predicting household participation in recycling and source separation practices. The reviewed studies highlight the model’s robustness, while also revealing opportunities for theoretical enrichment and

practical adaptation across diverse socio-cultural and policy contexts. This discussion synthesizes the findings along four main axes: core TPB constructs, extended TPB variables, contextual and geographical influences, and methodological considerations for future research.

4.1 Core Constructs of the TPB

The three central TPB constructs have consistently emerged as significant predictors of source separation intention. Among these, ATT was the most reliable predictor in some studies [9,11,12], while in others it had a secondary role to MN [10], or was shaped by antecedent psychological constructs such as MN or information exposure [13]. In particular, positive evaluations of recycling as a meaningful, easy, and socially responsible action tend to enhance individuals' willingness to engage in source separation. The influence of SN, however, is less consistent. In collectivist cultures, such as those in China and Thailand, SN exerted a stronger influence [14,15]. By contrast, studies in Malaysia and Ghana reported that normative pressure was less influential compared to other factors [7,16]. This variation suggests that the influence of social approval depends to a significant extent on community cohesion, trust, and the visibility of normative behaviors. In contrast, PBC was consistently found to be a crucial factor, often outperforming SN in predictive power [3,6,18]. PBC was consistently found to be a crucial factor, often outperforming SN in predictive power [3,6,18]. Studies further support this by showing that convenient recycling systems significantly boost PBC and real behavior [19,20,21].

4.2 Extensions of the TPB: Moral Norms, Environmental Concern, Knowledge, and Situational Factors

To overcome the limitations of the original TPB, many studies have expanded the model to include MN, EC, knowledge, and SF. These extensions have improved the model's explanatory power, especially in the context of complex pro-environmental behaviors. MN have been widely recognized as significant drivers of recycling intention [5,7,10,22]. When individuals feel confident that they have the necessary resources, time, and infrastructure to separate waste, their intention and behavior are positively reinforced [12,17]. In particular, Emmanouil et al. demonstrated that MN not only predict intention directly but also mediate the relationship between attitude and intention [13]. EC has been examined as a potential predictor of recycling intention in various studies. For instance, Vassanadumrongdee and Kittipongvises [15] found it to be a statistically significant factor influencing source separation behavior. However, in other cases such as Shen et al. (2019) [14], EC did not emerge as a significant predictor. In the Greek context, Ioannou et al. [9] emphasized that environmental awareness significantly shaped pro-environmental attitudes, highlighting the role of personal concern and knowledge in forming recycling intentions. Knowledge, particularly regarding sorting procedures and environmental consequences, has been found to positively influence attitudes toward recycling behavior in several studies. For instance, Pan and Liu [23] and Chuah et al. [3] reported that increased knowledge significantly improved attitudes, thereby indirectly reinforcing intention. However, in other cases such as Hu et al. [18], knowledge was included in the model but did not emerge as a statistically significant predictor of intention. Moreover, Wang Y. et al. [11] found that knowledge functioned as a moderating variable, strengthening the relationship between intention and actual recycling behavior. These findings suggest that knowledge may play an indirect, yet important, role in

shaping pro-environmental actions. SF, such as infrastructure availability, policy incentives, logistical convenience, and time constraints, have been found to significantly influence recycling behavior. Arli et al. [2] found that situational barriers negatively impacted PBC, while Zhang et al. [19] emphasized the importance of accessible recycling systems. Ney et al. [27] contributed to this area by integrating context-specific variables, namely, lack of facilities and social media usage, into their extended TPB model, highlighting their influence on clothing waste separation intention.

4.3 Geographical and Policy Contexts: Cross-Cultural Patterns and National Frameworks

European and Southeast Asian studies emphasize structural and institutional factors as stronger predictors of recycling behavior. For example, Vassanadumrongdee and Kittipongvises [15] found that trust in local authorities significantly shaped intention to separate waste at source. Zaikova et al. [24] also examined trust-related variables in Russia and Finland, although these did not emerge as significant predictors. Moreover, incentive-based interventions appear to play a critical moderating role: Wang et al. [5] reported that incentive measures positively moderated the intention–behavior link, while Govindan et al. [6] showed that both incentives and supervisory mechanisms strengthened the translation of intention into actual sorting behavior. The Greek case studies further highlight the interplay between individual behavior and national waste strategies [9,12,13,25]. Limited infrastructure, uneven public engagement, and unclear incentives have historically hampered the effectiveness of source separation. These findings indicate that behavioral models need to be reinforced by systemic interventions (such as recycling corners, green points, and environmental education programs) that are aligned with regional and national waste management strategies.

4.4 Limitations and Future Research

Most studies adopt quantitative approaches, with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) being the predominant method [26]. SEM enables researchers to examine both direct and indirect effects among TPB variables and has supported the integration of extended constructs. However, the heavy reliance on cross-sectional and self-reported data raises concerns about social desirability bias and limits the ability to evaluate how intentions evolve into sustained behavior over time. Longitudinal or experimental designs remain limited, making it difficult to capture the dynamic nature of behavioral change. Additionally, few studies address how contextual or structural conditions, such as limited infrastructure or access to services, affect the translation of behavioral intention into actual behavior, particularly in complex or resource-constrained environments. Furthermore, few studies triangulate self-reported intention with actual behavioral data, such as waste output measurements or participation rates in recycling programs, which could enhance the validity and practical relevance of TPB-based findings. Finally, TPB applications rarely assess the behavioral effects of specific policy interventions, such as incentive schemes, awareness campaigns, or changes in infrastructure, despite their direct relevance to perceived control and normative influences.

4.5 Implications

The reviewed literature suggests that promoting household waste separation requires more than just individual motivation. A holistic approach, incorporating psychological, infra-structural, and policy dimensions, is necessary. Strategies should include:

- educational campaigns that foster positive attitudes and moral responsibility,
- policy design that increases perceived control and convenience,
- integration of moral and contextual variables into TPB-based public interventions,
- deployment of digital tools and feedback systems (e.g., mobile apps, smart bins) to strengthen perceived control and sustain behavioral engagement,
- use of TPB-based metrics to assess the effectiveness of environmental policies and interventions over time,
- community-based interventions that enhance subjective norms and local participation

Lastly, future TPB applications in environmental behavior must continue evolving by embracing interdisciplinary insights, dynamic behavioral feedback, and system-level interventions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This review confirms the relevance and adaptability of the TPB in explaining household recycling and source separation behavior. While the foundational TPB constructs remain strong predictors of intention, their effectiveness is significantly enhanced when complemented by variables that reflect moral reasoning, perceived barriers, institutional support, and environmental awareness. Rather than offering a universal behavioral model, TPB proves most valuable when treated as a flexible framework, one that can be tailored to specific cultural, infrastructural, and demographic contexts. These findings underscore the importance of combining theoretical rigor with contextual sensitivity, both in academic research and in the design of policies that support sustainable behavior. Future research should continue to explore the dynamic interplay between psychological and structural variables, placing greater emphasis on longitudinal designs, underexplored populations, and real-world behavioral outcomes. Integrating TPB with broader behavioral theories may further strengthen its capacity to inform evidence-based environmental strategies.

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Optimizing Safety Stock Levels for Aircraft Spare Parts under Uncertainty and Circular Economy Principles

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Abstract

Balancing operational reliability with sustainability is a critical concern in aircraft maintenance logistics. This study presents a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) framework designed to compute optimal safety stock levels for individual spare parts in a maintenance hangar servicing multiple aircraft. The model integrates stochastic demand patterns, variable lead times and part criticality, ensuring that each component's safety stock is aligned with both operational requirements and environmental objectives. By incorporating refurbished and recycled parts alongside new components, the model supports circular economy practices, reducing dependence on newly manufactured parts and promoting resource efficiency. The model aims to determine safety stock levels that minimize stockout risks while avoiding excess inventory. By capturing demand uncertainty through probabilistic modeling, it ensures reliable service levels without overstocking, balancing operational reliability with sustainability. The framework is adaptable to different fleet sizes and maintenance contexts and aligns with industry goals of enhancing supply chain efficiency while embedding circular economy principles into maintenance operations.

Keywords: safety stock, spare parts inventory, stochastic demand, circular economy, aircraft maintenance

Global Climate Change

Environmental impact of climatic relevant particulate species emitted by shipping in the Eastern Mediterranean

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Abstract

Ship emissions and their impacts on the environment is a key issue for atmospheric research and climate policy. Particles and gases emitted by ships can contribute to various environmental problems such as acidification and eutrophication of water and soil in coastal regions caused by sulfur and nitrogen deposition, climate cooling due to the sulfur content of marine fuel, climate warming caused by the emissions of greenhouse gases and absorbing black carbon. The environmental impact of climate-relevant substances (CRS) emitted by shipping is one of the main topics of the emblematic initiative NAVGREEN. It will be addressed by the current presentation, in four aspects.

First, the findings from a literature review on pollutant levels and CRS in the Mediterranean atmosphere, especially in areas affected by shipping emissions, will be presented.

Methods applied to quantify the impact of shipping emissions on atmospheric pollutants and CRS in the Mediterranean will be assessed, with targeted implementation for mapping CRS at Greek port areas with increased shipping emissions, via atmospheric models, emission inventories and in-situ observations.

Finally, the impact of CRS, atmospheric and seawater pollutants – with emphasis on black carbon and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) – on the Greek marine environment will be addressed, with focus on the port of Piraeus.

Keywords: Eastern Mediterranean, shipping emissions, climatic relevant substances, atmospheric and marine environment

Regional Benchmarks for Water Footprint of Crops

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Abstract

Due to global food demand, population growth and water management issues, there is an evolving research activity concerning water footprint (WF) benchmarks in crop production and the investigation of the most important factors that determine WF values. This study explores the formulation of WF benchmarks (considering the level of the *best 25th* percentile of crop production) for all major crops in the Rhodes island/Greece, by estimating WFs for each year separately for 2000-2014, with a division into the blue, green and gray WF components. For the calculation of the WFs for selected crops, CROPWAT 8.0 simulation software was utilized to estimate the actual evapotranspiration of irrigated/ rainfed olives, citrus, irrigated grapes/ rainfed vineyards, vegetables, melons, spring/ summer/ winter potatoes, soft/ hard wheat, barley and fodder crops. The results from the WFs of olive groves and vineyards indicate that it is legitimate to separate WF benchmarks into rainfed and irrigated crops. This study is expected to make a contribution to sustainable agricultural water management in the context of the WF concept.

Keywords: water footprint, CROPWAT, crops, Rhodes island, Greece, benchmarking

Drought impact on the nitrogen use efficiency in the swards of different botanical composition

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Abstract

Drought is a critical factor affecting the productivity and persistence of temperate swards, as it limits water availability, reduces nutrient uptake, and suppresses plant growth. Prolonged dry conditions can lead to a decline in herbage yield and quality, compromising the overall stability and resilience of grassland systems. There are several benefits associated with the use of legumes in swards, including nitrogen (N) fixation reducing the requirement for N fertilizers, improved herbage production and quality, and enhanced N-use efficiency. This study investigated the effects of drought on the productivity and nitrogen use efficiency in the grass-legume swards of different botanical composition. Perennial grasses meadow fescue (*Festuca pratensis*) and perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) were mixed with different legume species — alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*), red clover (*Trifolium pratense*), and bird's-foot trefoil (*Lotus corniculatus*). The data on swards productivity, plants and soil response will be presented.

Keywords: drought, legumes, grasses, nitrogen efficiency, productivity .

Climate change impact on road networks: Investigation of slopes erosion due to insufficient hydraulics

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Abstract

In recent years, humanity has been facing climate change. On a global level, there is an increase in temperature and extreme weather phenomena. Such extreme events have also occurred in Greece, the most notable being the Mediterranean cyclone "Ianos" and the extreme flooding caused by the bad weather "Daniel," which led to the destruction of properties, infrastructure, and road networks. Such destruction has extensive economic, environmental, and social impacts. Consequently, there is an urgent need for a deeper understanding of the causes and manifestations of such weather phenomena, as well as monitoring their impact. Furthermore, there is a need to find optimal methods for preventing or avoiding any risks that may arise after an extreme event, as well as upgraded practices for repairing damage and destruction that may be caused by these risks. Such an approach cannot focus on just one issue or level; it must take a holistic view of the matter, considering the interactions among various parts, systems, and subsystems. In the context of a road network, one must examine how all the components of the network interact with each other, how the network itself interacts with other networks, and how all of these interact with the environment. This study explores the multifaceted impacts of climate change on the safety, functionality, and sustainability of road infrastructure, with a particular focus on the role of insufficient hydraulics in exacerbating landslide risks in mountainous areas.

Keywords: *slope erosion, insufficient hydraulics, extreme weather phenomena, rehabilitation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Extreme weather phenomena, such as intense rainfall, can overwhelm road drainage systems, particularly in cases where there is an absence of culverts, a lack of side ditches, or when existing culverts and ditches are too small or short to manage increased water flow effectively. The accumulation of water due to inadequate drainage can erode the slopes of roads, cause landslides or even the destruction part of the road network. The research focuses on what initially appears to be geotechnical failures, which ultimately stem from hydraulic failures. This correlation emphasizes the necessity of comprehensive hydraulic design to maintain the safety of road networks, as these failures can result in serious hazards, costly repairs, and significant disruptions to transportation.

Furthermore, the research investigates the best ways and practices to repair the damage, restore the harmed areas in the previous situation and even upgrade the road network. Moreover, it analyzes how inadequate infrastructure standards contribute to vulnerability in

the face of climate change. Out-dated practices often fail to account for projected environmental changes, thereby increasing the risks associated with extreme weather and landslides.

By focusing on the critical importance of effective drainage systems, including appropriately sized culverts, adequate side ditches, and comprehensive maintenance strategies, this presentation seeks to inform engineers and policymakers of the pressing need for enhanced hydraulic design in mountainous road networks. Moreover, it advocates proactive measures such as the implementation of robust design criteria, quality construction methods, usage of climate-resilient materials, and the integration of advanced monitoring technologies for early detection of potential failures.

Through this comprehensive analysis, the study aims to provide valuable insights and recommendations to enhance the resilience of road networks against climatic impacts, ultimately contributing to safer, more sustainable transportation infrastructure in the face of a changing climate.

2. CLIMATE CHANGE AND ROAD NETWORKS

Variability in climate patterns, characterized by an increase in extreme weather events, such as intense rainfall and prolonged droughts, significantly affects the safety and functionality of transportation systems. As a result, understanding the relationship between climate change and road networks is essential for developing mitigation strategies and enhancing resilience.

2.1 Impacts of Climate Change on Transportation Infrastructure

The accumulation of water at slope interfaces increases the risk of erosion and landslides, particularly in mountainous areas. Studies have shown that road drainage inefficiencies can significantly exacerbate erosion rates, leading to costly repairs and hazardous conditions for users. [1]

2.2 Vulnerability of Road Networks

Older road networks, particularly those designed under outdated hydrological models, are inherently vulnerable to climate-related disturbances. Many existing drainage systems lack the capacity to handle increased water flow associated with extreme weather events. As a result, roads may experience localized landslides, pavement failure, and structural damage. Inadequacy of current standards and regulations to anticipate climate impacts contributes significantly to the vulnerabilities observed in road networks. These outdated practices fail to account for projected increases in precipitation and temperature, leading to serious implications for safety and maintenance. [2]

2.3 Importance of Upgraded Infrastructure

Upgraded infrastructure is critical for enhancing the resilience of road networks against the impacts of climate change. It is essential that road designs integrate robust drainage systems capable of receiving greater amounts of stormwater. Upgrading these systems not only mitigates the risks of erosion and landslides but also reduces the frequency of road closures and disruptions due to flooding. Additionally, incorporating sustainable materials and construction practices can lead to longer-lasting infrastructure that withstands extreme

weather events. Infrastructure upgrades can contribute to safety, efficiency, and sustainability within transportation networks. [3]

3. CASE STUDY: KARDITSA MUNICIPALITY

3.1 Background of the Cyclone

Mediterranean Cyclone Ianos, also known as the "Ianos" storm, impacted Karditsa and other regions in Central and Western Greece in September 2020. The cyclone brought heavy rainfall, resulting in severe flooding and landslides. In some areas of Karditsa Municipality the rainfall exceeded 400mm within a very short period of time.

3.2 Impact on Infrastructure

The heavy rainfall from Ianos resulted in extensive damage to road networks and infrastructure. Many road sections suffered from erosion, leading to the destabilization of slopes and increasing the occurrence of landslides. In Karditsa, roads were blocked, and segments of the roadway collapsed. Insufficient drainage, characterized by a lack of culverts or undersized culverts and narrow ditches, failed to divert the excess water away from critical roadways, exacerbating the damage.

One notable example occurred on the road connecting Amarantos to Sarantoporo, where slope failures caused significant disruptions (Figure 1). Initially perceived as geotechnical failures, further investigation revealed that the underlying causes were primarily linked to hydraulic inadequacies. The absence of adequate drainage systems allowed water to accumulate at slope interfaces, leading to soil erosion and subsequent landslide events.

3.3 Recovery actions

In the aftermath of Cyclone Ianos, recovery efforts aimed to restore and rehabilitate damaged infrastructure. Key actions included the assessment of existing hydraulic systems and the implementation of improved drainage designs (Figure 2). The rehabilitation involved the construction of a new culvert to facilitate better stormwater management (Figure 3). Through this construction, appropriate collection and drainage of stormwater from the interbedding is achieved. Moreover, installing wider side ditches to prevent water accumulation on road surfaces.

This case study highlights the necessity of incorporating climate-resilient design principles into future road construction and maintenance practices. The emphasis on effective drainage solutions is paramount in preventing similar failures in the face of extreme weather events. The lessons learned from the Ianos storm underscore the importance of proactive planning and infrastructure upgrades to enhance the resilience of road networks against climate change.

Figure 11. Slope failure in Karditsa Municipality (authors' own)

Figure 12. Hydraulic design for adequate stormwater drainage (AutoCAD)

Figure 13. Construction of culvert (authors' own)

Figure 14. Final situation of the rehabilitation works (authors' own)

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance the resilience and safety of road networks against the impacts of climate change, the following recommendations are proposed:

Implement Robust Drainage Systems: Design and construct road drainage systems that can handle increased stormwater flow due to climate change. This includes improving the size and capacity of culverts and side ditches to ensure effective water management during extreme weather events.

Integrate Climate Resilience into Planning: Future roadway construction and upgrades should incorporate climate resilience principles. This involves conducting thorough hydrological and geotechnical studies to inform design choices that can withstand projected weather changes.

Enhance Maintenance Protocols: Establish regular maintenance schedules for drainage systems and road infrastructure. This includes the cleaning and inspection of culverts and ditches, as well as ensuring that vegetation management does not obstruct drainage paths.

Utilize Climate-Resilient Materials: Invest in materials and construction techniques that offer greater durability under extreme weather conditions. This includes exploring innovative materials designed specifically for enhanced performance in wet and unstable environments.

Establish Early Warning and Monitoring Systems: Deploy advanced monitoring technologies such as real-time sensors and GIS-based systems to detect potential failures in road infrastructure early. This proactive approach allows for quick response measures to mitigate risks before they escalate.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Climate change presents significant challenges for road networks, particularly in areas that face extreme weather events. The case study of Mediterranean Cyclone Ianos in Karditsa Municipality highlights the importance of proper drainage systems. The failure of these systems lead to severe erosion and landslides, which from their side lead to extensive damage to roads and infrastructure. To reduce the risks related to climate change, it is essential to enhance the design of drainage systems. Improving the capacity of culverts and side ditches will help manage excessive water flow during heavy rainstorms. Incorporating climate-resilient materials and technologies into road construction can increase the durability of infrastructure, reducing maintenance needs and repair costs.

In summary, this study emphasizes the need for engineers to focus on effective hydraulic design and proactive maintenance strategies. By investing in better drainage solutions and adopting durable construction practices, road networks can be strengthened against the impacts of climate change and to empower safety of public transportations.

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Improving efficiency & reliability in urban water distribution systems for combating climate change

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Abstract

This study presents the main activities of an ongoing project co-funded by the European Union and Türkiye within the Climate Change Adaptation Grant Programme (CCAGP). Overall objective of the project is to combat water scarcity in urban areas by enhancing climate change adaptation where the specific objective is to improve efficiency and reliability of urban water supply systems and raise public awareness for water savings. The target groups include water utilities, municipalities and water users in public areas. Three District Metered Areas (DMAs) from the water distribution network of Antalya city-Türkiye were chosen as pilot study area. Flow meters and pressure meters were installed to the DMAs and connected to the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition system (SCADA). Activities were applied in the three DMAs to reduce real water losses such as pressure management using hydraulic modelling, Active Leakage Control, monitoring pressure and flow rates, especially Minimum Night Flow (MNF). Standard water balance tables were calculated on monthly basis for each DMA to assess the reductions in water losses & Non-Revenue Water. Unbiased Performance Indicators such as Infrastructure Leakage Index were used instead of the biased use of percent water losses. Three separate training sessions were organized to metropolitan, provincial & district municipalities. Additionally, public awareness campaigns were conducted in selected public areas.

Keywords: climate change, Non-Revenue Water, water efficiency, water losses, water scarcity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the increase in population and living standards, industrial and agricultural developments, the water demand is increasing globally which creates pressure on water resources along with the adverse impacts of climate change. Urban water demand is one of the areas that requires sustainable and efficient use of water as there are important and priority investments to extract and transmit water from the source to the consumers and optimization of water supply infrastructure can be considered as a key climate change adaptation measure. There are commonly high levels of real water losses in water supply systems (WSS) due to leakages from service connections & distribution mains, and storage tanks overflow. Likewise, there are commonly high apparent water losses due to unauthorized consumptions, metering inaccuracies and consumption data handling errors. Additionally, excessive/uncontrolled water consumption increases the pressure on water resources and cause

significant economic losses [1]. Assessment of energy and carbon footprints for the urban water cycle supports sustainable and efficient management of water and climate change adaptation [2, 3]. Non-Revenue Water (NRW) refers to the volume of water consumed but not billed and lost in the WSS. NRW includes both total water losses (real and apparent) and Unbilled Authorized Consumption (UAC). In terms of sustainable operation of urban water supply and water distribution networks (WDN), reducing NRW implies reducing the energy used for the production, treatment, and distribution of water and also reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with the energy requirements of water supply. By increasing efficiency, a high cost-recovery level can be achieved and be invested in improving water management infrastructure, without impacting the tariffs which consumers currently pay. This principle is supported by the objectives of the European Union (EU) Water Framework Directive (WFD) (Article 9) [4]. Management and reduction of NRW requires financial support, advanced technologies, qualified trained personnel, and awareness of the public.

Climate change reduces the availability of fresh water in Türkiye and many countries worldwide. Therefore, an integrated holistic approach is required to manage all aspects of water usage. In this study, reducing NRW and improving efficiency & reliability in urban water supply systems was tackled in detail to mitigate the adverse impacts of climate change. This study presents the main activities and outcomes of an-going project co-funded by the European Union and the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change of the Republic of Türkiye within the Climate Change Adaptation Grant Programme (CCAGP). The project duration is 18 months and the total budget is 433,000 Euros. Akdeniz University is the lead beneficiary of the project where Antalya Water and Wastewater Administration General Directorate (ASAT), Malta Energy and Water Agency, and Malta Water Services Corporation are the co-beneficiaries. This study will present a good case study to enhance climate change adaptation by improving efficiency and reliability of urban water supply systems and raising public awareness for water savings.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Pilot study area

Antalya city in Türkiye, located along the coast of Mediterranean Sea, is selected as the pilot study area for the project as the city is expected to be highly affected by the adverse impacts of climate. Agriculture and tourism are the main active sectors in Antalya province which rely on adequate supply of water. Although the population of Antalya city is around 1.5 million, the number of domestic and international tourists visiting Antalya province is around 25 million which creates a high burden on water resources. The total volume of abstracted water for municipal water supply increased from 0.18 to 0.39 billion m³/year while daily water abstraction per capita increased from 293 to 391 L/cap/day between the years 2010 and 2024 in Antalya province. In Antalya city, the NRW is reported as 44% in 2020 [5] but increased to 49% in 2024 [6]. Additionally, the annual volume of UAC was 0.37 million m³/year in 2020 but increased to 0.69 million m³/year in 2024 [5, 6]. Therefore, sustainable management of urban water demand and detailed analysis and management of NRW components are critical for Antalya. Three District Metered Areas (DMA) were chosen as pilot study area from three districts of Antalya city, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of the three DMAs for implementation of the project (prepared by Canva online tool)

Flow and pressure meters were installed at the entrance to each DMA, and connected with the SCADA system. Activities were applied to reduce real & apparent water losses and UAC. Post-meter leakages were assessed using smart meters.

2.2 Main activities of the project

The outputs of the project focus on enhancing water distribution system (WDS) efficiency and reliability through setting up an efficient online monitoring system, reduction of NRW, capacity building and awareness raising by training activities & dissemination and also giving recommendations to revise Turkish regulation on water losses control. The project team selected and established three DMAs in Antalya as pilot study area (PSA) with the cooperation of Maltese experts. Flow and pressure meters were installed at the DMAs and connected to the SCADA system for online and continuous monitoring of water flow and pressure. The collected data sets were analyzed to improve water and energy efficiency. Around 30 smart meters were installed in public areas to monitor consumption and detect post-meter leakages. To reduce NRW, monthly Standard Water Balance (SWB) tables were prepared to analyze water loss components, Minimum Night Flow (MNF) was assessed, and hydraulic modeling, intelligent pressure management, and Active Leakage Control (ALC) techniques were applied. Customer meter inaccuracies were evaluated, with around 100 inaccurate meters replaced, and the Infrastructure Leakage Index (ILI) was introduced as a more accurate performance indicator. Climate change scenario analysis was conducted, considering future urban population growth and water demand changes, using a calibrated and verified hydraulic model to identify critical operational conditions. Capacity-building efforts included application of need assessment questionnaires for technical staff of municipalities/ water utilities. A technical visit to Malta was conducted for gaining good EU experience and training. Three workshops and on-site training sessions were organized for the technical staff of Turkish municipalities. Awareness raising campaigns about water saving, impacts of climate change and water scarcity problem were organized at local schools. Dissemination efforts included preparing bilingual leaflets, handbooks, and a project website (kentsuverim.com). Regulatory recommendations were developed in cooperation with Maltese experts, focusing on replacing percent water losses with an un-biased indicator (such

as ILI), establishing reference consumption levels for public areas, defining a maximum UAC level, and revising water tariff rules to encourage water conservation.

2.3 Needs assessment questionnaire for technical staff

A needs assessment questionnaire was applied to around 100 participants from different municipalities and water utilities in Türkiye. The questionnaire included several sections where the main sections were: overview of water losses, benefits of reducing water losses, calculation of water loss components and SWB table, applied methods in controlling water losses, efficiency and reliability in urban water supply systems and evaluation of water supply system infrastructure and operations. The aim of the questionnaire was to determine the contents of the project handbook and the website for more effective and successful implementation of water loss control. The questionnaire was created by utilizing technical notes and handbooks published on water loss control.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Establishment of three DMAs

One of the most important components in the project is monitoring both the flow rates and pressure levels entering each DMA. In this aspect, ASAT worked hard to install the electromagnetic flow meters, pressure meters and related valves at the three DMAs. A DMA is hydraulically an isolated area of WDN where all the flow rates entering the area and leaving it (if any) should be measured. It is very important to control that each DMA area is well isolated and that it does not receive any water from the network other than the measured point(s). Zero-pressure tests were conducted at all DMAs. The project activities involved integrating the monitoring system at the three DMAs with the existing SCADA system of ASAT. Thus, the monitored data sets are remotely accessed and recorded. At first, energy was supplied to each DMA from the closest possible source of the electrical distribution network. This was followed by connecting the monitoring system at each DMA with the SCADA system. Consequently, the measured flow rates and pressure levels are displayed at the screens of ASAT SCADA Center.

Figure 2. Installation of the monitoring system & integration with the SCADA system (photos authors' own).

3.2 Evaluation of the needs assessment questionnaire results

A total of 96 individuals (technical staff) from different metropolitan, provincial and district municipalities participated in the need assessment questionnaire and the results were evaluated for the main sections as presented in Figures 3-6. In Section 2 of the questionnaire, the participants were asked to define primary causes of water losses according to their importance and 91% of the participants expressed their willingness to have training on these topics.

Figure 3. Results of the participants for primary reasons of water losses.

In Section 3, the participants were asked to evaluate benefits of reducing water losses according to their importance and 88% of them expressed their willingness to have training on these topics.

In Section 4, calculation of water loss components and SWB table were assessed by the participants according to its difficulty level and 86% of the participants expressed their willingness to have training on these topics.

In Section 5, the participants were asked for their willingness to have training on establishing a Geographic Information System (GIS) database, installation of monitoring systems (SCADA etc.), hydraulic modeling of distribution network and calibration, isolation of the network into DMAs, detection and reduction of physical losses through ALC, management of network pressure, selection, maintenance and installation of material, MNF analysis, control of apparent water losses, use of management software including integration of GIS, SCADA and customer information systems at the DMA level, calculation of SWB, ILI and other indicators at the DMA level. More than 80% of the participants expressed their strong willingness to have training on the mentioned topics.

Figure 4. Results of the participants for benefits of reducing water losses.

Figure 5. Results of the participants for calculation of water loss components and SWB table.

Regarding the efficiency and reliability in urban WSS, the participants evaluated the importance of detection and control of post-meter leakages in public areas, conducting awareness campaigns and training sessions to prevent water wastage in public areas, implementation of a cost-based approach in water pricing, considering economic water losses level in water losses control practices, raising awareness and conducting training on the effects of climate change on water resources. For this particular section, 85% of the participants expressed their willingness to have training on these topics.

Figure 6. Results of the participants for calculation of water loss components and standard water balance table.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The on-going project described here addresses quantity management of water in urban areas which are under high risks due to conflicting issues of increasing population, increasing water demands, water scarcity and adverse impacts of climate change on water resources. This project aims at reducing water demand in urban WSS by reducing water losses and NRW, introducing specific key performance indicators for measuring water supply management (such as domestic water demand per capita (L/cap/day), ILI, energy use for consumed/billed water (kWh/m³), water saving (mainly reductions in post-meter leakages) and efficient water tariffs. This is crucial for both the overall and the specific objectives of the project which are to improve resilience of communities and cities and to protect natural water resources by reducing the pressure on them. As a major result of the project, the project team was successful to reduce water losses below the Turkish regulatory limit of 25% at the pilot study area. Additionally, ILI values were below 4, which indicates the best class for developing countries. The participation of Maltese partners in the project provided exchange of know-how and experience between Türkiye and Malta. The experience gained in this project will contribute to reduction of water losses in Antalya and other cities of Türkiye both in short and long terms as the results of the project are continuously disseminated through training workshops, project website and social media accounts. All municipalities in Türkiye are prone to expected future urban water demand variations and forecasted impacts of climate change.

Therefore, they should take necessary actions that increase the reliability of urban WSS. Training workshops and all dissemination activities of the project are directly related to improving reliability of urban WSS and to support climate change adaptation capacity of the municipalities in Türkiye.

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Greenhouse application of boron carbon oxynitride (BCNO) nanocomposite material as novel luminescent solar concentrator. Effects on growth and organoleptic quality of lettuce and basil plants

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Abstract

In the present study greenhouse experiments were conducted in order to investigate the effects of a novel luminescent solar concentrator (LSC) -boron carbon oxynitride (BCNO)- on growth, morphological and Physiological characteristics of lettuce and basil plants, grown hydroponically. The LSC compound emits strong blue light after absorption of UV light therefore may contribute to the quantity of light absorbed by chlorophyll of plants at that region. We used two experimental greenhouses (50m² each) with the same microclimate conditions. The first one was covered with plastic film and was used as the control and the second one was covered with plastic film, sprayed on the inner side with the luminescent solar concentrator solution. Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L., cv. 'Romana') and Basil (*Ocimum basilicum* var. "Agioritikos") plants were grown hydroponically in both experimental greenhouses in an experimental arrangement of randomized complete groups with three replications for each plant species. The nutrient solution was provided to the plants by drip irrigation at pH 5.7 and EC 1.8. The experimental results showed improved plant growth rates during cultivation time of Lettuce and Basil plants in the case of the presence of the covering nanocomposite material (BCNO). Similar results were obtained regarding the morphological and Physiological characteristics of the plants (dry biomass production, photosynthesis rate, transpiration rate and stomatal carbon dioxide (CO₂) conductance. These marginal consistent positive effects indicate that materials such as BCNO are promising for such an application in protected farming but needs more extend experimental investigation.

Keywords: luminescent solar concentrators, greenhouses, *Ocimum basilicum* var. "Agioritikos", plant growth rates'

Technical assessment of a hybrid renewable energy system for meeting water and electricity demand on the island of Mykonos

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Abstract

This study examines the technical feasibility of implementing a hybrid renewable energy system (HRES) to address water and electricity demand of Mykonos island. The island faces persistent challenges, including water scarcity and significant population fluctuations driven by tourism, with its population increasing up to tenfold during peak seasons. Two scenarios are being evaluated based on a one-hour timestep simulation, utilizing the existing infrastructure, consisting of water reservoirs (3,900,000 m³ in total), 22 wind turbines (50.6 MW), a desalination plant (1,000 m³/hour) and water pumps (1,500 m³/hour). In the first scenario, the system prioritizes meeting 99.99% of the island's water demand, while electricity demand is also being fulfilled – to a certain degree (72.58%). In the second scenario, electricity demand is prioritized (79.16%), with water demand fulfilled at 62.95%. This investigation highlights the project's potential to address both the water and electricity demand of the island sustainably.

Keywords: HRES, water scarcity, electricity demand, desalination plant, wind turbines, desalination.

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is a vital resource, influenced by both natural processes and human activities like urbanization, agriculture, and industry. These factors, along with climate change [1], impact water availability through reduced soil absorption, pollution, and groundwater depletion [2]. Population growth increases water demand across sectors, putting pressure on water supplies and aquifers [3]. Effective water management, including hydraulic works and conservation technologies, is essential to address these challenges [4].

Renewable energy sources (RES) play a key role in sustainable water management, especially for energy-intensive processes like desalination [5]. In Greece, islands such as Mykonos face water scarcity, exacerbated by tourism and over-extraction of groundwater. Renewable energy, particularly solar and wind, can power desalination plants, providing a sustainable solution to water shortages while reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Integrated water and energy management, supported by RES, is crucial for adapting to climate change [6]. Strategic investments and policies can transform Greek islands into models of green development, ensuring water and energy sustainability, enhancing resilience to environmental challenges, and improving the quality of life for residents.

2. METHODOLOGY

The investigation was carried out considering the water and energy needs of Mykonos. The wind farm includes 22 wind turbines with a total capacity of 50.6 MW, exceeding the energy demand of the island by 1.5 times. The PS includes four desalination plants (1,400 m³/h), two reservoirs (total 3,900,000 m³) and hydroelectric power plants. The wind turbines are placed at an altitude of 280-300 m, in accordance with the legislation. The wind data were adjusted based on the exponential law and converted from three-hour to hourly steps with linear interpolation for greater accuracy. Estimating water demand in Mykonos is difficult due to the use of private boreholes and unofficial sources. Tourist traffic dramatically increases consumption in the summer months, with a population of up to 130,000 people. Daily water consumption is estimated at 250 liters/person, while electricity consumption ranges from 2.5 to 3.5 kWh/person per day. The traffic of electric vehicles is calculated based on their number, daily distance (30 km) and energy consumption for each vehicle. The maximum daily energy demand is 350,000 kWh [7].

Irrigation needs are limited, as agriculture has shrunk due to tourism. In contrast, water supply is the biggest challenge [8], with demand at least 10 times higher than for irrigation. Two scenarios for the operation of the HRES have been developed, which differ in terms of prioritizing the distribution of electricity generated by wind turbines [9].

In the first scenario, priority is given to the supply of electricity to the desalination plants to meet water needs. Any surplus electricity is allocated to pumped storage, and if the reservoirs are filled or the maximum capacity of the pumps is reached, the excess energy is used to meet the electricity needs of consumers. If the water needs are not met and the reservoir volume exceeds 30% of its maximum capacity, the hydroelectric power plant is activated to generate electricity, which is fed into the desalination plants to ensure sufficient water reserves.

In the second scenario, priority is given to meeting electricity demand from consumers. In case of excess electricity, it is used for pumped storage. If the reservoirs are full or the capacity of the pumps has reached the maximum allowable level, then the excess available energy is channeled to the desalination plants to meet the water demand. If the demand for electricity exceeds the supply from the wind turbines, the activation of the hydroelectric power plant shall be considered, provided that the reservoir volume exceeds 30% of its maximum capacity, to enhance the energy supply to consumers.

3. RESULTS

The first scenario demonstrates more stable reservoir levels and consistently high-water availability (Figure 1), indicating effective water resource management. Water demand peaks in summer, but systematic desalination reduces reliance on the reservoir, though some demand remains unmet during peak periods. Hydroelectric production is lower as water conservation is prioritized, with the plant mainly supplying energy for desalination. Overall, unmet water demand is nearly zero, making this scenario highly efficient in ensuring a reliable water supply.

In the second scenario, the reservoir level drops sharply after June (Figure 4), unable to meet summer demand, leading to near depletion by October. Water demand spikes during

summer, but desalination only covers part of it, causing shortages, especially from May to September. Hydropower generation increases in summer but remains insufficient to meet energy needs, indicating potential capacity issues or poor water resource management. The largest unmet water demand occurs during summer, particularly between June and September, emphasizing the need for better water storage, desalination capacity, and energy production to handle seasonal peaks.

The reservoir level remains high during winter but drops sharply from June onward, coinciding with peak demand. This indicates that the stored water is insufficient to meet summer needs, leading to near-total depletion by October. The findings highlight the necessity for improved water resource management to ensure adequate supply throughout the year.

Figure 15. Reservoir water level - Scenario 1.

In contrast to energy, the unmet water demand in this scenario is nearly zero. The effective use of desalination, combined with the maintenance of the reservoir level, ensures full coverage of water needs throughout the year. This makes the second scenario particularly efficient in meeting water demand.

Despite better water resource management, the first scenario shows a higher percentage of unmet energy demand (Figure 2). This is due to the low hydropower production, as the reservoir water is not utilized to the same extent for energy generation. Unmet energy demand is notably higher during the summer months when total energy demand peaks, highlighting the challenge of balancing water conservation with energy production.

Figure 2. Unmet energy demand - Scenario 1.

In the first scenario, hydroelectric production is significantly lower compared to the second, as shown in Figure 7. Fewer periods of high energy generation indicate that priority is given to preserving water reserves rather than maximizing hydropower output. The hydroelectric plant operates primarily to supply energy for desalination, which explains the reservoir's stability. While some small production peaks occur during summer due to increased energy demand, they remain limited in both duration and intensity.

Figure 3. Energy produced by hydropower station - Scenario 1.

In the second Scenario, the reservoir level remains high during winter but drops sharply from June onward, coinciding with peak demand (Figure 4). This indicates that the stored water is insufficient to meet summer needs, leading to near-total depletion by October. The findings highlight the necessity for improved water resource management to ensure adequate supply throughout the year.

Figure 4. Reservoir water level - Scenario 2.

Unmet water demand is most evident during the summer months, with the largest shortages occurring between June and September (Figure 5). This indicates that the existing water supply infrastructure is insufficient to meet the high demand of the tourist season, highlighting the need for improvements in water storage and distribution systems.

Figure 5. Unmet water demand - Scenario 2.

Unmet energy demand increases significantly during summer, peaking between July and September due to seasonal population growth and higher cooling needs. From November to April, shortages are minimal, indicating that the system can meet demand in low seasons (Figure 6). However, during peak periods, deficits exceed 100,000 kWh, emphasizing the urgent need for additional energy sources or system optimizations to address these shortages.

Figure 6. Unmet energy demand - Scenario 2.

Hydropower generation fluctuates and increases during summer in response to higher demand (Figure 7). However, total production remains insufficient to fully meet energy needs, contributing to significant shortages. This suggests that either the hydroelectric station's capacity is inadequate, or water resource management is suboptimal, highlighting the need for improvements to ensure maximum energy production during critical periods.

Figure 7. Energy produced by hydropower station - Scenario 2.

In Scenario 1 (water demand coverage, pumped storage, energy coverage, which is the last priority, is at 72.58%, while water demand coverage reaches 99.99%, which is the main priority. In Scenario 2 (energy coverage, pumped storage, water demand coverage), energy coverage, which is the primary priority, stands at 79.16%, while water demand coverage is at 62.95%.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The first scenario demonstrates more stable reservoir levels and consistently high-water availability, indicating effective water resource management. Water demand peaks in summer, but systematic desalination reduces reliance on the reservoir, though some demand remains unmet during peak periods. Hydroelectric production is lower as water conservation is prioritized, with the plant mainly supplying energy for desalination. Overall, unmet water demand is nearly zero, making this scenario highly efficient in ensuring a reliable water supply.

In the second scenario, the reservoir level drops sharply after June, unable to meet summer demand, leading to near depletion by October. Water demand spikes during summer, but desalination only covers part of it, causing shortages, especially from May to September. Hydropower generation increases in summer but remains insufficient to meet energy needs, indicating potential capacity issues or poor water resource management. The largest unmet water demand occurs during summer, particularly between June and September, emphasizing the need for better water storage, desalination capacity, and energy production to handle seasonal peaks. Future research on the HRES in Mykonos should focus on integrating advanced technologies like large-scale energy storage and innovative desalination methods, exploring financing and pricing models, optimizing energy management through AI, assessing performance under various climatic and economic conditions, and evaluating social acceptance and environmental impacts to enhance system efficiency, resilience, and sustainability.

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Climate resilience of trees in urban areas through the science of phenology

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Abstract

Urban ecosystems are known to produce large amounts of greenhouse gases, thus intensifying the effects of climate change. Urban trees play an important role in them as they could contribute to mitigating the effects of climate change by storing carbon in tree tissue and sequestering atmospheric carbon. Resilience is a measure of the urban tree's adaptability to a range of stresses as their ability to extreme temperatures or withstand high winds. Plant phenology is a branch of science dealing with the relations between climate and periodic biological phenomena (such as budburst, plant flowering, or dormancy). Some species are more resistant than others to climate change, so when designing urban green spaces and selecting appropriate species, this is a parameter that should be taken very seriously into consideration. Main aim of this paper is to present the most resistant species according to the data based on monitoring. To estimate the resilience of tree species in climate change through the science of plant phenology, three Phenological Monitoring Areas (PMA) were created in three urban spaces in Thessaloniki area, in December 2020, within the framework of the project LIFE CliVut (Climate Value of Urban Trees) LIFE18 GIC/IT/001217. Each PMA contains 20 species (10 species of trees and 10 species of shrubs), 100 individuals (5 individuals per species). The monitoring of the phenological stages of the forestry species was carried out throughout 4 years on a weekly basis according to the protocol that was created in the frame of the same project considering BBCH scale. The species *Fraxinus angustifolia*, *Acer campestre*, *Sorbus domestica*, *Quercus ilex*, *Cornus sanguinea*, *Euonymus europaeus*, *Punica granatum*, *Phillyrea latifolia*, *Spartium junceum*, *Ligustrum vulgare* showed better resistance to climatic conditions.

Keywords: plant phenology, urban areas, urban trees, climate resilience

Desalination technology – is the answer to water scarcity on the Greek Islands?

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Abstract

Water scarcity is a significant issue for many Greek Islands, particularly during the dry summer months, when tourist demand increases and rainfall is limited. While water treatment technologies provide a promising solution, they must be integrated into a broader strategy that includes water conservation, renewable energy adoption, and local efforts to improve water management. It is clear that only through a holistic approach can the Greek Islands effectively address their water challenges in the long term. This paper presents an overview of the current state of desalination on the Greek Islands, focusing on the technology, its implementation, economics, and environmental concerns. The environmental impact of energy consumption, from fossil fuels used in desalination, is analysed, along with the unique challenges of using renewable energies on both interconnected and non-interconnected islands.

Keywords: Islands, water scarcity, renewables, environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Desalination technology offers a valuable solution to address water scarcity on the Greek Islands, where freshwater resources are often limited due to geographic and climatic factors. Many of these islands, including those with high populations and/or high levels of tourism, as well as smaller, more remote ones, face significant challenges in securing a consistent and reliable freshwater supply. In addition to the consequences of climate change, such as, high temperatures, longer lasting droughts, tourism also plays a significant role in impacting water availability and the effective management of this valuable resource. The high demand for water in tourist destinations, especially during peak seasons, can place considerable strain on local water supplies, often resulting in shortages that necessitate solutions, such as water transportation by water tankers ships and the rental of desalination units. Moreover, tourism activity, driven by the continuous growth of construction on the islands and the provision of high-standard services by tourist accommodations (such as pools and golf facilities) or private villas, places immense pressure on water resources. Furthermore, sustainable operation of tourism facilities can significantly contribute to minimizing their water footprint through actions such as measuring consumption, implementing water-saving practices, monitoring leaks, and training staff while raising awareness among guests.

Even outside the tourist season, meeting the growing demand for water in the Greek Islands is challenging due to dwindling freshwater reserves, the ineffectiveness of artificial lakes and dams (water reservoirs) caused by prolonged droughts, and the salinization of groundwater due to excessive and many times illegal drilling. The illegal drilling of wells and

the exceeding of existing permits create additional problems in addressing water scarcity on Greek Islands [1]. These practices contribute to over-extraction of groundwater, leading to issues such as seawater intrusion (water resource salinization), depletion of aquifers, and further deterioration of water quality, worsening the already existing water supply challenges. Moreover, rainwater harvesting is no longer widely used on many islands due to less consistent or lower rainfall, infrastructure deterioration and increased water demand.

As a result, desalination of brackish (BW) and seawater (SW) has become increasingly crucial for ensuring a reliable water supply. Reverse Osmosis (RO) has become the preferred method on the Greek Islands, serving both public (municipal) and private needs (e.g., hotels, villas). Reverse Osmosis offers several advantages, such as providing potable water, requiring less energy compared to thermal desalination technologies (Multi-Stage Flash-MSF, Multi-Effect Distillation-MED, Vapor Compression-VC) for seawater; and Electrodialysis (ED) for high brackish (BW) and seawater (SW) desalination. In addition, Reverse Osmosis (RO) systems are modular, easy to operate, fully automated, and can be installed in specially designed containers when necessary. The flexibility in the dynamic operation of the units (modularity) allows for seasonal adjustments and operation based on water demand.

The main challenges in improving water availability on the Greek Islands include the proper maintenance of existing water reservoirs, maximizing the production of high-quality potable water through RO desalination, upgrading aging water networks, and implementing telemetering and leak detection systems for efficient water resource management. These systems help control water distribution networks, ensuring optimal water usage and minimizing losses due to leaks. Several islands, including Thira, Syros, Naxos, Chios, and others, have already adopted these technologies, combining them with telemetering and leak detection systems while gradually upgrading their water networks.

The objective of this study is to evaluate the application of Reverse Osmosis on the Greek Islands, focusing on the environmental impact of brine disposal and energy consumption from fossil fuels, while addressing the unique challenges of using renewable energy on both interconnected and non-interconnected islands.

2. OVERVIEW OF WATER DESALINATION ON THE GREEK ISLANDS

Desalination technology was first introduced in Greece in 1964 with the design and construction of solar distillation plants, commonly known as solar stills. Between 1964 and 1973, several solar distillation plants were established on various islands, including Symi, Megisti, Aegina, and Salamis, with the largest plant built on Patmos Island in 1967. In the 1970s, a Multi-Stage Flash (MSF) unit, capable of producing 1200,0 m³ of distillate water daily, was installed on Syros Island for municipal use. In 1977, the first brackish water desalination plant, utilizing Electrodialysis Reversal (EDR) technology, was installed on Corfu Island, with a daily capacity of 15.000,0 m³.

In 1981, Reverse Osmosis (RO) technology was introduced to the Greek market for seawater desalination (Figure 1). The first RO plants were installed on five Aegean islands, on Mykonos, Syros, Thira, Nisyros, and Megisti, and on the Ionian island of Ithaki, as it is presented in Table 1. The first Reverse Osmosis (RO) plants had a high installed power, despite the use of energy recovery devices, primarily Pelton wheels, to reduce energy consumption. During this period, the specific energy consumption of seawater reverse

osmosis (SWRO) plants was notably high, averaging around 6.5 kWh/m³, with smaller capacity plants consuming even more. For example, the SWRO plant in Mykonos, with a nominal capacity of 1200,0 m³/day, had an installed power of 700 kW, while the 400,0 m³/day SWRO plant on Thira had an installed power of approximately 150 kW, [2].

Currently, a significant number of RO units are operating on the Greek Islands, with seawater desalination being the primary method (Table 2, Figure 2). According to available data, more than 120 RO units are installed on the Aegean and Ionian islands for public use, with a total daily capacity exceeding 100,000 cubic meters of potable water.

a.

b. Source: CRES

Figure 1a, b. First Reverse Osmosis plants on Ithaki and Mykonos islands [2].

The nominal capacity of the installed plants is ranged from around 20 to 4500,0 m³/day total water capacity, with some exceptions of BWRO units in the range of up to 10.000,0 m³/day. A significant number of SWRO units have been installed on the islands of Mykonos and Syros. Specifically, in Syros, the annual water production from SWRO plants reaches approximately 2,000,000 cubic meters. Desalination occurs at the DEYAS (Municipal Water Supply and Sewerage Company of Syros) SWRO plants in the Agios Dimitrios area of Hermoupolis, as well as at plants located in Vari, Poseidonia, Kini, and Galissas.

Table 1. First seawater RO plants on the Greek Islands

Location	Technology	Nominal Water Capacity (m ³ /day)	ERD	Year of Operation
Korfos, Mykonos	SWRO	500,0 (2x250,0)	-	1981
Ithaki	SWRO	500,0	yes	1983
Hermoupolis, Syros	SWRO	1200,0 (2x600,0)	yes	1989
Korfos, Mykonos	SWRO	1200,0 (2x600,0)	yes	1989
Megisti	SWRO	50,0	no	1991
Mandraki, Nisyros	SWRO	300,0	no	1991
Oia, Thira	SWRO	400,0	yes	1992
Hermoupolis, Syros	SWRO	800,0	yes	1993
Kini, Syros	SWRO	144,0	no	1993

The specific energy consumption of SWRO plants has decreased in recent years and typically ranges from 2.5 to 5.0 kWh/m³, while for BWRO plants, it is generally below 2.0 kWh/m³, [7]. This relatively low energy consumption is largely attributed to advancements in technology, including the development of high-efficiency energy recovery devices (ERD) for SWRO plants, along with the integration of high-efficiency pumps and improvements in membrane technology. In contrast to the previously mentioned RO plants, more recent SWRO plants highlight the advancements in technology and the reduction of the carbon footprint of ROs. For instance, the 1000,0 m³/day (2x500 m³/day) plant in Galysas, Syros Island (including ERD), has a nominal installed power capacity of 170 kW while the 500 m³/day SWRO in Kini Syros Island has a nominal installed power of 130 kW, also including energy recovery device [3].

The typical capital cost (CAPEX) of SWRO systems in Greece ranges from €450,0 to €1200,0 per cubic meter, while the capital cost for BWRO systems is generally lower. The average operational cost (OPEX) of RO systems on the Greek Islands ranges from €0.25 to €3.0 per cubic meter, depending on factors such as feed water quality, plant capacity, site characteristics, and other variables. Energy requirements account for a significant portion, approximately 35-40%, of the operational costs of RO plants.

a. Source: DEYA Chios

b. Source: DEYA Thiras

Figure 2a, b. Reverse Osmosis plants in Chios and Thira Aegean Islands [10, 11].

Recently, with the severe rise in energy prices, many Municipal Water Supply and Sewerage Companies (DEYAs) are facing the challenge of managing the increasing cost of water provision. The idea of utilizing energy from Renewable Energy Sources (RES) has become a viable alternative, and some islands have already begun addressing this challenge.

Table 2. Indicative RO plants on the Greek Islands

Location	Technology	Nominal Water Capacity (m ³ /day)	Year of Operation
Linari, Chios	SWRO	2x1164,0	2024
Tholos, Chios	BWRO	1296,0	2022
Fourni	SWRO	100,0	2021
Argostoli, Kefalonia	BWRO	10.000,0	2019
Heraklia	SWRO	300,0	2018
Pserimos	SWRO	100,0	2017
Telendos	SWRO	100,0	2017
Almyros, Crete	BWRO	2000,0	2014
Mykonos	SWRO	4500,0	2008

3. ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES OF RO PLANTS

The environmental impacts of RO plants primarily concern the feed water intake, brine disposal and energy consumption.

3.1 Feed water intake and brine disposal process

Considering the technical characteristics of the RO technology, it can be mentioned that a SWRO plant designed with a recovery ratio of 42% and a daily product water capacity of 2000,0 cubic meters requires approximately 4762,0 m³/day of feed water (seawater intake). The resulting brine disposal of the SWRO will have a capacity of 2762,0 m³/day, with a salinity of around 75.000 ppm in the case of Aegean seawater, (approx. 43.500 ppm TDS salinity), and a concentration factor (CF) of 1.72. Table 3 presents general design data of BWRO and SWRO plants [4, 7]. Moreover, the quality of the brine disposal is influenced not only by the feed water characteristics and concentration factor of the desalination plant but also by the pre-treatment chemicals (such as polymer additives, acids, chlorination, corrosion inhibitors, and de-chlorination), which depend on both the feed water quality and the intake system. Additionally, post-treatment and chemicals used for membrane cleaning also play a role in determining the brine quality.

Table 3. General design data for Reverse Osmosis Plants

	BWRO	SWRO
Feed water salinity, ppm TDS	<10.000,0	35.000,0-45.000,0
Recovery, (R) %	55-80	35-45
Pressure of operation, bar	15-25	50-75
Specific energy, kWh/m ³	<2	<5 with energy recovery device

Marine disposal can be minimized through various technological improvements, such as mixing, dilution, and diffusion. However, these methods are typically more suitable for large SWRO plants, which the Greek islands may not be able to afford. In general, the following unsafe scenarios should be considered:

- Brine discharged into a closed basin with insufficient mixing processes.
- Brine discharged near sensitive environments.
- High concentrations of desalination plants or other industrial activities in a specific area.

Additionally, the feed water intake system in large SWRO plants is a significant issue for marine life, which is why beach wells are often preferred. Beach wells draw water from the seabed, helping to minimize harm to marine organisms by filtering out larger debris and preventing direct intake from the surface, where many aquatic species reside. This method is generally considered more environmentally friendly than open intake systems, as it reduces the risk of harm to marine life. It is also employed in several plants on Greek Islands.

In any case, and in accordance with environmental legislation, desalination projects must include an investigation into the environmental impact, as well as the proper placement of the intake and outfall systems.

3.2 RES for desalination on the Greek islands

The operation of Reverse Osmosis (RO) units relies solely on electrical energy, which can be supplied by renewable energy sources (RES), taking advantage of the country's abundant solar and wind potential. However, to ensure continuous operation of the desalination units, a reliable power supply is required, which often necessitates the support of energy storage systems.

Small RO systems can be powered by hybrid off-grid systems (comprising PVs, small wind turbines, and batteries for energy storage), a technically feasible and applied technology in small Greek islands as well as in other countries. Examples of such systems can be found on the islands of Stroglyi and Agathonisi [4]. Larger existing desalination plants and future facilities can be powered by the high potential of RES resources available on the Greek islands, considering factors such as the limitations on RES penetration into the islands' electrical grids, seasonality, future plans for interconnecting Non-Interconnected Islands (NIIs), and the use of energy storage systems. Furthermore, desalination could serve as an ideal balancing solution, being activated during periods of high wind availability or high solar irradiation, with water storage offering a more cost-effective alternative to expensive electricity storage systems.

Non-Interconnected Islands are supplied by autonomous power stations, primarily based on oil generation units (diesel and heavy fuel for small and medium systems) and some steam turbines in the larger Non-Interconnected Islands, such as Rhodes. Diesel generators are among the most polluting forms of energy generation, with CO₂ emissions estimated to range from 780,0 to 1100,0 g/kWh, which are comparable to, and in the case of older generators, likely significantly worse than those of coal, [5].

From 1.11.2021 Crete is characterized as "Part of the Connection System," meaning that the Crete electrical system has been integrated into the interconnected electricity system and is no longer part of the Non-Interconnected Islands (NII). Based on that the Non-Interconnected Islands (NIIs), consists of twenty-eight (28) autonomous electrical systems, with a total capacity of around 1GW, categorized as follows:

- One (1) large system (peak load over 200 MW, Rhodes Island)
- Eleven (11) medium systems (peak load ranging from 5 MW to 100 MW)
- Sixteen (16) small systems (peak load up to 5 MW)

Many of the thermal power stations on NIIs, facing several key challenges, including the aging of power stations, high seasonality of demand (with significant variations between base load and peak load), various technical and contractual difficulties and technical limitations in exploiting RES production, [6]. The cost of electricity produced is high, ranging from around 200 €/MWh in large NIIs to more than 800 €/MWh in small NIIs. Moreover, the contribution of RES, particularly wind and PV plants, is also significant on these islands, accounting for an average of 20% of the total electricity production.

Source: IPTO

Figure 3. The map of electrical interconnection to be completed by 2030 (in Greek).

Figure 3 presents the existing electrical interconnection (blue line) and the planning investments of up to 2030, aiming to gradually interconnect all of the country's islands to the mainland (red and green lines), [8]. The complete interconnection of the Cyclades, the Dodecanese, the majority of the North Aegean islands, and Crete with the mainland, along with the enhancement of the transmission system, will provide the necessary infrastructure to harness the islands' high renewable energy potential. This will also result in significant environmental benefits by facilitating the reduction and gradual elimination of existing thermal power plants. Furthermore, the interconnection will lower electricity production costs

and reduce the cost of water produced by desalination units. It will also create opportunities for the development of new RES systems, although there are some limitations.

3.3 Wind energy for desalination – A case study

Based on a preliminary study conducted by CRES for Syros Island [3], to meet the load requirements of the island's SWRO plants, which have an estimated total installed capacity of around 2 MW, it appears that selecting wind turbines (WTs) with a total capacity of approximately 5 MW is the most suitable option, assuming an estimated Capacity Factor (CF) of up to 50%. The average wind speed in the area is 7.7 m/s, with the prevailing direction being North and the secondary direction North-Northeast. Considering the nominal power of commercially available WT models commonly found in the Greek market, it is determined that the investment for supplying the desalination units could focus on two WTs with a nominal capacity of approximately 2.5 MW each.

For selecting the required locations for the installation of the WTs, suitable areas across the entire island were considered (6 sites), taking into consideration the legal requirement for a minimum distance of 2.5 times the rotor diameter between two WTs, and a minimum distance from the nearest moving part of the WT to the boundaries of neighboring plots equal to the length of the blade radius. Given that the diameters of the WTs in question range from 80 to 90 meters, the potential plots must be approximately 400 meters long and 200 meters wide if a single area is selected (i.e., around 40 acres per turbine).

Taking into account various losses, including electrical losses, availability, weather conditions, and others, the overall system efficiency was optimized for local conditions. Net energy production was estimated to range between approximately 14 GWh and 20 GWh annually across the sites under study, with the latter site considered the most efficient.

Finally, the average wind speed and turbulence intensity play a crucial role in selecting the appropriate class of wind turbines. For the wind conditions of the island, Class IA wind turbines are considered the most suitable option, although Class II turbines could also be considered, depending on discussions with the manufacturer and the final location chosen.

Based on current market prices the CAPEX of wind turbines of this nominal capacity is around €1250,0/kW while the OPEX could be approximately of 3% of the initial cost. The installation cost (CAPEX) refers to the total cost of installing the system (studies, permits, equipment purchase, transportation, infrastructure work, installation, commissioning, etc.). The operational cost (OPEX) refers to the total work and materials required to support the system's operation (monitoring, routine maintenance, emergency repairs, spare parts, consumables, insurance, security, etc.), distributed evenly throughout the lifespan of the installation.

3.4 RES Desalination – Applications on the Greek islands

Despite the high solar and wind energy potential of the Greek islands, only a few desalination plants powered by renewable energy sources (RES) are currently in operation.

One notable example concerns Milos Island, where a SWRO plant with a total daily production capacity of 4500,0 cubic meters are powered by a wind turbine with a nominal capacity of 850 kW, [7]. The wind turbine was installed at the existing "Aioliki Milou S.A." wind farm located in Koutsounorachi. More analytically, between 2007 and 2009, as part of the national Operational Programme for Competitiveness (EPAN), Measure 6.3.2, a 3600,0 m³/day (3×1200,0 m³/day) SWRO plant was installed on Triovasalos, to meet the island's

water needs. A grid-connected wind turbine (WT) V52/850 kW provides the necessary energy for the operation of the RO unit (Figure 4). Additionally, a SCADA system is used to efficiently manage and remotely monitor both the desalination plant and the wind farm, ensuring seamless integration with the island's electrical grid.

A 2.8 km pipeline connects the desalination plant to the storage tanks. The island is equipped with four municipal potable water storage tanks, with a total capacity of 5000,0 cubic meters, all connected to the island's distribution network.

The initial overall budget for the project was €4.8 million, with a subsidy of approximately 40%. The company supplies potable water to the municipality of Milos at a rate of around €2 per cubic meter. The Wind SWRO plant is a state-of-the-art BOO (Build, Own, Operate) project, marking the first of its kind in the country.

The project's goal was to provide potable water, significantly improving the quality of life for the island's residents while also creating opportunities for local development, such as boosting tourism and small industries. Prior to the commissioning of the plant in the summer of 2007, the island relied on water transported by tanker boats from mainland, mixed with brackish water from local wells.

a.

b. Source: ITA Group

c.

d. Source: ITA Group

Figure 4 a, b, c, d. Wind -SWRO plant in Milos Island, [7].

Additionally, during the same period, and under the same programme (EPAN), Measure 6.3.2, a Wind Mechanical Vapor Compression (MVC) plant for seawater desalination was installed on Symi Island, [7], (Figure 5). The MVC plant produces 20 m³ per hour of distillate water, directly powered by a 350 kW wind turbine with a hub height of 60 meters and a rotor

diameter of 45 meters, [9]. The project was innovative and faced several challenges in its operation and maintenance due to the island's remote location and the complexities associated with the desalination technology.

a.

b.

Source: WME GmbH

Figure 5 a, b. Wind – MVC plant on Symi Island, [9].

A recent project involves the installation and operation of a SWRO plant with a daily water capacity of 200 cubic meters, powered by a 60 kWp photovoltaic station on Thirasia Island, Cyclades [12]. As reported, the SWRO plant consumes 50 kW of power, while the expected annual production from the photovoltaic station is approximately 80,000 kWh (Figure 6).

a.

b. Source: DEYA Thiras

Figure 6 a, b. Thirasia PV seawater Reverse Osmosis plant, [12].

The project was supervised by the Municipal Water Supply and Sewerage Company of Thira (DEYATH) and implemented in collaboration with the University of Stavanger, Norway, with the goal of improving the efficiency and reliability of the infrastructure. The total project cost is €0.83 million. The project funded by the EEA Grants for the 2014-2021 period, national resources through the Development and Investment Programme, and by the Municipal Water Supply and Sewerage Company of Thira.

4. SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE OF RES-DESALINATION PROJECTS

Social acceptance is a critical factor that must be considered in all renewable energy (RES) and desalination projects. Public awareness and effective information sharing are essential for the sustainability and success of such projects. It is crucial to analyze and communicate the benefits of RES and desalination installations, focusing on the sensitive environments of the islands, the local population, tourism investors, and island visitors, in order to encourage the adoption of energy and water-saving measures. Raising awareness and engaging the local community, scientific community, and general public is key to the islands' sustainability, protecting their sensitive environment, and promoting a better quality of life.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Desalination can address water scarcity on the Greek islands; however, specific conditions and limitations must be met. Desalination technology should be employed to provide potable water to citizens, while simultaneously implementing water conservation measures and promoting water-saving practices. These efforts should include efficient water management, the reduction of water losses, and the reuse of treated wastewater, ensuring that desalination is integrated into a broader strategy for sustainable water use on the islands. The integration of renewable energy sources (RES) is essential for reducing the carbon footprint of desalination and protecting the islands' sensitive environment.

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ARSINOE Project Special Session

Integrated cross - sectoral adaptiveness to water scarcity induced by climate changes and economy growth

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Abstract

Water scarcity escalating by long and frequent droughts is becoming a raising trend in many regions globally. Environmental, social and economy sectors have been jeopardized thereby, in their survival, operation and development.

Water resources sustainable planning and management in long term has to respond to new challenges, due to more intensive and uncertain climate change impacts, demographic trends and economic growth, resulting in more intensive water resource demands.

There is a need to develop and deploy comprehensive, multidisciplinary and complex analytical approaches that can show a correct identification and setting of water issues, enabling decision making under deep uncertainty and including all affected sectors in solving solutions. This is particularly of importance in case of water deficit and scarcity, under conditions of transboundary share of the same water resources

Integrated Water Management Model (IWaMM) is a simulation and optimization model for evaluation of a complex hydro system operation under superposed climate and socio – economic scenarios across coupled sectors. It integrates hydrological processes, climate changes, and use of water in economic sectors and environmental ecosystems, hydropower generation and agriculture, at a hydrological unit (basin, watershed) scale. Simulation includes Business As Usual, as well as adaptiveness strategies, applied in form of measures / actions for rational and effective use of water across sectors, thus ensuring water availability within the analyzed time frame. Multi objective optimization is used for ranking, taking economic value of environmental assets as one of the selection criteria.

The paper presents implementation of the model in the course of the project ARSINOE (<https://arsinoe-project.eu/>) in the Case Study of Ohrid and Prespa Lakes, shared by three countries (North Macedonia, Albania and Greece) to provide an improved representation of integrated transboundary water management under climate change scenarios.

Keywords: *water scarcity, climate resilience and adaptiveness, Integrated cross sectoral water management*

1. INTRODUCTION

IWaMM is an integrated water management model across environmental, social and economy sectors. It calculates and presents results of simulation of a complex hydro system operation under superposed climate and socio – economic scenarios.

The model estimates a long-term water balance under conditions of climate impacts (affecting both supply and demand side of a hydro system), demographic changes and economic sectors (agriculture, industry, seasonal sectors as tourism) foreseen growth, as well as energy generation (hydropower), while taking into consideration environmental constraints (water needs and dependence of environmental ecosystems). It integrates hydrological, meteorological, climate changes and socio –economic processes and impacts thereof on water availability and couples multi sectors water use to provide equilibrium and fair water allocation among water users, in long term conditions.

Simulations include BAU as well as adaptiveness scenarios, applied in form of measures / actions for rational and effective use of water across sectors, thus ensuring water availability within the analyzed time frame.

The core loop is the mass balance as the governing equation set for a hydro system that includes a reservoir (natural - a lake or artificial – dam impounded), supply and demand side, as well as losses, optimizing water preservation in terms of providing a long term availability and preventing overflows as well as water deficit. Calculations include water stocks and flows across sectors, in discrete time steps (mean monthly water volumes), identifying deficits (and time spots of occurrence) that may appear as a result of climate influence or / and sector policy.

The consumers per sectors are taken in consideration, based on a water – energy – food approach, and balanced (available water resources allocated) in a fair priority order, using multi objective optimization for that purpose. Time resolution on a monthly basis (mean monthly values of observed and projected data) is applied, in order to capture seasonal character of some of the users (e.g. agricultures, tourism), which usually coincides with the seasonal minimum of water natural supply or recharge.

In the course of the project ARSINOE, the model has been deployed in the Case Study of Ohrid and Prespa lakes that are shared by three countries in the Balkan Region (North Macedonia, Albania and Greece), in order to provide an improved representation of a climate resilient, cross sectoral and transboundary integrated water management under climate change scenarios. Applying this integrated approach enabled a correct identification and setting of water issues, as well as informed decision making, under deep uncertainty of climate pressures.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of the method

The method is specific in its composition, complementarity and integration of the analytical, planning and simulation part.

- Analytical: Data collection, sectors identification, diagnosis of water scarcity, baseline setting
- Simulation: Climate – hydro climate modelling enables creation of projections that help understand / forecast availability of water in the region and the observed sectors;
- Planning: Identification of endangered sectors, selection of priorities, fair allocation and operation regime, ranking and scheduling of adaption strategies, for a long term management of water resources in a climate resilient manner

Hydro - climate modelling is based on a seven - step methodology:

- Step 1: Setting of the baseline – Analytical part
- Step 2: Development of hydro – climate projections up to the projecting horizon - Simulation part
- Step 3: Water balance projections of the two lakes,
- Step 4: Socio – economic projections (GDP, population growth) that impact water consumption,
- Step 5: Water consumption projection per social and economy sectors
- Step 6: Energy production projection
- Step 7: Identification, ranking and selection of adaptiveness strategies of water use across sectors – Planning part

2.2 Hydro climate projections

2.2.1. Establishing the current water balance of the two lakes

Water balance equation for the two watersheds was established, followed by a mathematical representation of relation between the lakes (groundwater outflow – inflow through karstic masses), along with water demand per sectors. The equations enable calculation of mean annual lake levels.

2.2.2. Selection of modelling parameters

The following parameters for the modelling procedure were adopted:

- Climate scenarios: RCP 2.6 RCP 8.5, with data downscaled from RCMs, CMIP5 series,
- Socio – economic scenarios coupled with selected climate change scenarios: SSP1, SSP5,
- Representative climate change indicators: mean monthly sum of precipitations and mean monthly air temperature,
- Time projection horizon: 2100; milestone: 2050,
- Time resolution: mean monthly data,
- Spatial coverage: watershed areas of Ohrid and Prespa Lake (about 1400 km² each)

2.2.3. Collection and processing of observed (measured) data

- Measured data for the two climate indicators (temperature and precipitation) were provided:
- Ohrid : Two meteorological stations, one in Mk, one in AL, for 1961 -2020 and 1980-2020,
- Prespa: Two meteorological stations, one in Mk, one in AL, for 1981 -2020
- Data on water consumption were provided by analysis of available studies and report, as well as by a field research (communication with municipalities and local water utilities)

The watershed area and location of the measuring points can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Ohrid (1.404 km²) and Prespa watershed (1.360 km²) boundaries and location of meteorological stations (Source: Google maps)

2.2.4 Development of MMEs (dynamical downscale of GCM, RCMs)

Method of development of projections (climate modelling) consists of:

- Select RCMs models from MCIP5
- Make projections of the climate indicators (downscale mean monthly values from the RCMs, In the spots of locations of sources of measured data)
- Develop an ensemble formed of all the applied RCMs – MMEs – multi model ensembles
- Present the ensemble as time series of projected data (mean monthly values) for the subject climate indicator (air temperature, precipitation), in the time period selected for climate modelling (2021 – 2100)
- Compare the ensemble data with observed data time series

Figure 2. Common graph of measured data for Ohrid (1961-2020) and for Pretor (1981-2020), selected 5 projections for Ohrid and 7 for Pretor, of mean annual air temperatures (2021-2100), RCP 2.6

Figure 3. Sum of annual precipitations in Prespa (1980-2100), RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 (measured – blue line; projections – red line)

2.3. Water balance modelling

By applying hydro – climate model outputs in the water balance equation, projections of the water level fluctuations on monthly basis, by 2100, were estimated, for each of the lakes, under the two selected scenarios: RCP 2.6 and RCP8.5.

Application of the projected values of mean monthly sums of precipitation and mean monthly air temperature in the lake water balance equation.

$$St+(P+Q_{in}+G_{in}) - (E+ET+Q_{out}+Q_{ws}+Q_{ir}+G_{out})=St+\Delta t \quad (1)$$

- ST - Initial water storage in the watershed at the beginning of the analyzed period
- P – Input water in the watershed due to precipitation = $f(\text{mean sum of precipitations})$
- Q_{IN} – Input water in the watershed from another watershed G_{in} – Groundwater inflow
- E – Output water due to evaporation from free surface water = $f(\text{mean air temperature})$
- ET – Output water due to evapotranspiration = $f(\text{mean air temperature})$
- Q_{OUT} – Outflow water to another watershed
- Q_{ws} – Used water for population and industry and water supply
- Q_{IR} – Used water for irrigation
- G_{OUT} – Groundwater outflow
- $St+\Delta t$ - Water storage in the watershed at the end of the analyzed period

Simplified form applied in this iteration is therefore (for Prespa Lake):

$$P - (E+ET+G_{out}+ Q_{ws}+Q_{ir}) = \Delta S \quad (2)$$

Mathematical relation of the Ohrid Lake water balance is:

$$S_t + (P+G_{in}) - (E+ET+ Q_{ws}+Q_{ir}) = Q_{out} *T \quad (3)$$

Ohrid Lake water regulated discharge into the Crn Drin River, for RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 is included as an input in the energy module.

This was further improved and aligned to real operational regime of the first HPP in the cascade, as measured (observed) in the past 40 years.

In summary, Lake Prespa is expected to suffer further lowering of the water level, which shows to be more intensive under RCP8.5

The Lake Ohrid would preserve the current span of water level fluctuations, but the regulated discharge for the needs of hydro power generation would decrease under RCP8.5

Figure 4. Water level change of Prespa Lake (1980-2100), RCP 2.6 (measured data – blue line; projections – red line)

Figure 5. Mean monthly water level (masl) of the Ohrid Lake, in the period 1980-2100, RCP 2.6

2.4 Energy generation projections

The energy module was used to calculate the impacts of climate change on lowering of the regulated discharge from the lake Ohrid, on power generation, and therefrom, on power generation in the cascade of five HPPs (two in North Macedonia and three in Albania).

The results showed that under RCP 8.5, the contribution of Ohrid Lake discharge will affect the power generation in HPPs Globocica and Shpilje, by approximately 50% of decrease, whilst the impact on the other three HPPs, downstream, will be below 10% (Tables 1 and 2).

Table 1 Participation of outflow from Ohrid Lake in [GWh] of annual power generation in HPPs

Time period, Climate scenario	Participation of Ohrid Lake waters in power generation [GWh/annual]		
	HPP Globocica (MK)	HPP Shpilje (MK)	HPP Fierza (AL)
1980-2020	113.62	120.68	125.10
2021 – 2100, RCP 2.6	121.14	124.33	160.29
2022 – 2100, RCP 8.5	38.31	64.47	102.29

Table 2. Participation of outflow from Ohrid Lake in [%] of annual power generation in HPPs

Time period, Climate scenario	Participation of Ohrid Lake waters in power generation [% /annual]		
	HPP Globocica (MK)	HPP Shpilje (MK)	HPP Fierza (AL)
1980 2020	67.06	39,34	5,25
2021 – 2100, RCP 2.6	69.74	40,30	6,73
2022 – 2100, RCP 8.5	21.91	21.02	2.29

2.5. Water consumption projections

Water demands were projected for the following social and economic sectors: households, tourism, agriculture and industry. The consumption in 2020 was taken as a baseline, whilst the projections until 2100 were generated taking into account the outputs of socio – economic modeling, the GDP growth and the number of population change. The results of water consumption and allocation are given in the Figure 6 below.

Figure 6. Typical diagram of a water consumption forecast in a municipality

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Analysis of results

The main outputs achieved by the model first run were:

- Projections of selected climate change indicators (mean monthly sum of precipitations, mean monthly air temperature), for RCP 2.6 and 8.5, in the period 2021 – 2100,
- Water balance results on mean monthly basis, separately for Prespa and for Ohrid Lake (2021 – 2100), for the two selected climate scenarios,
- Lakes’ status presented as lake water level on monthly basis, up to the projecting horizon. Projections of mean monthly surface water discharge (Crn Drin River) from the Ohrid Lake, towards the five HPPs downstream (two in North Macedonia, three in Albania)
- Projections of GDP growth in the region,

- Projections of change of population number for six municipalities in the three countries (2021 – 2100, SSP1 and SSP5).
- Projections of water consumption per explored economy sectors (tourism, agriculture, industry, households)
- Projections of availability of water resources (water quantities, water levels) under selected RCP and SSP scenarios, by 2050 and 2100,

In the second run, the following improvements of registered inconsistency and were applied:

- Variation of the groundwater discharge from Prespa Lake, due to variation of the lake water level
- Variation of the values of the selected climate change indicators (mean monthly sum of precipitations and mean monthly air temperature, in the span of +/- 5% and +/-10%, respectively)
- Variation of the water consumption per sectors (in the span of +/- 15%)
- Variation of forecasts of the economic indicators affecting water consumption.

Two boundary scenarios selected for analysis, including RCPs and accompanied SSPs, showed that:

1. Both lakes will be affected by the climate changes,
2. Decrease of water level can be expected at Prespa Lake, in a more severe way for RCP8.5
3. To maintain the water level of Ohrid Lake, regulation of discharge will have to be more limited, which will lead to decrease of hydro power generation,
4. The most affected sectors will be environment, agriculture, and energy sector,
5. Adaption strategies have to be developed in a WEFEE nexus approach, using multi – criteria analysis and decision making approach
6. Cross - sectors and transboundary trade – offs will be further explored, leading to consensual, sustainable, long term solutions of interest for all countries and sectors.
7. This will be applied in the model further runs, for identification and selection of measures for adaptation of the involved sectors, to the forecast water scarcity.
8. Sectoral trade-offs have been identified:
 - between water supply from groundwater sources (households, agriculture), in Prespa lake watershed area,
 - between environment and energy (hydro power generated), at Ohrid Lake watershed
9. No transboundary issues in a common water use and share have been identified.

The main conclusion was that all the observed sectors would have to adapt to the water scarcity in the region, induced by the climate changes (reduced sum of precipitations and increased mean air temperature).

3.2. Defining adaptation strategies

As a part of the Water Allocation (WA) module of IWAMM, projections of water consumption (2021 - 2050 -2100) per economy sectors (industry, irrigation, tourism, households) in two municipalities (Resen and Ohrid, selected as the ones with the highest number of population in each watershed) separately, have been carried out, taking in consideration the changes in economy indicators. Thereby, adaptation measures were

included, in order to find the optimal alternative for future management plan of water resources of transboundary relevance

Based on the SIA applied in 3 consecutive sessions, the following groups of adaptation measures (alternatives A1, A2, A3 and A4) have been identified:

1. A1: Improved measurement and monitoring of water resources, especially of groundwater
2. A2: Improved measurement and monitoring of water consumption
3. A3: Improved (innovative) technologies for effective use of water in sectors
4. A4: Improving capacity, awareness, knowledge and skills of stakeholders and water sector actors, for a rational and effective use of water in adapting to water scarcity

Apart from the economy – society – environment sector adaptivity, additional adaptation options were suggested and discussed, for compensation of losses in hydropower generation, which included: 1) installation of floating photovoltaics in HPP reservoirs,, 2) adaptation of hydro generating units to enable processing of low flows, 3) hydrogen generation in combination with renewable energy sources surplus generation.

3.4. Evaluation and ranking:

For evaluation and ranking, the module of MCDA (Multiple-Criteria Decision Analysis), based on the AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) approach, has been applied, as a subroutine of the WA (Water Allocation) module of IWAMM. The criteria for evaluation have been adopted by taking in consideration the KPIs declared in the GA:

1. Climate resilience (improved sectors' independence on fresh water),
2. Cost effectiveness and grounds set for increase of green investments
3. Environmental positive impacts (more water available for bio systems)
4. Social and economic progress (demographic growth, employment, GDP growth)
5. Area of coverage of the measures – the span of affected sectors and systems

Table 3: Example of evaluation in aspect of criteria of freshwater reduction

Municipality /region	Scenario	Total consumption			Reduction of ffish water comcumpton	
		2020	2050	2100	2050	2100
					%	%
Resen	SSP1	2.232.461	2.725.378	2.849.915	20,905	21,620
	SSP5	2.232.461	3.211.127	4.064.024	20,097	18,798
Prespes	SSP1	1.323.506	1.593.266	1.779.977	19,374	23,405
	SSP5	1.323.506	1.737.575	2.164.470	19,268	23,013
Pogrdac	SSP1	509.395	591.626	582.945	19,270	20,165
	SSP5	509.395	647.231	708.843	18,928	21,525
Prespa Region total	SSP1	4.065.361	4.910.270	5.212.837	20,211	22,067
	SSP5	4.065.361	5.595.933	6.937.337	19,704	20,392

Table 4: Criteria comparison

Criteria Comparison	FW Reduction	Finance	Technical	Environmental	Social	Sum	Average
FW Reduction	1,00	2,00	2,00	5,00	0,25	10,25	0,222
Finance	0,50	1,00	3,00	5,00	3,00	12,50	0,271
Technical	0,50	0,33	1,00	0,20	2,00	4,03	0,087
Environmental	0,20	0,20	5,00	1,00	0,14	6,54	0,142
Social	4,00	0,33	0,50	7,00	1,00	12,83	0,278

Criteria Comparison	FW Reduction	Finance	Technical	Environmental	Social	Sum	Average
FW Reduction	0,16	0,52	0,17	0,27	0,04	1,17	0,233
Finance	0,08	0,26	0,26	0,27	0,47	1,34	0,269
Technical	0,08	0,09	0,09	0,01	0,31	0,58	0,116
Environmental	0,03	0,05	0,43	0,05	0,02	0,60	0,119
Social	0,65	0,09	0,04	0,38	0,16	1,32	0,263
	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	1,00	5,00	1,00

The main outcome of the process of identification, analysis, selection and ranking of recommended adaptation measures (options) is shown on the figure below.

Figure 7. Adaptation measures ranking

In summary,

- Measures for water resources monitoring are the highest ranked set,
- Measures leading to a more efficient and rational water consumption (such as: recycled water use in tourism and industry, up to 30% of the sector total consumption; use of advanced irrigation techniques and technologies, to reduce water consumption by 49%), achieve the second place in the ranking,
- Measures for improved water measurement and monitoring of consumption (reduction of losses in water distribution network up to 15%) take the third place
- Measures for raising awareness take the fourth place in the recommended implementation schedule.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The methodological and mathematical model IWAMM has been applied in the transboundary watershed area of Ohrid and Prespa Lakes, shared by three countries. Two boundary scenarios selected for analysis, including two RCPs and accompanying SSPs, showed that

1. Both lakes will be affected by the climate changes
2. Decrease of water level can be expected at Prespa Lake, especially for RCP8.5
3. To maintain the water level of Ohrid Lake, regulation of discharge will have to be stricter
4. The most affected sectors will be environment, agriculture, and energy.
5. Adaption strategies have to be developed in a WEFEE nexus approach, using multi – criteria analysis and decision making tools.
6. The most effective and successful strategies can be achieved with a comprehensive cross-sectoral integrated model of climate resilience.

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Enhancing Sustainability in Transboundary Regions: Stakeholder Engagement for Climate Resilience in Ohrid and Prespa Lakes under the H2020 ARSINOE Project

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Abstract

Climate impacts, as dynamic complex problems, combined with economic growth and demographic shifts, pose long-term challenges, especially for water-dependent sectors like agriculture, energy, tourism, and environmental systems. Traditional, isolated management approaches are no longer effective, particularly in transboundary regions where shared water resources face increasing pressures. There is a need to develop and implement multidisciplinary and complex innovative approaches, enabling stakeholders and decision makers' engagement, including all affected sectors in developing solutions.

The H2020 ARSINOE project addresses these challenges in the transboundary case study of the Ohrid and Prespa Lakes region, shared by North Macedonia, Albania and Greece. Using System Innovation and Frame Design Thinking methodologies, the project promotes stakeholder and policymaker engagement through national working groups and transboundary living labs. Participatory tools facilitate communication, problem identification and solution development, integrating research, planning and citizen innovation.

This approach supports sustainable, climate-resilient water management by fostering collaboration between the three countries, enabling continuous monitoring and adaptive strategies across sectors. Key outcomes include improved understanding of lake interconnections, integrated data use (hydrology, economy, demography), prioritization of water users and feasible strategies for climate resilience. The project delivers policy and management recommendations to ensure long-term sustainability, balancing water use with economic growth, while ensuring environmental protection in the Ohrid and Prespa region, that are characterized as UNESCO heritage and Biosphere areas.

Keywords: *climate resilience and adaptiveness, water scarcity, System Innovation Approach, Frame Design Innovation Thinking, stakeholder engagement, Ohrid and Prespa Lakes*

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change, coupled with economic growth and demographic shifts, presents an escalating challenge with long-term consequences. Its impact will be profound across all regions, influencing key sectors—particularly those reliant on water, such as **economy, energy, ecosystems and biodiversity, demography, agriculture, fisheries, tourism and**

cultural heritage. Traditional, **sector-specific and nationally - dependent approaches** to water management and planning are increasingly inadequate. These methods fail to address the interconnected nature of water resources, particularly in **transboundary regions**, where multiple stakeholders share the same water bodies. Conventional management strategies struggle to ensure sustainable water availability, making it clear that a **more holistic and integrated approach** is needed. To effectively tackling these challenges, it is essential to develop and implement **multidisciplinary, innovative solutions**. These approaches must facilitate **collaboration among stakeholders and decision-makers** while integrating insights from all affected sectors. By fostering cooperation and innovation, we can create resilient strategies that address **water scarcity, climate adaptation, and sustainable resource management**—especially in regions where water sources cross national boundaries.

As part of the Climate Resilient Regions through Systemic Solutions and Innovations (ARSINOE) project (<https://arsinoe-project.eu/>), a transboundary stakeholder engagement model has been introduced in the case study of Ohrid and Prespa Lakes. Given the complexity of the challenges faced in this shared water ecosystem between North Macedonia, Albania, and Greece, an innovative approach is essential to ensure effective collaboration and decision-making. To enhance stakeholder engagement and address the specific needs of the region, the project implemented a System Innovation Approach combined with Frame Design Innovation Thinking. This methodology aims to foster cross-border cooperation, align policy-making efforts and develop systemic solutions that support climate resilience and sustainable water management in the transboundary lake region.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Area under examination

The **Ohrid - Prespa Lakes system** is a unique interconnected freshwater ecosystem. Lake Ohrid, shared by North Macedonia and Albania, receives water from Prespa Lake through natural underground flows. Ohrid Lake together with Prespa Lake make the Ohrid - Prespa region to be one of the most recognizable UNESCO region, as mixed world heritage site. This transboundary region includes **six protected areas, three internationally recognized wetlands under Ramsar convention and a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve**, making it ecologically and culturally significant. The area also hosts **cascade hydropower plants** utilizing water from the Crn Drim River, as well as a vibrant tourism sector and industries like textiles, food and construction materials.

The Ohrid - Prespa region, located in southwestern Europe (40°40' - 41°2'N latitude; 20°23' - 21°16'E longitude), span the borders of Albania, Greece, and North Macedonia. Lake Ohrid and the Prespa Lakes are part of the Dasseretes basins, formed by tectonic depressions that occurred 2 to 5 million years ago in the western Dinarides. Lake Ohrid (41°2'19"N, 20°44'13"E) is recognized as the oldest lake in Europe, located in the Ohrid valley of southwestern North Macedonia, adjacent to Albania, at an elevation of 693.17 meters above sea level. Approximately two-thirds of its surface area is in North Macedonia, while the remaining third is in Albania. Lake Ohrid is an extraordinary aquatic ecosystem celebrated for its high level of biodiversity, including over 210 endemic species. Its long-standing presence and stable environment facilitate ongoing speciation among its organisms, particularly among benthic fauna, resulting in the creation of new subspecies and species through intralacustrine

speciation, a phenomenon typical of ancient lakes like Lake Baikal. In addition, the Prespa basin displays diverse habitats and houses over 1,300 plant species, prominently featuring the endemic *Lamento-Spirodela polyrrhize aldrovandetosum* community. Lake Prespa is recognized as one of North Macedonia and Greece's Ramsar Sites, valued for its significance as a vital habitat for migratory and breeding birds, as well as its rich biodiversity.

The North Macedonian part of the Prespa and Ohrid Lakes watershed includes of Ohrid and Prespa Lakes. A superlative natural phenomenon, Ohrid Lake provides a refuge for numerous endemic species of freshwater fauna and flora dating from the Tertiary period. Situated on the shores of the lake, the town of Ohrid is one of the oldest human settlements in Europe. Built mainly between the 7th and 19th centuries, it has the oldest Slav monastery (St Pantelejmon) and more than 800 Byzantine-style icons dating from the 11th to the end of the 14th century. In the shallow waters near the shores of the lake, three sites testify to the presence of prehistoric pile dwellings, and the small Lin Peninsula is the site of the remains of an Early Christian church founded in the middle of the 6th century. (<https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/99/>, accessed on 25.2.2025). Ohrid Lake together with Prespa Lake make the Ohrid –Prespa region to be one of the most recognizable UNESCO regions, as mixed world heritage site

The Greek part of the Prespa Lakes watershed is a rural thinly populated area of high importance for the protection of biodiversity, since it provides habitats for several endemic and/or protected species. The area belongs to Natura 2000 network and is protected under both Birds and Habitats Directives. Among others, it hosts one of the larger colonies of the globally Near Threatened *Pelecanus crispus* in the world. The main economic activities of the area are agriculture; fishery and tourism. **Climate change threatens the region's water balance**, impacting ecosystems, agriculture, energy production, and tourism. Studies highlight the urgent need for **climate adaptation measures**, emphasizing sustainable water management, improved governance, and coordinated action among the three countries. Through the **Ohrid and Prespa Lakes case study**, in this research and innovation project, stakeholders are developing a **comprehensive, climate-resilient water governance framework**, ensuring **sustainable water use, ecosystem conservation, and economic well-being**. The initiative fosters cross-border cooperation, aiming to equally address social, economic, and environmental interests while facing climate challenges in this vital transboundary water system.

2.2 Workshop organization

Stakeholder participation in fostering a sustainable region was facilitated through **national working groups and transboundary living labs** across **North Macedonia, Albania, and Greece**. Utilizing **participatory research tools**, the process enabled recruitment of motivated stakeholders to foster **collaboration, problem identification, and future scenario development**, leading to innovative solutions for the region. The approach integrated **analysis, research, planning, product design, and citizen innovation**, ensuring that stakeholder needs were effectively addressed. Over the **first two years** of the project, **national working groups and transboundary living labs** were successfully implemented in all three countries, strengthening regional cooperation and sustainable development efforts. All **national working groups** were conducted simultaneously in **North Macedonia, Albania, and Greece**. These sessions focused on **problem identification** in collaboration with stakeholders from each country. Additionally, **mental maps** reflecting stakeholder

perspectives were developed, providing valuable insights into regional challenges and opportunities, as well as future vision and possible solutions for most sustainable Ohrid and Prespa region on a long term.

Stakeholders were selected and identified from different sectors (water, agriculture, tourism, fishery, energy, academy, culture), categories (government/municipalities, academia, NGOs/associations, business and local citizens), and scale levels (local, regional, national). All three North Macedonian national working groups took place in the Skopje, with the presence of all local and national stakeholders.

1st national Workshop (North Macedonia): The first national workshop took place in June 2022. During this workshop: key climate change indicators were identified, including temperature and precipitation variations, water body status, sectoral vulnerabilities, and the causes and consequences of water scarcity. Discussions highlighted the interconnected impacts of climate change on water quantity and quality, environmental and economic sector dependencies, demographic and socio-economic changes, water pollution sources and poor groundwater management. The most affected sectors include water management, biodiversity and ecosystems, human health, hydropower and renewable energy, agriculture, fishery, and forestry, tourism and cultural heritage and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Key challenges identified were inefficient water use and the need for climate-adaptive strategies, lack of innovation and business models for sustainable water management and insufficient collaboration and information sharing across sectors and countries.

2nd national Workshop (North Macedonia): The second national workshop took place in January 2023 and it was named Future narratives and vision for the Ohrid - Prespa region. The second national working groups gathered stakeholders from North Macedonia to discuss future narratives and a shared vision for the Ohrid and Prespa Lakes region. At the workshop's outset, stakeholders identified major challenges: fragmented sectoral strategies leading to inefficient water use, endangered ecosystems due to inadequate conservation measures and lack of water measurement and monitoring, affecting long-term water management. The main sectors analyzed included water management, biodiversity, human health, hydropower, agriculture, fisheries, tourism, industry (SMEs), and cultural heritage. New drivers influencing climate resilience were identified, such as forest management, wildfire risks, renewable energy installations, and sustainable tourism planning. After discussions, stakeholders reached a consensus on the core climate adaptation priorities integrated climate-adaptive actions across all sectors, symbiotic water use strategies and improved water measurement and monitoring for sustainable management.

3rd national Workshop (North Macedonia): The third national workshop took place in June 2023 and was implementing the methodology of back casting to the future vision. Stakeholders outlined key milestones by working backward from 2050 to the present to realize the future vision established in the second workshop. They then identified the necessary innovations to achieve these milestones. The stakeholders contributed the potential innovative solutions for climate adaptation in the Ohrid and Prespa Lakes region, further strengthening the region's long-term resilience.

Stakeholders in the Greek part of Prespa were selected through a matrix representing all identified relevant *sectors* (administration/water management, environment, agriculture, fishery, tourism, education, forestry, engineering), *categories* (government/policy makers, research/academia, NGOs/associations, business and local citizens), and *scale levels* (local, regional, national). Many stakeholders had the experience of working together in the Greek

Wetland Management Committee, operating from 2008 to 2022 under the auspices of the former Management Body of Prespa National Park (<https://spp.gr/project/wetland-management-committee/>, accessed on 28.11.2025). All three Greek national working groups took place in the Prespa area, ensuring the presence of local actors. In order to overcome the difficulties of accessibility and unfavorable weather conditions, additional on-line workshops were organized, and stakeholders' input was collected through personal interviews.

1st national Workshop (Greece): The first national workshop took place in July 2022. Its main task was to draw a mental map depicting the current state of the all-encompassing system in the Greek part of Prespa. Key challenges related to the decrease in lake water quantity and climate change were identified: loss of biodiversity, vegetation changes around and inside the lakes, population decrease and relevant changes in economy, degradation of lake water quality, as well as possible negative effects on tourism related to the above issues. On the other side, ongoing projects such as drop irrigation, water supply improvement and biological sewage treatment, were pointed out as possible positive factors. The above-identified issues are interconnected in complex ways, which are eventually presented in the mental map. New insights were gained through applying this method, such as the strong link between decreasing water quantity and water quality, with the latter interacting also with important sectors such as biodiversity, fishery and tourism.

2nd national Workshop (Greece): The second national workshop took place in February 2023. Its first objective was the validation of the formerly developed mental map and to reach consensus on the problem statement. Through this process further elements were identified and placed on the map such as wildfires, forest management and installation of renewable energy infrastructure. The second step was to use these outcomes to envision a future narrative for the Prespa area in 2050, based on guiding principles derived from the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Stakeholders were encouraged to go beyond business as usual and think out of the box by focusing on positive visions rather than blockers. As a result, stakeholders envisaged a *reversed* trend of decreasing water level in Greater Prespa accompanied by good water quality without wastewater and pesticides ending up in the lake. Research and transboundary cooperation lead to a good understanding of the connection between the three lakes and other factors influencing their water level such as human pressures, as well as nexus among water quantity and quality. Other issues such as the duplication of local population compared to its present one were also stressed (Future vision Prespa 2050).

3rd national Workshop (Greece): The third national workshop took place in July 2023 and was based on the methodology of back casting. Important milestones towards the future vision (defined in the second workshop) were identified, going back from 2050 to the present. The next step was to identify the innovations which could be useful for achieving these milestones. The result of the third national workshop was an “innovation funnel” which, in combination with further feedback from stakeholders, served as an important contribution to defining transboundary Innovation Pathways.

1st national Workshop (Albania): The first national workshop took place in August 2022. The main task of the meeting was to describe the current situation of both Ohrid and Prepa Lakes and define a mental map of both lakes. Key challenges related energy, tourism, finishing, agriculture, irrigation, decrease of the water quantity and the concerns about water quality of both ecosystems. Attendants work to identify the list of ongoing projects in infrastructure and energy, water supply, waste treatments, mining and agriculture as possible

factors in Ohrid and Prespa Lakes. The identified factors are connected in their complexity and such interlinkage is evidence in the mental map. While drawing down this mental map the reasons behind the water quality and quantity of the lakes were more evident by the stakeholders themselves, the interconnection and the influence of such effects in the main sector like energy, tourism, agriculture, planning, etc.

2nd national Workshop (Albania): The second national workshop took place in February 2023. After validating the mental map from the first national workshop and the consensus of the problem statements. The second step was to envision the future narrative for Ohrid and Prespa in 2050, based on UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Participants were encouraged to think for a future vision for better results in these unique ecosystems. Thinking and finding solutions to face the events of climate change and if the water decreases what will happen and what the community will face. As a transboundary case with all the neighborhoods, country cooperation and agreements were envisaged as a priority issue. Thinking in an innovative way, how to come up with solutions that will have influences in the local community but not only to all the researchers and policy makers.

3rd national Workshop (Albania): The third national workshop took place in July 2023 and was based on a backcasting methodology. Milestones were established for a future vision from 2050 to the present, leading to the identification of valuable innovations needed to achieve these goals. The third national workshop produced an "innovation funnel," which, supported by stakeholder input, significantly contributed to the development of transboundary Innovation Pathways.

National Territory Planning Agency as partner in Arsinoe project, and representative of CS4 from Albanian site has previously identified the need and the engagement of the local and national stakeholder. The focus of Albanian partner in such consortium is the sustainability enhancement of the proper stakeholders, by improving environmental sustainability and ecosystem health in both Ohrid and Prespa Lakes regions, which are shared by multiple countries.

3. Results and Discussion

The stakeholders participating at the transnational living labs included representatives from ministries, municipalities, water authorities, environmental NGOs, universities/research centres, and professional associations from North Macedonia, Albania, and Greece. At the conclusion of the first transnational living lab, the core problem statement was defined: biodiversity, agriculture, fisheries, tourism, and cultural heritage are increasingly vulnerable to climate change impacts, particularly water scarcity. While existing institutions and projects are addressing these challenges, further support, expansion, and innovation are necessary to enhance climate adaptation. Similarities, differences and gaps were identified across all three countries, and stakeholders acknowledged climate change as a global issue affecting local water availability, biodiversity, and economic activity. They recognized the urgency of shifting to climate-adaptive water consumption and highlighted ongoing national and local action plans. First and foremost, stakeholders have reached a consensus on the need for new ideas and innovations to strengthen climate resilience. Identified differences between the countries were the following: each country analyzed different sectors in varying levels of detail, reflecting sectoral priorities and stakeholder engagement structures, policy specifics

were not equally addressed across all discussions, and climate change impact projections were discussed with horizons extending to 2050, 2070, and 2100, with varying approaches in each country. Identified gaps were the following: stakeholders require clearer insights into the CS4 objectives, expected impacts, and their role in implementation, some key stakeholders were absent from the initial workshops due to scheduling conflicts and the transboundary importance of the case study was not emphasized enough and should be prioritized in future living labs.

During the second transboundary Living Lab, stakeholders from the three countries envisaged the common transboundary vision of the Ohrid - Prespa region. They perceived the region as sustainable in the long term and the future vision was the following: through scientific research and cross-border collaboration, a deeper understanding of the hydrological connections between the three lakes and the pressures they face has been achieved. This has contributed to reversing the declining water levels in Greater Prespa and improving water quality across all lakes. Local authorities and citizens demonstrate high environmental awareness, supported by social innovations, capacity building, and citizen science applications. Community-driven initiatives, such as local incubators, empower residents to adopt resilient practices and pass this knowledge on to future generations. Efforts toward biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration extend beyond the lakes and wetlands to include surrounding forests. A joint transboundary coordination mechanism ensures cooperation across national, regional, and local levels, bringing together stakeholders from various sectors. To address climate-induced crises, a Transboundary Crisis Management Plan has been established. Covering extreme weather events, droughts, wildfires, and bird diseases, this plan, along with an early warning system, enhances prediction, response, and prevention strategies. The natural and cultural heritage of the UNESCO Ohrid and Prespa region is actively protected, ensuring sustainable tourism while minimizing human impact on surface water regimes, water sources, and lake ecosystems.

Stakeholders confirmed a set of key principles for sustainable development in the transboundary region, including improving water quality and reducing untreated wastewater, enhancing water-use efficiency across sectors, strengthening transboundary cooperation for integrated water management, protecting and restoring water-related ecosystems, investing in clean energy technologies and sustainable tourism, promoting cultural and natural heritage conservation and building resilience to climate-related hazards.

Stakeholders envisioned a thriving and sustainable Prespa region by 2050, characterized by reversed negative demographic trends, green job opportunities for youth in tourism, agriculture, fisheries, and clean industries: sustainable economic growth through scientific research, technology, and transboundary synergies, climate-adaptive agriculture, integrating diverse crops, modern technology, and efficient irrigation and balanced tourism development, respecting carrying capacity and seasonal distribution. They also envisioned a transboundary economic strategy, including common product labeling and improved infrastructure and robust water monitoring systems, ensuring long-term water quality and availability. Through scientific research and transboundary cooperation, the region will achieve reversed water level decline in Large Prespa and improved water quality across all lakes, high environmental awareness, driven by social innovation and citizen engagement, conservation and restoration of biodiversity, lakes, wetlands, and forests and coordinated transboundary governance for protected areas and crisis management. The region will create a transboundary Crisis Management Plan, with early warning systems for droughts, wildfires, and ecosystem threats,

strengthened protection of UNESCO heritage, eliminating anthropogenic pressures on water bodies and sustainable tourism and cultural heritage preservation, ensuring long-term economic and environmental balance.

As part of the methodology, a SWOT analysis was conducted for the Ohrid and Prespa Lakes case study, applying a strategy of problem posing and solving that leverages strengths to maximize opportunities. Key findings from the SWOT analyses are the strengths: strong awareness and concern among stakeholders about water status, responsibility, interest, and willingness to take action, existing and emerging initiatives for water and environmental management, and sectoral and national strategies aligned with regional plans. The following weaknesses were presented: limited communication and information sharing across sectors, lack of awareness about funding opportunities for innovation, unexplored business models that could support sustainable water management, and insufficient monitoring networks for water quality and quantity, limiting future scenario forecasting. The following opportunities were presented: availability of funding for climate adaptation initiatives, strong capacity within social and scientific communities, established long-term collaboration among institutions from all three countries, and growing trends in innovation for climate resilience. The following threats were discussed: climate change impacts on water resources, threats to biodiversity and ecosystems, and risk of failing to restore lakes and environmental systems to their natural state.

The results of the third national workshops were brought together in the third transboundary Living Lab. A common back casting funnel was created based on these results. Twenty-eight stakeholders from all three countries attended this Living Lab in person and were separated in groups, in which they were asked to comment and make improvements. The key themes and associated key sectors were institutional-legal framework-police, education-social cohesion, water-environment-biodiversity, tourism, agriculture, forests and wetlands, fishery, infrastructure, renewable energy, cultural heritage, funding schemes, multidimensional hubs in transboundary level. The stakeholders agreed to 46 milestones to be achieved in a timeframe starting from 2025 and going up to 2045-2050. The most urgent ones were mainly related to issues that are common to the whole transboundary area, e.g. common monitoring methodology, historical survey of water level, protection and restoration of forests and wetlands to guarantee the stability of ecosystems, defining relevant actors across the three countries, building infrastructure to withstand the intensity of extreme weather events associated with climate change. 42 possible innovations (either technological or social) were identified for reaching these milestones and were attached to them. Examples of the possible innovations include: advanced transboundary monitoring systems and management plans, an early warning system on transboundary level, smart sensor-based systems, raindrop collection, new crop varieties and rediscovery of old ones, sustainable farms linked to tourism, making products out of invasive alien fish, multifunctional hubs including innovative education. The draft innovation pathways were later shared with stakeholders, who were given the chance to provide feedback on them and add new ones. Links to innovations which are already at least partly implemented were added and innovation gaps were identified. The pathways cover many different sectors, based on the ones identified during the Living Lab. Barriers and enablers were identified for each innovation through PESTLE analysis, based also on the input from stakeholders in each country.

The stakeholder engagement methodologies implemented in the Ohrid - Prespa region aim to provide sustainable results by the following: enhancing climate resilience and sustainability

across the transboundary region, strengthening cross-border collaboration, fostering further research, innovation, and result deployment, establishing a new model for transboundary cooperation, enabling continuous monitoring, evaluation, and improvement of climate adaptation across sectors. Also, they will deepen understanding of the hydrological connections between the lakes and pressures impacting water resources, integrating diverse datasets (hydrological, economic, demographic) from partner countries and prioritizing water users and their needs, particularly environmental ecosystems, while identifying feasible climate-resilient alternatives for water use.

In brief, the study contributes to provide innovations pathways for policy and management recommendations to ensure a climate-adapted transboundary region with a balanced approach to water use and sustainable sectoral growth. Ultimately, the Ohrid and Prespa Lakes case study aims to establish a long-term sustainable water balance, factoring in climate change, demographic shifts, and sectoral growth (agriculture, industry, fisheries, tourism, and hydropower), while ensuring environmental protection and biodiversity conservation.

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Maximizing the Legacy of the ARSINOE Project: Innovation, Policy, and Sustainability

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Abstract

The ARSINOE project has pioneered an integrated approach to climate resilience, fostering innovation, stakeholder engagement, and policy impact. As the project nears completion, a robust legacy is being established to ensure long-term sustainability and uptake of its results. Key outcomes include the *Climate Innovation Window*, a repository of tested and validated climate solutions, and the *e-Community of Practice (e-CoP)* on climate change and sustainability, which continues to connect problem owners with innovative solutions. Additionally, policy briefs and ARSINOE recommendations provide actionable insights for European policymakers, supporting evidence-based decision-making.

The project has also developed several digital tools, including an open-source dashboard, knowledge graph, and data hub, facilitating access to climate-related information. The *MINKA* citizen science app, initially developed within ARSINOE, is being adopted in other initiatives, further amplifying its impact. Furthermore, ARSINOE's Living Labs and local communities ensure that the co-creation process initiated during the project continues beyond its duration.

Another key pillar of ARSINOE's legacy is the funding schemes developed under *Work Package 7 (Financial Issues and Financing Instruments/Business Models)*, which provide regions with structured pathways to secure financial support for climate adaptation. The project's influence extends beyond its initial scope, with several EU-funded initiatives (ICARIA, NATALIE, IDEATION, ENFORCE, ENHANCE) integrating ARSINOE's tools and methodologies. Finally, through the documentary *Grano Duro*, the project sheds light on climate challenges in the durum wheat value chain, making scientific insights accessible to broader audiences.

By establishing these assets and networks, ARSINOE ensures that its innovations, knowledge, and impact continue to benefit climate resilience efforts across Europe and beyond.

Keywords: *climate resilience, innovation, stakeholder engagement, policy impact, sustainability*

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Supportive tools for increasing urban resilience against heatwaves

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Abstract

This study introduces two tools designed to enhance urban resilience against extreme heatwave events and compound hazards in Athens. The first tool is an urban planning dashboard that aids in strategic response and long-term adaptation to heatwaves. Structured according to the Sendai Framework risk assessment rationale, the dashboard calculates risk as the product of hazard, vulnerability, and exposure. Users can navigate maps displaying attributes linked to these risk components for typical summertime midday conditions. The risk components include heatwaves (Urban Heat Island effect), air pollution, biodiversity loss, accessibility to urban green areas, socio-economic vulnerabilities, and population density. The dashboard allows users to explore the impact of pre-selected scenarios and interventions, generating new risk maps and projections for 2050 and 2100 under different climate scenarios.

The second tool focuses on operational response during extreme heatwave events. It investigates resource allocation strategies based on risk levels at the zip code level. Utilizing agent-based simulation (ABS), this tool models complex systems through autonomous, interacting agents. These agents make independent decisions, are goal-directed, and adapt based on their experiences. The compound hazard system for the operations response horizon differentiates from that of the strategic response horizon. The study integrates data on temperature, air pollution, population density, and socio-economic vulnerability to define a risk index for different zip code areas. This index prioritizes resource allocation to enhance urban resilience against extreme heatwave events. The approach categorizes resources of different owners, such as the Municipality, the Region, and Ministries, into three different capacity layers, namely information and guidelines, shading and cooling, first aid and health care, and mobilizes the allocation of the different layers depending on the heatwave category and respective requirements of each neighborhood. Examples of such resources include the urban green areas, the air-conditioned places, the distribution of bottled water, the workers that conduct patrols and offer support to vulnerables, digital labels for alert messages, and the health centres.

Keywords: *heatwaves, urban resilience, adaptation, strategic planning, operational response*

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***NexusNet COST Action
Special Session***

Decoupling Nexus Interlinkages: Strategies for Urban Resilience

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Abstract

Climate change is increasingly driving the frequency and intensity of extreme events, which significantly impact human societies' wellbeing and resilience. This situation is worsened by

population growth, urbanization, and changes in land use, which often heighten the vulnerability and exposure of human systems. Additionally, the complexity of modern human systems, characterized by the interconnectedness of critical entities, makes urban areas particularly prone to domino effects triggered by a single initial shock.

This study aims to understand and assess the Nexus effects of extreme events related to climate and other natural hazards, such as earthquakes, volcanoes, and tsunamis. It considers an extended Water-Energy-Food Nexus schema, incorporating Ecosystems, Climate, Soil, Transportation, Land Use, Health, and Information and Communication Technologies.

The analysis synthesizes practical case studies of extreme events that have occurred over the last few decades, primarily in Europe. It examines the implications across three timescales: short-term, mid-term, and long-term. The study employs a modified Nexus-oriented literature review approach, analyzing nine different types of extreme events: droughts, earthquakes, floods, heatwaves, landslides, tornadoes, tsunamis, volcanoes, and wildfires. At least three case studies are analyzed for each type of extreme event.

For each case study, the Nexus tree approach is applied. The synthesis of the Nexus trees for each extreme event will create the Nexus signature of that specific event. Based on these signatures, an inventory of recommendations for decoupling the nexus interlinkages will be developed. These recommendations will be categorized into operational, tactical, and strategic levels, corresponding to the three impact horizons. Special focus will be given to the implementation of Nature-based Solutions.

The ultimate goal of the NEXUSNET taskforce is to provide tangible tools and capacity to enhance urban resilience against climate change-induced and other extreme events.

Keywords: climate change, urban resilience, Water-Energy-Food Nexus, extreme weather events

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Investigating Flood-Driven Nexus Interlinkages: Insights into Strengthening Urban Resilience in Changing Climate Conditions

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Abstract

Floods, as one of the most frequent and disruptive natural hazards, are becoming increasingly severe under the pressures of climate change, rapid urbanization, and altered land-use patterns. Beyond their immediate physical damage, floods initiate complex and often underexplored chains of interdependencies across key urban systems, intensifying systemic vulnerabilities. This study employs a multidimensional assessment framework – Water-Energy-Food-Health-Transport-Ecosystem-Land Use-Soil-ICT (WEF+ Nexus) framework to analyze how floods trigger systemic vulnerabilities through short-, mid-, and long-term interlinkages, thereby reducing urban resilience.

Drawing on five major European flood events selected based on severity criteria from the EM-DAT disaster database (Serbia, Bosnia and Hercegovina, Croatia in 2014, Slovenia in 2023, Germany in 2021, Poland in 2001, and the UK in 2007), the analysis highlights how different types of flooding (riverine, flash, coastal, and pluvial) generate immediate and delayed disruptions. Nexus trees and interlinkage matrices were constructed to visualize and quantify cascading effects across critical sectors. Common interlinkages include disruptions in electricity and water supply, impacts on food production and transport, ecosystem degradation, public health threats, and land-use dislocations.

The findings emphasize that these impacts are rarely isolated, but rather, they interact in feedback loops that can exacerbate long-term recovery challenges. To address this, the study proposes a three-tiered set of recommendations – strategic, tactical, and operational. Operational, short-term actions involve practical, on-the-ground responses, such as rapid drainage system clearance or deploying mobile ICT units for emergency communication. Tactical, mid-term solutions suggest adaptive planning approaches, including mobile supply logistics and modular transport networks. Strategic, long-term interventions include green infrastructure deployment, flood-adapted land-use planning, and Nature-based Solutions (NbS).

This work contributes to urban disaster risk reduction and Nexus governance by offering a structured methodology to identify and mitigate cascading impacts of floods. The findings support the integration of WEF+ Nexus thinking into resilience strategies, planning policies, and early-warning frameworks across European cities.

Keywords: *climate change, floods, nexus interlinkages, urban resilience, disaster risk management*

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WEFE Nexus Interlinkages in the Context of Wildfire-Induced Extreme Events: Evidence from Mediterranean Case Studies

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Abstract

Climate change is driving an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme events, such as wildfires, heatwaves, and severe storms, which have significant implications for human societies. These events not only lead to loss of life and damage to infrastructure but also disrupt ecosystems, economies and public health systems, with vulnerable populations particularly at risk. The increasingly frequent occurrence of such events underscores the urgency of understanding the interdependencies between climate change, extreme weather, natural resources, and critical infrastructure. Recent catastrophic wildfires across Europe have highlighted the growing severity and frequency of such events. These wildfires have resulted in significant loss of life, hundreds of injuries, and widespread evacuations and rescues by emergency services and civilians. In addition to the human toll, they have caused extensive destruction of green spaces and ecosystems, placing severe stress on local biodiversity. Frequently driven by extreme weather conditions such as record high temperatures, long droughts, and strong winds, these events underscore the strong link between climate extremes and wildfire intensity, reinforcing the urgent need for integrated management. The aim of this study was to understand and assess the Nexus effects of wildfires. The analysis is based on an examination of the impact of wildfire in five case studies in the Mediterranean area (Greece, Spain, Turkey, Portugal, and Italy) across three distinct timescales – short-term, mid-term, and long-term – drawing on the scientific literature, grey literature, and social media sources. A Nexus tree was developed for each case study by mapping the interdependencies among the Water-Energy-Food Nexus, Ecosystems, Climate, Soil, Transportation, Land Use, Health, and Information and Communication Technologies. This approach enabled the creation of a Nexus signature for the wildfire events, providing valuable insights into the complex interactions and resilience mechanisms involved. Understanding these interconnections is essential for improving risk assessment, informing integrated policy responses, and enhancing the resilience of critical systems to future extreme events.

Keywords: *extreme events, nexus, wildfires, interlinkages*

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Unpacking the Role of Participatory Approaches as Catalysts for Co-Design in Climate Adaptation. Lessons from Multiple Case Studies

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Abstract

As the impacts of climate change intensify, the need for adaptive responses that are context-specific, inclusive, and socially robust has become increasingly urgent. Participatory approaches have emerged as critical catalysts in the co-design of climate adaptation strategies, fostering stakeholder engagement, local ownership, and more sustainable outcomes. This paper explores the role of participatory methods in shaping effective climate adaptation through the analysis of different case studies across diverse biogeographical and socio-ecological. Drawing on experiences from living labs in urban, rural, and coastal regions, the study highlights how co-design processes enabled through stakeholder dialogues, collaborative scenario building, and knowledge co-production have enhanced the relevance, legitimacy, and uptake of adaptation measures.

The findings reveal both the potential and limitations of participatory approaches, including challenges related to power asymmetries, representativeness, and institutional integration. The paper concludes with practical lessons and recommendations for designing participatory processes that are not only inclusive and adaptive, but also embedded within broader governance frameworks. These insights contribute to advancing the theory and practice of participatory climate adaptation, emphasizing the importance of reflexivity, trust-building, and long-term engagement.

Keywords: *co-creation, workshops, stakeholders, inclusivity*

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Urban and Peri-Urban Agriculture and WEFE Nexus approach for Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Urban Futures

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Abstract

Anthropogenic activities have caused significant biodiversity loss, disrupting ecosystems and threatening environmental stability. Despite efforts to implement sustainable strategies, current actions remain insufficient to address the rapidly escalating impacts. This study aims to develop a scalable methodology embedded with WEFE Nexus approach to assess the impact of projects on biodiversity conservation and inform sustainable socio-economic development strategies. The research focuses on Bogotá, Colombia, where agriculture is both a critical economic driver and a key factor influencing conservation. It specifically explores urban and peri-urban agriculture (UPA) as a Nature-Based Solution (NBS) to enhance biodiversity conservation and promote sustainable development. Using Bogotá and Cundinamarca as case studies, the study analyses how UPA systems can mitigate agricultural impacts through sustainable practices, transforming urban areas into biodiversity hubs. A System Dynamics Model (SDM) quantifies project impacts through an integrated dynamic indicator, utilizing biodiversity data from the IUCN Red List, including species risk levels and distribution, as well as feedback from stakeholders. This localized approach adapts national-scale data to assess biodiversity status and agricultural density in the study areas. Stakeholder engagement is central to the methodology, with surveys conducted among administrative decision-makers and local implementers to evaluate plan effectiveness and gather context-specific insights. The findings show that UPA systems and Nexus approach can significantly improve biodiversity, with the Simulated Red List Index (SRLI) showing a 13% improvement following UPA implementation. Stakeholders emphasized the need for increased financial support to sustain these efforts. The study highlights UPA as a transformative NBS for urban biodiversity conservation, offering a path to resilient urban ecosystems that balance ecological integrity with socio-economic equity. By integrating sustainable practices, participatory governance, and biodiversity monitoring, this research presents a replicable framework for other regions facing similar challenges, promoting inclusive, nature-positive urban development.

Keywords: *biodiversity, UPA, food-sustainability, RLI, Nexus*

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Groundwater numerical modelling in semiarid regions as a tool to support sustainability with a Water-Food-Energy Nexus focus: a case study

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Abstract

Groundwater plays an important role in sustaining water resources for agriculture, industry, and municipal uses, particularly in semiarid regions where surface water is limited. This study presents a case study of the development and calibration of a transient numerical groundwater flow model in a semiarid region in northeast Mexico, covering the historical period from 2010 to 2022. The model quantifies the groundwater budget and provides insights into the key dynamics governing the system, aiming to support sustainable water resources management.

The results highlight the necessity of an equitable approach to groundwater abstraction and allocation policies. We suggest that shallow unconfined aquifers should be prioritized for small-scale users, such as local farmers, who can rely on low-energy water extraction methods, including dug wells, windmills, and low power pumps. In contrast, deeper confined and semi-confined aquifers can be allocated to larger users, such as municipalities, industries, and large-scale agricultural operations, which have the resources to develop deep wells with larger pump systems. This approach fosters an equitable distribution of groundwater resources strengthening the interconnected components of the water-energy-food (WEF) nexus in semiarid environments.

By integrating numerical modelling with an understanding of the WEF nexus, this study underscores how sustainable groundwater management can enhance agricultural productivity while balancing energy use and water sustainability. A key takeaway is the necessity of designing and implementing robust monitoring networks to measure groundwater levels, river flows, precipitation, and meteorological variables. These data are essential for building and improving numerical models to enhance their predictive capabilities, ultimately supporting science-informed decision-making. Future research should focus on refining the numerical model by incorporating new data to simulate various scenarios, optimizing abstraction strategies and estimating sustainable yields under the lenses and values of groundwater sustainability. Practitioners and management authorities should implement these models to contribute to the development of policies that promote long-term water security and equitable access to groundwater resources in semiarid regions.

Keywords: *groundwater, numerical modelling, sustainability, WEF Nexus, water scarcity*

Exploring the development of a disaster risk management methodology to enhance urban and peri-urban resilience

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Abstract

Extreme weather events increasingly threaten Critical Infrastructure (CI) in both urban and peri-urban areas. Despite the scientific knowledge generated by disaster risk management (DRM) strategies, sector-specific approaches often fail to address the complex infrastructural interdependencies in interaction of these areas. This oversight leads to cascading failures and inefficient responses. This study seeks to investigate how sector-specific approaches address the infrastructural interdependencies between urban and peri-urban areas and explore how opportunities arising from existing gaps and challenges could inform effective mitigation methodologies. The goal is to explore resilience-building by examining the synergistic relationship of urban and peri-urban areas focusing on identifying joint DRM actions. Key topics of this paper include the analysis of CI interdependencies and understanding the reasons for limited cross-sectoral integration of DMR. The study proposes that transitioning to a unified multi-scalar DRM methodology is essential for building climate-resilient cityscapes.

Keywords: critical infrastructure, disaster risk management, extreme weather events, resilience, urban & peri-urban

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Advances in Environmental Sciences

An improved support vector regression model for the prediction of WEEE in Turkey

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Abstract

Waste of electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) has emerged as one of the most rapidly expanding waste streams worldwide, with Turkey experiencing significant growth in this category. Given the imperative for sustainable and efficient strategies, encompassing layout and capacity planning, workforce management, and remanufacturing processes, for governmental and municipal waste recycling initiatives, precise forecasting assumes critical importance. Moreover, as Turkey ranks among the leading global manufacturers of household appliances, the optimization of waste management strategies is contingent upon reliable projections of WEEE volumes. This study thus endeavours to forecast the quantity of WEEE in Turkey by employing a support vector regression (SVR) model, which integrates three distinct input variables. In the proposed SVR model, hyperparameter tuning is performed using grid search. The predictive performance of the SVR model is rigorously compared to that of a conventional linear regression (LR) model through the application of performance metrics including mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), root mean square error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The empirical results indicate that the SVR model exhibits superior performance relative to the LR model, thereby affirming its effectiveness in forecasting WEEE volumes in Turkey.

Keywords: *WEEE, forecasting, SVR, Turkey, hyperparameter tuning, grid search*

1. INTRODUCTION

The volume of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) is escalating rapidly, particularly within OECD member states, where market saturation with large influxes of new electronics is most pronounced (Widmer et al., 2005; Ongondo et al., 2011). Furthermore, it's worth noting that the manufacture of electric and electronic equipment (EEE) ranks among the world's most rapidly expanding industries. Concurrently, advances in technology and widening markets accelerate the turnover of obsolete devices, resulting in a substantial surge in waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and posing an emergent environmental challenge (He et al., 2006; Shittu et al., 2021).

In contemporary waste management frameworks, the systematic regulation of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) occupies a central position, complementing strategies for the handling of residual household refuse, recyclable materials, and hazardous waste streams not only in EU but

also in Turkey as a candidate of EU (Salhofer et al., 2016; Kilic et al., 2015). Additionally, it should be noted that Developing nations often face unique obstacles in e-waste management due to constrained resources, inadequate infrastructure, and underdeveloped regulatory systems. Therefore, it is imperative to undertake context-specific assessments that consider each country's particular socio-economic and environmental circumstances when determining optimal waste handling strategies. As a developing country, Turkey has confronted a range of challenges in its e-waste management efforts (Sagnak et al., 2021; Maden, 2024). Furthermore, the regulatory landscape encompasses both governmental and industry-level measures. For instance, Turkey's WEEE Regulation, originally enacted in 2012, was revised on December 26, 2022, to align with circular economy and resource-efficiency principles, thereby strengthening sustainable environmental protection (Ozsut-Bogar and Gungor, 2023). In order to maintain environmental protection and circular economy, Recent research underscores a growing emphasis on e-waste forecasting within circular economy frameworks, particularly regarding the necessity for transparent e-waste reporting. Precise quantification of anticipated e-waste volumes is pivotal for circular economy planning (Duman and Kongar, 2025, Althaf et al., 2019), as robust forecasting methodologies facilitate optimized resource recovery from discarded electronic goods (Duman and Kongar, 2025).

There exist notable studies to forecast WEEE in the world. The extant literature also presents a range of approaches for forecasting e-waste generation. Most methodologies are grounded in quantifying component flows and stock dynamics, often complemented by comprehensive life-cycle assessments. More recently, time-series forecasting techniques and artificial intelligence-driven models have been employed to project future e-waste volumes. Nevertheless, these advanced predictive frameworks typically demand extensive datasets to achieve high levels of accuracy (Duman et al., 2020). For instance, there are various studies in China using different methods (Xiao and Wang, 2022; Zhao et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2021; Tian et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2021; Guo and Zhong, 2021), in Ireland (Johnson et al., 2018), in Greece (Kastanaki and Giannis, 2022), in Jordan (Al-Khatib and Fraige, 2024; Fraige et al., 2023), in India (Bagwan, 2024; Agrawal et al., 2014; Ahmet et al., 2014; Dwivedy and Mittal, 2010).

Acknowledging the imperative of precise WEEE volume prediction, this research develops a Support Vector Regression (SVR) model that leverages three judiciously chosen predictor variables. Model hyperparameters are systematically calibrated through grid search methodology. The SVR's forecasting performance is rigorously evaluated against that of a conventional linear regression (LR) benchmark using key accuracy metrics—Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). This investigation's novelty resides in its pioneering application of SVR for WEEE forecasting in the Turkish context and its provision of the first comparative analysis against linear regression within this domain.

The structure of this manuscript is as follows: Section 2 delineates the proposed SVR methodology and the associated performance metrics; Section 3 details the empirical application of the model to WEEE forecasting in Turkey; and Section 4 concludes with the study's findings and implications.

2. METHODOLOGY

Support vector regression (SVR), which were proposed by Cortes and Vapnik, is one of the supervised machine learning methods in order to handle regression problems (Drucker et al., 1997; Cortes and Vapnik, 1995). SVR is the extension of Support Vector Machine (SVM) classification method. Nevertheless, contrary to SVM which generates binary output, SVR

produces continuous values. Support Vector Regression (SVR) builds upon the foundational concept of Support Vector Machines (SVM), utilizing a sparse kernel-based framework in which predictions are derived from a subset of training instances known as support vectors. Consequently, the optimization process in SVR is expressed through these support vectors, leading to a solution whose computational complexity is governed not by the dimensionality of the input space but rather by the number of support vectors involved. The entire system for regression is known as ε -SVR model (Vapnik, 1998). In this paper, SVR is classified into 3 ways as linear ε -SVR model, kernel SVR, and V-SVR.

2.1. Linear ε -SVR Model

The objective of ε -Support Vector Regression (ε -SVR) is to approximate a target function such that the predicted values deviate from the true response values by no more than a predefined ε margin. This is achieved by constructing an ε -insensitive tube around the estimated function, within which deviations are not penalized, thereby allowing for a controlled tolerance in the prediction error. In this part, we begin with a parsimonious linear ε -SVR model. Assume we have a training dataset $\{(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_i, y_i)\}$, where x_i is the observed input data and y_i is the estimated output. The form of a linear ε -SVR model is represented as given in Eq. (1):

$$f(x, w) = w^T x + b \quad (1)$$

where $w^T x$ denotes the dot product of observed input data x and the weight vector w . In ε -SVR, the function $f(x, w)$ is approximated by identifying the flattest possible ε -insensitive tube, a property formally described as *flatness*, which corresponds to minimizing the magnitude of the weight vector w (Zhang and O'Donnell, 2020). In order to achieve this, the norm of w is minimized. Accordingly, the approximation of $f(x, w)$ can be modelled as given in (2) and (3):

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 \quad (2)$$

$$s. t \\ |y_i - (w^T x_i + b)| \leq \varepsilon, \text{ for all } i \quad (3)$$

2.2. Kernel SVR

The preceding section outlines a linear ε -SVR model, which operates on input data within the feature space under the assumption that the function $f(x, w)$ is linear. To enable ε -SVR to capture nonlinear relationships in the data, a kernel function can be employed to map the original input data (I) into a higher-dimensional feature space (K) (Zhang and O'Donnell, 2020). The use of kernel functions is a widely adopted approach in Support Vector Machines (for both regression and classification), as it eliminates the need to directly compute complex, high-order separating hypersurfaces in the input space. Instead, the problem is transformed into a linear optimization task within the kernel-induced feature space, which is significantly more tractable. The form of a kernel SVR model is represented as given in (4) and (5):

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\bullet) : I &\rightarrow K. \\ f(x, w) &= w^T \varphi(x) + b \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + c \sum_{i=1}^l (\xi_i + \xi_i^*)$$

s.t. (5)

$$|y_i - w^T \varphi(x) + b| \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i, \text{ for all } i$$

$$\xi_i, \xi_i^* \geq 0, \text{ for all } i$$

2.3. V-SVR Model

This section examines the ν -SVR model, a widely used variant introduced by Schölkopf, Bartlett, Smola, and Williamson (Schölkopf et al., 1999). One of the main advantages of ν -SVR is its ability to automatically determine an appropriate ε value. In the traditional ε -SVR framework, choosing a suitable ε is crucial for achieving accurate regression results; however, this selection typically relies on empirical tuning and lacks a systematic approach. ν -SVR addresses this issue by introducing a new parameter, $\nu \in (0, 1)$, which enables automatic adjustment of the ε -insensitive tube. This parameter simultaneously governs the proportion of support vectors and the tolerated training errors, thereby making ε a variable within the optimization problem, rather than a fixed input as given in (6).

$$\min \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + c(\nu\varepsilon + \frac{1}{l} \sum_{i=1}^l (\xi_i + \xi_i^*))$$

s.t. (6)

$$|y_i - w^T \varphi(x_i) + b| \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i, \text{ for all } i$$

$$\xi_i, \xi_i^*, \varepsilon \geq 0, \text{ for all } i$$

In contrast to the optimization formulation of ε -SVR, the ν -SVR formulation replaces the explicit ε parameter with the new ν parameter. Schölkopf et al. (1999) demonstrated that ν serves as an upper bound on the fraction of training errors (i.e., the proportion of data points lying outside the ε -insensitive tube) and a lower bound on the fraction of support vectors (i.e., the proportion of data points that define the regression function). As a result, in practical implementations, users of ν -SVR are only required to specify the acceptable proportion of errors, rather than predefining a specific tolerance level for ε , thereby offering a more flexible and data-driven approach to model configuration.

2.4. Evaluation Metrics

In the evaluation and comparison of model performance, the literature commonly employs specific metrics. In the formulas presented below, X^i denotes the predicted value for the i^{th} observation, while Y^i represents the corresponding actual value. The regression model generates a prediction X^i for each ground truth value Y^i in the dataset (Chicco et al., 2021). In this study, the metrics R^2 , RMSE, and MAPE are utilized, and their respective formulations are provided below as given in (7).

$$\bar{Y} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m Y_i$$

$$MST = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2 \quad MSE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (X_i - Y_i)^2$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (X_i - Y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m (Y - Y_i)^2} = 1 - \frac{MST}{MSE} \quad (\text{Best value:1, Worst Value:0}) \quad (7)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (X_i - Y_i)^2} \quad (\text{Best value:0, Worst Value:}\infty)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left| \frac{Y_i - X_i}{Y_i} \right| \quad (\text{Best value:0, Worst Value:}\infty)$$

3. APPLICATION AND FINDINGS

This study aims to forecast the annual volume of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) in Turkey by employing an improved Support Vector Regression (SVR) model. The dataset encompasses WEEE quantities (in tons) alongside relevant indicators such as total population, GDP per capita, population of provincial and district centers, and the urbanization rate, covering the period from 2013 to 2022. These data are obtained from the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change and the Turkish Statistical Institute, as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Dataset used for WEEE prediction of Turkey

Year	Population	GDP per Capita (Dollar)	Province and District Centers Population	Urbanization Rate	WEEE
2013	76667864	12578.19	70034413	0.9135	4911
2014	77695904	12165.22	71286182	0.9175	6817
2015	78741053	11050.00	72523134	0.9210	32029
2016	79814871	10970.05	73671748	0.9230	39394
2017	80810525	10695.55	74761132	0.9251	37326
2018	82003882	9568.84	75666497	0.9227	37517
2019	83154997	9215.44	77151280	0.9278	46360
2020	83614362	8638.74	77736041	0.9297	67153
2021	84680273	9743.21	78908631	0.9318	52129
2022	85279553	10674.50	79613279	0.9336	40900

For model development, the data spanning 2013 to 2019 are allocated for training, while the years 2020 to 2022 are reserved for testing purposes. Model hyperparameters are optimized via grid search methodology. Table 2 provides the range of values considered, as well as the default and optimal values for each parameter within the SVR framework. The prediction performance of the proposed SVR model is benchmarked against that of linear regression (LR) and a default SVR model. All models are coded in Python 3.10, utilizing libraries such as pandas, numpy, and scikit-learn.

Table 2. The value ranges and default and best values of the parameters of the SVR model

Parameter	Value Range	Default Value	Best Value
Kernel Function	radial, linear, sigmoid, polynomial	radial	radial
Cost (C)	0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1000, 10000	1	100
Gamma (γ)	'scale', 'auto', 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1	'scale'	0.1
Epsilon	0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 10	0.1	0.01

Predicted values for both training and testing datasets, alongside performance metrics including Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), are summarized in Table 3. Additionally, the prediction accuracy of each model is graphically illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 3. Performance analysis of the prediction models for the training and test data set

Year	Actual	LR	SVR	Improved SVR
2013	4911	1249.49	6440.56	4758.22
2014	6817	13845.24	10402.29	6971.26
2015	32029	33325.87	30505.99	32186.12
2016	39394	33622.21	37062.10	39231.01
2017	37326	36873.84	38842.46	37480.16
2018	37517	37516.29	39048.30	37671.11
2019	46360	47921.07	42477.64	46208.84
Train MAPE (%)		28.71	15.85	7.43
Train RMSE		3787.94	2468.90	155.27
2020	67153	57224.48	40531.94	57035.29
2021	52129	40096.38	36278.04	51239.48
2022	40900	27394.82	31391.78	43194.46
Test MAPE (%)		23.63	31.1	7.46
Test RMSE		11912.87	18711.32	6011.76

Figure 1. The prediction accuracy of the models for training and testing data

4. CONCLUSION

The numerical results demonstrate that the improved SVR model offers a robust and effective approach for forecasting WEEE generation in Turkey. Moreover, hyperparameter tuning through grid search notably enhances the prediction accuracy of the SVR model. Future research could explore parameter optimization using metaheuristic algorithms such as genetic algorithms and swarm intelligence techniques. Furthermore, incorporating alternative explanatory variables may contribute to the development of more comprehensive predictive models.

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Revisiting Wastewater Forecasting in Istanbul: An Optimised Grey Bernoulli Modelling Approach

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Abstract

Forecasting wastewater generation is an intricate process affected by a range of latent factors and uncertainties, including the dynamics of economic growth. In recent years, the critical role of wastewater management in urban sustainability and public health has garnered significant academic and policy attention. The challenges of accurately predicting wastewater output are compounded by rapid urbanization and environmental variability, particularly in developing nations where resources for advanced monitoring are limited. Furthermore, robust predictive methodologies are essential to guide effective water pollution control and sustainable development initiatives. This study thus introduces two time series models: an optimized GM(1,1) model and an optimized NGBM(1,1) model, both refined through the genetic algorithm (termed GA-GM(1,1) and GA-NGBM(1,1), respectively). These novel models are employed to forecast wastewater generation in Istanbul, and their predictive performances are benchmarked against those of the conventional GM(1,1), NGBM(1,1), and ARIMA models. The findings underscore that GM(1,1) and NGBM(1,1) models optimised by genetic algorithm deliver superior forecasting accuracy compared to their traditional counterparts.

Keywords: forecasting, grey models, wastewater, sustainability, parameter optimisation

1. INTRODUCTION

Water, as a fundamental resource underpinning terrestrial life and fostering ecological development, paradoxically exhibits such remarkable solvent properties that it becomes highly vulnerable to pervasive contamination (Maryam and Büyükgüngör, 2019). Parallel to this, over the past two decades, research in water and wastewater management has surged to prominence, driven by the escalating challenge of water scarcity, a crisis exacerbated by burgeoning populations, intensified industrial and agricultural practices, and the multifaceted impacts of climate change (Demirel et al., 2022; Hou et al., 2021; Meneses et al., 2010). It's also worth noting that there is an escalating demand for water across diverse sectors, including agriculture, industry, food processing, environmental services, energy production, and domestic consumption while concurrently, global water reserves are experiencing rapid depletion (Ayyildiz et al., 2020).

Turkey, as one of Europe's most populous nations, also ranks among the countries with the highest volumes of wastewater generation, especially in Istanbul (Ulusoy et al., 2024). It's also well known that treated municipal wastewater and sewage sludge represent valuable irrigation resources in arid and semi-arid environments. Beyond supplying a cost-effective water source, their use delivers essential plant nutrients and organic matter, thereby enhancing soil fertility under water-limited conditions. Employing treated effluents for agricultural irrigation not only alleviates effluent-disposal challenges and associated environmental contamination but also diminishes dependency on synthetic fertilizers (Ozturk et al., 2011). This reality highlights that water and wastewater management have emerged as critical research areas over the past two decades, driven by the escalating global water scarcity resulting from population growth, industrial and agricultural activities, and climate change in Istanbul. Parallel to this, the incorporation of advanced monitoring, forecasting and control strategies within wastewater infrastructures has received broad support from water and environmental engineering specialists (Çimen Mesutoğlu & Gök, 2024).

In light of the critical role of wastewater management, this research presents two enhanced time-series forecasting techniques: the Genetic Algorithm-optimized GM(1,1) (GA-GM(1,1)) and the Genetic Algorithm-optimized NGBM(1,1) (GA-NGBM(1,1)). These advanced models are applied to predict wastewater generation in Istanbul and are evaluated against the standard GM(1,1), NGBM(1,1), and ARIMA approaches.

The present manuscript is organized into five parts. A concise synthesis of extant scholarly work is provided in the Literature Review. The Methodological Framework section in the third part articulates the approach devised for forecasting wastewater generation in Istanbul. The Empirical Application and Findings section details the implementation of the model and interprets the results. Finally, the Conclusions and Implications section offers the study's overarching conclusions and discusses their broader significance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review section explores various aspects of wastewater management, including wastewater treatment, wastewater forecasting, and advanced forecasting grey models. Additionally, it examines the interconnections between wastewater treatment and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The studies reviewed highlight the importance of predictive modeling in wastewater management, the role of artificial intelligence in improving forecasting accuracy, and the broader sustainability implications of wastewater treatment systems.

Predicting wastewater quality in treatment plants is crucial for optimizing sampling efforts, reducing costs, and improving decision-making efficiency. El-Rawy et al. (2021) explored different machine learning techniques to forecast the removal efficiency of key wastewater parameters, including total suspended solids (TSS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD5), ammonia, and sulfide at the El-Berka wastewater treatment plant in Egypt. Their study compared three predictive models—traditional feed-forward (TF), deep feed-forward backpropagation (DFB), and deep cascade-forward backpropagation (DCB)—alongside a deep learning time-series forecasting (DLTSF) approach utilizing long short-term memory (LSTM) networks. The results indicated that the DCB model exhibited the highest accuracy, while the DLTSF model achieved superior

performance for BOD5 forecasting. These findings underscore the potential of advanced machine learning approaches for enhancing wastewater treatment plant efficiency (El-Rawy et al., 2021).

Forecasting wastewater discharge is critical for effective environmental management. Gou et al. (2022) introduced a novel four-parameter grey prediction model (FDGM) to predict wastewater discharge trends in Chongqing, China. Their model demonstrated higher accuracy compared to traditional grey models, with forecasts indicating a significant increase in wastewater discharge by 2025. These insights underscore the need for timely governmental interventions to address rising wastewater levels (Gou et al., 2022).

In a similar context, Al-Dahidi et al. (2024) conducted an extensive performance and forecasting analysis of the As-Samra wastewater treatment plant in Jordan. Their study employed principal component analysis (PCA) to evaluate historical operational data, revealing significant seasonal production patterns. The authors implemented various machine learning techniques to develop a one-month-ahead forecasting model, with support vector machines (SVM) emerging as the most effective predictor. Their research highlights the importance of hybrid forecasting approaches in improving wastewater treatment plant performance and environmental sustainability (Al-Dahidi et al., 2024).

Energy efficiency in wastewater treatment plants is a key factor in urban sustainability. Oliveira et al. (2021) investigated the application of deep learning models—long short-term memory networks (LSTMs), gated recurrent units (GRUs), and convolutional neural networks (CNNs)—to forecast energy consumption in wastewater treatment facilities. Their study revealed that CNN-based models provided superior forecasting accuracy compared to LSTMs and GRUs. Additionally, the authors explored transfer learning techniques to address data scarcity, demonstrating that pre-trained CNN models significantly enhanced predictive performance (Oliveira et al., 2021).

Similarly, Medeiros et al. (2024) evaluated the effectiveness of Transformer-based models in predicting electricity production from biogas generated during wastewater treatment. Their findings indicated that while LSTMs outperformed Transformers, the latter showed promising potential in certain forecasting scenarios. These results suggest that adopting Transformer-based models could contribute to optimizing energy recovery in wastewater treatment plants (Medeiros et al., 2024).

In another study, Xu et al. (2024) developed an interval time-delayed grey model to predict construction waste, addressing key challenges related to data uncertainty and delayed effects. Their results confirmed the effectiveness of grey modeling techniques in forecasting waste generation, thereby aiding policymakers in developing more effective waste management strategies (Xu et al., 2024).

Wastewater treatment plays a crucial role in achieving the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Delanka-Pedige et al. (2021) conducted an evaluation of wastewater treatment infrastructures, comparing algal-based and activated sludge-based systems. Their research utilized process parameters derived from the SDGs to assess environmental, economic, and social sustainability. Findings indicated that mixotrophic algal systems performed better in terms of overall sustainability, while membrane bioreactor (MBR) systems excelled in social sustainability due to superior pathogen removal capabilities (Delanka-Pedige et al., 2021).

Obaideen et al. (2022) examined the contribution of wastewater treatment to 11 of the 17 SDGs, emphasizing its impact on water availability (SDG 6), health improvements (SDG

3), energy production (SDG 7), and climate action (SDG 13). The study also proposed indicators to enhance wastewater treatment facilities' alignment with SDG objectives (Obaideen et al., 2022).

The integration of advanced forecasting methods and machine learning techniques has significantly improved wastewater treatment performance, energy efficiency, and sustainability. Studies highlight the importance of predictive models in optimizing treatment processes, enhancing energy recovery, and aligning wastewater management practices with global sustainability goals. Future research should focus on refining hybrid forecasting approaches and expanding the application of AI-driven models to further enhance wastewater treatment operations.

3. METHODOLOGY

GM(1,1), NGBM(1,1), and GM(1,N) constitute the foundational grey forecasting models. Recent literature indicates that researchers have predominantly focused on modified or enhanced versions of these models to boost predictive accuracy (Zhao and Guo, 2016; Ye et al., 2024; Gu and Wu, 2024). These advanced iterations typically employ optimization techniques to fine-tune their parameters. In this study, we utilize a Genetic Algorithm for parameter optimization and introduce a hybrid methodology to forecast wastewater generation in Istanbul.

The GM(1,1) framework inherently produces trajectories that grow or decay exponentially, rendering it ill-suited for series characterized by randomness, nonlinearity, or volatility. To address these shortcomings, the nonlinear grey Bernoulli model (NGBM(1,1)) is employed (Wang et al., 2011; Chen et al., 2019).

The NGBM(1,1) integrates the conventional GM(1,1) formulation with the Bernoulli differential equation (Hsu, 2010). Notably, the initial two steps of the NGBM(1,1) procedure mirror those of the standard GM(1,1) model. The other steps are as follows (Wang et al., 2011).

Step 1. Formulate the grey differential equation and estimate its parameters to derive the first-order grey differential equation for NGBM(1,1), which is expressed as Equation (1).

$$y^{(0)}(k) + \beta_1 z^{(1)}(k) = \beta_2 \left(z^{(1)}(k) \right)^\gamma, \gamma \neq 1, k = 2, 3, \dots, n. \quad (1)$$

Step 2. Note that $y^{(0)}(k)$ represents the grey derivative, and the background value $z^{(1)}(k)$ is defined as given in (2) while The coefficients β_1, β_2 serve as the model's generating parameters.

$$z^{(1)}(k) = 0.5 * \left(y^{(1)}(k) + y^{(1)}(k - 1) \right) \quad (2)$$

Here, the parameter γ denotes the power exponent, acting as a nonlinear tuning variable that enhances the NGBM(1,1) model's flexibility and adaptability for accurately tracking

nonlinear sequences (Wang et al., 2011). Assuming γ is known, we substitute successive values of k into Equation (2), yielding the form presented in Equation (3).

$$\begin{aligned} y^{(0)}(2) + \beta_1 z^{(1)}(2) &= \beta_2 (z^{(1)}(2))^\gamma \\ y^{(0)}(3) + \beta_1 z^{(1)}(3) &= \beta_2 (z^{(1)}(3))^\gamma \\ &\vdots \\ y^{(0)}(n) + \beta_1 z^{(1)}(n) &= \beta_2 (z^{(1)}(n))^\gamma \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Step 3. The relationship can equivalently be expressed in matrix notation, $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{Z}\boldsymbol{\beta}$, as given in the Equation (4).

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} y^{(0)}(2) \\ y^{(0)}(3) \\ \vdots \\ y^{(0)}(n) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} -z^{(1)}(2) & (z^{(1)}(2))^\gamma \\ -z^{(1)}(3) & (z^{(1)}(3))^\gamma \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ -z^{(1)}(n) & (z^{(1)}(n))^\gamma \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\beta}_1 \\ \hat{\beta}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Step 4: Develop and solve the whitening differential equation within the grey system framework. The whitening differential function for NGBM(1,1) is presented in Equation (5).

$$\frac{dy^{(1)}(t)}{dt} + \beta_1 y^{(1)}(t) = \beta_2 y^{(1)}(t)^\gamma, \gamma \neq 1 \quad (5)$$

Step 5. Substitute the estimated parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\beta} = [\hat{\beta}_1, \hat{\beta}_2]^T$, into Equation (5). Solving this whitening differential equation then yields the general solution as given in Equation (6).

$$y^{(1)}(t) = \left[C e^{-(1-\gamma)\hat{\beta}_1 t} + \frac{\hat{\beta}_2}{\hat{\beta}_1} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \quad (6)$$

Step 6. In this context, C represents an integration constant. By applying the initial condition as given $y^{(1)}(t)|_{t=1} = y^{(1)}(1)$, and substituting it into Equation (6), we derive Equation (7).

$$C = \left[(y^{(0)}(1))^{1-\gamma} - \frac{\hat{\beta}_2}{\hat{\beta}_1} \right] e^{(1-\gamma)\hat{\beta}_1} \quad (7)$$

Step 7. Derive the time response function for the NGBM(1,1) model i subsequently derived, as shown in Equation (7).

$$\hat{y}^{(1)}(k) = \left\{ \left[(y^{(0)}(1))^{1-\gamma} - \frac{\hat{\beta}_2}{\hat{\beta}_1} \right] e^{-(1-\gamma)\hat{\beta}_1(k-1)} + \frac{\hat{\beta}_2}{\hat{\beta}_1} \right\}^{\frac{1}{1-\gamma}} \quad (7)$$

4. APPLICATION AND RESULTS

This study aims to predict the amount of wastewater generated in Turkey in the coming years using grey prediction models. The dataset, covering the period from 1994 to 2022, is obtained from the Turkish Statistical Institute (<https://www.tuik.gov.tr/>) and is visualized in Figure 1. Due to missing values in certain years, linear interpolation is employed to impute the incomplete data.

Figure 1. The amount of wastewater in Turkey from 1994 to 2022

The dataset are divided into training and testing sets, with 80% of the dataset (1994–2016) used for training and the remaining 20% (2017–2022) reserved for model validation. A rolling procedure is utilized in constructing the proposed prediction models. In this approach, the value for 2017 is forecasted using the initial training data (1994–2016). Following each prediction, the oldest observation is removed from the training set, and the newly predicted value is appended, maintaining a constant window size. This process is repeated iteratively.

To improve the prediction performance of the non-linear grey Bernoulli model NGBM(1,1), parameter optimization is conducted using a Genetic Algorithm (GA). The model includes two key parameters: the background value (α) and the power index (γ). The optimization aims to minimize the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), which served as the fitness function in the GA framework. The GA parameters are configured as follows: crossover rate of 0.9, mutation rate of 0.01, elitism rate of 0.2, population size of 50, and a maximum of 1000 iterations.

The prediction performance of the GA-NGBM(1,1) model is compared with the classical GM(1,1) model and an optimized ARIMA model. In the ARIMA approach, the optimal values for the autoregressive (p), differencing (d), and moving average (q) components are selected based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), resulting in the best-fitting parameters of (p=0, d=1, q=0).

The proposed grey models and the optimization procedures are implemented in MATLAB 2022b. Predicted values, along with MAPE and RMSE metrics, are presented in Table 1. The GA exhibited rapid convergence of MAPE to a stationary point, demonstrating the efficiency of the optimization process.

Table 1. MAPE and predicted values of the proposed prediction models

Year	Actual Value	GM(1,1)		GA-NGBM(1,1)		ARIMA(0,1,0)	
		Pred.	Error	Pred.	Error	Pred.	Error
2017	4647137.527	4958332.65	6.7%	4666880.80	0.42%	4635031.09	0.26%
2018	4795130.053	5161517.54	7.6%	4796609.61	0.03%	4784164.96	0.23%
2019	4877402.535	5362779.89	10.0%	4915983.54	0.79%	4936761.46	1.22%
2020	4959675.016	5581785.07	12.5%	5042844.41	1.68%	5011815.29	1.05%
2021	5169954.223	5815188.39	12.5%	5170608.86	0.01%	5089809.61	1.55%
2022	5380233.429	6052873.05	12.5%	5290282.55	1.67%	5306549.41	1.37%
MAPE			10.3%		0.77%		0.95%
RMSE			535796.12		53055.34		55319.35

5. CONCLUSION

According to Table 1, the GA-NGBM(1,1) model yielded the most accurate results. Specifically, the rolling GM(1,1) model produced a MAPE of 10.3%, whereas the GA-optimized NGBM(1,1) model achieved a significantly lower MAPE of 0.77%, with optimal parameter values of $\alpha=1$ and $\gamma=0.09$. The optimized ARIMA model, by comparison, resulted in a MAPE of 0.95% and an RMSE of 55,319.35.

The numerical findings indicate that the GA-NGBM(1,1) model outperforms both the traditional GM(1,1) and the optimized ARIMA model in terms of prediction accuracy. Furthermore, the integration of parameter optimization and the rolling forecasting procedure substantially enhances the predictive capability of the NGBM(1,1) model. Consequently, the proposed GA-NGBM(1,1) approach provides a robust and effective methodology for forecasting wastewater generation in Turkey.

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Carbon pools and CO₂ equivalents in oak forest ecosystems

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Abstract

Most terrestrial organic carbon reserves are found in forest ecosystems and are essential for climate change mitigations. In this work, we investigated the carbon stock and the CO₂ equivalents in two oak habitats with distinct phenology (deciduous vs. evergreens) in the region of Xanthi, Greece. We determined the following carbon pools: Above-ground (ABG), below-ground (BGB), deadwood, forest floor, and soil carbon. Above-ground biomass was estimated through allometric equations from data collected from sampling plots. Below-ground biomass was derived from the above-ground biomass using root/shoot conversion factors. Deadwood was estimated from the standing trees plus the lying deadwood or logs. Forest floor litter was collected yearly through traps (50x50x30cm), which included all litter material above the soil. Soil samples were collected once from the forest floor at 0-10 cm depths. Carbon stocks were estimated from biomass, and the CO₂ equivalents were determined from Carbon stocks as t/Ha.

Keywords: forest biomass, Mediterranean forests, CO₂ removal, allometric equations

Integrating Archaeology and Physical Chemistry for a new approach to archaeological surveys

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Abstract

Archaeological surveys combined with physico-chemical analysis and the statistical treatment of the data give a comprehensive picture of a territory impacted by ancient settlements. Even though information could be hidden because of different historical circumstances and local conditions (i.e. overlapping stratification, concurrent influences etc.) traces of different activities persists as fingerprints.

High throughput techniques like pXRF have been applied on environmental matrices (soil and stream sediments) and artifacts (coins) for both predictive and descriptive goals. pXRF measurement, validated by laboratory top level techniques, can be used in multi-scale investigations (intra-situ and medium-large territorial scale) to obtain detailed chemical and/or geochemical maps that constitutes a valid diagnostic and predictive tool for areas with high archaeometallurgical potential.

We focused our attention studying the ancient mining and smelting sites, of “Colline Metallifere”, a wide territory located in the south-west of Tuscany with a long-standing tradition of ore mining and processing. Between the 9th and 12th centuries certain regions of Italy, drawing simultaneously upon transalpine and Mediterranean connection, became the economic and political motor of the new Medieval Europe, paving the way for the Renaissance.

Keywords: *cultural heritage, pXRF, archaeological predictive modelling*

The application of Material Flow Analysis as an approach towards the estimation of Materials Circularity in WEEE Management

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Abstract

Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) constitutes a priority waste stream, *inter alia*, due to its rapid growth rate and the presence of valuable, scarce, and hazardous substances, coupled with significant challenges in collection and treatment. Within the framework of the circular economy, closing material loops and reducing resource consumption and environmental burdens are central goals. The EU Circular Economy Action Plan sets ambitious targets, including doubling the circular material use rate by 2030 and decoupling economic growth from resource use. In this context, WEEE is recognized as an urban mine for critical raw materials.

Material Flow Analysis (MFA) offers a robust methodological approach for assessing the environmental performance and circularity potential of WEEE management systems. MFA systematically tracks the flows and stocks of materials within a system defined spatially and temporally, linking sources, pathways, and final sinks. It provides a system-level understanding of material interconnections and supports evidence-based decision-making to enhance resource efficiency and sustainability.

This study applies MFA to evaluate the circularity performance of WEEE management systems through the assessment of End-of-Life Recycling Input Rates (EOL-RIR). Preliminary findings reveal that low separate collection rates for specific WEEE categories, along with technological limitations in recovering certain materials, continue to hinder circular material flows, indicating substantial opportunities for improvement.

Keywords: Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), Material Flow Analysis, materials circularity, circular economy indicators, solid waste management

Environmental Education

Urban vineyards as a nexus: harnessing citizen science for environmental sustainability, community engagement, and science-society integration

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Abstract

Urban vineyards have become a critical element of sustainable urban development, offering significant environmental, economic, and social benefits. They enhance biodiversity, expand green spaces, strengthen local economies, and foster social cohesion, all while preserving cultural heritage. Aligned with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), the Biosoil project was developed to leverage urban agriculture as a means of advancing sustainability. This interdisciplinary initiative involves collaboration between scientists, agronomists, and citizens, applying sustainable soil management techniques to urban agriculture. By engaging communities in citizen science, Biosoil educates participants on sustainable urban agricultural practices and encourages them to monitor and assess the effectiveness of these methods in their local environments. This study examines how urban vineyards contribute to environmental sustainability and community engagement, positioning them as a bridge between science and society. Through interdisciplinary approaches from environmental science, urban planning, and social research, this research contributes to the broader discourse on urban agriculture and sustainability, emphasising the role of citizen-driven initiatives in achieving SDGs 11 and 12. Specifically, we highlight the role of urban agriculture in enhancing biodiversity, promoting green spaces, and utilising biosolids for soil improvement. The findings underscore strategies for improving collaboration through co-creation models, educational workshops and interactive tools, demonstrating the potential of citizen-driven urban vineyards to integrate scientific inquiry with public participation.

Keywords: *urban vineyards, citizen science, SDG 11, SDG 12, biosolids, community engagement, environmental sustainability*

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Impact of Virtual Reality application and Digital Transformation on Water Education

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Abstract

In the realm of Digital Water Transformation, there is a gap between the industry perspective and academic insights with the obvious need for skilled experts. Virtual Reality (VR) technologies have been integrated into various domains, revealing numerous potential benefits for educational purposes. Particularly in cases of expensive and specialized equipment used in laboratory exercises, there are many constraints that limit the students' physical access including: equipment and/or expert availability, the number of students and available time, lack of funds for equipment purchase in smaller universities, and time and space constraints for part-time and remote students. Developing a VR application that simulates the operation of physical equipment can be highly beneficial for students who lack access to the equipment, but also helpful for those who have already operated the equipment by giving them the possibility to practice at their own time. As part of the WATERLINE Horizon Europe project, a VR application for fluid mechanics laboratory exercises was developed at the University of Niš, Faculty of Civil Engineering and Architecture, and tested in two phases. The first testing phase was mainly concerned with basic VR functionality and suggestions for further development. During the second testing phase, all participants joined a theory session and then engaged with the VR application. They filled two questionnaires: one assessing the perceived learning and the other evaluating the user experience of the VR application. The results of the User Experience Questionnaire show that the application ranks in the top 10% of results in all but one scales compared to the UEQ benchmark designed by the questionnaire authors.

Keywords: *virtual reality, digital water, water education, digital transformation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Some of the essential skills needed in the water industry sector are innovation, industry related knowledge and applying Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in Water Resources Management (WRM) [1]. However, such skills are not sufficiently present in existing employees in this field and in higher education curriculum. Barriers for integration of new and emerging digital technologies in water education include lack of funding and equipment, especially in developing countries, conservative thinking and prejudice against integrating traditionally different fields, difficulty in adopting new skills and technologies, and weak connection between industry and academia.

Incorporating Virtual Reality (VR) into traditional education has multiple potential benefits. On one hand it can introduce new opportunities or extend existing ones by providing learning experiences similar to real-world ones to students that cannot access them. This includes students learning remotely, working students that cannot adhere to all class schedules, but also students from institutions lacking valuable equipment and laboratories due to insufficient funding. On the other hand, introducing students to novel digital technologies such as VR while still at the university can be beneficial to their future engagement in the industry. These future engineers will be more open to the adoption of innovative technologies in their work and require less further training for acquiring modern technical skills.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 contains the description of relevant state-of-the-art research. The description of the VR application developed as part of the transformation of the three-tier Learning Environments (LEs) task is given in section 3. In section 4, the two phases of the VR application testing are described, including results of the testing process. Finally, section 5 contains the main conclusions of this research.

2. RELATED WORK

Virtual reality is a powerful educational tool that enables immersive learning experiences. The research performed in [2] explores its recent applications in various fields including education. Using the Cospaces VR platform, the water cycle is demonstrated to help young learners grasp processes like transpiration and condensation. The authors state that unlike traditional methods, VR fosters a deeper connection with the subject, enhancing learning. As educators embrace interactive teaching strategies, this research promotes VR adoption to enrich student engagement and better prepare them for the future.

An interactive VR application for education, focusing on soil and water conservation is presented in [3]. The Android-based app uses a picture book format, allowing learners to engage via a smartphone-powered VR headset for an immersive 3D experience. Users navigate the VR book with a double-circle interaction symbol, triggering features like audio narration, text annotations, and audience questions. Experimental results show improved learning outcomes and engagement. Interactive data is stored in the cloud using the Experience API, enabling future analysis of learning behaviors during 3D VR interactions.

Another VR-based educational tool to train fieldworkers in accurately measuring water discharge in open-channel flows is introduced in [4]. Initially tested with around 60 participants from various environmental sectors, the VRLab reduced monitoring costs, minimized reliance on specialized staff, and improved users' understanding of hydraulic phenomena and decision-making. It is possible that enhancing interactivity and immersion could further improve training effectiveness. This could be achieved by utilizing advances in VR technology, mathematical models, graphics software, and peripherals like headsets and gloves to create a more realistic river environment, enriching technicians' learning experiences.

Earlier studies also suggested VR's growing utility in various fields. A VR simulation system for Water Distribution Networks (WDNs), featuring an intuitive interface for accessibility is proposed in [5]. Utilizing VR's immersive and interactive capabilities, the system enhances understanding and operation of complex WDNs. A case study demonstrated its effectiveness in monitoring, modelling, optimization, and control. By integrating hydraulic

and water quality models, the system enables real-time 3D visualization. Further incorporation of additional models such as leakage or rehabilitation models, could lead to aiding utilities in managing operations, training staff, and improving efficiency while reducing costs.

Using VR systems is shown to significantly improve students' academic performance [6]. Numerous VR systems are available, many of which are applied in education and engineering. This study provides qualitative evidence supporting the benefits of VR over traditional methods. Furthermore, it highlights that greater student engagement in VR environments is linked to higher academic achievement.

The author of [7] explored the potential of VR and Augmented Reality (AR) in enhancing higher education, particularly in dentistry, which requires significant training resources. VR and AR offer cost-effective alternatives to traditional infrastructure while enriching learning experiences. These technologies support integrated work-based learning and reflective practices, allowing students to engage in practical training beyond lecture halls or clinics. In resource-limited settings, AR and VR can serve as mobile learning platforms, enabling students to gain essential hands-on experience before completing their programs.

The use of VR technologies, software, and content as educational tools in Geography is considered in [8]. Based on their experience in undergraduate and postgraduate teaching, the authors highlight how VR enhances fieldwork observation skills and understanding of geographical locations before physical visits. The study also demonstrates VR's role in developing critical analytical skills regarding visual technologies and their impact on representing people and landscapes. Additionally, it examines how VR and AR improve graduate employability, particularly in geovisualization, aligning with the growing industrial demand for these skills.

Bearing in mind related research described in this section, it is clear that the application of VR technologies in education has many benefits. The specific approach used for development of a VR application for learning the basics of fluid mechanics is given in the following section.

3. PIPE LOSSES VR APPLICATION

The Pipe losses VR application was developed by the team at the University of Niš as part of the Horizon Europe project WATERLINE - Transforming Advanced Water Skilling Through the Creation of a Network of Extended reality Water Emulative Centres [9]. The aim of the WATERLINE project is the creation of the alliance for Digital Water (DW) of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The whole approach is based on the quadruple helix model of innovation including higher education and research institutions, public policy, industry and business and civil society organizations and associations as stakeholders [10]. One of the most important tasks within the project was the transformation of the three-tier learning environments: the emulation learning environment based on an existing laboratory setup in partner institutions, the assisted reality learning environment extending the physical learning environment and the virtual reality learning environment (ViLE) intended as a virtual version of the physical laboratory setup. The development of the ViLE included development of a VR application and a two-phase testing of technical aspects of the application, as well as the perceived learning by the testing participants.

Figure 1. Laboratory model HM 150.11 used as a starting point for the VR application

After consideration of existing laboratories and equipment at the departments for Hydraulic Engineering and Water Management a laboratory model (Figure 1) for learning the basics of Fluid Mechanics was selected as a starting point for ViLE. This laboratory model provides the opportunity to study the pressure losses in pipes, piping elements and shut-off devices [11]. It has multiple pipe segments with individual valves and different characteristics, such as pipe segment length and diameter, elbows, etc. Each pipe segment contains one or more points for measuring pressure using the model's piezometers.

The development process of the ViLE is shown in Figure 2. It consisted of four stages: (1) analyzing the laboratory model, (2) creating a 3D virtual model, (3) developing the simulation, and (4) designing learning materials. First, the real-world laboratory model was examined, and key elements were selected for integration into the VR model. Mathematical models were created based on expert knowledge. The 3D model included the base, key components (e.g., selected pipes), and accessories (e.g., valves, measuring points). A VR environment was then developed, integrating computational logic and user interactions. Finally, measured data visualization and educational materials, including instructional videos and lesson plans, were incorporated.

Figure 2. The development process of the ViLE

Due to the model’s complexity and limited development time, the virtual model (Figure 3) was simplified to include only three types of pipes, each operated individually from others:

- one straight pipe with fixed diameter where pressure loss is caused solely by the friction,
- one pipe with diameter change, including sudden expansion and sudden constriction of the pipe, and
- three pipes with elbows, each with different angles and/or curve radius.

The application was developed using Unity for VR development with OpenXR, while Blender was used for 3D modelling of assets. The main technical challenge was the accurate representation of pressure loss at measuring points according to physical pipe characteristics, the state of the valve and input parameter values, such as input pressure and flow rate. Since a large percentage of potential users are inexperienced with VR technology and headsets, a guided tutorial for the simulator of the laboratory model was incorporated into the application. To make the experience as realistic as possible special attention was given to the details, such as realistic model height and position as well as the sound of the machine when a valve is open. Additionally, a whole section of the application was devoted to learning materials consisting of theoretical background, equations for calculations of output values and instructional videos.

Figure 3. The simulator scene in the developed VR application

4. TESTING AND RESULTS

The testing of the VR application was performed in two phases of different aim and scope. The first phase focused mainly on application functionality and general ease of use and user experience. Testing was performed in three partner institutions, including University of Niš where the application was developed. Participants consisted of bachelor and master students and teaching/research staff. Besides different prior knowledge levels, participants were also from different departments, only some of which were related to water. User responses were recorded with a virtual environment evaluation questionnaire [12] and a feedback capture grid. Additionally, researchers performing the testing were instructed to observe and note participants' reactions during the testing, including body language, facial expressions and verbal utterances. After analyzing testing participants' feedback, a plan for further improvement of the application and learning units was developed and executed over a several months period.

The second testing phase was performed on the final version of the VR application and complete accompanying learning units. The main goal was to measure and compare the perceived learning of VR application with the real-world laboratory model. In this phase the testing was performed in two partner institutions, including University of Niš. However, the number of participants was higher compared to the first phase of testing. The questioners used for recording participants answers were based on the Cognitive, Affective, Psychomotor (CAP) test [13] and the standardized User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) [14]. The testing protocol for the VR application consisted of the following steps:

1. Participants studied the learning units accompanying the VR application
2. The application is demonstrated to participants
3. One half of participants completed the CAP questionnaire
4. All participants tested the VR application
5. All participants completed the CAP questionnaire
6. All participants completed the UEQ questionnaire

In the described protocol one half of the participants filled out the CAP questionnaire twice, once before and once after using the VR application. The goal was to assess the difference in efficiency of using only the learning material and combining it with the VR application.

Since the application was based on a real laboratory model, a part of the testing was done using the real model combined with theory provided in learning unit material. Participants in this portion of testing had a different protocol:

1. Participants studied the learning units accompanying the VR application
2. One half of participants completed the CAP questionnaire
3. All participants were trained on the real laboratory model
4. All participants completed the CAP questionnaire

This additional testing protocol enables the comparison of training on a real-world model and a VR application based on that model.

4.1 Testing results

Considering that the first testing phase was mainly focused on the application functionality and user experience, the main testing results are feedback capture grids filled by the participants. Each grid consists of four quadrants: what the participant liked, what they considered needs improving, questions that have arisen and ideas that emerged from the experience. By analyzing responses several directions for improvement were identified and addressed while developing the final application version:

- The need for a guided tutorial for beginners – The existing tutorial of the simulator was revised to include detailed instructions and clear markings of following steps the user should perform.
- The significance of a virtual library of learning materials – Additional material was added to the Learn section of the application, but also on the eLearning platform that is an extension of the application
- Making the application flow more intuitive – Changes of the user interface were made to make it simpler to navigate and multiple mechanisms for achieving common actions were added to the application.
- Adding additional visual representation of the model state – Display of input and output values was redesigned, and additional visual representation was added for clarity.

Virtual environment evaluation questionnaire responses were also aggregated for all participants and are shown in Figure 4. The chart shows that participants rated the application relatively highly across all characteristics, with some variance in average ratings. According to testing participants, the strongest trait of the application is that the tasks are interesting with an average mark of 4.125. The lowest score was achieved for the variety of emotions felt and more significantly the effective guidance of the application narrative. The latter is the characteristics that was the focus of the following phase of application development, as the ability to guide the user through the application flow is essential for effective application use. It is also noticeable that all of the directions for improvement identified by the feedback capture grids are directly or indirectly connected to this characteristic.

After the application development was completed, the second phase of testing was performed. All participants completed the UEQ questionnaire, which consists of 26 items describing the quality of the application, assigned to 7 scales [15]. Each item is represented by a pair of qualifiers with opposite meaning (e.g. attractive and unattractive) and participants rate each item with values between -3 and 3. The results can be used to compare the user experience of two interactive products or compare one product to a benchmark. The chart in Figure 5 shows the UEQ questionnaire results of the developed VR application compared to the benchmark that contains the data of 9905 evaluations of 246 products [15]. Based on this

chart, for five out of six scales, the VR application can be classified as Excellent, which corresponds to being in the range of top 10% best results. The remaining scale classifies the application as Good, i.e., 10% of results in the benchmark data set are better and 75% of results are worse than the results of the application. Therefore, it can be inferred that considerable progress concerning the user experience has been made during the second phase of development.

Figure 4. Average values of ratings given by participants in the virtual environment evaluation questionnaire in the first phase of testing

Figure 5. UEQ scale results compared to a benchmark.

5. CONCLUSION

Virtual Reality enhances traditional learning and fosters innovation in water education. This paper outlines the development of a VR application for fluid mechanics and presents the results of two testing phases. The first phase identified areas for improvement, which were

addressed in subsequent development. User experience testing in the second phase ranked the application in the top 10% for nearly all evaluation scales, demonstrating significant progress.

Beyond improving user experience, this study underscores VR's potential to transform digital water education by overcoming barriers such as equipment access, time constraints, and financial limitations. Features like a structured tutorial, virtual library, and improved navigation enhance engagement and conceptual understanding. VR applications not only supplement physical labs but also provide immersive, self-paced learning environments crucial for hands-on disciplines like fluid mechanics.

Early exposure to digital tools like VR equips students with industry-relevant skills, improving employability. Future improvements of the VR application could include a modular user interface for building a custom simulator and developing more complex modules for the simulator. By refining VR applications, this research contributes to bridging the gap between academia and industry, fostering a new generation of professionals ready for the digital transformation of water management.

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Enhancing awareness and engagement of students and young researchers on New Genomic Techniques to increase the food system sustainability

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Abstract

The use of New Genomic Techniques (NGTs) is of great interest for innovation and sustainability.

NGTs can help increase the sustainability and resilience of our food system by enabling the development of new plant varieties resilient to climate change and resistant to pests. This guarantee higher yields but require fewer fertilizers and pesticides, helping to reduce the use and the risk of chemical pesticides.

NGTs can contribute to reduce the inputs required by agricultural systems, improving the quality of agricultural and forestry land, protecting crops from effects of climate change, reducing the loss of biodiversity and environmental degradation, and finally ensuring greater safety for the consumer.

An Italian network supported by Inail projects, is being created, which have a similar role to an educating community. This can contribute, with training and dissemination actions, to promote knowledge of current regulations and their application, and to evaluate the risks and benefits of biotechnology applied to cultivated plants.

Furthermore, dissemination and communication activities will be carried out aimed at operators in the agricultural production chains and also at consumers to present and discuss some of the most interesting topics that arouse divisions in public opinion. These topics are not yet the subject of clear regulatory activities because technology progress is changing faster than regulators. The project aims to create a debate among experts, researchers and students on the topics having the common thread to assess the risk for the environment, the agricultural systems and for food safety.

Keywords: New Genomic Techniques, sustainability, education, European Green Deal, biotechnology

1. INTRODUCTION

General policy frameworks such as the European Green Deal, Farm to Fork and biodiversity strategies are aimed at making the EU economy sustainable by transforming climate and environmental challenges into opportunities. These initiatives accelerate the transition towards a sustainable food system, addressing the environmental, social, agricultural and public health implications and protecting nature by reversing the trend towards ecosystem degradation [1,2,3].

Of great interest for innovation and sustainability is the use of New Genomic Techniques (NGT). NGTs are innovative tools which produce crops identical to those that could have been obtained with classical techniques such as seed selection and crossbreeding and in most cases determine more targeted, more precise and faster changes compared to conventional breeding techniques [4].

NGTs can help increase the sustainability and resilience of our food system by enabling the development of new plant varieties that are resilient to climate change and resistant to pests, which guarantee higher yields but require fewer fertilizers and pesticides.

Therefore, NGTs can contribute to reduce not only the inputs required by agricultural systems, in particular pesticides and chemical fertilizers, but also plants water needs, improving the agricultural and forestry land quality, protecting crops from climate change effects, reducing the loss of biodiversity and environmental degradation, and finally ensuring greater safety for the consumer. NGT are techniques that can help breed new plant varieties faster, and with higher precision than classical breeding techniques, such as seed selection or cross-breeding. NGTs can produce a wide diversity of plant products, and these plants may have only small changes that might also occur in nature or through classic breeding or they may have more complex modifications [4] (examples in **Table 1**).

Table 1. Promising NGTs examples.

EXAMPLES OF NGTs AND THEIR PROMISING IMPLICATIONS IN SUSTAINABILITY	
Bruise-resistant bananas	can reduce food waste
Drought-tolerant maize varieties	to adapt to climate change
Mustard greens modified to reduce bitter flavours	can increase variety for healthier diets
Poplar varieties with favourable wood properties	for use in manufacturing, developed in Europe
Pathogen-resistant potato	to reduce pesticide use and food waste

Technically, NGTs constitute a broad group of techniques that can be used to achieve different results; such as targeted mutagenesis and cisgenesis (including intragenesis). Their characteristics are the higher precision and speed in introducing the desired genetic modifications and the insertion of genetic material only from a crossable species. In addition, in some cases, products containing or consisting of plants with genetic modifications introduced by NGTs cannot be differentiated by analytical methods from products containing or consisting of plants bred with conventional breeding methods.

In order to obtain innovation in the agri-food system by NGTs and at the same time maintaining the high levels of human, animal health and the environment protection guaranteed by current legislation, the European Commission has launched a political initiative to propose an exemption for plants obtained through targeted mutagenesis and cisgenesis and

for food and feed obtained from them. This has been the subject of discussion in the European Parliament.

As a result of this debate, the European Commission legislative proposal (COM (2023) 411) adopted on 5 July 2023 [5], distinguishes between two categories of plants developed by new genomic techniques (NGT plants):

1. NGT plants that could occur naturally or be produced by conventional breeding techniques, including random mutagenesis using chemical and/or physical mutagenic agents ('category 1 NGT plants'). Such plants would be treated similar to conventional plants and would only require a verification procedure to confirm that they are equivalent to plants obtained by conventional breeding.
2. NGT plants characterised by more complex sets of genetic modifications and that should remain subject to the requirements of the EU GMO legislation ('category 2 NGT plants').

Furthermore, the proposal introduces specific criteria, listed in Annex I of the EC proposal COM (2023) 411, to determine whether a NGT plant is to be considered equivalent to conventional breeding and therefore be exempted from the European Union GMOs Legal Framework.

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) was asked by the European Parliament to provide a scientific opinion on the analysis by the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES) of Annex I of the European Commission proposal for a regulation 'on plants obtained by certain new genomic techniques (NGTs) and their food and feed and amending regulation (EU) 2017/625'. EFSA concluded that, as regards risks for human and animal health and the environment, there are no specific hazards linked to targeted mutagenesis or cisgenesis. Concerning targeted mutagenesis, EFSA specified that, the potential for unintended effects, such as off-target effects, may be significantly reduced compared to transgenesis or conventional breeding. Therefore, due to how these novel techniques work, and compared to transgenesis, a lesser amount of data might be needed for the risk assessment of these plants and products made from them [6].

The directives applied so far for GMOs have lagged behind scientific and technological progress and were not designed to facilitate the development and marketing of innovative NGT products. The EU needed an adapted framework for safe NGT plants, adapted to their specificities. NGT can be considered of great benefit for farmers who will have a wider choice of plant varieties, lower costs and higher environmental performance due to less use of pesticides and fertilisers; for consumers who would have a broader choice of safe products, improved nutrition, less undesirable substances such as pesticides; for researchers and plant breeders, including SMEs, more tools to increase breeding speed and precision; for food system: climate resilience, saving natural resources, lower emissions, reduced food waste and higher food security.

According to the proposal under discussion, approved on 24 January 2024 by the Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety of the European Parliament, organisms produced with NGTs comparable to those present in nature or obtained with conventional techniques will remain within of current legislation but with a simplified process with respect to GMOs. Until the waiver is approved, however, NGT products must be treated as GMOs [7]. The history of the use of New Technologies for plant breeding has been summarized in **Table 2**, with particular attention to what has happened in Italy from 1990 to today [9].

Table 2 The history of using New Technologies for plant breeding, in Europe and Italy.

YEARS	DIRETTIVES	IN EUROPE	IN ITALY	TECHNIQUES
1990-2000	90/220/EEC on the deliberate release into the environment of GMO	The first GM crops were field tested mainly in Italy and France.	Italian politics initially showed interest in biotechnology. But in 1999/2000, new political developments blocked research on plants.	Recombinant DNA technologies - Transgenesis. The modified traits included over a dozen tolerance or resistance characteristics within 24 different plant species.
2001-2005	2001/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 March 2001 on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms and repealing Council Directive 90/220/EEC	The need to regulate the use of GMOs and the increased public skepticism about it, led to the adoption of Directive 2001/18/EC, characterized by a strong precautionary approach.	Directive 2001/18/EC implemented by Legislative Decree N. 224/2003, modified with Legislative Decree N. 227/2016. Law No. 5 was approved on Jan 2005, to regulate the coexistence between conventional, organic, and GMO agriculture. But, the law has resulted in a <i>de facto</i> 20-year-long ban by the absence of 'Experimental Protocols'.	Italy went from 300 promising field trials during the period between 1992 and 2004 to zero in the following 20 years. Only one field trial with GM cherry, olive, and kiwi trees at the University of Tuscia continued until 2012, then destroyed.
2015	(EU) 2015/412 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 2015 amending Directive 2001/18/EC as regards the possibility for the Member States to restrict or prohibit the cultivation of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in their territory	Member states have the possibility to ban the cultivation of all types of GMOs on their territory. Member States can now cite any reason, but not health or environmental issues, since these are under the purview of the EFSA.	Since the so-called Opt-Out came into effect on April 2, 2015, 19 states have prohibited the cultivation of any type of GMO on their land, including Italy. [8]	The Paradox: National governments claim to keep their territories GMO-free , but Europe imports approximately 83% of the soy it uses as transgenic feed and food. Italy, for example, imports and consumes five thousand tons of GM soy per day.

<p>2016 - 2018</p>	<p>The European Court of Justice (CJEU) exempted older genetic manipulation techniques, such as random mutagenesis that have been in use for commercial production half a century before Directive 2001/18, describing them as having a “long safety tradition.”</p>	<p>CJEU affirmed that gene editing gives rise to a GMO, according to the legal definition in Article No. 2 of Directive 2001/18/EC, and therefore, edited plants fall under GMO regulations.</p>	<p>In 2016, Italian Research and the Competent Authority questioned whether plants obtained by editing were subject to the same regulations applied to GMOs. National authorities were in a legal vacuum, waiting for the EU. Since 2018, Italian scientists have started an active dialogue with politicians and society. In an effort to improve communication and dissociate from the term GMO, they proposed a different name for the new genomic techniques: ‘Assisted Evolution Techniques’ (TEA).</p>	<p>NGT/TEA With the development of genome-editing technologies based on CRISPR/Cas, several scientists, reignited the debate about plant genetic modification. A key feature of this system is the ability to introduce small, targeted changes in a genome without permanently integrating a transgene to confer the desired characteristics.</p>
<p>2023- 2024</p>	<p>Proposal for a new Regulation on plants produced by certain new genomic techniques 5 July 2023.</p>	<p>NGTs are distinguished into two categories: NGT-1 are plants indistinguishable from those produced through conventional breeding methods and therefore subject to simplified approval procedures NGT-2 would fall under the regulatory regime for ‘classic’ GMOs</p>	<p>Italian Parliament decided to support gene editing in plant breeding, and has facilitated its applications for field trials of these edited plants. For open trials of NGT plants, an amendment was drafted to Legislative Decree 224/2003, where the part referring to the Experimental Protocols was eliminated.</p>	<p>NGT/TEA In 2024, the first Italian experimental field with NGT in Italy - a rice variety less susceptible to the fungal pathogens that cause rice blast disease - it was devastated. It shows that the dialogue with society still has problems, but also that times have changed: while the destruction had no repercussions, solidarity and support for scientists came in abundance from different parts of society.</p>

In recent years, Italy has invested millions of euros through national and international funding to apply NGTs to various crops. This investment has facilitated the acquisition of advanced technological know-how and the training of a new generation of scientists. Italy's interest in NGTs is also demonstrated by the regulatory intervention of June 2023 with which Parliament approved that plants produced with genome editing techniques through site-directed mutagenesis or cisgenesis should be placed in the field according to Art. 9-bis (Urgent provisions regarding agricultural genetics) [10], in order to allow, in application of Directive 2001/18/EC and its transposition Legislative Decree 224/2003 [11], the carrying out of research activities at authorized experimental sites, in support of plant production capable of responding adequately to water scarcity and in the presence of particularly intense environmental and biotic stresses. It will be possible to carry out the tests until the end of 2025, pending the new European Union regulation on the matter. In addition to extending the deadlines, the amendment broadens the objectives of the field experimentation, which will no longer only concern plant production capable of responding to conditions of environmental stress and water scarcity, but also to varieties "with improved qualitative and nutritional characteristics".

This is the government's best response to the attack that the first experimental rice field with TEA, built in Pavia, suffered. Agriculture, science and politics confirm that they are united in supporting the extraordinary added value guaranteed by these innovative tools. Therefore, our project is of great importance as it involved an intense dissemination and communication activity aimed at operators in the agricultural production chains but also at consumers to present and discuss some of the most interesting topics that arouse divisions in public opinion, and which are not yet the subject of a clear regulatory activity by the Italian legislator for accelerated technological progress compared to the regulator's review capacity.

1.1 Italian regulatory activities process from the contained use to the deliberate release.

Recent years have seen exponential growth in applying cutting-edge biotechnological techniques in various research fields, such as human health, agriculture and industry. Such rapid success brings challenges related to protect human health and the environment.

Legislative Decree No. 206 of 2001 (Directive 2009/41/EC) is in force in Italy, which establishes that anyone intending to use a GMM must receive prior authorization from the Italian Competent Authority, the Ministry of Health. With the implementation of this provision, the Competent Authority, through a Technical Health Committee, has the task of evaluating and authorizing the plants where the activities (research, development and production) are carried out and the type of genetic manipulation, as well as the foreseeable, immediate or future risks that the GMM or the combination of GMMs used may present for human and animal health and for the ecosystem in general.

Therefore, it is essential to provide up-to-date information on national regulations, educate on laboratory practices with genetically modified organisms and microorganisms (GMOs and GMMs), create awareness and motivate for biosafety (**Table 3**).

Table 3 Italian regulatory activities process from the contained use (*in vitro* plant cells/ in glasshouse plants) to the deliberate release (experimental field).

Contained use

Directive 2009/41/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 May 2009 on the contained use of genetically modified micro-organisms (GMM). Authority Competent Ministry of Health.
GMM means a micro-organism (also plant cell in culture) in which the genetic material has been altered in a way that does not occur naturally by mating and/or natural recombination.

Glasshouses

Directive 2009/41/EC- Annex IV, Table I B. Containment and other protective measures for glasshouses and growth-rooms
 Users of **GMOs in confined environments** can, on a voluntary basis, contact the competent Authority (Ministry of Environment) to request verification of the suitability of the confinement measures adopted.

Deliberate release

Directive 2001/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 March 2001 on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms (GMO).

The European Commission has adopted a proposal for a new Regulation on plants produced by certain **new genomic techniques**. 5 July 2023, part of a package of legislative proposals to support the EU's Farm to Fork and Biodiversity strategies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Inail Project, "Prevention and protection of health and the environment in laboratories using advanced and innovative biotechnological methods", was aimed at promoting staff training and awareness to ensure compliance with the directive 2009/41/EC and 2001/18/EC by biotechnological techniques users with innovative methodologies characterized by the close synergy between students, safety managers and researchers [11,12].

This activity allowed the effective transfer of knowledge within the educational community, such as a national network that facilitates the sharing of knowledge and the promotion of tools and methodologies for risk assessment, with particular attention to NGT. The previously achieved experience with the recent Inail research project, carried out in collaboration with the Ministry of Health, which can be viewed on the website <https://www.biotechsafety.org/>, highlighted how it is possible to combine innovation and safety. The aim was to minimize risks without hindering research, through digital tools, collaborations with qualified partners and a participatory and innovative approach to training,

The project's training activities, whose priority objective was to increase culture and skills for the prevention and protection of health and the environment in the event of contained use of GMMs, were also aimed at young researchers on the knowledge of innovative biotechnologies applied to plants, on current legislation and on the methods available to evaluate possible risks for the environment, health and agricultural systems [13].

After this initial phase, an Italian network is being created, which have a similar role to an educating community, which can contribute, with training and dissemination actions, to:

- promote knowledge of current regulations and their application,
 - evaluate risks and benefits of biotechnology applied to cultivated plants,
- through the involvement of researchers, experts from public and private bodies, producers and consumers.

These new project goals are still ongoing. Training events were and will be aimed at young researchers to know more about the different biotechnologies applied to plants, on the current regulations and on the methods available to evaluate possible risks for the environment, human health and agricultural systems. The objective is to train young experts with specific skills in the preparation and/or evaluation of dossiers necessary for the risk assessment and approval of new products deriving from the application of New Genomic Techniques.

Furthermore, dissemination and communication activities will be carried out aimed at operators in the agricultural production chains and also at consumers to present and discuss some of the most interesting topics that arouse divisions in public opinion, and which are not yet the subject of clear regulatory activities because technology progress is changing faster than regulators. Indeed, the project aims to create a debate among experts, researchers and students on the topics that have the common thread to assess the risk for the environment, the agricultural systems and for food safety.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interesting results obtained to date from this project have created solid foundations to increase students and young researchers' awareness and involvement on New Genomic Techniques with the final goal of the food system sustainability.

We achieved the following results:

- Several training workshops held in Northern, Central and Southern Italy [13] (**Figure 1**).
- Creation of a network between university researchers, research institutes, and regulatory institutions, that provide an exchange of experiences and solutions, gathered through an effective and systematic comparison of theoretical knowledge and practical daily working experience (<https://www.biotechsafety.org/>).
- Innovative use of neuromanagement techniques to operate more effectively on the attentional, perceptive and decision-making processes of users.
- Spreading of educational messages through young workers using methods of proven effectiveness which are based on both rational and irrational components (**Figure 2**).

The project aimed to reach not only researchers and experts on biotech safety but also young researchers and high school students, to induce awareness already in the early educational phases.

Great interest and appreciation for the innovative methodology used in the previous project, obtaining a certificate of merit as a Good Practice 2024 downloadable from the International Social Security Association (ISSA) database (<https://www.issa.int/databases/gp>).

The positive outcomes of the training were highlighted both by the satisfaction questionnaires and by the neuromanagement analysis carried out to test the potential effect of specific biosafety training for GMM/GMO laboratory users.

Figure 1. The training courses took place in Northern, Central and Southern Italy. In the histogram, the various training activities carried out over the years, calculated on the basis of the number of training days carried out, have been divided by Italian region. (*mainly in 2022 and 2023, during the key project phases of the project, in Rome because of its reachable location Central Italy. The webinars reached a pan-national audience).

Figure 2. Biotech safety training from 2020 to 2024, calculated in number of training hours and divided by type of courses held.

The use of neuro-metric instruments and attentional behavior allowed to investigate that emotional and cognitive correlates with the perception of risk in a biotechnological laboratory. Overall, the neurocognitive analysis achieved greater neurocognitive activation for the trainees, which is not observed in the survey of conscious knowledge (questionnaire).

But above all, it is worth underlining the proportional increase in authorization requests for the contained use of GMMs presented to the Competent Authority, the Ministry of Health, in the last two years (**Figure 3**). As showed in figure 3, the number of GMM plant authorizations has increased from 2021 to 2023, probably due to the considerable training effort.

Figure 3. Trend of authorized plants from 2017 to 2023 (Source Italian Ministry of Health).

During all the Project’s training activities, particular attention was paid to disseminating correct scientific information regarding the development and new applications of New Genomic Techniques. Following recent training and dissemination activities, as well as the legislative changes mentioned above, there has been an increase in notifications submitted to the Ministry of Health for the use in laboratory and then in greenhouse of plants destined to be released into the field for experimental purposes as plants created through the use of NGT (according to the process reported in Table 3).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The complex Italian situation regarding the use of GM crops in agriculture highlights the challenges our policymakers, legislators, but also food business, scientists, and the entire civil society, are asked to face in the future. It is necessary to find a good balance between environmental protection, consumer’ health and economic interests which must not conflict with innovation and scientific progress. Instead, regulatory decisions should consider all aspects at stake and should be able to effectively and correctly communicate the political, economic, scientific and ethical issues. This can be ensured, first and foremost, through dialogue between law and science.

The complex agri-food context is characterized by strong resistance and skepticism, but there is a need to promote innovative solutions to address urgent issues such as climate change and sustainability [9].

The project idea of addressing the challenges related to NGTs and GMOs through promoting a serious, informed and open dialogue between different actors and stakeholders appeared to be the only solution to ultimately ensure active and informed involvement of citizens in the decision-making process.

Our method involves an innovative approach. It is now known that decision-making is a complex mental function influenced by multiple cognitive, behavioural and emotional processes. Several tasks have been developed to evaluate different types of decision making. Personal experiences subjected to analyses and studies, can provide us with information relating to the possible results associated with a given decision, and it is precisely through these studies that emerges that decisions made based on experience involve emotional and motivational factors. But above all, it is worth underlining the proportional increase in notification requests for contained use of GMMs (including those related to new technologies) presented to the Ministry of Health in the last two years, underlining how the widespread training/information activity through motivational methods has been successful.

In conclusion, considering that the new Proposal on NGTs ensures a high level of health and environmental protection, applies only to NGT plants as safe as conventionally bred plants, contributes to sustainability across a wide range of plant species, especially within the agri-food system, and creates opportunities for research and innovation, including for SMEs, effective communication and dialogue between stakeholders and researchers are essential.

Hence, dissemination and communication activities will be carried out aimed at operators in the agricultural production chains and also at consumers so as to present and discuss some of the most interesting topics that arouse divisions in public opinion, and which are not yet the subject of clear regulatory activities of the Italian legislator for accelerated technological progress compared to the review capacity of the regulator. Experts on the topics that will be identified, and which will have as their common thread the assessment of risk for the environment, for agricultural systems and for food safety will be invited to the debate, together with the researchers.

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Pro-Environmental Behavior under Risk and Ambiguity: Evidence from a Lab Experiment

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of risk and ambiguity on environmental donations. The results are derived from a dictator game where donors are students participating in a laboratory experiment, and the recipient is an environmental agency financing sustainable projects. The findings show that participants use the objective riskiness regarding the donation's outcome as an excuse to avoid donating. This is evident under clear risky prospects. Risk-averse, ambiguity-averse individuals tend to place greater weight on the potential benefits than the disadvantages associated with the uncertainty of the outcome of pro-environmental actions. Additionally, the subjects' perceived level of ambiguity—and the general difficulty participants face in assessing objective probabilities—tends to increase selfish behavior, suggesting a link between cognitive abilities, generosity and pro-environmental behaviors. Considering the timing of decision-making, contributions seem to be related with instantaneous and intuitive decisions.

Keywords: *Environmental Preferences, Dictator Game, Subjective Probability, Decision-Making, Experiment, Risk Preferences, Ambiguity Box, Dual System Theory.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Nature has constantly gifted us with the abundance of its resources, and given the various dangers that daily threaten its existence, the time has come for every individual to contribute for its long-run preservation. The natural environment is undergoing rapid and detrimental changes, with threats such as global warming, loss of biodiversity, and air pollution becoming more pressing than ever before (Polasky et al., 2019; Piao and Managi, 2022). Human activities are widely recognized as one of the primary drivers of these environmental issues, including climate change and biodiversity loss (Hansen and Stone, 2016). In response to the accelerating changes in the natural world, significant shifts in human behavior are urgently needed to address the crises related to averse environmental disasters (Caferra et al., 2025). In this context, pro-environmental behavior (hereafter PEB) refers to a set of altruistic actions aimed at environmental conservation, which in turn contributes to the overall sustainability of the natural world (Stern, 2000; Lange and Dewitte, 2019). PEB has been studied in various contexts and from different perspectives, making it difficult to provide a singular classification. In this regard, we can distinguish between normative, hedonic, and gain frames (Lindenberg and Steg, 2007; Piao and Managi, 2022). The first two types of motivations are based on non-monetary reward behind individuals' choices: the normative view defines PEB as the right thing to do, while the hedonic motivation is based on a sense of gratitude arising

from these virtuous actions. On the other hand, gain motivations come from profit-maximizing individuals who are primarily interested in the potential gains and losses associated with their choices, including those related to supporting the environmental cause. Considering the first two motivations, voluntary actions, such as donations to environmental organizations, are today crucial for sustaining and preserving the global public good of the environment (Piao and Managi, 2022).

Voluntary BEP is arguably one of the best ways to study the intrinsic motivations of individuals to contribute to environmental causes, even without direct monetary rewards. For this reason, several studies have sought to explore this type of behavior using various techniques. Among these, one of the methods for studying actual and incentivized behavior in a controlled environment is through economic experiments. Numerous experimental settings have been used to study individuals' BEP, highlighting both the relevance of the topic and the importance of continuing research in this field (Loshel et al., 2017; Weimann et al., 2022).

The present study examines individuals' voluntary pro-environmental actions using a modified dictator game, where the donors are the participants in the experiment, and the receiver is the environment. Specifically, we consider an environmental organization called "Treedom," an Italian organization involved in sustainable projects. Treedom is an online platform that allows people to plant trees in various parts of the world as part of reforestation and sustainable development projects. Users can choose where to plant trees—whether in Africa, Latin America, Asia, or Europe—and each tree is linked to a project that helps improve both the environment and local communities. Treedom focuses on initiatives that promote biodiversity, combat climate change, and enhance the living conditions of people in vulnerable areas. Additionally, each tree planted is tracked through the platform, providing donors with insight into its long-term impact. At the end of the experiment, based on individual choices, we donate about 300 euros to this platform.

The main innovation in the proposed version of the dictator game lies in the introduction of risky and ambiguous framing, following the work of Cettolin et al. (2017) and Caferra et al. (2024), which, instead of focusing on pro-environmental preferences, examines social preferences for redistributive purposes under uncertainty. Therefore, the proposed experiment replicates previous studies on social preferences, focusing specifically on charitable giving for environmental donations.

The study of Risk and Ambiguity in the context of environmental donations can be worthy of investigation for several reasons. When considering risk, in this context, it is known that individuals tend to make decisions based on their degree of risk aversion. This becomes particularly relevant in the context of donations. As highlighted in the literature, the outcome of the donation itself may be subject to risk (Garcia, 2020). Moreover, the donor's income can also be at risk, subject to fluctuations depending on the current economic scenario (Cettolin et al., 2017). For this reason, we employ various experimental settings in which, in some cases, the risk associated with the donation outcome increases, while in others, the risk pertains to the donor, as they themselves may, at the end of the experiment, receive no compensation (thus experiencing an economically disadvantageous condition) with a certain probability inherent in the specific task.

In experimental economics, the dictator game has long been a useful tool for studying altruistic and redistributive behaviors (List, 2007; Engel, 2011). In this game, one participant (the "giver") decides how to allocate a sum of money to another participant (the "receiver" or "beneficiary"), who has no influence over the giver's decision. This experimental setup aims

to mimic a real-world situation where individuals assess probabilities (i.e., ambiguity) and compare them with scenarios where probabilities are clearly defined (i.e., risk). In this context, however, the experimental design was extended to focus on environmental preferences, particularly charitable giving towards environmental causes.

Ultimately, when examining risky decisions and costly, virtuous behaviors—such as sacrificing part of one's income to make a donation—it is crucial to consider a key factor in individuals' decision-making: the allocation of time. In fact, the way individuals spend their time can tell us a great deal about both the method they use to reason and the expected outcome of such reasoning. According to Dual System Theory (Kahneman, 2011), intuitive choices resulting from heuristics and social norms in individuals who use System 2 can lead to completely different outcomes compared to choices based on critical reasoning from System 1. In the context of risky choices, this leads to behaviors such as risk-as-feeling or risk-as-analysis (Caferra et al., 2024). Another strand of literature identifies the role of Dual System Theory in cooperation choices (Bear and Rand, 2016). Cooperation may either be an intuitive social norm or the outcome of a longer process of reflection. The conflicting findings of these studies render it especially interesting to observe how individuals behave when considering this dimension.

The following sections outline the experimental design in detail (Section 2), present the results (Section 3), and offer concluding remarks (Section 4).

2. THEORY AND DESIGN

The study replicates Caferra et al. (2024) experimental design with a focus on environmental preferences and pro-environmental behavior (PEB), rather than social preferences and resource redistribution. It involved 62 University of Bari students in March 2024, using the Qualtrics platform. Participants donated to an environmental foundation supporting sustainability projects like tree planting. The experiment had two phases: the first phase used a modified dictator game with three conditions—ambiguity, risk, and certainty—to test how different types of risk (for the giver or the recipient, the environment) affected decisions. Ambiguity was introduced with a moving square box to obscure probabilities, while risk conditions used clear probabilities. The second phase involved 40 allocation decisions to estimate participants' α -maxmin preferences, measuring ambiguity aversion, using a utility function to assess risk and ambiguity preferences. One random decision is selected for payment for each subject. The total donation to the Treedom platform was around 300 euros.

2.1. Phase 1: Modified Dictator Game

The idea is, akin to Garcia et al. (2020), to introduce a lottery -for-self, introducing risk on the Giver, and a *lottery-for-others*, that in this case is a *lottery-for-the-environment*, introducing risk on the beneficiary side. These conditions corresponded to the Risk-G and Risk-B treatments in the referenced experimental design (see Table 1). The general formula for the risky scenarios was $p: (1+p)x$ and $(1-p): (1-p)x$, or $p: (1/p)x$ and $(1-p): 0x$. This setup indicates that, with probability p , a subject would receive $(1+p)x$, and with probability $(1-p)$, the subject would receive $(1-p)x$. This example helps clarify the formulation in Table 1. Risk-neutral participants were defined by the equation $x=p(1+p)x + p(1-p)x$, which results in the same donation amount as in a no-risk scenario (shown on the left side of the equation), whether in the Risk-B ($X-x$) or Risk-G (x) condition.

For the ambiguity condition, the risk scenarios were reintroduced, but now p represented the number of blue squares in the ambiguity box, indicating the probability of extracting a square of that color. To facilitate comparison between treatments, the p values in the ambiguity boxes were set equal to the risk treatment values (0.5, 0.5, 0.8, and 0.2). While the experimenter knew the actual number of squares, participants could only estimate this number, introducing an element of ambiguity into the decision-making process (as explained in the next section)

Table 1. Dictator game under conditions of certainty (top), risk (middle) and ambiguity (bottom)

	Certainty			
	Giver	Beneficiary	Giver	Beneficiary
0-Certainty	$X-x_0$	x_0	$X-x_0$	x_0
	Risk-B		Risk-G	
	Giver	Beneficiary	Giver	Beneficiary
1-objective risk	$X-x_1$	0.5: $1.5x_1$; 0.5: $0.5x_1$	0.5: $1.5(X-x_1)$; 0.5: $0.5(X-x_1)$	x_1
2-objective risk	$X-x_2$	0.8: $1.25x_2$; 0.2: $0x_2$	0.8: $1.25(X-x_2)$; 0.2: $0(X-x_2)$	x_2
3-objective risk	$X-x_3$	0.5: $2x_3$; 0.5: $0x_3$	0.5: $2(X-x_3)$; 0.5: $0(X-x_3)$	x_3
4-objective risk	$X-x_4$	0.2: $5x_4$; 0.8: $0x_4$	0.2: $5(X-x_4)$; 0.8: $0(X-x_4)$	x_4
	Ambiguity-B		Ambiguity-G	
	Giver	Beneficiary	Giver	Beneficiary
1-objective risk	$X-x_1$	$p: (1+p)x_1$; $p: (1-p)x_1$	$p: (1+p)(X-x_1)$; $(1-p): 0(X-x_1)$	x_1
2-objective risk	$X-x_2$	$p: (1/p)x_2$; $(1-p): 0x_2$	$p: (1/p)(X-x_2)$; $(1-p): 0(X-x_2)$	x_2
3-objective risk	$X-x_3$	$p: (1/p)x_3$; $(1-p): 0x_3$	$p: (1/p)(X-x_3)$; $(1-p): 0(X-x_3)$	x_3
4-objective risk	$X-x_4$	$p: (1/p)x_4$; $(1-p): 0x_4$	$p: (1/p)(X-x_4)$; $(1-p): 0(X-x_4)$	x_4

- **Ambiguous cases:** In line with Caferra et al. (2024), participants were first presented with eight ambiguous prospects—four for Ambiguity-B and four for Ambiguity-G (see Table 1), with the order randomized. Ambiguity was introduced through the use of an ambiguity box, which contained 100 moving squares of two colors (red and blue). The proportion of each color remained constant within a given decision scenario but varied between different scenarios. This ensured a stable underlying objective probability. The continuous motion of the squares made it difficult for participants to accurately count the exact number of each color, introducing an element of ambiguity. After participants made their choices, a random square was drawn using the probabilities predefined by the experimenter to determine the payoff.

Participants were informed that the probability p represented the chance of extracting a blue square from the box. They were also given a multiplier that would affect the amount of the endowment transferred or retained, depending on p , as described in Table 1. Based on this information, participants were required to estimate the probability.

- **Risky cases:** In the second phase of the experiment, participants were asked to make decisions regarding various risky prospects with well-defined, objective probabilities. The probabilities for each event were clearly communicated (examples of decision screens can be found in the Appendix). To minimize any learning bias from familiarity with the true

probabilities, the order of the different prospects was randomized, and all risky decisions were presented after the ambiguous ones.

- **Certain case:** Lastly, participants allocated their money according to the traditional dictator game procedure, where neither the amount transferred nor the amount kept was subject to any risk.

Figure 16. The ambiguity box (static representation)

2.2. Phase 2: Allocation game

After the dictator game, participants took part in 40 allocation decisions. These decisions were used to estimate their α -maxmin expected utility functional preferences, as described by Caferra et al. (2023). In each decision, participants allocated 10 ECU between two options (blue and red), while observing animated squares in the ambiguity box. Ultimately, one of the two outcomes was randomly selected based on the underlying probabilities.

To recap the key aspects: if the true probability of an event was p , we assumed that the minimum perceived probability for this event was $p - \delta$ and the maximum perceived probability was $p + \delta$, where δ represents the degree of ambiguity about the true probability. In this framework, α serves as a measure of ambiguity aversion, which we assumed to be specific to each individual and estimated on a subject-by-subject basis. We employed a constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) utility function (following Hey and Panaccione, 2011), incorporating a constant risk aversion parameter (ra) in the utility function (u), and objective probabilities for the outcomes $p_1 < p_2$. The following objective function was maximized:

$$\max_{x_i} \quad \alpha \min_{p_j} \sum_{j=1}^2 (p_j - \delta)u(x_i) + (1 - \alpha) \max_{p_j} \sum_{j=1}^2 (p_j + \delta)u(x_i) \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i=1}^2 x_i = m$$

Where m was the endowment, x_1 was the portion allocated to the blue outcome and $x_2 = 1 - x_1$ was the portion allocated to the red one. This structure enabled us to estimate key choice parameters (i.e., risk aversion, ambiguity aversion). We conducted intensive simulations in MATLAB to identify the optimal problem set for determining the true parameters (see Caferra et al., 2023 for more details).

3. RESULTS

Table 2 presents the summary results both in terms of the average contribution, which serves as a proxy for the intensity of pro-environmental behavior (PEB), and in terms of the level of selfishness exhibited by the participants. The reduction in PEB is most evident when the risk is placed on the beneficiary (Risk-B). Specifically, average contribution levels decrease from 4.3 at the lowest risk levels to 2.9 at the highest risk levels. The probability of being selfish and donating less than 1 ECU (with the first decile of income used as the threshold) more than doubles from the low-risk case to the high-risk case. When the risk is placed on the donor (Risk-G), no clear trend emerges based on the level of risk. This finding is intriguing for several reasons. Efficiency-seeking participants should ideally make the donation that minimizes the loss of resources. Therefore, if risk is an issue, as it is when it falls on the beneficiary (in this case, the environmental foundation), we would expect an opposite effect—namely, an increase in donations if the probability of losing resources shifts to the donors, while the donation remains secure. However, this does not occur. In fact, participants seem to undervalue the receiver's lottery (i.e., the risky choice tied to the donation) compared to how they evaluate the same lottery when it involves themselves, even with the same expected value. This appears to align with the findings of Garcia et al. (2020), where participants use risky contexts as an excuse to avoid donating. The effect is far less pronounced in the case of ambiguity, which could be due to the objective difficulties in identifying and estimating the underlying risk, which weakens the justification for avoiding donations through the excuse of risk. However, only after performing an inferential analysis using subject characteristics as variables will it be possible to draw definitive conclusions.

Table 2. Summary statistics of results

0-certainty	Average (sd)	3.69 (3.06)	%Selfish	29%
	Risk-B		Risk-G	
	Average (sd)	%Selfish	Average (sd)	%Selfish
1-objective risk	4.301 (2.74)	16.12%	3.470 (2.74)	30.64%
2-objective risk	3.102 (2.63)	32.23%	3.128(2.71)	35.40%
3-objective risk	2.929 (2.33)	32.23%	3.307 (2.39)	25.80%
4-objective risk	2.925 (2.48)	38.70%	3.339 (2.60)	30.60%
	Ambiguity-B		Ambiguity-G	
	Average (sd)	%Selfish	Average (sd)	%Selfish
1-objective risk	4.289 (2.79)	19.35%	3.434 (2.48)	32.25%
2-objective risk	4.862 (3.32)	20.57%	3.674 (2.82)	25.80%
3-objective risk	4.373 (2.85)	19.35%	4.017 (2.61)	19.35%
4-objective risk	3.852 (3.06)	22.50%	3.414 (2.48)	27.41%

The inferential analysis is based on observing the average contribution levels of subjects across different treatments $PEB_{i,t}$, the probability of being selfish and showing low contribution levels ($Selfish_{i,t}$), and the probability of reducing the evaluation of the lottery-for-environment, $Decrease_{i,t}$, which takes a value of 1 if there is an decrease in the PEB when risk is present, compared to the equivalent certain donation made in the absence of risk. It is

particularly interesting to identify the variables that, in risky and uncertain contexts, may still preserve and enhance the willingness to make altruistic and virtuous choices. Additionally, this exercise is conducted to reduce excessive behavioral heterogeneity within the game and to make the analysis more systematic. From a strictly monetary perspective, the payoff from the donation is 0, meaning the maximum profit occurs when subjects keep the entire endowment for themselves. Therefore, spontaneous donations emerge as deviations from this equilibrium, aligned with the intensity of pro-environmental preferences that increase PEB.

Given these observations, we formalized the analysis using an econometric estimation model. The data were treated in a panel format with repeated observations for each subject, controlling for fixed effects. Two types of response variables were used: i) the choice made and ii) the probability of being selfish ("selfish"). For the latter, a random effects panel probit model was employed. The basic model can be expressed as follows:

$$Y_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Riskiness_{i,t} + \beta_2 \alpha_i + \beta_3 ra_i + \beta_4 \delta_i + \beta_5 Female_i + \beta_6 Risk_{i,t} + \beta_7 Ambiguity_{i,t} + \beta_8 Time_{i,t} + \beta_9 Shift + u_i + \epsilon_i$$

where $Y_{i,t}$ is for $PEB_{i,t}$, $Selfish_{i,t}$ or $Decrease_{i,t}$ for individual i in decision t , on the basis of the different specification made. Specifically, we use a random effect regression model for $Y_{i,t}$, while a random effect probit model is used for the other two variables.

The $Riskiness_{i,t}$ variable identifies the level of risk in the situation (i.e., objective probabilities) for treatment t , as indicated in the row names of Table 2 (0-certainty, 1-objective risk, 2-objective risk, 3-objective risk, 4-objective risk, 5-objective risk); and α ($mean=0.59$; $sd=0.24$), ra ($mean=0.64$; $sd=0.39$), $delta$ ($mean=0.08$; $sd=0.02$) were the parameters of ambiguity and risk aversion, and the degree of ambiguity, respectively, for individual i . $Female_i$ was a dummy variable for gender (i.e., 1=female; 0=non-female) for individual i . $Risk$ was a dummy variable controlling for decisions made under conditions of risk, and $ambiguity$ controlled for decisions made under conditions of ambiguity. $Shift$ referred to the shift of risk/ambiguity, assuming 1 if the risk is on the giver's side.

$Time$ is the logarithm of the seconds spent ($mean=2.77$; $sd=1.08$) within each decision t .

Finally, $u_{i,t}$ was the individual-specific random effect, ϵ_i was the error term and $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8, \beta_9$ were the coefficients to be estimated.

Table 3 presents the results concerning the average donation levels (PEB). As can be observed, the various columns reflect different disentanglements of the proposed treatments. When considering the aggregated analysis (Column 1 – Full), we note the overall negative effect of risk levels on the specific decision. In general, it could be said that the experience of risk reduces donation levels, regardless of whether the risk pertains to personal income or the outcome of the donation itself.

When the sample is divided by treatments under Risk (Column 2 – Risk) and Ambiguity (Column 3 – Amb), the effect becomes more pronounced and noticeable when the level of risk is clearly communicated. Comparing Risk-B and Risk-G, it is observed that when risk pertains to the outcome of the donation, participants, on average, tend to evaluate the lottery-for-the-environment and thus the donation less favorably. This is not the case when the risk is personally borne by the individuals. This suggests that the riskiness of the donation becomes an excuse to avoid donating, thus reducing pro-environmental preferences.

On average, regardless of the level of risk, when the risk is associated with the giver, the average donation levels decrease (Column 1 – Shift coefficient: $-.364^*$). We can therefore conclude that individuals, when faced with risky and uncertain economic conditions, tend to refrain from donating, thereby diminishing their pro-environmental actions.

An interesting effect is related to the response time. From the aggregated analysis (first column), it emerges that the longer the time taken to respond, the lower the likelihood of donating. Pro-environmental preferences and voluntary pro-environmental behavior seem to be linked to following heuristics and social norms, while more deliberative choices reduce the instinct to cooperate (Bear and Rand, 2016).

Table 3. Random effect Model

Dependent Variable: PEB							
	Full	Risk	Amb	Risk-B	Risk-G	Amb-B	Amb-G
Riskiness	$-.138^{**}$ (.067)	$-.197^{**}$ (.087)	.057 (.093)	$-.276^{***}$ (.102)	$-.022$ (.142)	.058 (.119)	.048 (.112)
ra	.252 (.472)	$-.176$ (.599)	.615 (.63)	.107 (.587)	$-.518$ (.698)	.559 (.702)	.677 (.702)
alpha	1.031 (.717)	1.039 (.933)	.942 (.855)	.78 (.964)	1.241 -1.059	1.207 -1.017	.625 (1.05)
gender	$-.519$ (.335)	$-.542$ (.46)	$-.64$ (.441)	$-.607$ (.474)	$-.38$ (.517)	$-.377$ (.569)	$-.966^*$ (.548)
Time	$-.28^{***}$ (.108)	$-.146$ (.126)	$-.136$ (.126)	$-.286$ (.183)	$-.176$ (.196)	$-.106$ (.194)	$-.161$ (.159)
Shift	$-.364^*$ (.204)	.017 (.194)	$-.589^*$ (.302)				
Risk	.167 (.308)						
Ambiguity	1.057^{**} (.419)						
delta	3.926 (9.433)	3.835 (9.435)	5.585 (9.138)	5.862 (10.265)	-1.135 (11.869)	9.513 (12.05)	.734 (9.833)
Constant	3.868^{***} (.723)	3.612^{***} (1.22)	3.465^{***} -1.184	3.954^{***} (1.42)	3.681^{***} (1.41)	2.772^* (1.54)	3.723^{***} -1.268
Observations	1054	558	558	310	248	310	248
Adjusted R2	0.015	0.11	0.034	0.111	0.105	0.042	0.057

Note: Robust standard errors are in parentheses *** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

The results are similar when considering the probability of being selfish, as shown in Tables 4 and 5. Here, the effect of time is more pronounced, and a gender effect is also noticeable, likely linked to the greater risk aversion observed in the literature (Eckel and Grossman, 2008).

Under conditions of ambiguity, the probability of being selfish decreases, further supporting the previous findings where the risk effect is more pronounced in contexts where the level of risk is clearly communicated.

Table 4. Random effect Probit Model

Dependent Variable: Selfish							
	Full	Risk	Amb	Risk-B	Risk-G	Amb-B	Amb-G
Riskiness	.063 (.051)	.152* (.079)	-.025 (.096)	.392*** (.139)	-.04 (.115)	.076 (.142)	-.172 (.123)
ra	-.349 (.471)	-.098 (.558)	-.752 (.77)	-.326 (.643)	.255 (.679)	-.917 (.797)	-.543 (-1.108)
alpha	-.331 (.631)	-.276 (.819)	-.915 (-1.132)	-.601 (-1.038)	-.054 (.973)	-.812 (-1.234)	-1.052 (-1.507)
delta	-7.63 -8.898	-7.008 -11.463	-9.193 (13.96)	3.834 -15.945	-9.115 -13.656	-18.735 (18.73)	-7.218 -19.642
gender	.776** (.338)	.73 (.445)	1.682*** (.609)	1.247** (.629)	.546 (.53)	1.999** (.778)	1.74** (.837)
Time	.16** (.079)	.266** (.105)	.031 (.13)	.382** (.177)	.335** (.153)	.098 (.17)	.081 (.187)
Shift	.154 (.121)	.057 (.176)	.363 (.234)				
Ambiguity	-.472*** (.181)						
Constant	-.632 -1.025	-1.406 -1.303	-.614 -1.701	-3.533** (1.79)	-.967 -1.545	-.317 -2.203	-.625 -2.331
Observations	992	496	496	248	248	248	248
loglikelihood	-443.1860	-241.455	-221.807	- 136.848	-117.441	-132.988	-94.6498

Note: Robust standard errors are in parentheses *** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table 5. Random effect Probit Model-Marginal effects

Dependent Variable: Selfish-Marginal Effects							
	Full	Risk	Amb	Risk-B	Risk-G	Amb-B	Amb-G
Riskiness	0.013	0.021	-0.016	0.034**	-0.008	-0.016	-0.021
ra	-0.073	-0.020	-0.113	-0.046	0.048	-0.117	-0.067
alpha	-0.043	-0.023	-0.008	-0.021	-0.010	0.050	-0.129
delta	-1.909	-1.938	-2.449	-1.275	-1.729	-3.289	-0.884
gender	0.161**	0.150**	0.220*	0.208*	0.103	0.244**	0.213**
Time	0.032*	0.047*	0.007	0.046	0.064	0.013	0.010
Shift	0.033	0.002	0.043				

Note: Robust standard errors are in parentheses *** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Now let us consider the probability of observing a decrease in the evaluation of the lottery-for-the-environment, i.e., the value of the donation made to the environment, using the certain case in the absence of risk as a reference point. The main results are presented in Tables 6 and 7. It is interesting to observe that, in this case, even in ambiguous contexts, there is an effect related to risk, meaning that an increase in the underlying objective risk reduces the probability of donating more.

Table 6. Random effect Probit Model.

Dependent Variable: Decrease							
	Full	Risk	Amb	Risk-B	Risk-G	Amb-B	Amb-G
Riskiness	0.095** (.044)	0.095 (.07)	0.114* (.064)	0.2** (.093)	-.034 (.104)	0.222** (.098)	0.041 (.094)
ra	-.541 (.491)	-.131 (.484)	-1.135 (.741)	-.596 (.475)	.31 (.654)	-1.101 (.834)	-.989 (.688)
alpha	-1.666** (.694)	-1.928*** (.739)	-1.54 (.978)	-1.457** (.689)	-2.62** (1.052)	-1.949* (1.108)	-1.278 (1.074)
delta	19.052** (8.828)	14.591 (9.947)	24.131** (11.219)	15.704* (9.348)	14.546 (12.87)	28.637** (13.711)	21.494* (11.43)
gender	-0.31 (.351)	-0.445 (.366)	.032 (.503)	-.186 (.359)	-.736 (.518)	-.053 (.576)	.109 (.537)
time	0.125* (.067)	-.073 (.108)	0.182* (.103)	0.027 (.126)	-.177 (.204)	.3 (.186)	.078 (.144)
Shift	0.093 (.117)	0.088 (.153)	0.101 (.175)				
Ambiguity	.022 (.145)						
Constant	1.224 (.895)	.296 -1.054	1.9 -1.246	1.02 -1.004	-.683 -1.518	2.652 -1.623	1.3 -1.274
Observations	992	496	496	248	248	248	248
loglikelihood	-443.186	-241.4555	-221.8072	-136.848	-117.441	-132.988	-94.6498

*Note: Robust standard errors are in parentheses *** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1*

Of particular interest is the effect related to risk aversion, ambiguity aversion, and the degree of ambiguity, which was initially less evident and not statistically significant.

Let us start by noting that ambiguity aversion and risk aversion follow the same direction, i.e., they are negatively correlated with the probability of observing a reduction in donations. When removing ambiguity aversion from the analysis, risk aversion becomes statistically significant (this result can be provided upon request). However, when ambiguity aversion is included, we observe that it better explains the effect of risk aversion. Several studies indicate that individual risk aversion is positively linked to the probability of donating (Cettolin et al., 2017), and this may be because risk aversion is associated with various subjects' profiles (Dohmen et al., 2011). Furthermore, risk aversion is not compatible with selfish behavior of individual profit-maximizers who are only interested in their own interests (Müller and Rau, 2016). To this end, it is interesting to analyze the subject profile of individuals, as ambiguity aversion appears to follow the same pattern as risk aversion in identifying individual profiles. Currently, very few studies in the literature examine this effect (Fuhrman-Riebel et al., 2021).

The degree of ambiguity, on the other hand, increases the likelihood of reducing the donation level. Again, the identified variable seems relevant for identifying the subject profile of individuals. In fact, distortions in the perception of probability might be linked to lower cognitive ability (Choi et al., 2022), which in turn is associated with lower levels of generosity (Chen et al., 2013). Consequently, difficulties in handling probabilities may lead individuals to exhibit greater aversion in other-regarding preferences.

Table 7. Random effect Probit Model-Marginal effects

Dependent Variable: Decrease-Marginal Effects							
	Full	Risk	Amb	Risk-B	Risk-G	Amb-B	Amb-G
Riskiness	0.021**	0.022	0.021*	0.049**	-0.006	0.038**	0.008
ra	0.119	-0.030	-0.212	-0.146	0.060	-0.188	-0.198
Alpha	-0.367***	-0.438***	-0.288	-0.357**	-0.507***	-0.333*	-0.256
delta	4.197**	3.313	4.514**	3.847*	2.812	4.899**	4.307**
gender	0.068	-0.101	0.006	-0.045	-0.142	-0.009	0.022
Time	0.027**	-0.017	0.034*	0.007	-0.034	0.051*	0.016
Shift	0.020	0.020	0.019				

Note: Robust standard errors are in parentheses *** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the impact of risk and ambiguity on pro-environmental donations, using a laboratory experiment based on a dictator game. Considering the contextual variables where the decision is made, the results suggest that participants tend to use the objective risk of the donation outcome as an excuse to avoid contributing. In particular, the risk associated with donation outcomes has a negative effect on pro-environmental preferences, reducing the likelihood of making a donation. This effect is more pronounced when the risk is clearly communicated, and a decrease in donation levels is also observed when there is uncertainty about personal income.

Considering individual characteristics, an interesting aspect is the relationship between risk perception, ambiguity aversion, and pro-environmental behavior. Participants who are more averse to risk and ambiguity tend to do not reducing donations under risk, suggesting that these two variables are good indicators for identifying an individual's behavioral profile. In fact, as suggested by the literature, more risk-seeking individuals may exhibit selfish attitudes compatible with the individual profit-maximizer profile. On the other hand, individuals more averse to risky and ambiguous situations may be motivated by other factors. The difficulty in handling probabilities seems to be associated with a lower tendency to act prosocially, indicating a link between cognitive abilities and generosity.

Finally, the analysis of response times highlighted that immediate decisions, often guided by heuristics or social norms, are more likely to favor pro-environmental behaviors. Therefore, people are moved by the intuitive desire to cooperate.

As observed in this study, voluntary pro-environmental actions are not easy to implement and depend on a range of heterogeneous characteristics across individuals. From this perspective, experiments can provide valuable insights into the drivers of this behavior due to

their controlled environment. Our analysis highlights how realistic characteristics that represent everyday decision-making contexts, such as the presence of risk and uncertainty, can lead to significant variations in individuals' environmental commitment. Additionally, individual characteristics such as risk aversion, ambiguity aversion, and the perceived degree of ambiguity in defining probabilities help explain different levels of pro-environmental preferences and behaviors within these contexts. This makes it particularly interesting to further explore the connections between the parameters estimated in these models and individuals' daily decision-making processes.

This paves the way for further studies aimed at identifying individual preferences for environmental commitment, shedding light on the diverse factors that influence pro-environmental behavior and the complexity of the decision-making processes behind such actions.

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UN Sustainable Development Goals - A challenge for industrial and social development with a sustainable future.
The case for development through the creation of a corresponding culture, starting from Preschool Education – How are the foundations laid in preschool?

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Abstract

The achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals/SDGs is based on the sustainability of all levels of education, from preschool to higher education.

The successful implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals/SDGs and sustainability are linked to all levels of Education from pre-school to University education.

Consequently, to achieve the aforementioned goals and implement the best modern methods and tools, there is a need for synchronization of the educational system, adapted to sustainable development, at all educational levels.

Therefore, Sustainable Development requires broad cooperation between Ministries-organizations-enterprises and Educational Universities & Institutions, because it is based on reliable data and implementation/monitoring procedures as well as on international environmental practices and in particular on EU and UN strategies and policies.

Also, sustainable development and the implementation of the SDGs are fully consistent with European law and the strategy of the UN and the EU, as education at all levels, including pre-school education, constitutes an important strategic approach in the efforts of countries to transition from the old economic model to the one promoted by the UN.

Additionally, the successful implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals is based primarily on all levels of education, with particular emphasis on preschool education and training, with the aim of creating the corresponding culture from an early age.

It is noteworthy that the Sustainable Development Report 2025 for Europe is accompanied by an online visualization tool, which can be accessed online via [sdgtransformation center.org](https://sdgtransformationcenter.org). All of this is provided online (specific country profiles, full excel database and

index), with the support of the European Union (Heinrich-Böll-Stiftung). The data is all available online.

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The EU Sustainable Development Report 2025 (ESDR2025) therefore includes a fully updated database as well as a summary report with the most important conclusions. It was prepared by the SDG Transformation Center at the United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) in Paris, France, in collaboration with regional European networks, as well as the Heinrich-Böll-Stiftung (HBS).

It is becoming clear that ESDR2025 is up-to-date and innovative, focusing, among other things, both on taking stock of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and on future prospects.

However, education has an important role in the project regarding the framework of the three pillars of Sustainable Development (Environment-Society-Economy). It is considered vital for people's attitude and ability to consider environmental and development problems. In addition, the UN emphasizes that education is an important prerequisite for environmental and ethical awareness as well as for values, skills and attitudes, consistent with Sustainable Development.

Moreover, according to SDG 4: Quality Education, it is envisaged to ensure equitable and high-quality education without exclusions, while promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all citizens.

Young people experience how important education is for personal and social development and what obstacles exist worldwide. However, education programs should focus, among other things, on the areas of Sustainable Development (SDG4: QUALITY EDUCATION), in order to achieve the Goals, starting with early childhood education and training.

There is consensus that sustainability competencies bridge knowledge and action, facilitating collaboration, while the lack of awareness and adoption of these tools has caused obstacles to the practical application of pedagogical practices and the required curricula for the development of these competencies and their gradual contribution over time to the full implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

Keywords: *UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), sustainable early childhood education, quality education, society, economics.*

“RiViVe” - Education perspectives for rethinking biodiversity in a transdisciplinary and collaborative way

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Abstract

We present here RiViVe, an educational project designed within the Italian NFBC - National Biodiversity Future Centre to address the challenges related to the loss of biodiversity and to its valorisation in a transdisciplinary and collaborative way. Through multidimensional approaches, RiViVe involves a group of artists, ecologists, anthropologists, social scientists and environmental humanities in the co-creation of an educational path open to participants interested in biodiversity (for research, education, public communication, management, etc.) aiming at improving their ability to interact with different audiences, disciplines and knowledge.

In the educational concept of RiViVe, biodiversity is not proposed as an abstract concept, detached from everyday experiences, but as a specific quality of a place, strictly entangled with its environment, culture, society, and ecology. This is why Collelongo-Selvapiana (L’Aquila, Italy) was chosen as the location of the RiViVe residency. Collelongo-Selvapiana is not only a site of the Long-Term Ecological Research Network (LTER), but also a place where young generations keep old traditions alive. It is an archaeological site, an open-air museum surrounded by beech woods where people have found their own way to coexist with the wild.

The Collelongo-Selva Piana beech forest is part of a larger forest area that also extends to the territory of the Abruzzo, Lazio, and Molise National Park. It is part of the vegetation system of the Serra Lunga, a mountain range in western Abruzzo. The main LTER research site is Selva Piana, which has been active since 1991. In 1993, the first tower in Europe for measuring carbon, water vapor, and energy fluxes between forests and the atmosphere was installed.

Within RiViVe, the connection between humans and the lands they inhabit is crucial, as well as the exchange of different forms of knowledge and wisdom between people who live in the same area and experience diverse aspects of the same land. The distinctive atmosphere or character of a place, the sum of all physical and cultural elements that give a location its unique identity are embodied by the concept of *genius loci*, the “spirit of place”.

During the residential laboratory, the most current issues regarding the diversity of human and other than human living beings - on a theoretical and practical level – will be addressed, such as taxonomy and biodiversity monitoring and evaluating practices. The aim of RiViVe is

to inspire new visions and trajectories of research and action in the younger generations and in all those who deal with biodiversity issues in various roles, and to develop skills necessary to operate as "agents of change".

Keywords: ecological education, science and society, informal communication

Mother's Digital Purchase Behavior of Newborn Products

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Abstract

Becoming a mother for the first time is a profound life transition that significantly impacts a woman's identity, shifting her role from an individualistic woman to a mother with heightened levels of anxiety. The process of purchasing baby products plays a crucial role in shaping a mother's self-definition and public self-perception. Questions such as, *what products should I buy for my baby?* and *how will my purchasing behavior differ from my previous habits?* become central to the new mother's online decision-making process. This process spans from the initial data collection stage, through the evaluation of alternatives, to the actual purchase.

The objectives of this study are to examine the online consumption behavior of first-time mothers in terms of data collection and purchase decision-making: (1) To identify key parameters influencing online purchasing decisions. (2) To explore the online buying motivations of experienced mothers. (3) To determine the primary sources of information influencing online purchasing behavior.

- The primary purpose of digital consumption among new mothers is information gathering about new baby products (80%), purchasing baby clothing (50%), and acquiring strollers (20%). 60% of respondents reported making online purchases at least twice a year.
- The key motivations for purchasing baby products online include discounted prices, product availability, and time savings (67%, 60%, and 50% of respondents, respectively).
- Maternal satisfaction with online shopping is influenced by factors such as meeting expectations, fair pricing, and return policies (50%, 42%, and 40% of respondents, respectively).

An online survey was distributed to women who gave birth within the past year in public hospitals in Israel. The survey collected information about their purchasing habits for baby products, including both durable and non-durable goods, such as cribs and clothing. The data collection employed a "snowball" sampling method, resulting in 135 fully completed questionnaires.

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly accelerated the shift towards online shopping, making it a central component of consumer behavior.

The findings highlight that online shopping plays a crucial role in the purchasing journey of new mothers, with the internet serving as a primary source of information. The study suggests that digital consumption among mothers is primarily rational, often involving extensive data collection before and after purchases.

Keywords: *digital consumption, motherhood, high-involvement baby products, online shopping behavior*

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